

School of Business and Creative Industries

**Investigating the challenges facing internal auditing in the
banking sector: The case of banks in Bangladesh**

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This dissertation is submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration (DBA).

Abstract

The main purpose of this research is to investigate the challenges of internal auditing (IA) in the banking sector and how the effectiveness of IA has been debated in practice by identifying the factors that affect IA practices in general and in Bangladesh. The key aim is to fill a high-level gap and explore consistency in developing an effective internal banking auditing (IBA) framework supported by practical guidance that can guide banking organisations to implement IA effectively. The data for this research were collected and analysed utilising twenty-one semi-structured qualitative interviews conducted with IA professionals, policymakers and regulators with extensive expertise who are representative of a variety of banking organisations in Bangladesh. The results of this research revealed that the interviewee's viewpoints on the main challenges in banking organisations varied and were visualised, and they recommended the implementation of an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance. The respondents indicated that the current state of IA practices needs to be improved, with the overall maturity of standards for the effectiveness of IA in safeguarding governance control mechanisms being underdeveloped. They also suggest that current practices should focus on a risk-based IA approach, prevention of errors and fraud, digital transformation and systematic process and control implementation. This investigation further endorses the need for technological advancements and incremental improvements in IA through the application of the IBA framework, which provides an initial boost to internal controls and compliance for the IA department and greater accountability to protect the interests of shareholders, and stakeholders in the banking sector in Bangladesh. The primary contribution of this research to the existing body of knowledge is the development of a validated IBA framework for the banking sector and its effective implementation supported by practical guidance. This research also provides academics and industry practitioners with a better understanding of the key elements of the internal and external environments that are critical to the implementation of an IBA framework, which influences their ability to effectively manage emerging risks and current control issues. This research recommends that future researchers use larger samples, quantitative data collection tools, statistical data analysis and in-depth analysis of innovative IA techniques to provide a better understanding of current technological advances and economic, and environmental changes to predict the future role of IA. The complexity of the IBA framework was identified as the main limitation of this research, which can be mitigated by conducting future research to simplify and customise the IBA framework following its practical application.

Dedication

To my loving parents, who dreamt that I would succeed in life and make them proud.

Declaration

I hereby declare that the thesis has not been submitted in full or in part for the award of another comparable degree.

I further declare that this research is the result of my independent effort and investigation, and fully referenced.

Signed:

Personal details withheld.

Date: 19/03/2022

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Abbreviations

ACCA	Association of Chartered Certified Accountants
BAS	Bangladesh Auditing Standards
BCBS	Basel Committee on Banking Supervision
BIS	Bank for International Settlements
BOD	Board of Directors
BOI	Board of Investment
CAE	Chief Audit Executive
CAGB	Comptroller and Auditor General of Bangladesh
CCM	Continuous Controls Monitoring
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CIA	Chartered Internal Auditor
CIMA	Chartered Institute of Management Accountants
CMS	Compliance Management Systems
COSO	The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission
CPA	Certified Public Accountant
DBA	Doctor of Business Administration
DoS	Director of Studies
ERM	Enterprise risk management
GCG	Good Corporate Governance
GRC	Governance, Risk management and Compliance
IA	Internal Auditing
IAASB	International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board
IAF	Internal Auditing Function
IBA	Internal Banking Auditing
ICAB	Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh
ICB	Investment Corporation of Bangladesh
ICCD	Internal Control and Compliance Division
ICMAB	Institute of Cost and Management Accountants of Bangladesh
IGG	Institutional Governance Guide
IIA	Institute of Internal Auditors
IIAB	Institute of Internal Auditors of Bangladesh
IPPF	International Professional Practices Framework

ISA	International Standards for Auditing
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
ISPPIA	International Standards for the Professional Practice of Internal Auditing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NED	Non-Executive Director
NRB	NRB Commercial Bank
NYSE	New York Stock Exchange
OCAG	Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General of Bangladesh
PDCA	Plan, Do, Check and Act Cycle
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social-cultural, Technical, Environmental and Legal
QMS	Quality Management System
RJSC	Registrar of Joint Stock Companies and Firms
RSRC	Rules, Systems, Risks and Controls
SEC	Security Exchange Commission
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SOX	Sarbanes-Oxley (SOX) Act in 2002
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
USA	United States of America
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
WHO	World Health Organisation

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research background

Internal auditing (IA) is becoming more necessary and important as regulatory bodies enhance corporate governance practices and the market environment becomes more competitive in recent years (Josh and Karyawati, 2021). The investigations into several global corporate scandals have highlighted the need for IA to monitor and control the adherence of processes to standard procedures and regulations for organisations (Lenz and Hahn, 2015; Oussii and Taktak, 2018; Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). This demonstrates how IA has become one of the key practices and has evolved into an essential component of corporate governance that has undergone dramatic changes and broadened its scope to make greater contributions and influence effectiveness (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011). However, the advent of IA is claimed to facilitate the financial compliance function by assisting the accounts department, which aims to safeguard the assets of their organisations (Arena, 2013). There is a need for effective and efficient governance and accountability. The role of IA has emerged as a critical component for these needs to ensure an organisation's overall success. In this context, IA is a combination of assurance and consulting activities that provides comprehensive insights into dealing with emerging risks by utilising effective strategic plans, tactics and analytics. It also contributes to achieving strategic, operational and financial objectives through the use of a systematic and disciplined approach (Pickett, 2012), adding value to its key functional areas and assisting in the achievement of long-term success and growth.

The identification of its operations, roles, activities and commitments to its stakeholders has become one of the main challenges for organisations (Erasmus and Coetzee, 2018). This indicates that the scope of IA has increased significantly to cover more important functions such as governance, risk management and control processes (GRC) (Alzeban and Gwilliam, 2014; Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim, 2015). Research has shown that recent scholars are primarily concerned about the effectiveness of IA and its process of ensuring the quality of financial reporting in becoming an integral component of the corporate governance (Badara, 2017; Mihret and Grant, 2017). For instance, IA failures are evident and have been recognised in many jurisdictions such as bank accountability and transparency deficiencies. Additionally, there are considerable challenges to overcome such as establishing a relationship between the risk management framework, strategic planning and enterprise

value model, while sound risk management should be implemented within a stated risk boundary.

Various philosophies are underlined by IA, which include accounting, reporting, explaining and justifying activities, and taking responsibility for outcomes (Lenz and Hahn, 2015). This recognition stems from the fact that IA is a key component of control infrastructure; therefore, IA should be able to examine any aspect of corporate operations. IA can focus on how it can bring value to organisations, for example, whether policies and procedures are adequate, secure and functioning as intended (Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema, 2012; Erasmus and Coetzee, 2018). In addition to being used to explore opportunities, IA is one of the key control mechanisms that has a major role to play in using risk-based audit plan, ensuring the effectiveness of corporate governance, and maintaining quality and assurance programme in organisations (Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012; Reding *et al.*, 2013). Thus, the focus should be on how organisations deal with the most important issues of good corporate governance, value creation, performance and growth in a way that is effective and acceptable.

Over the past few years, regulatory organisations have also expressed their views on IA. There is a desire to understand the role and consequences that IA has to discharge properly in its professional and statutory responsibilities. It has become evident that IA is not operating as expected to detect issues, errors and fraud (Chersan, 2016; Ismael and Roberts, 2018). Improving this situation has become a matter of concern, with a growing emphasis on the IA practice itself (Van Gansberghe, 2005; Van Schendelen, 2012). One problem that emerged from the IA literature is the need for more transparency, transformation and innovative services, which points to a new research opportunity (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013). This represents a particular set of challenges for proper and sound assessment of IA practices, which underlines an increased emphasis on the need for integrity and effectiveness. For instance, research conducted by Endaya and Hanefah (2013) and Chersan (2016) demonstrates that efforts are being made to enhance the effectiveness of IA as an essential guarantee for the proper functioning of internal control systems. However, there is an increasing awareness that this field is still under development and further empirical examination is needed.

Many academics are determined to understand and evaluate the effectiveness of IA (Lenz and Hahn, 2015; Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). It is evident that effectiveness and efficiency should be examined separately due to the fact that the audit could be effective but

inefficient (Beckmerhagen *et al.*, 2004). It is also possible that the audit is efficient and the auditors provide sufficient time to audit activities but the objectives are not met. Delivering effectiveness is more important than efficiency in organisations. No matter how efficient the audit is, if the IA is not effective it is useless for organisations (Bednarek, 2018). Despite these arguments in relation to the benefits of IA effectiveness, determining how effective IA procedures are and whether the results have been recognised is difficult for organisations. Current IA research does not always provide a clear explanation of the rationales and justifications for changes in IA practice. In this context, precise, realistic and straightforward indicators are required to assist organisations in measuring the efficacy of IA, as this is a critical component of understanding the drivers of the IA quality (Dittenhofer, 2001; Beckmerhagen *et al.*, 2004; Cohen and Sayag, 2010; IIA, 2016). IA should define performance metrics and related measurement criteria depending on its organisational context as its aims (IIA, 2016). However, the strategic value of IA serves as a metaphor for positive transformation in the banking sector, reinforcing its importance. This is achieved by implementing measures that result from the effectiveness and efficiency of IA, rather than viewing it negatively as a result of inefficiency and insignificance.

This research acknowledges that the ability of IA to change its effective audit environments (e.g. internal or external) is not to be presumed, as suggested in current IA research, but rather to be explored to uncover the complexities of its challenges and its effectiveness in practice. It is necessary to understand these issues because they may have consequences for the achievement of IA's objectives and how it is integrated into the current banking sector. In order to resolve some of the shortcomings in existing IA research (Chapter 2, Sections 2.4 and 2.7), this research provides an empirical analysis of IA by developing an effective framework for application to specific stakeholders, along with the ways in which they incorporate it into the internal and external environments across various jurisdictions. Thus, the aim of this research is to investigate how banks that are facing significant IA challenges can establish an Internal Banking Auditing (IBA) framework supported by practical guidance to help them.

The rest of this chapter discusses the structure of this research: definition of the research problem; relevance of the research significance; outline of the motivations for undertaking the research; examination of the research aim, objectives and questions; summary of the literature review; research methodology; and explanation of the contributions to the research.

1.2 Problem statement

IA is an essential component of the financial structure, with critical responsibilities for achieving sound financial management in the public and private sectors (Hermanson and Rittenberg, 2003; Eulerich and Lenz, 2019). Thus, it is necessary for IA to be effective because it can add value to an organisation's performance (Cohen and Sayag, 2010). The need for organisations to establish good internal control systems has caused them to reconsider their IA expectations (Radu, 2012). It is also acknowledged that policy and institutional expectations to maintain well-developed IA in organisations have increased due to accounting scandals, and legislative and professional responses, which emphasise IA as critical to support internal controls, risk management and corporate governance (Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone, 2006; Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim, 2015).

Research evidence identified that IA is one of the key pillars of corporate governance, which aimed at providing assurance on monitoring and internal controls, risk identification and assessment, management and communication processes, and timely advice to management and the board (Gramling *et al.*, 2004; Leung, Cooper and Perera, 2011). The increasing failures of IA practice, internal control systems and monitoring mechanisms have brought into question the effectiveness of IA (Allegrini *et al.*, 2006; Sinha and Arena, 2020). Although it is acknowledged that the effectiveness of IA has been widely debated in practice, studies in academic research have not focused on its challenges and it has thus remained under-explored and under-researched. To date, no research has been conducted to investigate the challenges facing IA and to establish an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance in a developing country context, specifically in Bangladesh in the banking sector.

Over the last two decades, IA has witnessed a fundamental shift in organisations concerned with the implementation of international norms and standards in legislation (Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Alhajri, 2017). The research evidence also suggests that the inefficiency in internal control systems has been debated to address the current state of IA standards in the banking sector in Bangladesh. In order to support this idea, a practical implementation is needed to ensure that the organisation's IA practices and internal control systems are more in line with the level of compliance with standards and how well the operations and systems work in terms of relationships with management and accountabilities. A number of worldwide accounting scandals have received much attention in recent years, including Bangladesh; these are outlined in Table 1.1. Collectively, these indicate that IA remains a very complex problem for a wide range of organisations around the world.

Table 1.1: Major accounting scandals

Accounting scandals	Year	Country	Accounting scandals	Year	Country
Northern Rock	2007	UK	Basic Bank	2013	Bangladesh
Satyam Computer	2009	India	Tesco Plc	2014	UK
Lehman Brothers	2010	USA	Toshiba	2015	Japan
Olympus Corporation	2011	Japan	BHS	2016	UK
HSBC, Lloyds, Barclays Bank	2012	UK	NRB Commercial Bank	2016	Bangladesh
J.P. Morgan	2012	UK	Farmers Bank	2017	Bangladesh
Royal Bank of Scotland	2012	UK	Janata Bank	2018	Bangladesh
Sonali Bank	2012	Bangladesh	Rupali Bank	2018	Bangladesh

Source: Adapted from the Centre for Policy Dialogue (2018)

Current literature on managerial auditing makes virtually no reference to appropriate IA implementation guidance as a possible method for solving problems and achieving management objectives. Under these circumstances, the practical implementation of IA has been monitored due to the growing number of cases of corruption, white-collar crimes, money laundering and accounting fraud in the context of banks. This illustrates that inadequate IA has led to the rise in financial fraud and corruption (Umar, 2011). Badara (2017) argues that Enron's bankruptcies, financial mismanagement and fraudulent activities have increased the need for WorldCom and other institutions to ensure that there is no corporate oversight or inadequate corporate review. The rising attention on the effectiveness of IA is a concerning matter, as it is a key issue for organisations in preventing new scandals because of corporate crises, financial reporting failures and financial scandals (Abuazza *et al.*, 2015; Camfferman and Wielhouwer, 2019).

To the best of the Researcher's knowledge, there is no widely accepted framework, methods or techniques for effectively addressing IA challenges. Also, the literature evidence suggests that there is no widely recognised approach, tools or techniques to identify and evaluate IA challenges and practices (Arena and Azzone 2009; Endaya and Hanefah, 2013). Limited research discussed the problematic issues of IA effectiveness, which used various approaches to analyse IA practices. For example, Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2018) examined the effect of environmental factors on IA practice, while Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam (2003) and Yee *et al.* (2008) used the International Standards for the Professional Practice of Internal Auditing (ISPPPIA) to examine and assess the effectiveness of IA. Scholars have established conceptual frameworks to determine IA effectiveness without examining the empirical evidence (Arena and Azzone, 2009; Endaya and Hanefah, 2013).

A series of global banking and financial crises, continuing financial scandals and accountability failures in large organisations have been observed as reflecting ineffective governance, lack of risk management, inadequate control measures and poor compliance control processes (Kirkpatrick, 2009). This indicates a very competitive market environment and a crisis of confidence among modern-day corporate leaders as well as a number of major changes to the legislation and governance processes that are required. Despite the importance of avoiding fraud, banking organisations are reluctant to invest in controlling and improving the governance system. A significant finding shows that there is little interest in developing an auditor's efficiency, skills and competencies (Rijamampianina, 2016).

Although IA has played an important role in internal governance and control systems, other aspects have all contributed to an increase in the pace of emerging risks that could threaten the stability and governance of organisations (Lenz and Jeppesen, 2022). These include economic changes, increased reliance on technology, new market and product opportunities, increased regulation, changing workplace behaviour and the pace of organisational change (Shahimi, Mahzan and Zulkifli, 2016). Specifically, this research is focused on the notion that the value of effective IA and public awareness of its inefficiency have not led to a prior analysis of the challenges IA faces in banks in Bangladesh. This notion is reinforced by the significance of IA, which cannot be overemphasised due to the fact that IA activities have been recognised by organisations as a mechanism for ensuring the efficient functioning of internal control systems (Singh and Newby, 2010; Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Alhajri, 2017).

Therefore, the purpose of this research is to enable the Researcher to improve research expertise by investigating and evaluating current challenges of IA in the context of the banking sector. This will be accomplished by reviewing significant academic and industry-based contributions, identifying gaps in the literature and establishing an effective IBA framework supported by practical implementation guidance.

1.3 Research significance

The significance of this research can be seen from both theoretical and practical viewpoints (Eulerich and Eulerich, 2020; Rousey, Barbe and Raimbault, 2020). From a theoretical point of view, this research endorses how institutional theory offers a discipline focused on the effectiveness of IA and helps to investigate the current challenges associated with the banking sector. It also looks at how the principles of IA practices ingenuity helps to overcome the challenges faced during the IA's development and implementation of its activities. From

a practical viewpoint, the main goal is to see if IA practice can improve and strengthen the effectiveness and efficiency of IA by developing and implementing an IBA framework that meets stakeholder expectations while also meeting the strategic vision of the top management to survive in the current risk and control environment.

It is critical for the IA to demonstrate its effectiveness and efficiency in the banking sector in Bangladesh, especially following incidents, such as accounting failures in several banks in recent years. It has been argued that problems arise when internal auditors issue risk warnings but top management does not change its course of action, resulting in significant organisational failures (Roussy, Barbe and Raimbault, 2020). This raises concerns about internal auditor's capabilities, which underpin the need to assess and evaluate IA's effectiveness and efficiency. Nonetheless, recent debates have argued that a digitalised organisational environment has a significant impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of IA, affecting its scope, agility of IA planning, and its effective implementation in banks, particularly in Bangladesh. Therefore, the growing need for digital literacy is expected to increase, emphasising the impact of information technology (IT) risks, such as cybersecurity threats (Betti and Sarens, 2020; Lenz and Hoos, 2023). Furthermore, the presence of digital resources and capacity constraints, such as insufficient IA staffing, inadequate IT skills and knowledge, and a lack of professional qualifications, is essential for addressing the increased risks and complexities associated with IT operations in banks in Bangladesh. This also limits the ability to implement risk-based audit methodologies because of the lack of expertise in carrying out transformational actions.

Given the high level of unpredictability in banking organisations, it is necessary to consider adopting an agile and adaptable approach that emphasises incorporating flexibility into their operations to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the IA. They should adopt a unified, predictive and proactive approach to respond to unprecedented disruptions, such as environmental changes, liquidity crises, capital shortages and cyberattacks, and operate effectively in the face of such disruptions. In this regard, banks should adopt a more forward-thinking approach to manage IA activities and make strategic decisions to tackle technological risks, digital disruption, and governance failures, which result in a lack of process optimisation. This can be accomplished by leveraging data analytics and cognitive technologies to gain insights, identify key risk factors, implement an efficient talent management model, and acknowledge that both internal and external environments can be sustained by tackling the challenges and opportunities for implementing an effective IA framework in the banking sector in Bangladesh.

This investigation provides a thorough examination of the current state of IA, emphasising the development of an effective IBA framework in this field. The main areas of focus are the challenges that IA face, the consequences of IA practices, and the effectiveness and efficiency of IA in banks in Bangladesh. These aspects shed light on IA in Bangladesh, which has slowed the progress in IA practices and still necessitates the creation of a sustainable environment for conducting IA, with a systematic investigation of how this research helps improve the effectiveness and efficiency of IA. This research provides valuable insights into the systematic evolution and advancements in IA research, which can help develop and validate an IBA framework to improve IA performance effectively in the banking sector. This review emphasises the importance of increasing adherence to existing frameworks to improve IA operations and advance the implementation of IA in response to internal and external environmental changes.

This research also offers empirical evidence on how IA challenges adhere to current frameworks amongst banks in Bangladesh. This should provide evidence of the necessity to integrate IA practices and internal control systems. The combination of institutional and ingenuity theories should help IA research to examine the key shortcomings that could be identified by the implementation of IA and the components of the internal control systems in the banking sector. Mihret, James and Mula (2012) indicate that further research is needed in the field of IA practice. While previous researchers concentrated on IA practice and applied quantitative approaches, qualitative methods need to be utilised going forward (Eulerich and Eulerich, 2020). The aim of this research is, therefore, to fill the research gap by investigating the current challenges of IA in banks and to contribute to the literature by combining institutional and ingenuity theories to understand the internal governance mechanism in a developing country context, specifically in Bangladesh.

This research should be considered worthy of inclusion in the IA literature for a number of reasons. Since IA is a part of the internal control systems, the unsuccessful practice of IA can, in turn, lead to weaknesses in these control systems. Thus, it is important to understand the process of IA to strengthen the internal control systems. This would improve internal control mechanisms, leading to higher performance and helping to minimise malpractice, fraud and corruption. Current research evidence also points out the complexity of internal control systems in achieving consistency (Islam and Stafford, 2021). In this regard, this research should provide useful guidance for IA practitioners, regulatory organisations and professional associations in creating new standards for internal auditors to help them

strengthen their attention or awareness in order to deliver transparent services to auditees and stakeholders.

To summarise, this research contributes to the IA knowledge base by providing a contemporary perspective on the current literature and state of IA practice. It presents evidence to identify research gaps and highlights the necessity of developing an IBA framework supported by practical guidance, emphasising the significance of a paradigm shift in corporate governance. Therefore, this research provides compelling arguments that lead to an understanding of how IA should be sustained in banking organisations over time and what significant measures should be taken to improve its effectiveness. Also, it assists in determining current challenges that impede IA practices, thus expanding the current literature domain that appears insufficient.

1.4 Research motivation

The motivation for undertaking IA research in the context of developing an effective framework supported by practical guidance is related to the high level of attention given to this issue in the banking sector, both within professional auditing practice and by other audit groups. Related stakeholders, such as government regulators, professional bodies, independent auditing organisations and academics, have made significant IA statements in a number of ways. Apart from making a substantial investment in IA and promoting it in policy manuals and public documents, independent auditing organisations have also carried out different research projects utilising surveys to highlight the relevance, impact and future of IA on different industries (KPMG, 2014; PwC, 2016). The government regulatory bodies and professional bodies have also followed a similar strategy to generate a variety of evidence based on the consequences of IA for the banking sector. Such studies provide insight into the theoretical discussions taking place on IA (ICAEW, 2016; FRC, 2017; IIA, 2018).

The existing literature indicates that it is necessary to understand and measure the competitiveness and soundness of the banking sector by focusing on aspects of corporate governance that influence the performance of the banks (Rashid, Zobair and Chowdhury, 2020). Changes to existing regulations and the creation of new policies have brought new dimensions and challenges for banks, increasing the competitive environment with significant emerging risks. The literature also suggests that the strategy and efficiency of existing and new banks are likely to vary in the short term; however, they should converge over time (Jokipii and Rautiainen, 2023). Also, these normative reasons for IA have been

repeated in the official documents of the standard setters because if the strategy and efficiency that occur in banks should encounter significant deficiencies in effective internal control systems and auditing standards, this may lead to questions in relation to transparency, accountability and significant pressure from stakeholders.

In this context, the banking system has highlighted unprecedented changes in Bangladesh, moving to a market-based open economy, adopting a more stable, liberal, and deregulated programme under the influence of the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (Sufian and Kamarudin, 2013). As auditing policies were implemented in 1991 with a view to achieving greater output and developing a competitive banking environment, further evaluations were needed on a regional and global basis. Due to a lack of empirical research at the practitioner level, the current body of knowledge should be considered useful in enhancing the effectiveness of IA performed in banking organisations. This research identifies an increased need for a framework to prevent auditing scandals or auditing failures, to comply with auditing standards and to determine what the stakeholders' expectations are in IA in banks in Bangladesh. Thus, the IBA framework should be validated by means of experiment and provide clear and succinct practical guidance that should be able to help organisations assess the effectiveness of IA, as it is the key aspect of recognising the current challenges of IA.

This research addresses significant issues that impede the creation of sound IA, which involve an understanding within the broader context of the institutional framework and regulatory environment in banks. The aim of this research is, therefore, to decide whether IA is creating an innovative and robust approach to manage the institutional weakness and to concentrate on developing an IBA framework supported by practical guidance for the banking sector and the scholastic community. In order to accomplish the above, this research sets out its aim, research questions and objectives in the following sections.

1.5 Research questions

The following research questions are developed by considering the phenomenon and the research problem stated above:

- What are the main challenges facing IA in banks in general and in Bangladesh, specifically?
- What are the key factors that affect the current IA practices in banks and in Bangladesh?
- How can the effectiveness of IA in banks and in Bangladesh be enhanced?

- How effective is the current IBA framework in general and in Bangladesh?

1.6 Research aim and objectives

The aim of this research is to investigate the challenges facing IA in the banking sector and to develop an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance. More precisely, the broad objectives of this research are as follows:

- To identify and evaluate the current challenges of IA in banks;
- To analyse the current practices of IA in banks;
- To evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh in order to develop an effective IBA framework.

The aforementioned objectives are intended to identify how this large-scale research will answer the research questions effectively and efficiently supported by empirical evidence. The above research questions are further addressed in Chapter 7, followed by an interpretation of the thematic results on the identified research gaps by considering responses to questions and statements posed in semi-structured interviews. Table 1.2 demonstrates how the research objectives were met. The first and second objectives of this research are presented in Chapter 2 (Literature Review). Chapter 3 (the development of the IBA framework) meets the third objective, which also includes the collection of primary data from semi-structured interviews and validation of the IBA framework supported by practical guidance.

Table 1.2: Operationalisation of the research objectives

Research aim	Research objectives	How they have been met
To investigate the challenges facing IA in the banking sector and to develop an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance.	Identify and evaluate the current challenges of IA in banks	Literature review (Chapter 2)
	Analyse the current practices of IA in banks	Literature review (Chapter 2)
	Evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh to develop an effective IBA framework	Chapter 3 and collection of primary data utilising semi-structured interviews to validate the IBA framework derived from Chapters 2 and 3

Source: The Researcher

1.7 Literature review

A comprehensive review of the literature was conducted to gain a thorough understanding of IA in various contexts. In the United Kingdom, research analysis included Ismael and Robert (2018). In the United States, studies by Gramling *et al.* (2004), Chambers and Odar (2015) and Abbott *et al.* (2016), were included. In other countries, including Australia, Bangladesh, China, Germany, Italy, Iran, Israel, India, Malaysia, New Zealand, Nigeria, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and the Netherlands, the literature review included studies by Siddiqui and Podder (2002), Zain, Subramaniam and Stewart (2006), Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2009), Leung, Cooper and Perera (2011) and Zaman and Sarens (2013). A review of the current IA environment in Bangladesh, which is focused on the regulatory environment and institutional framework supported by the summary of literature evidence, has also been undertaken.

Historically, the aim of IA has been to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of organisations by implementing, monitoring and enforcing accounting and auditing standards for financial reporting (Gamayuni, 2018). This consists of five key components: verification of written records, policy analysis, procedure evaluation, internal services and staffing (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013). Thus, it is claimed that the most commonly used measures of IA relate to its efficiency in terms of delivering the annual IA work plan, and accepting and adopting the IA charter. The stakeholders' perspective on the effectiveness of IA is rarely considered in current literature (Lenz and Hahn, 2015). Despite the assertions of others that developments in IA are intended to address the operational and structural dimensions of the audit profession, they have been described as a desire to address the issue of audit procedure for the establishment of IA effectiveness (ICAEW, 2015). In this regard, Arena and Azzone (2007) suggest that future research could address the issue of IA's effectiveness. Siddiqui and Podder (2002) conducted additional research in this area, identifying the need for auditor independence, objectivity and competence. Thus, the modern approach shifted the emphasis to the resilient influence of internal control systems.

Internal control mechanisms had a greater impact on audit work efficiency and had a direct impact on bank's operations (Hazaea *et al.*, 2023). Effective internal control systems may have an impact on the effectiveness of internal auditors (Badara and Saidin, 2013). Mastan *et al.* (2015) identifies adequate and suitable resources, professional personnel, an independent AC and an IA charter as IA success factors. These factors have been introduced to facilitate the equal role of corporate governance to IA by monitoring risks and ensuring the reliability of financial reporting (Zohra and Huq, 2014). Previous research has

suggested that the commercial objectives of the organisation doing the audit are met (audit organisation), in addition to the relevance of IA practice in meeting regulatory concerns. For example, Mihret, James and Mula (2012) state that it is critical to investigate the practice of IA using institutional theory because it should allow researchers to decode motivations for implementing structural elements. Despite the fact that auditing practices are socially constructed, Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi (2020) claims that there is a lack of qualitative research to address the problematic issues of IA.

Despite the fact that IA is part of a larger context of previous developments in internal control systems, it requires scholarly attention to fully understand its significance and impact. Prior developments in internal control systems have been introduced, accompanied by similar justifications, prompting other scholars to speculate that there are more control systems than just operational efficiency. These studies focused on comprehending the conceptual and operational functions of internal control systems as well as providing institutional explanations for changes in audit practice (DeFond and Zhang, 2014). It has been argued that these control systems are used to legitimise the audit profession by depicting representations of scientific rationality associated with audit expertise (Power, 2003; Mennicken, 2008). Such auditing representations are required if the profession is to resolve regulatory oversight in the face of public scrutiny (Curtis and Turley, 2007). Thus, this research looked beyond IA's organisational justification to understand the complexities of its formulation and implementation.

Several theories, including the role theory (Mokhitli and Kyobe, 2019), the stakeholder theory (Erasmus and Coetzee, 2018), the agency theory (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011), institutional theory (Ahmad, 2015), the stewardship theory and the contingency theory (Badara, 2017) have been used to explain IA issues. Nonetheless, the theoretical focus of previous audit-related work is based on the agency theory (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011). It has been argued that the agency theory concept focuses primarily on the standard principal-agent relationship; thus, it is insufficient to address IA research from a variety of perspectives and contexts, particularly in the investigation of IA effectiveness (Mihret, James and Mula, 2012; Alqudah, Amran and Hassan, 2019). Given the broader context of this research to investigate the challenges affecting the effectiveness of IA in banks, it is most appropriate to apply a combination of theories (i.e. institutional and ingenuity theories), which is discussed in detail in Chapter 3 (Sub-Section 3.2.2).

To comprehend the reasons for IA effectiveness, researchers must first adopt a theoretical framework that considers institutional phenomena to be its domain. Given the fundamental belief of institutional and ingenuity theories that the institutional environment is socially constructed, this research argues that these theories are the best fit for developing an IBA framework in banks. While previous research has taken an approach that incorporates theories in the development of a theoretical framework, no attention has been given to the effectiveness of IA in the context of a developed framework (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Badara and Saidin, 2013; Endaya and Hanefah, 2013; Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). Therefore, the purpose of this research is to fill that gap by conducting research based on a systematic approach that combines theories in the IA domain.

To summarise, the evidence presented above suggests that there is a theoretical-practical gap in identifying the challenges and the practice of IA, which creates uncertainty about the extent to which IA is used effectively as an indispensable element and audit mechanism to achieve the development and well performance of sound corporate governance. The theoretical evidence that guides practices and training is significant; this theoretical-practical gap allows for more evidence-based practice to be explored. Few studies have been carried out to bridge the theoretical-practical divide (Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Alhajri, 2017; Sinha and Arena, 2018). Furthermore, researchers have called for additional research to bridge this knowledge gap.

1.8 Research contribution

The argument for creating value to avoid accounting scandals and decrease failures in organisations highlights the need for the reliable and systematic implementation of IA, and an effective framework supported by practical guidance in the banking sector. To support this notion, this research contributes insights into the current IA challenges and practices, especially with regard to the use of institutional approaches in both theoretical and empirical aspects that are not yet adequately researched. Considering research in this area has been predominantly practice-based and conducted by major auditing and consulting organisations such as the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), Deloitte, Ernst & Young (EY), PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG) and Protiviti (Kasim *et al.*, 2012). These studies are limited to descriptive content and lack empirical evidence. Thus, key contributions arising from the achievement of this research aim can be summarised as follows:

- A significant contribution is made to the literature on theoretical aspects through an extensive review of various IA principles, themes and issues. This can be accomplished by conducting a systematic literature investigation of academic and industry-based literature and recognising the importance of internal and external elements in adopting and implementing IA in the banking sector;
- A substantial contribution is made to the literature by proposing an IBA framework (Figure 3.4) for the banking sector. The aim of this framework supported by practical guidance that can be customised and affects each organisation differently in the naturally complex interactions between internal and external environments, while ensuring effective leadership in top management and efficient internal control systems;
- This research contributes to a better understanding of the IA process and the necessity of the internal control systems in banks. The Researcher's aim is to highlight key IA elements by providing prescriptive guidance on how to accomplish them by recognising their benefits and challenges. This can be achieved by conducting theoretical and empirical research within the areas of IA and corporate governance. Thus, this research provides banking professionals and scholars with practical recommendations on how to effectively implement IA elements;
- This research exemplifies the use of qualitative approaches and thematic data interpretation deemed most appropriate for such a heterogeneous field and thereby deepen understanding of IA practices across banking organisations. Based on the analysis, the majority of IA research is conducted theoretically and/or quantitatively in nature. This research contributes to the literature by applying both primary (qualitative methods) and secondary (systematic literature evaluation) data collection techniques;
- Finally, the empirical findings of this research should be applied to the interpretation and improvement of IA regulations. Given this fact and the difficulties associated with practicing IA, the results may provide guidance to regulatory bodies such as the Ministry of Finance or the Institute of Internal Auditors of Bangladesh (IIAB), in revising the IIA standards or implementing a new, effective framework. The findings also include practitioners' perspectives on the IA concept, practical difficulties and critical internal-external factors that may impede effective IA practice.

1.9 Methodological approach

It has become more difficult to recognise which of the methodological paradigms is best applied in developing a research project, as research in accounting and auditing has become increasingly complex (Baker, 2001; Lenz and Jeppesen, 2022). In this research, the Researcher employed an interpretive research philosophy and a qualitative approach to collect empirical evidence by addressing the research questions set out in Section 1.5 and achieving the research objectives outlined in Section 1.6. Selecting qualitative research is concerned with the motivations and causes of human behaviour by asking ‘what’, ‘how’, and ‘why’ inquiries regarding human actions to the subject matter by applying a naturalistic approach (Creswell, 2014). In this section, the methodological approaches have been summarised by this research, which is further discussed in greater detail in Chapter 4. The purpose of this section is to discuss some of the specific methods and strategies that can be employed in the design and interpretation of this research (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: The research framework design

Source: Adapted from Creswell (2014)

Inductive and deductive reasoning are the two basic research approaches for academic research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). By starting with specific data, discovering patterns, making hypotheses and finally deriving conclusions, inductive reasoning aims to theoretically generalise. As inductive reasoning is typically connected with qualitative methodologies, it is generally appropriate for this research. In contrast, deductive reasoning is a top-down strategy in which researchers develop a hypothesis (or hypotheses) based on existing theory and then design a research strategy to test the hypothesis, thus confirming or questioning the original theory. Quantitative methods are commonly used in deductive research (Patton, 2002; Wilson 2010). As previously stated, qualitative research entails

examining the research subject's natural environment to comprehend occurrences (Lichtman, 2014). Individuals should be investigated in their natural settings and inside their reality, which is an important component of qualitative research (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Lichtman, 2014). Researchers can also explore the subject 'in depth and in detail' using qualitative methodologies (Patton, 2002, p. 93).

This research's exploratory design is divided into two stages (Figure 1.2). The aim of the first stage is to investigate the current challenges of IA and to develop the theoretical IBA framework that creates a foundation for effective IA practice in banks. In the second stage, this theoretical IBA framework is further validated through conducting semi-structured interviews and analysing thematic data, which is presented in Chapter 6. To accomplish the research objectives and answer the main research question, an interview guide is developed to collect the primary data (Appendix). In a similar manner, Rijamampianina (2016) investigates critical success criteria in conducting IA evaluations of the capital markets in underdeveloped countries using qualitative interviews. This research also focused on gathering published secondary sources of data analysis from a variety of academic and industry-based publications, which establishes a critical foundation for developing a theoretical framework (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013) through a systematic review of literature (Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020) and conducting an empirical investigation to gain insights into subjective experiences, opinions and motivations collected from qualitative research (Walonick, 1993). To answer the aim and questions, this research applied an exploratory research design as illustrated in Figure 1.2 below.

Figure 1.2. Qualitative research design

Source: The Researcher

The empirical stage is conducted in collaboration with appropriate IA professionals, such as the AC members, chartered accountants and bank professionals, while the data is collected using semi-structured interviews. The theoretical IBA framework is further modified and validated in the second stage depending on the responses of participants who have extensive experience in the IA development and implementation in their prospective organisations. The qualitative technique of thematic analysis (TA) is chosen as the method of analysing data. Understanding how to use a 'rigorous thematic approach to provide meaningful analysis that addresses specific research questions' is essential (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 97). Furthermore, by allowing an assessment of the interview data from two perspectives, this approach complements the research questions. First, the data is used to explore the current challenges and practices of IA in the banking sector, which generate a perspective based on inductive coding. Second, the data is examined for consistency with the research questions and if the data gives sufficient information from the standpoint of the research questions.

The Researcher aims to provide links between the phenomena with current IA frameworks in academic and industry-based contributions in addition to describing the empirical data. This qualitative data should help researchers to gain a better understanding of the extent of IA research and the reasons why it differs from theoretical discoveries. Finally, the Researcher verifies that the entire process is conducted in accordance with the approval of research ethics (University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Code of Ethics) and that confidentiality and data security are maintained.

1.10 Research limitations

This research is constrained by time, money and the unprecedented worldwide disruption due to the COVID-19 pandemic in recent years. Thus, the scope of this research is limited to the theories underlying IA's ability to conduct large-scale research. Also, since this research examines the results of semi-structured interviews, generalisations are not possible. This investigation makes no mention of whether the IBA framework implementation and outcomes of IA and internal control systems are comparable to those used by a number of banks in the context of Bangladesh. Furthermore, this research is limited by a few implications, which are summarised as follows:

- First, there is a risk that the qualitative data intended to be collected by conducting interviews with various participants involved in developing the IBA framework might not be available for the interviews, which implies that although various

participants will be interviewed, they may not give sufficient information for qualitative data collection;

- Second, the data gathered through interviews is to be analysed using thematic analysis techniques. There is a possibility that the analytical approach may not produce the desired data, particularly if the data is too complex to analyse;
- Third, due to the worldwide COVID-19 disruption, including Bangladesh, obtaining information on conducting face-to-face interviews is expected to be difficult. However, the Researcher believes in conducting interviews with IA professionals from the banking sector as well as engaging in conversations with various other groups within and outside the banking sector.

1.11 Research outline

This section provides an overview of the research contents as well as the structure for organising and presenting the large-scale research in detail. Figure 1.3 illustrates the structure of the seven chapters in this research and is discussed by a summary of their contents.

Chapter 1 establishes the problem statement, the research aim, objectives and questions; explains the motivations, significance and contributions of this research; evaluates the summary of the literature review; discusses the summary of the adopted methodology and methods of this research; and provides the overall structure of how current IA challenges are to be explored and the IBA framework to be validated.

Chapter 2 establishes the literature review that serves as the theoretical foundation for this research. This chapter examines the concept, nature and development of the IA discipline, and academic and industrial-based contributions. This chapter also examines the key IA challenges and current practices supported by literature evidence. The theoretical background to IA, empirical contributions and the identification of initial gaps in the existing literature are key highlights of this chapter.

Chapter 3 assesses the derivation of developing the theoretical IBA framework; applies the four-quadrant framework, categorises the contribution of academic and industry-based literature; and highlights the systematic literature gap, which helps to determine potential motivations and opportunities for further research. This chapter also analyses the current IA frameworks and synthesises framework gaps to propose the theoretical IBA framework supported by key elements with justification.

Figure 1.3: The research outline

Source: The Researcher

Chapter 4 discusses and justifies the research methodology and methods. This chapter begins with a review of the relevant research philosophy, followed by a discussion of research design. This chapter describes the various aspects of conducting this research, including the research approach, strategy, data collection methods, data analysis

techniques and the research quality including reliability, validity and ethical considerations of this research.

Chapter 5 investigates the findings of this research. The interview results are classified into the two sections of the theoretical IBA framework. Themes and sub-themes are identified that correspond to the interview questions. Initially, a number of opposing and confirming viewpoints are presented, which are divided into two parts for understanding and clarity.

Chapter 6 elaborates on the findings of the qualitative data analysis and its implications that are used to validate the IBA framework for the banking sector. Following the findings, this research is thoroughly discussed and analysed, supported by the responses of the participants. The validated IBA framework is then presented a practical implementation guidance and the outputs of the IBA framework at the end of this chapter.

Finally, this research is summarised in Chapter 7. It includes a detailed research conclusion, a review of the research aim and objectives, key findings and answers to research questions, research contributions, research limitations and recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a review of the main research contributions made within the context of previous IA literature by leading academic and industry-based researchers to address the following:

- The concept, nature and development of the IA discipline over the last two decades;
- Literature contributions on IA focusing on the challenges of practicing IA: the effectiveness of IA; the alignment of IA with key functions, structure and process and current practices of IA.

The identification and review of major research contributions are examined through the analysis of academic and industry-based IA literature. In this chapter, a comprehensive analysis is established and key shortcomings are discussed by revealing the current IA challenges and practices for future development. This also requires a systematic literature review (SLR), where the research evidence collected is summarised and conducted with a level of thoroughness to achieve the research aim and objectives (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). This approach, shown in Figure 2.1, is divided into five phases.

Figure 2.1: Systematic review methodology

Source: Adapted from Denyer and Tranfield (2009)

This systematic investigation focuses on the general concept and nature of IA, followed by a detailed examination of its effectiveness in the current practices in the banking sector. The complexity of the banking sector is subject to explicit regulation and thus, this chapter aims to serve as a baseline for developing the theoretical IBA framework presented in Chapter 3. The systematic investigation approach is thought to be useful for supplementing the literature, resulting in more systematic and knowledgeable research contributions (Eulerich and Lenz, 2019). Such an approach is used to overcome arguments (Aspters and Corte, 2019). This chapter also summarises the gaps identified in current IA research in comparison to existing literature on contemporary IA challenges.

2.2 Concept and nature of IA

Traditionally, IA has been viewed as a useful tool for assisting administrations in examining regulatory policies to control organisational governance and operations as well as ensuring asset protection and the efficiency of data contained in accounting records to increase possible productivity. Previous literature identifies numerous rationales that may be ascribed to emphasis compliance assurance, financial control and safeguarding resources while dealing with regulatory requirements (Allegrini *et al.*, 2006). The argument is that credible audits would allow internal auditors to meet professional demands, whereby IA creates an imperative for a more systematic, structured and objective assessment of the various operations and controls within organisations (Sawyer, 2003). As a result of this formalisation, more implied rationales are incorporated to assess if (i) operational and financial information is reliable and accurate, (ii) risks to the organisation are defined and minimised, (iii) appropriate internal policies and procedures, including external regulations, are followed, (iv) adequate operational requirements are met, (v) resources are used cost-effectively and efficiently, and (vi) the goals of the organisation are efficiently accomplished with a view to working with management and supporting leaders in the successful execution of their management obligations (Sawyer, 2003).

Over the last two decades, a feature of the IA literature has undergone considerable changes as its value-added potential has increased, resulting in an expansion of the scope of engagement. It is debated in the literature that IA is being forced to realign their practices due to evolving risks and new audit objectives that have developed in technological advancements and a rapidly changing macro environment (Hazaea *et al.*, 2023). To address this development, the introduction of internal control systems has been used to provide assurance and insight into the IA process and structure with a focus on driving organisations towards success (Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema, 2012). Negakis

and Tachinakis (2013) note that IA is conducted by a practitioner with clear scientific and technical experience who is an employee of the audited organisation. In the practice of IA, the definition and standards serve as authoritative references (Bou-Raad, 2000; Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012). The IIA described IA as ‘... an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve operations in organisations. It also enables organisations to achieve its objectives by using a structured and organised approach to evaluating and improving the effectiveness of risk management, control and governance processes.’ (2018, p. 11).

When the IIA first adopted a new definition of IA, managers and the BOD found that the new definition was actually compatible with practice (Nagy and Cenker, 2002). This IA definition explicitly sets out the objective of adding value to organisations, which enhances the quality of insights and knowledge for decision-making (Badara and Saidin, 2013). Internal auditors should be involved in all aspects of the organisation’s activities, offering assurance and advisory services to establish and maintain effective internal controls. Such practices should be carried out independently and objectively (Siddiqui and Podder, 2002). This is a significant issue for IA activities, including GRC that have been carried out with a consultative approach and an emphasis on efficiency and effectiveness of operations. Thus, current IA practice necessitates internal auditors having extensive knowledge and expertise in the field (Moeller, 2009). The concept of IA encompasses a number of key elements, including its independence and objectivity in nature for effective operations, functions and methods of monitoring activities, which are outlined in the following Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Reflection on the conceptual characteristics of IA

Sources	Meaning of Judgements
Robertson (1983)	IA is an independent activity to verify and evaluate the organisation’s work in its interests. The purpose of IA is to help members of the organisation to perform their functions effectively. Internal auditors submit to their organisation’s analysis and evaluation data, recommendations and other necessary information resulting from the audit.
Yoo, Lyytinen and Berente (2007)	IA is an integral part of enterprise management control. The main tasks of IA are the solution of individual functional management problems and the development and verification of enterprise information systems.

International Standards on Auditing (2009)	IA is a control system organised at an economic entity in the interests of its owners and regulated by its internal documents that complies with the established accounting procedure and the reliability of the internal control systems. Institutions of IA include auditors appointed by the owners of an economic entity, audit commissions, internal auditors or groups of internal auditors.
Protiviti (2015)	<p>IA is an element of the internal control systems in an enterprise. IA services are created at large enterprises with an extensive network of branches. The tasks of IA services may include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - confirmation of the accuracy of the information provided to management; - control over the condition and safety of assets; - executive control; - assessment of the effectiveness of management, production and financial investments. <p>IA is not independent; it is subordinate to the organisation's management – acts in accordance with its task and reports to it. At the same time, the IA is independent to those persons whose activities it verifies.</p>
IIA (2017)	IA is the activity of providing independent and objective guarantees and consultations aimed at improving the organisation.
IIA (2020)	To enhance and protect organisational value by providing risk-based and objective assurance, advice and insight.
Comptroller and Auditor General of Bangladesh (CAGB) (2018)	<p>The objectives and scope of work of the IA service usually includes assurance and consulting activities aimed at evaluating and improving the effectiveness of corporate GRC as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - events related to corporate governance; - activities related to risk management; - activities related to internal control.

Source: The Researcher

Table 2.1 shows that the characteristics' evaluation of IA is capable of a wide range of activities and that IA is an activity concerned with determining the efficiency and effectiveness of internal control systems, following financial and operational compliance laws, rules and regulations. However, empirical research indicates that IA is a crucial foundation of good corporate governance.

A research study by Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2018) shows that IA can be defined by the range of risks identified and by the review of internal control systems in organisations. This demonstrates risk management, compliance and internal control evaluations as major

elements of its audit work throughout the organisation, but it also performs peripheral work such as helping with fraud investigations and consultation. Such IA is guided by process optimisation to identify risks and internal controls set by management for individual departments to assess whether the controls are sufficient to reduce risk to an acceptable level (Anderson *et al.*, 2017). As previously stated, the analysis of the management's policies and standards resulted in the development of an audit plan that supported the IA's worth as a valuable monitoring instrument (Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012).

The literature identifies IA as having suffered from a lack of attention due to an apparent absence of an organised strategy, a clearly defined position and an apparent lack of stature supported by a solid, generally recognised professional programme. Despite the fact that there is yet to be a comprehensive consensus on the role of IA, management has expressed considerable support in prior research, especially when compared to other aspects of corporate governance such as the AC and external auditor (Stewart and Subramaniam, 2010; Christ *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, the perceived lack of strong professional leadership in organisations has complicated a lack of perceived significance and a lack of consensus on the position (Cooper, Leung and Wong, 2006). This is aggravated by the concept of IA, which encompasses both consulting expectations and the function of assurance (Yee *et al.*, 2008; Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). However, it is argued that there is controversy among internal auditors about how to achieve independence in both roles (Mihret and Woldeyohannis, 2008).

Eulerich and Lenz (2019) examine the factors related to the role of IA in leading efforts towards a more integrated approach. This research is critical for understanding that IA allows assurance mapping to ensure coverage across organisations from various roles and other entities, whether internal or external environments, and that it is effective, sufficient, secure, accurate and aligned with the organisational objectives. As a major provider of objective assurance, IA should provide better management assurance and serve as a guarantee that the governing body and the organisation obtain the necessary level of assurance across all activities and capabilities (Marais *et al.*, 2009; Chersan, 2016). The literature evidence argues that internal auditors should focus on areas that are considered important for ensuring or obtaining the necessary skills and competencies needed to fulfil responsibilities set out in the IA definition and its standards.

Due to management constraints (PwC, 2018), internal auditors are not capable of working independently as there may be significant risks in conducting the audit work that affects the

outcome. This implies implementing multiple IA functions as a provider of assurance services or consultancy, which can increase independence when evaluating the perceived status of IA activities within a specific audit programme in organisations. To be recognised as a value-added service for organisations, IA must be effective for strategic benefits, improving performance, aligning resources and the ability to face unexpected challenges and demands in deviations (Al-Twajjry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003; Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). It is, therefore, necessary for organisations to plan an audit programme, define and review the internal control systems and establish a sound governance structure to achieve the independence of IA. This motivation, which results in many different practices of independence and objectivity, assurance, and consultancy activities, is considered another important feature of the integrity that is expected of IA. These are covered in the following sub-sections.

2.2.1 Independence and objectivity

The absence of conditions that jeopardise the ability of IA activities to carry out their obligations objectively is defined as independence (IIA, 2013). Scholars such as Sarens and De Beelde (2006) and Stewart and Subramaniam (2010) have demonstrated that a variety of individual and organisational factors influence this independence to maintain a perceived status. For example, there has been little evidence in recent years as to whether internal auditors are free from pressure by senior management in areas such as audit procedures, audit scope limitations, personnel management processes, time constraints and resources, conflicting duties, audit activities and staff involvement (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009). However, internal auditors should be able to express their opinions without fear of repercussions or jeopardising their position because they are independent.

Traditionally, IA independence has included organisational independence, also known as an IA department's organisational position within an organisation and the objectivity of internal auditors in audit work (Suwaidan and Qasim, 2010). In this regard, organisational independence is linked to the confirmation of audit findings and the supervision of the IA department (Dunn, 1996). Internal auditors have sufficient power in their organisational standing to work efficiently and fulfil commitments, which are the primary reasons for maintaining and strengthening IA independence. However, internal auditors' independence is affected by a lack of understanding of their role and reporting lines to management (Al-Twajjry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003). The lack of IA independence could be caused due to restricted access to management and essential documents, limited support from

management and a lack of awareness of the role (Alzeban, 2015; Al-Akra, Abdel-Qadera and Billahb, 2016).

In practice, IA is broadening to compensate for the loss of control caused by the significant complexity of its operations (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006). Internal auditors are frequently expected to participate in day-to-day management activities rather than provide a function of processes (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009). Such management expectations pose a serious threat to the scope of the internal auditor's work. In addition to adhering to professional standards, internal auditors are expected to recognise and manage any threat to independence and objectivity. Social constraints on internal auditor involvement, such as interactions between internal and external auditors, managers, and regulators, may have an impact on the organisation's operations, which reflects on their positions and economic improvements (Jameson, 2011). Another piece of research looked into the possibility that certain governance mechanisms could influence independence and objectivity (Hay, Stewart and Redmayne, 2017). It is obvious that an independent, accessible and competent AC contributes to the independence of the internal auditor. Furthermore, the ambiguity of the roles of assurance and consultation may impair independence.

The literature has evolved to investigate IA independence and objectivity, which remains an unresolved issue. The findings show that the regulations require for IA independence and objectivity but provide no guidance on how to achieve independence by gaining access to transactions and activities in organisations and reporting to the AC. Regulators may follow the lead of regulatory requirements to improve the independence of their internal auditors (Al-Akra, Abdel-Qadera and Billahb, 2016). This implies that the rules should be strictly enforced to ensure that IA reporting to the AC can improve independence. The next subsection discusses potential assurance and consulting activity extensions.

2.2.2 Assurance and consulting activities

Assurance services are an objective review of evidence with the goal of providing organisations with an unbiased assessment of GRC (IIA, 2012). Traditional IA such as financial audits, performance audits and quick response audits are included in assurance activities (Anderson, 2004), whereas the IIA provides 'financial, performance, compliance, system security, and due diligence obligations' (2013, p. 58). The primary goal of IA in assurance audits is to provide objective assurance (PwC, 2015). For instance, institutional pressure on internal auditors to perform additional assurance-type duties provides only a temporary benefit, which undermines professionalism in the long run (Nagy and Cenker,

2007). Recent developments in IA practice, which have shifted towards value-added lines rather than retaining smaller assurance boundaries, demonstrate the tension between institutional pressure and professionalisation (Mihret and Grant, 2017). Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam (2003) investigated how IA's functions were primarily limited to traditional services such as ensuring compliance with legislation, verifying the accuracy of financial statements and providing internal control services, while other value-added services such as risk management, leveraging on the wealth of collective information received less attention to improve organisational competitiveness (Shahimi, Mahzan and Zulkifli, 2016). This reflects a shortage of skilled personnel, technical assistance, a reduced budget allocation and a small number of IA departments for IA to deliver these services.

In contrast, consulting services, advisory activities and related client service activities are defined as follows: 'the advisory and related client service activities, the nature and scope of which are agreed with the client, are designed to add value and improve the GRC of organisations without the internal auditor taking on management responsibilities' (IIA, 2012, p. 37, cited in Pickett, 2012). Regardless of how IA's dual roles as an assurance provider and consultant should be implemented, IA independence is an important concept (Bednarek, 2018). The independence of the internal auditor provides a successful IA service for management because it provides objective and uncontrolled assessment, audit reporting and audit recommendations.

The role of IA is to provide consultative support to the BOD and senior management team and advise on organisational reform and future investment opportunities (Shahimi, Mahzan and Zulkifli, 2016). Mihret and Woldeyohannis (2008) discovered that a financial incentive pushed management to seek IA consultancy services, transforming IA into value-added activities. To support this notion, non-profit organisations may prioritise compliance with regulations, which may be more controlled by resource providers. As a result of the stricter management, IA may be directed towards a compliance focus (Hass, Abdolmohammadi and Burnaby, 2006). In terms of compliance, whether audit work quality, as defined by IIA standards requiring IA to provide consulting services and management support, a high level of efficiency in the audit's planning and execution contributed to its effectiveness (Cohen and Sayag, 2010). While management support is the most important aspect of IA success, the quality of audit work through value-added services is also equally important.

In addition, risk management, governance and contingency planning are the most important aspects of IA consulting, while key consulting responsibilities include assisting management

with control concerns in new systems, participating in quality teams, conducting internal control training and developing regulations (Anderson, 2004; Selim, Woodward and Allegrini, 2009; Stewart and Subramaniam, 2010). The findings of the previous research indicate that IA has a limited role in consulting in banks, which require more consulting services than other sectors. For example, research shows that IA's involvement in environmental and social assurance and consulting is linked to management support and public reporting of sustainability information (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2018). The aim of IA is to assist management in carrying out their responsibilities more effectively by providing analysis, assessments and recommendations for relevant remarks on the actions under review. Therefore, it is critical to examine whether norms and standards are being followed in organisational functions by identifying any deviations or exceptions and taking corrective action as necessary.

In conclusion, the literature on IA independence and objectivity in today's unprecedented professional environment focuses on providing more consistent results on the organisation's status in relation to its resources and practices. The internal auditor's role as a provider of assurance and consulting services can be focused on the most significant risks, while internal control and risk management systems must be interactive (Pickett, 2012; Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Badara and Saidin, 2013). As a result of the risk results obtained from external and IA activities, a sound audit should be conducted and a cost-benefit balance should be achieved for IA quality assurance.

2.3 Development of IA

In the early 1900s, the auditing profession was viewed as more clerical than professional, focusing on the quality of accounting data by analysing vouchers, checking assets and identifying financial and accounting problems (Ramamoorti, 2003; Whittington and Pany, 2008). The need for clarity arose for a variety of reasons, including increase in record-keeping errors, asset misappropriation and financial fraud in commercial and non-profit organisations (IFAC, 2011). Although IA has grown in importance in recent decades, whether for industrial, governmental or non-profit organisations, it is critical for top management to measure and evaluate the appropriateness and effectiveness of the organisation's processes, which should be aligned with the organisational objectives (Diamond, 2002). The following Figure 2.2 depicts key developments in IA.

Figure 2.2: Key IA milestones

Source: Deloitte (2018)

Since the passing of the Sarbanes-Oxley (SOX) Act in 2002, IA has played an increasingly important role in improving transparency, accountability and good governance within organisational operations (Fulop and Szekely, 2017). While the SOX Act of 2002 does not specifically address the role of IA in corporate governance, the AC and external auditors are still subject to corporate governance requirements. In the last decade, the evolution of IA has been focused on increasing the efficiency of internal control systems, increasing stakeholder satisfaction, developing skills and expertise, increasing concern about measuring and evaluating the IA process and implementing technologies (Bota-Avram and Cristina, 2009; Deloitte, 2020). Nonetheless, it is clear that organisations are becoming more involved in operational auditing, risk management, internal controls, governance and information technology principles (Mermud and Sungun, 2013).

With the establishment of the IIA in 1941 and the SOX Act in 2002, the IA profession did not face the need to innovate. Further development of the Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) integrated framework had improved capabilities such as IT internal audit and data analytics, and following the global financial crisis, IIA guidance was propelling the profession forward across the world. At the end of the noughties decade of unsettling instability, with organisations facing changing strategic,

operational, financial, regulatory and cyber threats, there was a need to continually evolve to succeed in the new organisational environment (Deloitte, 2018). Furthermore, internal controls and governance legislation, such as the UK Turnbull Guidelines, the Corporate Governance Code and the COSO integrated framework, have emphasised the necessity of IA to be developed and implemented in different organisations and industries (Ismael and Roberts, 2018).

The practice and landscape of IA began to shift in the 1980s. The key improvements were the implementation of IA in all public organisations and the formation of a corporate AC comprised of non-executive directors (NEDs). This implies that IA plays a role in the prevention and detection of financial reporting fraud (COSO, 2013). In the 1990s, risk management, as a method of evaluating audit resource allocation, received attention in IA practice resulting in another significant shift (Reding *et al.*, 2013). In this regard, IA's goal was to provide assurance on financial and reporting issues while still maintaining organisational control. The organisational environment had changed by the end of the 1990s and new concerns such as globalisation and the growth of information technology had emerged. As market complexity has increased and automated technology has been introduced, developing business models and organisational procedures have been gradually altered (Deloitte, 2018). These modifications have an impact on the scope and methods of IA's work. Furthermore, the new facility is no longer capable of assisting organisations in adhering to its controls and IA standards to maintain their operations' long-term viability. IA's scope, mission and function have evolved from a simple and straightforward support system to a sophisticated support system that exists to help organisations meet new expectations. Independent verification of whether organisational activities are carried out in accordance with the organisation's goals, regulatory requirements, policies and procedures, and business expectations is included in IA.

With escalating economic pressures, demand and appreciation for IA have increased and the early twenty-first century can be seen as a dynamic period for achieving organisational performance goals (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011). This emphasised the shift from a control-driven to a business-risk approach, while macroeconomic trends such as the rapid pace of change and globalisation have influenced awareness of the importance of strong corporate governance and resulted in a demand for a new skill set for internal auditors. Significant reforms have been influenced by corporate scandals and disputes, accounting issues and regulatory requirements such as the United Kingdom Combined Code on Corporate Governance (2003, 2014) and the SOX Act of 2002. Given the current constraints

on potential capacity and resourcing issues, it is worthwhile to consider whether they must evolve in tandem with the effectiveness of IA requirements to meet stakeholder needs.

A variety of activities, such as participation in the review of knowledge management systems, alignment of strategy and performance measures, the development of strategic frameworks, corporate social responsibility, benchmarking activities, and the use of a balanced scorecard should be considered to increase key IA development areas (Burnaby *et al.*, 2009; Stewart and Subramaniam, 2010). The evolution of major organisational concerns should have an impact on IA (Sarens, 2009; Kasim *et al.*, 2012). It has been suggested that effective IA adds value to organisations by ensuring compliance with established procedures, laws and regulations, and providing opportunities to improve existing processes (Yee *et al.*, 2008). With underlying competencies rarely discovered, determining whether or not the audit is effective is difficult (Badara, 2017; Mihret and Grant, 2017). Therefore, the success of IA can be measured by examining issues that may have an impact on its effectiveness.

The perception of internal control systems has become an important component of ensuring information transaction reliability, operational control effectiveness and existing corporate governance reforms (Grabmann and Hofer, 2014). It demonstrates how demand from shareholders, regulators and credit agencies has prompted a greater emphasis on IA in recent years. While it was designed to prevent accounting errors and failures, bribery and corruption, it is unclear whether internal auditors have the necessary capabilities to ensure that a close relationship with the external auditor does not affect shareholder value (Rijamampianina, 2016). Based on this concept of prior failures, IA has been expanded to become a more integrated approach by aligning with internal control systems. The year 2000 marked the beginning of a shift in IA practices due to the demand for an integrated strategy. The literature shows that there is a strong and consistent link between attaining integration and the IA being implemented in a rigorous manner in organisations across the world. Working with other departments ensures accountability of procedures where different departments undertake actions and potential links are exchanged and communicated.

A lack of common language and practice, a lack of planning, a lack of correlation between theory and reality, unethical procedures, programme overconfidence, inadequate risk management and a lack of effective governance implementation may all contribute to global financial failures. The above evidence indicates that the financial crisis was an unexpected occurrence and many organisations were unprepared due to a lack of a strategic IA. These

organisational failures have occurred because of a combination of market expansion, a lack of IA silo approach methodologies and a lack of widely accepted standards and guidelines on IA development. Work intensity and the number of organisations have increased in combination with global advances in economic and social consensus. It has been difficult to remain on track in terms of budgets that have increased to mitigate risks and resource issues. The detection and mitigation of potential risks has become a mandate, which has changed dramatically in the aftermath of accounting scandals in global corporations such as Enron, WorldCom and banking organisations in the 2000s and beyond. The financial scandals have increased organisations' risk exposure, necessitating the use of various risk evaluation and control methodologies, while traditional IA procedures had become insufficient to meet organisations' needs.

The following section discusses the most important contributions to academic literature that cover specific areas of IA that are relevant to this research. As previously stated, academic studies on IA have progressed at a slower rate than industry-based literature. Finally, the Researcher concludes that the research findings are supported by the evidence derived from qualitative and quantitative studies conducted by industry professionals, which are equally applicable and necessary to complement the academic literature and should be integrated to enrich a large body of empirical evidence.

2.4 Key contributions to the academic literature

This section addresses key contributions to the academic literature by leading scholars. The point when IA had changed from using a conventional to a modern approach was chosen as an appropriate juncture for enhancing the effectiveness of IA. This occurred around in the last decade. Given their growing practical significance, IA-related issues have received relatively little research attention. Furthermore, empirical contributions on how to achieve or measure the effectiveness of IA, such as the value proposition in internal control systems and the degree and direction of process implementation in monitoring the IBA, can be viewed as an early stage in emerging risk mitigation, tools and techniques for IA implementation, which have only recently begun to materialise. Based on the established key contributions of this research, it can be examined and observed that the emphasis goes further in categorising the quadrant utilising effective tools, which deepens and strengthens the foundation for academic inquires and key aspects of this research. Thus, several researchers have undertaken their research in the following ways:

- First, the aspects of addressing concepts, development areas and the key development of conceptual framework, are considered to be the most important by Arena and Azzone (2007), Burnaby *et al.* (2009), Burnaby and Hass (2011), Mihret (2014), Lenz and Hahn (2015), Fulop and Szekely (2017) and Behrend and Eulerich (2019);
- Second, the nature of the IA process implementation is considered by Dittenhofer (2001), Mihret and Woldeyohannis (2008), Stewart and Subramaniam (2010), Lenz and Sarens (2012), Motubatse (2014), Kidron, Ofek and Cohen (2016), Mihret and Grant (2017), Najah and Omar (2018) and Salehi, Mahmoudi and Gah (2019);
- Third, IA effectiveness has also been considered. Therefore, analysis may have overturned the implementation of IA effectiveness or developed an adequate framework to dispute IA effectiveness by Mihret and Yismaw (2007), Lenz and Sarens (2012), Endaya and Hanefah (2013), Badara and Saidin (2014), Dellai and Omri (2016), Coetzee and Erasmus (2017), Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen (2018), and Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan (2020);
- Fourth, other researchers considered investigating an IA approach taken by post-implementation in organisations to derive the importance of long-term practical implementation. These included Arena and Azzone (2009), Sarens and Abdolmohammadi (2011), Chambers and Odar (2015), Chersan (2016), Alhajri (2017), Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2017), Ismael and Roberts (2018) and Eulerich and Lenz (2019).

Chapter 3 analyses research type in detail (theoretical versus empirical) and quadrants. Academic IA literature has been slow to emerge with the majority of academics focused on specific aspects of IA, such as the transformation and failures of various tools and methodologies, rather than IA as a strategic approach to fraud detection and development of an effective framework in the banking sector. In this chapter, each component of the literature review discusses a specific aspect of IA research, which conceptualises the key aspects of IA. However, documentation, synthesis and assessment of IA research is timely and provides three crucial insights:

- First, the results of IA research are mixed from the perspective of its effectiveness in the current organisational environment. While new challenges and new demands have emerged, IA is expected to increase its contribution to the evaluation of internal control systems and decrease its contribution to adding value and performance to the organisational environment;

- Second, current literature on the functional implications of IA indicates that it can have a substantial impact on the decisions and actions of top management and on the integration between the AC and auditors, while the successful performance of the functions is crucial to improve the organisational performance;
- Third, the IA structure and its components have maintained the integrity of the IA process and retroactively challenged the management position that is most prevalent in this area of research. This is expected in view of the availability of assessment to recognise potential risks and control issues, and overcome existing challenges to create additional value for organisations throughout their evolution process.

2.4.1 The effectiveness of IA

An emphasis has been placed on the concept of IA effectiveness in recent years, which has been taken seriously by a number of researchers (Lenz and Hahn, 2015; Dellai and Omri, 2016; Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Effectiveness has become an essential issue occupying a prominent position in studies conducted by researchers and professional bodies. Dittenhofer (2001) defined effectiveness as the achievement of the IA's objectives and strategies. The IIA (2012) defined efficiency as the level of quality with which objectives are met. Recent studies have also adopted a few definitions of IA effectiveness, which measure this term as the degree to which the goals set are achieved (Khalid, Haron and Masron, 2017).

There is a substantial body of knowledge on the concept of IA effectiveness that addresses critical factors (Dittenhofer, 2001; Gramling *et al.*, 2004; Badara and Saidin, 2013; Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen, 2018). However, several of these studies need to be updated to reflect current empirical research methodology (Dittenhofer, 2001; Gramling *et al.*, 2004). Recent research employs systematic methodology for identifying and reviewing sources and published content (Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). Scholarly literature and some empirical studies suggest that the importance of IA is primarily focused on its ability to provide reassurance and encouragement to senior executives to promote organisational learning in favour of strategic changes. Figure 2.3 shows key factors in the effectiveness of IA.

Figure 2.3: IA effectiveness

Source: Adopted from IIA (2017)

Few studies have discussed key factors considered to be IA effective and relevant to its estimation (Dellai and Omri, 2016). The research evidence of the IIA (2017) identified that demonstrating integrity, competence and due professional care, independence and objectivity, alignment with the strategies, objectives and risks, positioning and resources, quality and continuous improvement, information and communication, and risk-based assurance are all contributors to the IA’s effectiveness. Sterck and Bouckaert (2006) suggest that effective IA requires the availability of key factors such as strategic coordination for the development of audit competencies, a central advancement unit and top management support. Another study looked at IA effectiveness to see how it affects organisations and the factors that were identified were management support, IA quality, auditee attributes and organisational setting (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007). Further to support this notion, other findings suggest that management support and IA quality also have a significant impact on IA effectiveness (Yeboah, 2020). Other research identified the factors associated with IA effectiveness that can be assigned to each stage of the auditing, preparation, fieldwork and evaluation processes.

Most researchers used various methods to analyse and synthesise contradictory results and produce an IA effectiveness evaluation (Coetzee and Erasmus, 2017; Shamki and Alhajri, 2017; Tahajuddin and Kertali, 2018). Although IA’s value-added role demonstrates its

effectiveness, it is also important to analyse the effectiveness to determine possible outcomes (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). This is because the output of IA is expressed in the quality of the results, and by having it checked individual entities and organisations should be motivated to improve their performance. In this regard, two important instruments, namely assessment and monitoring, have been proposed for achieving management transparency in policymaking. Nonetheless, given the evidence in the literature indicating the relationship to an IA paradigm shift, there is still a lack of empirical studies dedicated to IA effectiveness.

Although few empirical studies have been carried out, they have demonstrated that the contribution of effective and high-quality IA to organisational success and achievement is consistent and well-defined (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; D'Onza *et al.*, 2015). It has been suggested that objectively evaluating effectiveness frequently reflects internal auditors' efforts but not the IA outcomes that have been achieved. IA should improve the quality of financial reporting because it reflects the effectiveness of IA in planning, communication and approval, resource management, policies and procedures, teamwork, leadership reporting, programme creation and quality control, and public complaint follow up (Gamayuni, 2018).

Yee *et al.* (2008) examined whether senior managers should be satisfied with the professionalism and efficiency of internal auditors in order for IA to be effective. Arena and Azzone (2009) sought to understand the organisational drivers of IA effectiveness in recent developments in corporate governance. They claimed that there is a need for a more detailed analysis of the effects of audit competencies. The absence of a link between IA effectiveness, career advancement and professional competence demonstrates that organisational characteristics have a greater influence on effectiveness than qualifications or work environment (Cohen and Sayag, 2010). Independence, competency, scope of audit work, performance of internal auditors, cooperation between internal and external auditors, management support and understanding of the benefits of efficient IA are all factors that influence IA effectiveness (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007; Lenz and Hahn, 2015). Perceived effectiveness can provide more insightful details on IA effectiveness. In line with this, only a few studies in the current literature have used variables to systematically assess the effectiveness of IA.

Recent research reveals an unbalanced reliance on IA's perceived effectiveness rather than an objectively assessed strategy (Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). Furthermore, current studies may contain contradictory elements that are known to influence the

effectiveness of IA. Almost none of this research previously carried out has identified similar factors that influence IA effectiveness or used the same metrics to evaluate IA effectiveness. A number of academics indicate that there are significant differences in IA practices between public and private sector organisations (Goodwin, 2004; Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). This demonstrates how public-private environments can influence the relationship between IA effectiveness and other important factors. While a number of scholars acknowledge the impact of organisational characteristics on IA efficacy (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007; Lenz, Sarens and Hoos, 2017), empirical findings are mixed. There is a strong need for empirical research into the relationship between IA effectiveness and other organisational characteristics. However, there is little evidence for this idea in the current literature.

The scope of this evaluation should broaden to include contributions from the literature to present a more comprehensive picture of IA's effectiveness, impact and operationalisation. The findings could be made into a step-by-step guide for use by professionals to learn about the metrics and measures that were used to make the IA effective and possibly impactful. The literature also focuses on inconsistencies in the metrics used to measure these variables and their effects on effectiveness, which should be discussed in future studies. Thus, the lack of a widely agreed functional concept of IA and the inability of any entity to assess whether or not IA is being correctly applied and how to do so effectively throughout is the consistency that has yet to be addressed.

2.4.2 IA functions

Research indicates that IA follows independent, objective and professional principles in accordance with existing regulations and the Code of Professional Ethics of internal auditors (Chambers and Odar, 2015). This is because independent audits and assessments of compliance with internal mechanisms, policies and regulations, including senior management oversight, internal control, risk management and internal capital adequacy assessments, are needed to identify gaps, constraints and causes (Nedyalkova, 2019). Although organisations have various goals, approaches and risks, there is a broad range of functions that relate to organisations (IIA, 2017). This suggests internal auditors should evaluate most of these functions as illustrated in Figure 2.4, based on the degree of change in organisations and emerging risks. They are not unique to any form of organisation or industry to determine how to manage a review of a particular function as key objectives and risks.

Figure 2.4: Key attributes of IA functions

Source: Adapted from Fulop and Szekely (2017)

Since its beginnings, the importance of IA functions has prompted changes that have impacted the role as a key component of good corporate governance practice, as a result of stakeholder expectations, repeated financial scandals and the broad focus of governance regulations on the concepts of internal controls and risk management (Rijamampianina, 2016; Ismael and Roberts, 2018). It is, therefore, the new strategies, practices and technologies used by organisations that force IA to adopt a new vision of its role and responsibility to maintain relevance in providing assurance and advisory services to organisations (Deloitte, 2018). Failure to act implies that risks in organisations are faced with a lack of IA skills and capabilities (Deloitte, 2018). This means the focus of the IA service and the delivery models are revised, but the core objective of assure and advice remains the same.

Effective IA functions through proactive assurance are believed to assist organisations by keeping control of emerging risks (Deloitte, 2018). Based on research by Negakis and Tachinakis (2013), the core IA categories are management audit, financial audit, operational audit and production audit. Their purpose is to provide specialised management services with a view to making the organisation's financial services more effective. The quality of IA work depends not only on the application of the rules and methods but also on the full commitment of the auditor as a professional. Professionalism depends on the objectivity of

attitudes and the auditors of the judiciary, on the quality of the application of audit standards and on the impact and practicality of the audit recommendations. IA involves the cooperation of staff and management to obtain an appropriate quantity of truthful data necessary for the success of the audit function (Fulop and Szekely, 2017). The best way to create an environment of mutual confidence and cooperation is for IA to follow a 'participatory' approach; be transparent in its research and goals, and maintain professional relationships.

It is important to understand that successful audit functions need to choose a scientific and rational approach to ensure that organisations achieve strategic goals more effectively and efficiently using appropriate methods. By identifying potential problems in the effects of the implementation of the IA in a thorough and objective manner recommended targeted solutions are identified (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). Cohen and Sayag (2010) argue that IA functions could be successful if they achieve the desired objectives. Effective functions are required to provide assurance on financial reporting information prepared by management and resources (Alhajri, 2017; Gamayuni, 2018).

The Moeller (2005) and IIA (2012) note that effective IA functions have the following six dimensions: (i) planning, (ii) approval and communication, (iii) management resources, (iv) policies and procedures, (v) coordination, and (vi) reporting to the BOD and senior management. Attaining the IA goal has many positive outcomes such as a reduction in accounting scandals and fraud (Jensen, 1993), effective risk management (Drogalas *et al.*, 2011), achievement of corporate objectives (Negakis and Tachinakis, 2013), recommendations for more effective management (Dittenhofer, 2001), added value to the organisation, provision of reliable information and avoidance of mistakes in financial statements preparation (Sawyer, 2003). The literature indicates that the IA functions are an integral part of the ability to plan, implement and communicate findings objectively (Dittenhofer, 2001). Implementation of audit findings is key to the effectiveness of IA (Van Gansberghe, 2005). The findings were corroborated by Sawyer (2003) who said that the work of internal auditors had not been completed until the damage had been repaired and corrected.

Further, the role of IA functions is modified and significantly influenced by contextual factors such as accounting scandals, financial crises and the fall of large organisations, changes in legislation and standards, and technological innovations (Behrend and Eulerich, 2019). Consequently, it is suggested that IA needs to adapt and develop over time to remain relevant and to be recognised by organisations (Cohen and Sayag, 2010). It is considered

to be a means of monitoring and regulating the effectiveness of internal control and a means of identifying risky operations in order to provide guidance to minimise these risks and to contribute to the continued effectiveness of internal control systems (Najah and Omar, 2018). IA functions are identified as establishing, monitoring and assessing the accounting system, design, soundness, adequacy and implementation of the internal control systems, ensuring compliance with policies, plans and procedures, reviewing financial reports before external audits, economics, performance and operational quality, and protection of IT databases (Suleiman and Dandago, 2014).

It is necessary for IA functions to operate IA as a business activity and a strategic business department. IA functions should be accountable and open for organisational performance, quality development and positive impacts. This can be accomplished, for example, through the acquisition of skills and competencies, the expansion of roles and responsibilities, the continuous management mechanism and the evaluation of the degree to which its goals have been attained. Over time, IA functions have grown from only playing a reactive role to a constructive role in organisations that remain important. Thus, this indicate that independent and objective assurance and consulting activities are designed to add value and improve banking activities.

In summary, there is little understanding of how IA in banks achieve their objectives by offering a structured, focused approach to evaluate and enhance the performance of risk management, control management and corporate governance processes. It is, therefore, necessary to investigate how the attributes of auditing functions influence and configure what auditors can and cannot do in the audit structure and how they relate to other IA users in banks.

2.4.3 IA structure

In recent years, IA's role in responding to changes in global business practices has emerged (Omolaye and Jacob, 2017). This change creates significant opportunities for IA to provide management consulting services and assist the BOD in risk management (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). This presents a one-of-a-kind challenge for IA in terms of adapting its structure to the activities of organisations to ensure their effectiveness and quality (Ismael and Roberts, 2018). It has been argued that core principles and standards explicitly formulate IA, which should be aligned with key organisational strategies, objectives and risks, and highlight the importance of a well-implemented structure (Eulerich and Lenz,

2019). A proper IA structure is a critical determinant of compliance and quality assessment. As previously stated, the IA structure is determined by the following factors:

- The overall understanding of IA is improved by optimising the alignment of organisational objectives and auditing structure;
- The benefits and drawbacks of various IA approaches and processes are based on key roles and objectives. For example, the audit charter should specify what IA is responsible for.

IA can be defined as an inspection mechanism concerned with identifying and reporting violations of rules and procedures (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013). While this goal remains important, internal auditors should act more like assurance providers to support the structural integrity of the organisation. The primary responsibilities of management are the establishment and monitoring of internal controls, which can change because of internal movements. While management and the BOD have the right to seek and obtain the opinions of the professionals they employ, negative assurance falls short of providing audit leaders and the organisation with the value they deserve. There is a need to address changing regulatory concerns as part of internal controls. This includes managers demonstrating the importance of planning, implementing, supervising and monitoring internal controls in organisations (Ismael and Roberts, 2018).

Figure 2.5: Respective roles of management and IA

Source: The Researcher

As shown in Figure 2.5, the number of links in maintaining IA's independence is unlikely to be significant due to IA's direct reporting to the BOD and senior management. Thus, the likelihood of misinterpretation or omission of a positive control environment is reduced. Risk

assessment is dependent on the professional competence of its staff and the training provided by the organisation. For example, if an organisation is affiliated with the IIA and its IA is required to comply with the International Professional Practices Framework (IPPF) in terms of proficiency and due professional care, a lack of training or persistent language barriers may be less problematic in organisations. Stewart and Subramaniam (2010) argue that the problems with verification issues in operations, which should comply with controls through audits, and problems with monitoring can always interfere with effective internal controls between IA, the BOD and senior management.

From a neutral and objective position, IA's primary responsibility is to examine the efficacy of internal control systems, risk management, and governance procedures (Van Peurse, 2005). Although negative preconceptions about internal auditors still exist (Eulerich and Lenz, 2019), the Global IIA, in particular, promotes a more positive role model for internal auditors who are capable of aiding the BOD and senior management in accomplishing their goals (Goodwin and Yeo, 2001). IA can also help to preserve, shape and improve organisational culture by interacting directly with employees (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006; Eulerich and Eulerich, 2020).

The person in charge of establishing, reviewing and updating a sufficient and effective internal control structure should ensure that one is established, reviewed and updated to confirm that it remains effective (INTOSAI, 2018). For example, a level of competency that allows for an understanding of the importance of designing, executing and maintaining the IA charter should be maintained (Najah and Omar, 2018; Eulerich and Eulerich, 2020). Mihret and Yismaw (2007) found that organisational policies such as the IA charter are a determinant of IA effectiveness. Internal auditors, on the other hand, may fall short in practice, and academics have expressed serious reservations about their usefulness (Van Peurse, 2004; Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). Thus, IA should be viewed as a value-added service that is both efficient and effective. While management, including the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), has been supportive of IA, there has yet to be a solid consensus on the function of IA. The perception of a lack of status and agreement on the job has been exacerbated further by the perception of a lack of strong professional leadership (Cooper, Leung and Wong, 2006). IA has suffered from a lack of prominence due to an insufficient organised approach to the body of knowledge, a poorly defined position and an apparent lack of widely recognised professional programme.

In terms of the structural debate to improve the internal control environment, it should be followed by raising awareness among managers of the risks and responsibilities to mitigate through a sustained campaign on the importance of internal controls. This can be achieved through training programmes, seminars and building the capacity of their financial and accounting staff to enable them to discharge their duties. IA does not carry out the process of incorporating internal controls into management and professional objectives, but rather provides an independent and objective assessment of adequacy and offers suggestions for improvement.

2.5 IA process

Dittenhofer noted that internal auditors assess management activities and people in their organisations that can be used to understand ‘effective audit procedures [that] should result in the determination of the nature and quality of the effectiveness of the auditee’s control operations.’ (2001, p. 445). This refers to the quality of the individual audit process performance. In traditional hierarchical implementation of IA, the process is divided into four dimensions: planning, execution or fieldwork, reporting, and monitoring and follow up on findings (Dittenhofer, 2001; Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005). The key dimensions and attributes of the IA process derived from this literature review can be seen in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: The IA process derived from the review of literature

Source: The Researcher

The scope and aim of the audit, the rules and regulations, the potential risks, the independence and competency of the internal auditors and the audit programmes are all important factors to consider when organising an audit (IIA, 2017). Internal auditors obtain trustworthy information such as process performance data as audit evidence to guarantee that audit conclusions are accurately documented and quickly accessible as expert knowledge in their audits. The audit findings should be reported to the appropriate management level to ensure that the auditee takes the necessary corrective action to address the core causes of the shortcomings detected. In this regard, IA should be monitored through self-assessments and peer reviews of audit teams to improve performance, for example, by identifying training needs for internal auditors in areas like IT or risk management. It is critical to follow up on audit findings to verify that management remedial measures are effective and that changes to organisational processes are in line with the goals.

Internal auditors have implemented various ways to conduct their management monitoring job such as combined audits and collaborations. This entails identifying a first step towards merging the IA's efforts with the goal of supporting a thorough audit. Auditing financial accounts, monitoring legal and administrative compliance, assuring the accuracy of management decisions and conducting performance audits are all part of a thorough audit. Other advice given to auditors conducting value for money and comprehensive audits is to incorporate a quality assessment of strategic planning and service delivery (Khemakhe, 2001). Such risk or impact evaluations are also necessary to guarantee the accountability of the organisation's policy or programme.

In previous studies, audit findings have been found to indicate concerns about control and management that affect performance and accountability (Cohen and Sayag, 2010; Lenz and Sarens, 2012). Streamlining audit procedures to incorporate checklists for different types of audits such as compliance, operational and financial audits, would result in increased efficiency, as indicated by Khemakhe (2001). The findings also highlighted that follow-up audits are necessary to guarantee that audits are effective. Internal auditors must have a degree of skill in certain areas because the scope of IA involves the review and appraisal of an organisation's activities. Internal auditors must have past and current working experience and/or opinions and a level of expertise in specific areas. The efficiency of IA team also values a wide range of skills and expertise, gather knowledge about organisations and implements customer centric approach, as members recognise that the audit engagement

should take them into uncharted territory, necessitating the acquisition of a number of new talents (Shahimi, Mahzan, Zulkifli, 2016).

IA is consultative in nature as long as internal auditors are involved in the scope of work to add value and improve the operations of organisations, while the overall IA independence may not be compromised (IIA, 2015, Shahimi, Mahzan, Zulkifli, 2016) . This shows that the adoption of the ISO risk management standard suggests that combined assurance such as the incorporation of quality audit criteria into process audits, is a new direction for IA (IIA, 2017). IA is commonly required in any quality management system to carry out its role since it is closely linked to continuous monitoring, non-compliance reports and opportunities for improvement. This has shown that the essence of the ISO 19011: 2018 guidance is the incorporation of a risk approach with enhanced technologies into the auditing programme. Although ISO 19011: 2018 is the guiding standard, IA has been improved with greater consistency by including other international standards such as ISO 14001: 2015, ISO 9001: 2015 and ISO 45001: 2018. The ISO 19011: 2018 standard is based on the 'Plan, Do, Check and Act Cycle' (PDCA) philosophy (Figure 2.7).

Figure 2.7: View of PDCA cycle based on ISO 19011 stages

Source: Adopted from ISO (2015)

While ISO (2015) provided evidence of the quality management system audit, including pre-examination, review and post-examination phases, Beckmerhagen *et al.* (2004) pointed out that the IA programme requires frequency, techniques, responsibilities and specifications for planning and reporting. They found that these requirements are based on the relevance of the processes, critical changes and past audit results. In doing so, the programme should

take into account the status and relevance of the processes such as the technical and management areas of the audit. As part of the audit procedures, the programme should comply with the ISO specifications and any other requirements established. The review of the IA process and the reinforcement of the internal control systems can, therefore, create an effective audit function, especially where internal auditors need to maintain their independence while maintaining the required level of trust within the organisation.

The performance of audit work, audit programme and audit reporting debate demonstrate the ongoing challenges of implementing IA practices that lead to better risk assessment. In carrying out audit work, internal auditors should identify the framework, policies and procedures for monitoring applications within the organisation (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005). Thus, the audit programme and the reporting of audits, the establishment of procedures and the implementation of policies for risk assessment and overall control of the organisation are better. It is important to manage key processes, ensuring consistency and minimising defects by monitoring and managing quality aspects that this section has sought to discuss and link the integration of the quality management system into the audit process.

2.5.1 Process of monitoring in IBA

Given the high expectations of the BOD and supervisors of banks, the role of IA depends on its ability to address risks and seize opportunities while complying with the regulatory standards and providing sufficient information to support the BOD or senior management's decision-making process (Deloitte, 2018). To this end, the IA's role has to change from an auditor or an assurance role to that of a trusted advisor in negotiating or reconstruction efforts. This could involve effective compliance functions, efficiency and profitability objectives in the banking operations at a monitoring level that provides counselling and value creation, which enhances and focuses on achievement. In this context, IA and compliance services should use current methodologies like guidelines and best practices to strengthen operations and bring value to the organisations they serve, all while adhering to local and international rules. Likewise, as illustrated in Figure 2.8, in the context of monitoring, process should become the last line of defence to detect and address banking risks and challenges in a timely manner.

Figure 2.8: Process of monitoring in IBA

Source: The Researcher

Senior management cannot delegate their responsibilities for the establishment, maintenance and operation of effective internal control systems in banks. The BOD should ensure that the integrity of the internal control systems of the bank is regularly verified by senior management. The Bank for International Settlements (BIS) (2016) further notes that internal controls consist of policies, systems, processes and procedures carried out by the BOD, senior management and other professionals to safeguard banking assets, control risks and achieve the bank's objectives.

IA provides an independent review of banking activities, objectivity, internal controls, efficient data collection and reporting, and management information systems to assist the BOD and senior management in monitoring and assessing the adequacy and effectiveness of internal controls, which is aligned with the goal of coordinating assurance (IIA, 2017; KPMG, 2019). Building internal control systems in line with proper, effective and efficient legitimacy provides the organisation with stability and makes its activities understandable to key stakeholders (Leung and Cooper, 2009). Therefore, this is not only a matter of compliance, but more importantly offers rationales for ensuring banking security, survival and development. It has been argued that banks should develop a comprehensive roadmap to apply Basel III as reflective of the internal control systems (Sinha and Arena, 2018).

The auditee is presented with potential changes through a recommendation based primarily on audit results. An audit report usually contains the management action, which is defined as a response to the advice and a deadline, and the action's owner. Each IA function should have a monitoring strategy in place to make the management actions easier to implement (ECIIA, 2018). Internal operational and financial control systems that are well-designed and routinely enforced assist the BOD and senior management in safeguarding the bank's resources, producing credible financial reports and adhering to laws and regulations. It should also help in the early discovery of large errors and irregularities by reducing the likelihood of significant errors and abnormalities. However, as the regulatory environment develops, the compliance function has a significant opportunity to stay ahead of the curve by making targeted adjustments to its operating model and processes resulting in higher supervision quality while enhancing efficiency.

The audit approach is followed by the development of a monitoring process in the audit system, which includes identifying and evaluating potential risks that may jeopardise the achievement of the organisation's goals, as well as focusing and optimising resources to address significant risks (Kidron, Ofek and Cohen, 2016). While this position may not be consistent with the regulatory frameworks governing external audits, it is perceived that capacity-enhancement training should be provided to internal auditors as the literature does not provide a detailed account of how to ensure independence, objectivity and professionalism in auditing and how to be effective in banking operations risk management. Deloitte (2014) has attributed problems related to the implementation of new requirements concerning supervisory oversight of senior management, internal control, risk management and the assessment of the adequacy of internal capital.

The above review revealed that the IA's role has undergone significant changes over the years with an increasing focus being placed on changing processes in monitoring and embedding them across the IBA. As the research identified poor quality or absence of the IA process as a major contributor to the possibility of discovering weaknesses related to the control process that resulted in the financial crisis (Hazaea *et al.*, 2021), it is evident that the monitoring process has become an essential component of IA, but there are still significant deficiencies in many banking organisations and the pace of change is gradual in this area (KPMG, 2016). By evaluating IA employed at banks, which developed system efficiency and improved risk management, the need to integrate with the central bank and commercial banks has been established. By applying the Basel Committee methods and improving

disclosure procedures in banks, efficient management is ensured and this assists with categorisation.

2.5.2 Key challenges of IA

As the IA concept evolved to address potential long-term uncertainty and complexity, the global downturn highlighted the need for a paradigm shift, necessitating recalibration to overcome the challenges associated with its effectiveness and implementation. Marinkovic and Sestovic (2015) state that a specific control function and mechanism that performs its actions after a specific business action could address the need for effective IA implementation. This section contains important literature on the issues that various scholars have discussed in relation to the challenges of IA.

Integrating IA and internal control systems are the primary areas of surveillance in accounting and auditing research. This implies that IA is an important component of a good corporate governance structure with the mission of ensuring financial reporting credibility through a continuous process of assimilation and adaptation to current reporting requirements. In this regard, there is growing concern about the need for risk management participation in modern IA practice, which is critical for new and more severe risks such as information security, where effective functional implementation is critical to improving organisational performance (Botez and Melega, 2020). This adequate level of understanding of IA ensures an important resource and provides an integrated picture of risk profile efficiency by not only recognising potential risks and overcoming existing ones but also adding value to organisations. This also acknowledges the need for new strategies and processes, as well as innovative tools and skill sets, to anticipate new and emerging risks and support the effective management of critical risks.

Despite being promoted on the basis of operational efficiency, integrating internal control systems into day-to-day practice is also challenging because it necessitates assessing the impact of the digitisation process and mastering each new innovative solution to understand how it affects the risk profile due to the current risk and control environment. The use of new technologies increases the level of technological innovation, which is also debated in the literature, whereas the potential to improve method efficacy is dependent on technological advancements combined with case-specific, strategic and careful implementation (Lois *et al.*, 2020). Some studies have shown that administrators and internal auditors disagree about the risks posed by new technologies and how to manage them (Zaman and Sarens, 2013; Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

To fulfil management expectations in a fast-changing and dynamic environment, regulatory and professional organisations must develop new approaches to IA operations or adapt current ones beginning with planning, reporting and implementation. As previously stated, internal auditors cannot afford to devote a significant amount of time to defining frameworks, developing skills and capabilities or developing methods for managing control systems and risks. Thus, it is unlikely that more resources and power should be available to create the new capabilities required to put new ideas into action. Mihret and Grant (2017) indicate that there is still a wide range of progress and success rates when it comes to IA development. In particular, complicated and consistent implementation challenges are more likely to arise in underdeveloped countries. The key challenges of IA are illustrated in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Key IA challenges

Area	Key IA challenges	Clarification
IA	Role and status	Recognising IA as a quality assurance function that complements a strong internal control framework and providing a clear implementation guidance.
	Internal control environment	Improving strategic vision, skills, incentives, resources, and a plan by educating practitioners about the risks and their responsibilities in mitigating them through a sustained campaign of training programmes and guidance.
	Organisational culture	Examining the availability of qualified accounting personnel in detail and take appropriate steps to supplement it.
	IA charter	Issuing a formal IA charter to reaffirm the role of IA and to fulfil the auditee's expectations.
	Operational constraints	Recognising operational independence communicated through the IA policy manual.
	Budget constraints	Allocating financial resources appropriately and preventing frauds utilising innovative tools and techniques.
	Risk management	Implementing sound risk management and developing internal control policies and procedures to mitigate risks and control issues.
	Financial reporting	Integrated financial reporting, monitoring and applying the quality assurance review.
	Size and quality	Operating IA as an independent department for reporting either to the BOD, AC or CEO directly with findings and observations. Maintaining transparent recruitment policy and improving quality by recruiting CAE, or IA-related expert, or some other assurance service provider to monitor the IA department.
	Scope and complexity of the organisation and its environment	Developing a short-term, medium-term and long-term plan for developing capacity of IA, which should be in line with enhanced scope of IA.
	Capacity building of IA	Providing training to IA practitioners on risk-based auditing, computer-assisted auditing tools and techniques, and value for money audit. Developing professional knowledge, competency and providing training manual. Developing independent research abilities to monitor future challenges and changes. Recruiting specialists as IT auditor and statistical methods analyst.

IA staff discipline	Implementing the Departmental Promotion Committee (DPC) and promote and provide incentives to those who meet the eligibility criteria.
	Complete the process of fresh recruitment of IA staff expeditiously.
	Equip IA department with modern office equipment.
Outsource auditing	Outsourcing value-added organisations to conduct verifications, reporting as an interim basis using the set of requirements criteria so that IA can provide more generous solution.

Source: The Researcher

Different jurisdictions have different levels of knowledge and understanding of IA problems (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011). The extent to which public sector entities, political classes and academics are aware of the IA legislation differs as well. The understanding, engagement and competency of key stakeholders are critical to the success of IA implementation. The failure of an IA implementation can be due to a failure to involve employees in the building of closer cooperation between the audit and finance departments. The unwillingness of auditors and accountants to implement IA rules in organisations has resulted in the failure of most countries to implement standards (Chambers and Odar, 2015).

The expectations of IA have never been higher, as its role has been allocated a strategic perspective in many organisations. It is noted that GRC is in the hands of regulators, stakeholders and the general public (Dellai and Omri, 2016). Therefore, internal auditors should be proactive and responsive to the challenges of the market. More importantly, if resources are allocated to actions that do not support a strategic objective, the BOD is responsible and should identify the rationale for this waste of resources and redirect them to optimal use (KPMG, 2019). In this context, IA has become a key governance tool in its strategic approach to monitoring the efficiency and effectiveness of organisations. The AC and the BOD, including through a periodic independent external assessment, should ensure that its function has an appropriate position and the necessary human resources and processes to respond to its objectives and strategic initiatives (KPMG, 2019).

The key factors as identified in the ambiguities of the IA concept, components and methodology are considered important due to the difficulties that auditors encounter. The scope of the audit universe is large and faces rapid changes in many cases, while the size of the audit department is very small in relation to the size of the organisation. Thus, the main problems should be considered in addressing the diverse nature of work, assessing the effectiveness of control systems, standards and governance issues. However, the support provided in the conduct of IA is of paramount importance. The specific areas of concern have led to the problems of conducting a proper IA such as the lack of support for

the AC, and the independence and resourcing of internal auditors. This consideration is a challenge for developing a balanced audit plan. For example, there are overlaps between the division of responsibilities with internal and external auditing or other auditing department within organisations. Effective IA practice is categorised by high interactions with the auditee, clear organisational structure, appropriate governance systems and support for organisational culture, which are considered the key factors. A lack of such elements may cause problems for in any organisation across different industries. It is, therefore, necessary to clarify the division of roles and obligations between such departments and for the IA to avoid overlaps.

In addition, IA is faced with constant competition for resources, a demand for cost reduction and a reduction in the number of employees. A small audit department with small resources within a large organisation face significant risk. It is a challenge to operate a single-person audit unit, which often has limited budgetary resources to purchase co-sourcing services and/or various audit tools. A single-person audit department has difficulties maintaining quality such as reviewing reports and having the necessary knowledge and experience in all aspects of the organisation's operation, particularly with limited resources, in addition to carrying out internal and external assessments. It should be noted that there is a relatively high proportion of single-person audit departments in developing countries (Siddiqui and Podder, 2002; Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003). The IA department is faced with new requirements such as qualified personnel with an IT-oriented background. Developing, expanding and enhancing expertise in line with the organisation's development and new risk areas is always a challenge.

IA is being challenged to deliver deeper insights and value beyond assurance as market volatility and complexity rise, notably in the areas of strategy execution, new risks and expanding the use of data analytics. IA departments have numerous problems meeting these new and higher requirements (Deloitte, 2018). Internal auditors are required to provide assurance on a variety of emerging risks and timely insights to help guide important strategic choices. With the risk environment expanding, the BOD and senior management are under more pressure to remain on top of present and developing threats (PwC, 2018). If IA is one of the gatekeepers who failed during the Asian economic crisis and the financial scandals in the UK and the USA, then IA should now have solutions and one such solution is to improve the risk management method (Chambers and Odar, 2015). Another study discovered that IA had identified numerous deficiencies in organisations such as Enron and Lehman Brothers, which failed in the early 2000s, but these warnings were ignored (Lenz and

Sarens, 2012). This was because the supervisory committees did not focus on the reduction of risk exposure and the general needs of IA. Among the factors impeding effective IA are a lack of an effective audit process and competence, a lack of staff and training, institutional independence, infrequent administrative support and ineffective audit results (Gurama and Mansor, 2018).

Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2009) note that long-term IA is crucial due to the movement of other organisational functions. Thus, it suggests a lack of support for furthering the careers of internal auditors. Ramamoorti (2003) acknowledges that developing a clear understanding of the value proposition for IA professionals that they offer to manage perceptions both inside and outside organisations remains a challenge (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). Mebratu (2015) identifies a number of challenges facing IA such as lack of independence, unclear formal mandates, limited access to operations, inadequate funding, incompetent leadership and lack of management support. Internal auditors face environmental challenges such as management support and other factors such as budget allocations, employment arrangements and the strength of the AC (Bame-Aldred *et al.*, 2013).

The improvement of expertise is a very significant problem facing internal auditors, and this can be addressed by a continuous programme of professional development (Bota-Avram and Cristina, 2009). Developing the skills of the IA departments can also affect perceived interest and its acceptance by stakeholders (Mihret and Grant, 2017). There is a need for organisations to commit more resources to the establishment of independent and qualified IA departments. It has been observed that IA in the banking sector has been identified as being of higher quality due to the higher level of internal control needed in the financial services sector. The profession faces the challenges of achieving clarity and internal consensus on its public interest commitments and improving its compulsory IA requirements (Chambers and Odar, 2015).

While internal auditors' traditional qualities and skills should remain valuable, they must be further developed and enhanced through increased technological capability. Thus, it can be argued that the traditional internal auditor's role and capabilities may begin to merge with the technical capabilities of a computer programmer or data analyst (IIA, 2019). The ability to assess and evaluate data to gain new and deeper insights should be a significant advantage. Thus, internal auditors would be better positioned to provide a bridge between the human and technological elements of organisations. Modern IA is becoming increasingly

automated and conventional auditors' unique experiences with technology and human factors can enable others to provide valuable knowledge to management as trusted business consultants (IIA, 2019). This might be done by identifying IA inputs, evaluating the procedure and deciding on the output that should yield the desired results. Effective IA is enabled by knowledgeable, appropriate, resourceful and competent auditors who evaluate organisational performance to create good governance, mitigate risk management, strengthen internal control and provide constructive criticism. To measure the effectiveness of IA, it is critical to first identify the stakeholders' goals and then focus on achieving those goals. There must also be added value for those stakeholders, particularly the AC and senior management (Erasmus and Coetzee, 2018; Gurama and Mansor, 2018).

Despite the expansion of IA, the above research evidence reviewed and clarified the criticism insights into IA's literature and how it has evolved over the last two decades. It is evident that only a few studies have been identified that indicate organisations are determined to implement it as an internal control mechanism. Research did not address the risks that could threaten organisations in implementing and developing IA to add value and reach a mature state based on key theoretical findings supported by practical evidence on the IA challenges (Arena and Azzone, 2009; Stewart and Subramaniam, 2010; Barac and Staden, 2014; Hazaea *et al.*, 2021). The lack of generally recognised, realistic guidelines for IA as well as the difficulties for organisations in determining whether or not they are implementing IA effectively and how to do so successfully across the governance structure are among the challenges that have yet to be solved. These highlighted elements support the development of a theoretical IBA framework (Chapter 3) to address the challenges of IA implementation.

2.6 Current practices of IA in Bangladesh

IIA (2017) notes that the performance of the IA department should be carried out in a manner consistent with applicable professional standards that improves the quality of the internal control systems. Internal controls and IA, for example, continue to be important areas with significant weaknesses across the banking sector's governance system resulting in accounting failures, financial data mismanagement, corruption, bribery and, most notably, organisational collapse. As indicated by Kristensen *et al.* (2019), the internal control environment depends on detailed financial rules and regulations, which outline in greater detail the procedures that should be followed for all transactions. This section identifies the literature that consists of an overview of the institutional framework of IA in Bangladesh, the regulatory environment and the relevant literature reviewing IA practices.

Key IA practices, such as independence, audit reporting, scope of audit work, audit programmes, audit reviews, audit work performance, professional competence and objectivity, are important from the perspective of internal auditors (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011). This means that internal auditors should follow the necessary audit procedures and guidelines (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005). Previous research has concluded that the primary role of IA is to provide insights into how well an organisation's resources are being used, and assurance on the structures and processes that drive the organisation towards success, which can be achieved by reviewing the soundness of internal controls (IIA, 2018; Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011).

As compliance processes become more complex, IA's role is likely to expand in areas such as culture and behaviour, risk governance, non-financial reporting measures and sustainability. Functioning independently within organisations, the IA plays an important role in monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of the internal control systems in meeting the strategic objectives (Kristensen *et al.*, 2019). To perform its functions effectively, the lack of key IA attributes such as audit practice should comply with (i) ISPPIA and (ii) be independent and not involved in maintaining the internal controls. As this is the case, there is a need to develop a transformative strategy to modernise internal control systems into a proper auditing function.

Adopting a risk-based approach that focuses on structured issues with the objective of ensuring (i) reduced propensity to falsify financial information and compliance with the organisational strategy, (ii) internal monitoring mechanism, and efficiency and effectiveness of operations, (iii) improvement in the work quality and financial reporting quality, and (iv) compliance with the applicable laws and regulations helps to develop a transformative strategy, (v) identified risks inherent to strategic initiatives are mitigated properly (Abidin, 2017). As organisations address the growing array of risks created by new technology, disruptive innovation and cybersecurity, a vibrant IA practice should be an indispensable resource supporting sound corporate governance. Thus, the current practices of IA in banks in Bangladesh are a result of the institutional framework and regulatory environment that are supported by the literature evidence. This concept is examined in the following sub-sections.

2.6.1 Institutional framework of IA in Bangladesh

Institutions play an important role in the development of a governance system. This implies that effective governance necessitates a strong institutional framework that fosters accountability, openness and justice within the organisation (Farooque *et al.*, 2007).

However, the weaknesses and emerging issues in Bangladesh's institutional framework for IA practices currently focus on statutory requirements, compliance capacity and requirement enforcement. PwC (2019) note that sustainable growth necessitates robust financial reporting supported by a strong institutional framework. It is suggested that a lack of transparency, failures in disclosure and accountability, and a weak financial management position are to blame for the banking sector's vulnerability (Schoen, 2017). In Bangladesh, however, there are legal requirements for IA in certain types of organisations.

Indeed, the IA functions in banking and insurance, which were required by the relevant industrial legislation in 1991 and 1994, have been the only functions performed by internal auditors in organisations. Under the Public Finance Act (1999), IA was either established within the organisation or outsourced, and was made mandatory for public sector organisations. In addition, IA is legally required for a number of other specific organisations such as airports and the railway sector. For other organisations, only indirect formal incentives for (non-compulsory) IA development exist in corporate legislation. In this regard, the latest corporate legislation (Bangladesh Company Act, 2006) has increased the accountability of management and the governing bodies in organisations to report on risk management and internal control systems (Johra, 2016). The Investment Corporation of Bangladesh (ICB), the Registrar of Joint Stock Companies and Firms (RJSC) and the Bangladesh Bank (BB) all play vital roles in the financial sector's development. The Board of Investment (BOI) also provides some support services, while BB, the Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General of Bangladesh (OCAG) and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) regulate financial reporting standards. The Security Exchange Commission (SEC) and the ICAB are two pioneering entities aiming to establish greater corporate governance in Bangladesh (Bhuiyan and Biswas, 2007). This emphasises the auditors' independence, the development of internal auditors' abilities and competencies, the board's recognition of internal auditors, the monitoring of mandatory compliance with auditing standards and the internal auditors' Code of Professional Ethics.

Policymakers have gone one step further by mandating that IA report directly to the AC. This clearly demonstrates their determination to reduce the ambiguity of IA's role as well as give IA greater organisational independence from senior management (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). To enable the BOD to make such disclosures, senior management (e.g. CEO, Chief Financial Officer (CFO) or Managing Director (MD) must provide assurance to the board that the risk management and internal control systems are effective and efficient. This is especially important from a practical standpoint, as organisations should be expected not

only to consider potentially influential IA challenges but also to assess their actual impact within the organisation using well-defined indicators. The IIA's professional standards provide a limited number of such indicators (KPMG, 2017). Thus, there is a need for further research to broaden understanding of IA practices by investigating indicators or metrics used for operationalisation and quantification while understanding the challenges that influence effective IA practices.

2.6.2 Regulatory environment

The audit is carried out by the bank's auditor in accordance with the applicable requirements as per current legislation. Bangladesh Auditing Standards, Bank Company Act 1991 (as amended in 2013), Banks and Financial Institutions (FIs) Act 1993, Companies Act 1994, and specific regulations issued by the central bank of Bangladesh are among the major corporate laws and regulations governing financial and non-financial organisations in Bangladesh (e.g. Prudential Guidelines for Banks and FIs). There have also been revisions to the above-mentioned Acts, and a number of rules, timelines and announcements issued by regulatory and professional bodies in order to carry out their supervisory and regulatory functions. Laws and other rules have been shown to impose isomorphic pressure on organisations to establish comparable structures (Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone, 2006; Carcello *et al.*, 2017).

To understand the expectations of IA and how it is perceived, relevant national and international laws and regulations pertaining to the IA activities of banks should be considered. Compared to regulation in most other countries, the legislation does not directly address the IA in developing countries such as Bangladesh, which, underpinned by Prawitt, Smith and Wood (2009), suggest it is a relatively unregulated department and profession. While non-financial organisations are subject only to previously discussed requirements, a number of binding regulatory guidelines address the establishment of IA activities but are limited in scope to the financial sector. As far as banks are concerned, the bank's ordinance requires the existence of an IA activity. Such regulations specify that IA should be independent from management and should assess the organisation's compliance with its reporting and due diligence obligations (Afroze and Zohra, 2014).

Furthermore, given the pressure imposed on the Bangladeshi government and professional accounting bodies by significant foreign lending institutions, institutional legitimisation is a crucial element driving the decision to adopt International Accounting Standards (IAS). Such pressure arises not only from the need to establish credibility with international investors but

also from the requirement for robust accountability mechanisms. This suggests that the adoption process's perceived undemocratic aspect is causing and exacerbating disagreement among diverse stakeholders, resulting in very low compliance with these standards (IIA, 2018; Zaman Mir and Rahaman, 2005). The lack of uniformity and compatibility among various business rules and regulations continues to be a major impediment to the growth of IA. Inconsistent legislation, conflicting powers and obligations are important deterrents to regulatory bodies carrying out their monitoring and surveillance responsibilities. Thus, some organisations' financial reporting and auditing methods become more problematic; this is notably true in the banking sector, which is governed by many regulators.

In practice, there is no amount of legislation can replace the trust, confidence and belief needed for sound IA practices (Barisic and Tusek, 2016) and the government cannot legislate on the personal integrity of key players (Walker, 2003). Legally, there is little regulation directly addressed to IA for the banking sector. It has been argued that IA is not legally mandated in non-financial organisations and is still a global self-regulatory profession (Sarens *et al.*, 2011). It is headed by the IIA, which issues the IPPF, including the internationally accepted IIA standards. Compliance with these standards is mandatory for all members of the IIA and its national institutions (Abdolmohammadi, 2009).

2.6.3 Summary of evidence

There are two types of research based on IA practices: those that look at the environmental factors that influence IA practice without using any specific theory as a foundation, and those that look at the environment and its impact on IA practice using institutional theory. The IIA standards were not in use because there was no legislative backing for IA (Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003). It is claimed that the IIA has no impact on IA practice, as evidenced by the fact that the majority of organisations lack an established IA department; some organisations do have an IA department but do not completely follow the IIA requirements. In their research, Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone (2006) and Arena and Azzone (2007) discovered no particular Italian provisions regarding the practice of IA. The formation of the IA department and the practice of IA have been influenced by Italian legislation on internal control systems. By interviewing the BOD, they were able to compare the requirements of the institutional context with the responses of internal auditors in practice confirming the relevance of institutional forces to IA practice. Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim (2016) also claim that the IA function has evolved in a number of areas, including auditing tasks, the time and effort required to complete audit activities, the structure of the IA function,

internal auditor skills, tools, the relationship with the IT department, size, budgeting and the relationship with the external audit function.

The liberalisation of financial markets and the resulting influx of foreign investors have prompted emerging markets to move more quickly towards best IA practices (Sarens *et al.*, 2011). Despite the influence of international financial markets, recent institutional changes and major economic development issues are likely to have an impact on IA practices (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011). The impact of the Institutional Governance Guide's (IGG) laws on increasing the quality of IA is dependent on the influence of the IIA's parts. Amoush (2017) argues that the IGG plays an important role in improving the quality of IA by increasing IA ethics commitment, professional performance and the enhancement of IA methodologies for effective practices.

Previous empirical evidence on IA and risk management, internal control efficacy, auditing experience, and internal and external auditors have a favourable link with IA effectiveness (Badara and Saidin, 2014). Furthermore, Goodwin (2004) compared the role of IA in the public and private sectors, and their findings suggest that (i) organisational status, (ii) IA size and percentage outsourced, (iii) the nature of IA activities, and (iv) the relationship with external auditors all have significant effects on the need for more IA research. Job descriptions, recruitment, performance standards, professional development, training, continuous coaching and career development are all part of the process of building a work environment that allows employees to achieve their full potential (Selim *et al.*, 2014). Endaya and Hanefah (2013) discovered competency and knowledge gaps in the literature to measure IA efficacy in achieving the organisation's objectives and it was determined to conduct a valid and adequate empirical examination. Thus, information needed to manage, conduct and regulate IA activities as well as account for their performance and results should be integrated with performance management and accountability. Management and accountability were recognised by Al-Twajiry, Brierley and Gwilliam (2003) as measures of the IA's performance.

Despite recent advancements, several compliance departments continue to fail to report to the supervisory board, which is required to ensure regular reporting to the management body (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007; Badara and Saidin, 2014). This indicates that professional competency, including objectivity and independence, and the scope and quality of work are ongoing issues in banks (Barac, Coetzee and Van Staden, 2016). Although Goodwin (2004) revealed that IA techniques in the private and public sectors are similar, another research

discovered considerable disparities between the two sectors, especially in terms of consultancy activities (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006). Furthermore, in certain situations, management fails to evaluate services, such as assurance and counsel, and co-sourced services to outside service providers (Goodwin, 2004; Arena and Azzone, 2009). As an element of the IA's success, the responsibility is to give impartial and objective assessments to aid the organisation in attaining its objectives and improving operations.

The Researcher understands that IA has a higher status in the public sector than in the private sector. Despite the fact that both sectors outsource IA work frequently, public sector organisations are more likely to use external auditors. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between internal auditors in these two sectors in terms of their interactions with external auditors in conducting the audit work. The research reviewed above contribute to the evidence that IA regulations and standards have a variety of effects on practices in a number of countries, including Bangladesh. The researchers did not, however, go into detail about how or why internal auditors' responses to laws or standards can influence IA practice. Thus, it is unclear how much regulation and standardisation influence IA practice.

2.7 Contributions made by industry-based publications

This section analyses relevant industry-based literature that validates academic research findings to reinforce the contributions and arguments made in the literature discussed in Section 2.4. The majority of industry publications are focused on and determined to take a more empirical and advanced view of IA than academic sources. This is further supported by the practical implementation guidance for the banking sector, which shows how IA can be used in the real world. Despite the fact that industry experts and academics believe that the fragmented nature of emerging risks indicates ineffective management, IA has received a great deal of attention (KPMG, 2019). For instance, internal auditors should examine the risk of fraud on a regular basis and assess management's ability to handle fraud when developing an annual audit plan. Another piece of research identified that internal auditors should devote sufficient time and effort to evaluating the audit results and internal controls related to fraud risk management (Deloitte, 2012). This indicates that a well-defined mitigation strategy is required to deal with potential fraud discovered during the IA assignment. In this environment, it is becoming increasingly important to provide stakeholders with a more realistic view of the organisation (EY, 2013). Such expectations further support the notion of IA's involvement in the identification, evaluation and monitoring of resources.

The challenge for audit functions is to devise a method that allows IA to systematically assess the organisation's culture. In addition to surveys and interviews, IA should devise a strategy for making the intangible tangible by employing an evidence-based risk culture model. The main issues are that systems and controls are not flexible enough to keep up with regulatory changes; there is a shortage of skilled professionals, and it is evident that regulators do not provide detailed guidance and support for the implementation of new requirements (EY, 2017). In practice, IA is facing significant challenges due to regulation and supervision, technological change and limited resources in the financial sector (KPMG, 2018). However, the greatest challenge of IA may be maintaining independence while balancing organisational needs against supervisory demands in banks.

As previously stated, the audit approaches would necessitate significant changes by auditors, regulators and standard setters. These changes could include the following: (i) changes in audit timing and frequency, (ii) increased training in technology and analytical methods, (iii) full population review rather than sampling, (iv) re-examination of concepts like materiality and independence, and (v) mandatory provision of the audit data standard (AICPA, 2012). Thus, it is critical that the IA is adequately funded, staffed and trained with specialised skills and competencies that are appropriate to the nature, size and complexity of the organisation's operating environment. Furthermore, the IA must have independent authority, reporting lines and adequate access to the AC (Deloitte, 2012).

Industrial researchers have been concerned about developing a new landscape of mitigating emerging risks and a completely strategic approach, advancing skills and capabilities, and implementing governance competencies for IA. It is necessary for IA to focus on understanding and addressing new trends that have emerged as implementation challenges while also providing a holistic approach, easily accessible practical guidance, soft controls and organisational culture, and identifying potential value-added benefits in the gaps that should be reassessed in the future. Industry-based research examines which IA approaches have worked (or have not worked) in the banking sector, identifies potential IA challenges and focuses on developing strategic IA implementation. Thus, predictive audits must be prioritised to provide more foresight to stakeholders by fostering the right culture, which includes a supportive tone from the top that is replicated throughout the organisation. To improve the training of new skillsets, an academy should be established to provide individuals with a hands-on learning environment in which to innovate. The IA should be transformed to support continuous auditing by giving individuals appropriate and relevant skill sets, tools and technology.

2.8 Literature gap

Several studies tend to agree that IA and its effectiveness are related in the context of the banking sector (Christopher, 2019). The literature findings are tested after analysing the empirical evidence to identify an initial research gap, as described in this section. There are five potential emerging IA challenges that hinder the effective practices of IA in the banking sector. These are a lack of IA skills and competencies, a lack of independence, poor application and quality of the audit work, a lack of support from top management and a lack of development in roles and the profession. Also, there is a scarcity of comprehensive work in the field of IA with only a few studies conducted in the context of developing countries such as Bangladesh. Scholars have suggested to conduct more in-depth research on the challenges of IA, developing an effective framework supported by empirical evidence and providing practical implementation guidance (Botha and Wilkinson, 2019; Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Based on the above literature findings, IA is playing a critical role in combating mismanagement, corruption, bribery and financial fraud. However, the initial literature gaps can be summarised as follows:

- Lack of strategic focus on aligning IA with key banking auditing challenges;
- Lack of clear practical guidance on IA and difficulties in understanding how to integrate IA into the internal control systems;
- Inadequate support from the BOD and the AC in monitoring and assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of IA;
- Lack of understanding of how IA practices are to be maintained; factors that affect IA practices and value proposition to achieve a sound IA in the banking sector;
- Lack of a strong institutional environment within the framework of IA in developing countries context, especially Bangladesh; what steps should be undertaken to improve the quality assurance in the banking sector in Bangladesh.

The above evidence compiled from the academic and industry-based literature helped to produce a systematic review methodology (Chapter 2: Sections 2.4 and 2.7) that indicates there is no literature on current challenges facing IA in banks in Bangladesh. This also suggests that the effectiveness of IA is an undeveloped process due to a lack of attention on the part of the regulatory authorities; such issues have previously been overlooked by regulators, policymakers and academics in the area of research.

2.9 Conclusion

The research evidence mentioned above have discovered a strong link between how to define or measure the necessity of IA and the key elements that contribute to making the practices of IA more effective and measurable. This chapter explored the concepts and nature of IA and deepen understanding of how IA research has progressed, and gave a critique of the research by identifying challenges that can help to advance IA practice and improve its effectiveness. This chapter focuses on key contributions from academic and industry-based literature in the IA domain to achieve the research aim and objectives. In this regard, an SLR was performed to investigate the difficulties in operationalising and quantifying the effectiveness of IA in the current literature and to identify the factors that are perceived to influence IA effectiveness. This chapter discussed a wide range of literature from various perspectives on IA research in academia and industry. However, the majority of the academic literature reviewed was descriptive rather than prescriptive in nature in this chapter, which synthesised on different characteristics and purposes with some examples demonstrating explanation of terminologies, clear empirical foundations and implications for further development.

The Researcher reviewed a large amount of material that examined the challenges in the literature and served as a foundation for this research. The analysis of the results also reveals that there is still a lack of understanding about the challenges that lead to successful IA implementation. Thus, with more case studies, research into the challenges affecting IA efficacy will evolve into mature control governance. For effective IA operationalisation in banks, it is necessary to conduct more research and to apply the theoretical foundation with the support of practical guidance. The literature also suggests that there are theoretical inconsistencies when quantifying specific challenges and their impacts on the effectiveness of IA.

The evidence in this chapter suggests that the banking sector is facing increasing difficulties due to emerging risks. The ongoing transformation of the risk landscape is altering the role of IA in banks and falling behind ineffective internal control systems. In the last decade, the risk environment has undergone significant changes, particularly owing to the financial crisis and digital disruption. This has led to ineffective standards and governance, which significantly affects the quality assurance of IA. Various digitalisations encompass the development of novel products and services; integration of technology; market rivalry; and environmental, social, and governance factors, which not only introduce significant risks but also demand a fundamentally different scenario. Consequently, banking organisations

should adopt a new mindset and approach to ensure the quality of their IA operations. Due to the growing significance of these challenges, it is imperative that IA adopt a proactive approach. The conventional and unchanging audit lifecycle is no longer sufficient, and a streamlined IA process needs to be established. Stakeholders anticipate and require prompt quality and assurance regarding the appropriate actions that banks should take to address and minimise these challenges. Banks should accomplish this by implementing a proficient IA framework that assumes a prominent position and influences IA development and implementation strategies. Moreover, the nature of the various risks is emerging as a significant theme and obstacle, thereby elevating the significance of IA from a comprehensive perspective.

The literature also highlights the necessity of reforming IA practices and assessing their efficacy, which affects the banking sector, especially Bangladesh. Despite its retrospective and insufficiently responsive methodologies, banking organisations should strive to develop a comprehensive IA plan that enhances the capabilities of the BOD and the AC, generates value, and aligns with the overall goals. Hence, it is imperative to thoroughly evaluate the approach to implementing a highly effective IA framework and the transition towards unified digital transformation. However, the key findings of the literature include advancing a proactive risk assessment procedure, employing predictive analytics to promptly address risks, facilitating communication through persuasive implementation of IA driven by risk and data, and improving the process of monitoring and reporting to ensure the most effective and sustainable corrective measures for effectiveness and efficiency.

Finally, this chapter lays the groundwork for the development of the theoretical IBA framework, which addresses initial literature gaps for the banking sector. Chapter 3 further investigates academic and industrial-based literature and current IA frameworks via an SLR evaluation to identify more specific literature and framework gaps. The findings serve as a secondary (derivative) foundation for the proposed IBA framework, which is discussed further in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3: Development of the IBA framework

3.1 Introduction

The previous chapter reviewed academic and industry-based literature, identified initial literature gaps on current IA challenges and served as the foundation for developing the IBA framework in the banking sector. The focus of this research is on the most noteworthy IA literature, exploring IA challenges affecting the banking sector and evaluating current IA practices along with their strengths and weaknesses. Over the last decade, IA has evolved into the best-practice instrument in corporate governance for internal assurance services across organisations, while a significant number of theoretical frameworks and conceptual standards have been developed to provide a unique perspective and increase awareness. As illustrated in Chapter 2, it has become evident that IA effectiveness and its operationalisation have evolved into a more demanding and challenging environment, where strategic focus, skills and expertise requires further development (Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020).

The aim of this chapter is to develop a theoretical IBA framework (Section 3.4) that addresses key shortcomings in current challenges of practicing IA in banks. This chapter discusses how the proposed elements of the IBA framework have been developed in response to the literature gap (Section 3.2). The key elements of the IBA framework including the internal and external environment are discussed in theoretical terms supported by the literature evidence before being refined and validated in qualitative field research. This chapter also focuses on relevant theories (Sub-Section 3.2.2), which are based on specific IA concepts, themes and assumptions discussed in Chapter 2 and the outcome of the literature gap (Sub-Section 3.2.1). The remainder of the chapter discusses the evaluation of current IA frameworks (Sub-Section 3.2.3) followed by a synthesis of literature gap derivations (Section 3.3) and concludes with new insights into framework findings and their implications. Furthermore, Chapters 5 and 6 present and validate the theoretical assumptions by obtaining new empirical insights from the analysis and discussion of research findings.

3.2 Derivation of the IBA framework

This section extends the proposed theoretical IBA framework's derivations through a review of relevant academic and industrial-based literature (Chapter 2) and the literature gap formulation (Chapter 3) on IA. However, this research is motivated by the desire to develop

an effective IBA framework by examining contemporary challenges of practicing IA and evaluating academic and industry-based contributions over the last two decades. The theoretical framework is based on a review of literature that focuses on current theories, which are combined to produce the theoretical derivations of the research framework rather than a single theory approach. The review also addresses all relevant literature gaps in order to fill the gaps that were found in the literature review. As shown in Table 3.2 (Sub-Section 3.2.1), the four-quadrant framework is being used to categorise the literature contributions allowing for a thorough categorisation of the research problem and the identification of research gaps. Chapter 2 (Sections 2.4 and 2.7) summarised major patterns and topics in IA literature emphasising that academic research has concentrated on specific areas of IA rather than a comprehensive, multifaceted approach to the research problem (Zain and Subramaniam, 2007; Cohen and Sayag, 2010; Mihret, 2014; Lenz, Sarens and Hoos, 2017; Sinha and Arena, 2018).

Due to their complexity, banking organisations have struggled to implement long-term sustainable IA as evidenced by various case studies and industry-based research (ICAEW, 2019; KPMG, 2019). A literature evaluation indicates a failure in corporate governance encouragement to establish and implement a robust strategic approach due to the significant deficiencies in organisations; only a few meet the requirements of IA areas. Therefore, the theoretical IBA framework seeks to align major components of IA research within the current risk and control issues, policies, regulations and monitoring controls in operational activities across banking organisations. However, it is evident that the evaluation of the current IA standards, frameworks and acts do not address some or all of the fundamental elements of IA that are necessary to establish an effective IBA framework in the context of the banking sector. This implies that the first stage of implementing an effective framework is to understand key factors that are relevant to the external and internal environment by examining banking auditing challenges, IA alignment with emerging risks, internal control systems, IA standards and governance and IA quality assurance. Top management can then decide which opportunities to pursue and how to implement them (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; Chambers and Odar, 2015; Marinkovic and Sestovic, 2015; Rensburg and Coetzee, 2015).

Considering internal banking failures, it is often overlooked that IA can be a powerful tool for defining the optimal balance of risk, profit and compliance. Despite the fact that one of the most compelling functions of IA is to provide assurance about the effectiveness and quality of internal controls, the effects of inadequate management oversight and accountability in

banks remain unclear. This is important to accomplish through monitoring and the development of strong internal control systems, which seems to be dependent on the risk, complexity and nature of IA activities. Under those circumstances, IA should determine whether banking organisations meet the main objectives of adequate risk recognition and assessment of specific banking activities such as operations, reporting or compliance.

Addressing failure to implement key control structures and activities, such as approvals, segregation of duties, verifications, results in the acquisition of insufficient knowledge, reconciliations and operational performance reviews, professional membership, certification and training. Another key point is that adequate information and communication between different levels of management within the bank should be implemented in monitoring the application of the organisation's policies and procedures, particularly ineffective audit programmes, upward communication of problems and monitoring activities in performing audit work. Regulators and policymakers remain keenly interested in banking organisations' ability to demonstrate the effectiveness of internal controls and how potential combinations between IA standards and governance help to achieve the strategic vision. In this regard, IA can help proactively manage risks for operational effectiveness and efficiency by reviewing key organisational processes, assessing the existing control environment and evaluating employee communication of the organisation's risks, controls and best practices. IA can also evaluate adherence to policies and procedures affecting key business processes and review the effectiveness of key policies and procedures.

Another element is to align IA with emerging risks, which is heavily reliant on dynamic risk assessment in conjunction with clarity and transparency of corporate and business strategies and objectives. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding of major strategic issues in both the internal and external environments. It has been argued that banking organisations should modify their IA frameworks by assisting and detecting key emerging risks that are unclear, while assigning them to appropriate stakeholders for evaluation and explanation (Alrjoub and Ahmad, 2017; PwC, 2018; Sinha and Arena, 2018). Given the constantly changing operating environment in banks, internal auditors must focus on critical components that drive organisations towards greater governance, accountability and sustainability controls. Thus, key IA themes and challenges cover a broad range of factors influencing IA development and implementation in organisations. The initial literature gap described in Section 2.8 exposes key shortcomings of IA across the banking sector. However, the proposed IBA framework presented in this chapter highlights the need to align

IA with key strategic elements within the internal environment based on the summarised shortcomings presented below:

- Key banking auditing challenges;
- Internal control systems;
- IA alignment with emerging risks;
- IA standards and governance;
- IA quality assurance.

The aforementioned elements were conceptualised based on literature trends and themes, scholars' recommendations and evaluations of the current IA frameworks discussed in Sub-Section 3.2.3. The ISO 9001: 2015 framework on IA, the IPPF (2017), the SOX Act of 2002 and the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) framework are among the important IA frameworks, Act and standard that have been discussed, which necessitate developing an effective IBA framework for the banking sector. Table 3.1 summarises major features of the theoretical IBA framework focusing on the relevant IA domains that serve as the framework's theoretical foundation. Existing case studies undertaken by various researchers over the years support this evolution (Chapter 2, Sections 2.4 and 2.7).

Table 3.1: The IBA framework's derivation from literature

IBA Framework Factor	Literature Reference
IBA Framework Factor: Inputs	
Key banking auditing challenges	Mihret, James and Mula (2010); Chambers and Odar (2015); Marinkovic and Sestovic (2015); Rensburg and Coetzee (2015); Bananuka, Mukyala and Nalukenge (2017)
Internal control systems	Fadzil, Haron and Jantan (2005; 2008); Singh and Newby (2010); Najah and Omar, (2018)
IA alignment with emerging risks	Alrjoub and Ahmad (2017); Sinha and Arena (2018)
IA standards and governance	Burnaby <i>et al.</i> (2009); Leung and Cooper (2009); Marais <i>et al.</i> (2009); Burnaby and Hass (2011); Tackie, Marfo-Yiadom and Achina (2016); Feghali and Hallak (2019)
IA quality assurance	Al Matarneh (2011); Gros, Koch and Wallek (2016); Saleem, Zraqat and Okour (2019); Salehi, Mahmoudi and Gah (2019)
IBA Framework Factor: Foundation	
IA process	Sarens and De Beelde (2006); Coram, Ferguson and Moroney (2008); Cohen and Sayag (2010); Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema (2012); Ahmad (2015)
IA functions	Nagy and Cenker (2002); Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2009); Leung and Cooper (2009); Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz (2012); Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim (2015); Johl <i>et al.</i> (2013); Rijamampianina (2016); Alhajri (2017); Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2017); Ismael and Roberts (2018)
IA practices	Fadzil, Haron and Jantan (2005); Cooper, Leung and Wong (2006); Sarens <i>et al.</i> (2011); Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2011); Power and Gendron (2015); Chersan (2016)

IA effectiveness	Dittenhofer (2001); Siddiqui and Podder (2002); Mihret and Yismaw (2007); Lenz and Sarens (2012); Lenz and Hahn (2015); Dellai and Omri (2016); Erasmus and Coetzee (2018); Lenz, Sarens and Hoos (2017); Shamki and Alhajri (2017); Gamayuni (2018); Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen (2018); Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan (2020)
IBA Framework Factor: Integration	
IA role and profession	Mihret and Woldeyohannis (2008); Stewart and Subramaniam (2009); Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz (2012); Motubatse (2014); Mihret and Grant (2017); Omolaye and Jacob (2017); Christopher (2019)
IA policy and framework	Endaya and Hanefah (2013); Kidron, Ofek and Cohen (2016); Botha and Wilkinson (2019)
IA structure and reporting	Munro and Stewart (2011); Salameh <i>et al.</i> (2011); Amoush (2017); Eulerich and Lenz (2019)
IBA Framework Factor: Outputs	
Corporate	Johl <i>et al.</i> (2013); CBOK (2014); IIA (2015)
Business	Sarens <i>et al.</i> (2011); Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2011); Power and Gendron (2015); Chersan (2016)
Operational	OECD (2011); Salameh <i>et al.</i> (2011); Deloitte (2012); FRC (2018); Eulerich and Lenz (2019); Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan (2020)

Source: The Researcher

The literature argues that key IA challenges have been hindered with establishing IA practices (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020), the failure of IA (Christopher, 2019) and internal control systems (Alzeban, 2015; Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005), while Burnaby *et al.* (2009) and Leung and Cooper (2009) found that the use of compliance with IA standards has been significantly affected in many countries. The foundation of IA with its effectiveness (Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen, 2018), the IA profession (Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Nuijten, Twist and Steen, 2015) and the IA regulatory reforms (Al-Akra, Abdel-Qadera and Billahb, 2016) have been examined in the literature. Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2011) discuss how perceptions of roles, effectiveness, and evaluation have influenced IA functions significantly. IA quality and financial reporting quality (Abbott *et al.*, 2016), aligning IA with an organisation's processes, and focusing more on weak processes and less on procedures and records (Abuazza, Labib and Savage, 2019) should have been integrated with the organisation's strategies at corporate, business and operational levels so that risks can be mitigated in a sufficient manner and through a strategic approach.

3.2.1 Literature gap and outcome

This section identifies the gaps in the existing literature by categorising the academic and industry-based contributions within the IA literature addressed in Chapter 2. In this regard, the four-quadrant framework is adopted to evaluate the literature, which is judged to be the most relevant on a certain topic to identify gaps that need to be explored further (Althonyan,

2003). Although there are other techniques and approaches available to evaluate relevant theories and literature on IA, the Researcher discovered that this tool is mostly effective in identifying shortcomings in existing IA research. This classification is based on two dimensions: the purpose (vision) and the nature of the results (implementation). The vision of IA is concerned with the concepts and developments of IA rather than the dynamics of the implementation process, whereas implementational research is focused on practical advice for that process. The outcome or results of either form of research can then be descriptive or prescriptive, yielding four essential categories of IA research in a matrix: i) visionary and descriptive (quadrant I), ii) visionary and prescriptive (quadrant II), iii) implementational and descriptive (quadrant III), and iv) implementational and prescriptive (quadrant IV). As demonstrated in Table 3.2, the framework is widely used to obtain a clear classification of research material.

Table 3.2: Literature evaluation framework

		Visionary	Implementational	
		Research outcome	Descriptive	Quadrant I Describes IA concepts and discusses the development of IA. Aligning the theoretical constructs of IA with key development areas. Key development of conceptual framework to IA. Implementation of IA unlikely to be discussed. Highlights the gap based on theoretical constructs and assumptions supported by the literature.
Prescriptive	Quadrant II Provides perspective on the nature of process on which IA functions have been established. Highlights different types of process may be discussed prescriptively within key organisational areas. Introduces theoretical IA frameworks explaining the nature of IA. Highlights the unresolved theoretical issues related to IA functions and internal control systems. Research may be presented the proposition of IA effectiveness.			Quadrant IV Provides perspective on IA approaches and outlines some practical implementation guidelines. Indicates different types of IA practices may be discussed as part of implementation within key organisational areas. Key practical implementation challenges and recommendations may be discussed. Indicates the benefits of IA areas (effectiveness, functions, structure) based on empirical data and may be examined. Highlights the gap in developing an IBA framework with practical guidelines.

Source: Adopted from Althonayan (2003)

The integrated approach to IA concepts and development, including gaps in Quadrant I, is demonstrated in Table 3.2 above. Quadrant III describes the process that leads from the

effectiveness of IA to the implementation of practical IA-based guidance and literature gaps. Quadrant II focuses on the functions of IA by identifying the nature of the process that supports advanced IA practice, whereas Quadrant IV focuses on how the effectiveness of the IA approach can be offset through practical implementation. Each quadrant allows for the summarisation and evaluation of key gaps in existing IA topics and themes. Key contributions from academia and industry are classified into quadrants and research types (Chapter 2): theoretical or empirical. The purpose of this classification is to close any gaps in the literature that have a significant impact on the research problem. The investigation is then to focus on the quadrant with the fewest supporting materials.

Table 3.3: Research literature evaluation

		Research philosophy	
		Visionary	Implementational
		Quadrant I	Quadrant III
Research outcome	Descriptive	Al-Twajiry, Brierley and Gwilliam (2003); Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone (2007); Stewart and Kent (2007); Burnaby <i>et al.</i> (2009); Marais <i>et al.</i> (2009); Burnaby and Hass (2011); Mihret (2014); Chambers and Odar (2015); Lenz and Hahn (2015); Power and Gendron (2015); Tackie, Marfo-Yiadom and Achina (2016); Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim (2015); Alrjoub and Ahmad (2017); Fulop and Szekely (2017); Behrend and Eulerich (2019); Feghali and Hallak (2019)	Mihret and Yismaw (2007); Ahmad <i>et al.</i> (2009); Cohen and Sayag (2010); Lenz and Sarens (2012); Endaya and Hanefah (2013); Badara and Saidin (2014); Lenz, Sarens and D'Silva (2014); Ahmad (2015); Dellai and Omri (2016); Lenz, Sarens and Hoos (2017); Erasmus and Coetzee (2017); Shamki and Alhajri (2017); Gamayuni (2018); Tahajuddin and Kertali (2018); Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen (2018); Alqudah, Amran and Hassan (2019); Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan (2020)
	Prescriptive	Mihret and Woldeyohannis (2008); Leung and Cooper (2009); Singh and Newby (2010); Stewart and Subramaniam (2010); Al Matarneh (2011); Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema (2012); Motubatse (2014); Gros, Koch and Wallek (2016); Kidron, Ofek and Cohen (2016); Amoush (2017); Mihret and Grant (2017); Omolaye and Jacob (2017); Najah and Omar (2018); Shahimi and Mahzan (2018); Botha and Wilkinson (2019); Christopher (2019); Saleem, Zraqat and Okour (2019); Salehi, Mahmoudi and Gah (2019)	Fadzil, Haron and Jantan (2005); Allegrini <i>et al.</i> (2006); Sarens and De Beelde (2006); Cooper, Leung and Wong (2006); Zain and Subramaniam (2007); Coram, Ferguson and Moroney (2008); Arena and Azzone (2009); Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2009); Coetzee and Fourie (2009); Mihret <i>et al.</i> (2010); Munro and Stewart (2010); Salameh <i>et al.</i> (2011); Sarens and Abdolmohammadi (2011); Sarens <i>et al.</i> (2011); Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2011); Johl <i>et al.</i> (2013); Rensburg and Coetzee (2015); Chersan (2016); Rijamampianina (2016); Alhajri (2017); Bananuka, Mukyala and Nalukenge (2017); Ismael and Roberts (2018); Narayanaswamy, Raghunandan and Rama (2018); Sinha and Arena (2018); Eulerich and Lenz (2019)
		Quadrant II	Quadrant IV

Source: Adapted from Althonayan (2003)

Table 3.3 summarises the most significant contributions to the literature for each quadrant, classifying researchers into quadrants depending on the nature of their research

contributions, which have been described in detail throughout Chapter 2. Academic IA literature that emerged in the early 2000s, along with a rapidly changing banking sector operating environment, required internal auditors to concentrate on key elements that enhanced organisational efficiency to strengthen governance and sustainability controls for their organisations (Siddiqui and Podder, 2002; Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003). For example, the international standards for IPPF are an evolving framework that help bank auditors to understand how risks, independence and integrity can be managed. Nevertheless, there is still no evidence of a correlation between the introduction of this system and how it has improved the effectiveness of IA (Yee *et al.*, 2008; Ahmad *et al.*, 2009; Arena and Azzone, 2009).

Academic scholars and industry professionals have taken an empirical stance on how organisations have successfully developed and implemented IA. The Researcher discovered that the majority of academic research falls into Quadrant III, with Quadrants II and I continuing to follow. Researchers have shifted from a theoretical to a more practical approach to IA in recent years (Quadrant IV). Academics and practitioners in the industry have recognised and agreed on the growing need for continuous investigation and exploration of new IA trends and themes. Due to the internal and external environments in this field evolving differently, the consequences of banking organisations' complexity are divided into internal and external factors. The internal factors include strong corporate governance, accountability in organisations and transparency in top management. The external factors include technological advancements, regulatory changes and the influences of external auditors and outsourcing. While some regulators continue to insist on internal auditors acting as control police, there is a need to investigate the role of regulators in impeding and preventing the development of IA. Adoption of technological advances needs to be considered as an effective method to achieve agility. Internal auditors can lack the necessary IT knowledge and skills, therefore the use of recent technological advancements, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain audit analytics, may help to IA be more effective (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020).

There are challenges in fulfilling the changing role and scope of IA's work, which has shifted from being a financial-oriented role to becoming an important tool in controls and risk assessment (Cooper, Leung and Wong, 2006). It also focuses on organisational performance perceptions at the level of compliance challenges (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). This includes the availability of internal auditors with the necessary knowledge, skills and integrity to help IA's ability to be successful in new management supervision and

transparency without jeopardising the IA programme and to have the ‘right to audit’ to improve clear control structures, particularly outsourcing arrangements. Furthermore, adequate assessment tools and methods should be available for the incorporation of monitoring activities, the provision of key controls and activities, and adequate resources and information sharing to invest in technology, tools, processes and talents. It is also critical to balance the traditional role of providing independent assurance with generating insights into unknown or poorly managed emerging risks.

Table 3.4: Best practices of IA

	Best practice IA	Future IA challenges
IA area	Reporting to all relevant addressees at the same time	Top management oversight and accountability
	For significant discoveries that are critical to the entire organisation, group mail communication is required	Strong internal control culture Developing an adaptive and progressive culture and process for quality control
	Audit reports follow a standard format that includes a management summary and a fast evaluation	Assessment of the emerging risks Clear methodology for measuring the effectiveness of IA
	All IA members meet on a regular basis	Key control structures and activities
	The IA policy, framework and governance entities must work closely together (policy and framework)	Greater collaboration with assurance providers
	The various governance bodies' roles are clearly stated	Inadequate communication of information
	The IA's interfaces with other governance entities are well defined	Contingency planning for high impact, low likelihood events
	Internal auditors with the highest credentials, professional certifications in the field of IA	Ineffective IA programmes
	Teams of internal auditors who work together	Integration of monitoring activities
	IA is in charge of training and qualifying high-potential talents and retain them	Integration in qualified talents and skillsets

Source: Adapted from Eulerich and Lenz (2019)

In order to resolve the challenges in Table 3.4, it is emphasised first the degree to which the IA charter can be revised to reflect its evolving role and scope of work. Second, a constant review of the framework and improved cooperation with the control mechanism that helps to build value through the provision of assurance and advisory services. Third, use deeper insights and value beyond assurance, particularly in the areas of strategic implementation of IT governance, and enhance the use of specific skills and experience to focus primarily on risk assessment and evaluation of IT controls (PwC, 2017). Fourth, adopt new IA regulations that affect organisations and expect the regulatory environment to become more imperative at the accepted level (Deloitte, 2018). To a certain extent, the coordination of

activities with the organisation's strategy and objectives and the efficiency of the organisational procedures engage in real-time collaboration in implementation and report on progress. Fifth, shift from a formal to a more innovative way of working. Finally, sixth, increase collaborative auditing, especially in the context of integrated enterprise risk management and monitoring activities.

IA has a significant mission to enhance quality governance and increase stability in the banking sector. Experiences and observations of IA have shown that the implementation of any worldwide IA practice is not a mechanical operation and is not limited to the development of legislation and generic guidelines but involves a significant change of mindset. In addition, the practices and challenges summarised in the above-mentioned issues can be overcome if governments continue to focus on the development of IA, highlighting the need for step-by-step implementation, the involvement of qualified specialists in the AC and IA functions and collaboration with industry-recognised institutions and professionals. Stakeholders, including regulators, are seeking for an approach to IA that is informative, forward-thinking and focused on building value for banking organisations, which goes beyond analysing past practices.

Thus, this research argues that the prescriptive-implementation quadrant is under-researched. Table 3.5 summarises the gap in academic and industry-based literature and is categorised into the quadrants as discussed earlier. Over the last two decades, key scholarly contributions have been extended to show the key trends, themes and issues in research. The investigation found that there is a significant gap represented in the research that discusses key challenges and aspects of developing and implementing IA.

Table 3.5: Research literature gap

Research literature gap			
	IA Gap	Research Author (Year)-Academic	Research Author (Year)-Industry
Quadrant I	Lack of reliability on organisational IA status, outputs and performance	Al-Twajjry, Brierley and Gwilliam (2003); Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone (2007); Stewart and Kent (2007);	Protiviti (2009); Deloitte (2018); KPMG (2019)
	Lack of resource allocation and poor governance mechanism	Burnaby <i>et al.</i> (2009); Marais <i>et al.</i> (2009); Burnaby and Hass (2011); Mihret (2014);	
	Lack of knowledge in IA and external auditing	Chambers and Odar (2015); Lenz and Hahn (2015); Power and Gendron (2015); Tackie, Marfo-Yiadom and Achina (2016); Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim (2015); Alrjoub and	
	Lack of understanding of what constitutes IA and how IA can enhance its value proposition		
	Lack of professionalism and independence from top management		
	Inconsistent development of the theoretical framework		

	<p>Lack of a fully dynamic IA framework</p> <p>Fear of policy change and administrative reforms</p> <p>Lack of independence and objectivity aligned with IA roles</p> <p>Difficulty in aligning corporate governance and IA development factors</p> <p>Difficulties in resolution of management acceptance of risks</p> <p>Failure to understand the development of IA characteristics</p> <p>Weak quality assurance and improvement programme</p> <p>Confusion as to how new IA approaches are introduced</p> <p>Inability to use the level of commitment from top management</p>	<p>Ahmad (2017); Fulop and Szekely (2017); Behrend and Eulerich (2019); Feghali and Hallak (2019)</p>	
<p>Quadrant II</p>	<p>Lack of expertise and resources</p> <p>Inconsistent analytical framework and quality of strategic planning</p> <p>Lack of support from management</p> <p>Lack of transparency, integrity and financial reporting process</p> <p>Lack of adequate training and reporting standard</p> <p>Failure to communicate to the AC on the progress of the audit strategy and audit results on a regular basis</p> <p>There are not enough instruments or mechanisms in place to make systematic follow up possible</p> <p>There are no quality assurance or improvement programmes in place</p> <p>The IIA standards need external reviews but none exist</p> <p>There are not any action plans supervised by the AC to track implementation</p> <p>Fear of disclosing the process model may require justification</p> <p>Lack of access to relevant IA information</p> <p>Lack of internal control in the auditing programme</p> <p>Monitoring gaps in structural and functional arrangements</p>	<p>Mihret and Woldeyohannis (2008); Leung and Cooper (2009); Singh and Newby (2010); Stewart and Subramaniam (2010); Al Matarneh (2011); Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema (2012); Motubatse (2014); Gros, Koch and Wallek (2016); Kidron, Ofek and Cohen (2016); Amoush (2017); Mihret and Grant (2017); Omolaye and Jacob (2017); Najah and Omar (2018); Shahimi and Mahzan (2018); Botha and Wilkinson (2019); Christopher (2019); Saleem, Zraqat and Okour (2019); Salehi, Mahmoudi and Gah (2019)</p>	<p>Ernst and Young (2006); OECD (2011); Deloitte (2012); Protiviti (2013); FRC (2018); IMF (2018); ICAEW (2019)</p>
<p>Quadrant III</p>	<p>Lack of capacity building and institutional development</p> <p>Lack of understanding between IA effectiveness and frameworks</p> <p>Lack of effectiveness on IA department performance</p> <p>Lack of the level of independence, objectivity and competency</p> <p>Poor clarity on cost-effectiveness of controls</p> <p>Difficulty in defining critical way of evaluating IA practice</p> <p>Underestimating the organisational setting and auditee attributes</p> <p>Lack of technical and financial resources</p>	<p>Mihret and Yismaw (2007); Ahmad <i>et al.</i> (2009); Cohen and Sayag (2010); Lenz and Sarens (2012); Endaya and Hanefah (2013); Badara and Saidin (2014); Lenz, Sarens and D'Silva (2014); Ahmad (2015); Dellai and Omri (2016); Lenz, Sarens and Hoos (2017); Erasmus and Coetzee (2017); Shamki and Alhajri (2017); Gamayuni (2018); Tahajuddin and Kertali (2018); Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen (2018); Alqudah, Amran and Hassan</p>	

	Inconsistency of financial accounting records	(2019); Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan (2020)	
Quadrant IV	Poor compliance standards with IA practice		
	Lack of quality of the internal control systems		
	Lack of excellence in operational responsibilities		
	Poor alignment with the strategies, objectives and risks		
	Lack of sufficient alignment of internal audit strategy to the business strategy		
	Limited effects of standards in IA practices	Fadzil, Haron and Jantan (2005); Allegrini <i>et al.</i> (2006); Sarens and De Beelde (2006); Cooper, Leung and Wong (2006); Zain and Subramaniam (2007); Coram, Ferguson and Moroney (2008); Arena and Azzone (2009); Christopher, Sarens and Leung (2009); Coetzee and Fourie (2009); Mihret <i>et al.</i> (2010); Munro and Stewart (2010); Salameh <i>et al.</i> (2011); Sarens and Abdolmohammadi (2011); Sarens <i>et al.</i> (2011); Soh and Martinov-Bennie (2011); Johl <i>et al.</i> (2013); Rensburg and Coetzee (2015); Chersan (2016); Rijamampianina (2016); Alhajri (2017); Bananuka, Mukyala and Nalukenge (2017); Ismael and Roberts (2018); Narayanaswamy, Raghunandan and Rama (2018); Sinha and Arena (2018); Eulerich and Lenz (2019)	
	Limited resources such as technology tools or funding for training		
	Lack of dynamic incorporation between IA and government bodies link into monitoring mechanism		
	Lack of coordination with assurance functions		
	Poor risk management and compliance for audit planning		
	Lack of understanding in risk assessments		
	Poor control over performance evaluation mechanism		
	Misalignment between IA roles and evaluation techniques		
	Inadequate challenges in retention of staff in IA department		
	Lack of training guidance to leading IA practices		
	Lack of opportunities in further skills development in the internal control evaluation process		
	Lack of adherence to the IIA standards as a benchmark for leading practice		
	Lack of effective implementation of IA charter		
	Poor application of methods and practice to measure the value of IA		
	Overlooking the challenges in IA profession and poor skills and knowledge on shifting demands over IA practice		
Poor control over corporate governance frameworks and IA roles			
Failed to prevent global financial crime			
Difficulties in determining the factors associated with the size of IA functions			
			CBOK (2014); IIA (2015)

Source: The Researcher

Despite the inadequacies indicated above, the findings from current literature are used to lay the groundwork for constructing an effective IBA framework of organisational aspects involved in IA development and implementation, which is described in more detail in Section 3.3. The following four gaps have been identified based on a systematic literature analysis of secondary sources data:

1. There is a need to fully comprehend the nature of IA because it is unaddressed in the context of the banking sector. Current IA frameworks are intended to address a variety of emerging risks, which is unaddressed in the literature. Thus, it is important to build an IBA framework that can be used effectively to deal with these risks, while a thorough understanding of how IA works with new risks is needed.
2. The gap between the IA process and the internal control systems has been identified. The literature acknowledges that the IA process and internal controls are hindered by ineffective implementation and a lack of maturity. However, there is a scarcity of literature explaining why the IA process and internal controls were not properly implemented. The changing role of IA in bridging this gap in support of the leadership agenda, the impact on value proposition, evolving skills, competencies, meeting a new role, active involvement in strategic vision development and integrated vice versa internal control systems are all necessary to understand. Key stages of the IA process need to be better understood, documented and considered the effects of IT in terms of the relationship between internal auditors, auditees and outsourcing organisations.
3. The gap is identified between the effectiveness of IA and the framework in the literature. The majority of the literature focuses on the evaluation, quantification and design of IA measuring instruments. However, there is a need to explain the quality, efficiency and performance of IA in greater detail, particularly in terms of strategies, principle, guidelines and approaches used to improve the effectiveness of IA, as well as how IA resolves problematic issues while addressing a lack of integrity, tools and regulatory challenges.
4. There is a knowledge gap in the literature regarding the development of practical guidance and the effective implementation of IA. To overcome challenges, increase efficiency and meet stakeholder expectations, current IA frameworks should be problem-solved through the use of institutional pressures and ingenious solutions.

3.2.2 Relevant theories

This section presents and discusses the theoretical foundations of the institutional and ingenuity theories relevant to IA practice, with the goal of identifying an appropriate framework to explain how combined theories have been implemented and interpreted in IA research. The purpose of this section is to investigate how and to what extent IA practitioners, other relevant stakeholders and regulatory bodies can apply institutional and ingenuity concepts and principles while confronted with the challenges of advancing IA and

improving its quality and effectiveness. To understand the phenomenon, the theory explains how to identify the relationship between supporting theories within the context of the research problem and specific boundaries as well as how to construct a systematic structure based on concepts and principles (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Hatch and Cunliffe, 2013; Nilsen, 2015). Institutional and ingenuity theories have been combined to help explain the research problem and show how institutional norms and ingenuity solutions work in both the internal and external contexts.

3.2.2.1 Institutional theory

The institutional theory emphasises the systematic process of institutionalising best practices and regulatory compliance to improve an organisation's effectiveness (Scott, 2005; Joksimovic and Ahmed, 2017). This also demonstrates why it is critical for IA professionals in organisations to develop core competencies in order to deliver services efficiently as well as how continual engagement with AC members helps to focus on the organisation's performance and improve IA effectiveness (Josh and Karyawati, 2022). Key factors, such as corporate governance structures, laws and regulations, organisational characteristics, compliance with IA standards and IA professional characteristics, correspond to some extent with the features of institutional theory, which have further effects on added value contributions.

Scholars have applied institutional theory to develop theoretical frameworks within different dimensions in the context of IA effectiveness (Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003; Arena and Azzone, 2006; Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; Arena and Jeppesen, 2016). In order to support the concept of institutional theory, this research aims to contribute to the development of a theoretical framework that considers institutional phenomena to be its domain. Given that the fundamental belief of institutional theory demonstrates that the institutional environment is socially constructed, this is regarded as the most appropriate theory for investigating the challenges of IA, evaluating IA practices and enhancing the effectiveness of IA within banking organisations.

In 1957, Selznick developed institutional theory to better understand how organisations are influenced by and can contribute to the society in which they operate (DiMaggio and Powel, 1983; Greenwood, Hining and Wheten, 2014). Furthermore, by integrating externally legitimated formal structures and organisational practices, the new institutional theory (also known as neo-institutional theory) replaces the previous 'definitional' method with interaction on social phenomena in organisations to increase internal and external constituent

commitment (Hu, Hart and Cooke, 2007). This theory further emphasises the rules imposed on the conditions for action by external bodies (particularly government), the values and norms that are internalised in roles as part of the socialisation process and the cultural controls that underpin the belief systems supported by professions (Collier and Woods, 2011). The main idea of institutional theory is that both internal and external factors play a role in how and why organisations conform to dominant norms, traditions and social influences as well as how they change, evolve or dissolve (Hu, Hart and Cooke, 2007; Lawrence and Shadnam, 2008).

Both the institutionalisation process and the isomorphism process have an influence on the organisation's goals and methods of operational activities (Cohen and Sayag, 2010; Norman, Rose and Rose, 2010), structure, management and coordination (Hu, Hart and Cooke, 2007; Meyer and Hollerer, 2014). This neo-institutional theory appears to characterise the problem in terms of boundaries, based on the notion that external factors have significant influence on the interaction of an organisation's structures, resources, processes and governance (Casson and Rose, 2014). In this regard, the institutional context is a critical component of isomorphism (Lawrence and Shadnam, 2008), which refers to the organisation having a single legal form, a proclivity to deviate from expected patterns and the possibility of becoming illegitimate. Research done by Jaffe (2001) and Lawrence and Shadnam (2008) indicates that external rules, often described as 'rationalised myths', can have an impact on an organisation.

Furthermore, the essence of institutional theory focuses on how institutional pressures from the institutional domain, such as coercive, normative and mimetic pressures, shape 'institutional isomorphic change' (DiMaggio and Powel, 1983, p. 150). In the context of IA, these pressures adhere to professional practices and compliance with laws and regulations, which necessitate organisational effectiveness and sound practices. To support this notion, culture, society, politics and economics can all be used to support the claim that IA contributes to a beneficial shift in organisational behaviour to meet the needs of stakeholders (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007; Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009; Norman, Rose and Rose, 2010). Thus, an IA framework is important to be credible in terms of corporate governance and to be able to explain the relationship between key IA elements. Coercive, normative and mimetic isomorphism are the three types of isomorphism discussed below.

- Coercive isomorphism is compelled when informal and formal organisational structures or rules from various sources are combined (Daft, Murphy and Willmott,

2014). Coercion stresses the role of regulatory compliance, political influence and the need for legitimacy, which are considered critical factors for organisations and decision-makers to adopt rules and practices for undertaking IA activities (Lawrence and Shadnam, 2008). External pressure occurs on organisations to ensure that a given behaviour is accepted in the form of decision-makers following or adopting certain institutionalised rules and practices, which is referred to as coercive isomorphism (Daft, Murphy and Willmott, 2014). Peer organisations, competitors, regulatory agencies, political influence by supervisory authorities and economic forces are examples of this pressure (Teo, Wei and Benbasat, 2003; Hsu, Lee and Straub, 2012). There is no doubt that regulatory pressure on IA practices (the Bank Company Act 1991 in Bangladesh, the SOX Act of 2002 in the USA) is validated in a practical way through research (Hsu, Lee and Straub, 2012). This challenge is strongly related to the 'rationalised myth' of coercive isomorphism because the research goal is aimed at understanding the practices of IA, the exercise of internal controls and reliance on external environments as regulatory effects from the perspectives of industry and academia.

- Normative isomorphism focuses on social standards through socialisation to manage the categorisation of specialised jobs, which disperses activities and whereby this isomorphic relates to influence from professional bodies, consultants and professionalisation operating in the field (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Lawrence and Shadnam, 2008; Hsu, Lee and Straub, 2012). Hu, Hart and Cooke (2007) suggest that the impact of normative pressures can be seen in professional contacts among specialists at events such as conferences and professional association meetings. It can also relate to the core expertise and capabilities of IA practitioners. The ability of IA to communicate and keep track on operational aspects of IA has become more important (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006).
- Mimetic isomorphism raises questions regarding the cognitive impact of imitating successful organisations, which is a potential alternative and perceived to be more legitimate (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Jaffe, 2001; Hsu, Lee and Straub, 2012). It looks at the factors that influence specific organisational decisions in the context of certain practices, methods or structures (Lawrence and Shadnam, 2008; Halimah et al., 2009; Sarens, De Beelde and Everaert, 2009).

In order to develop an effective IBA framework, this research is supported by institutional theory and its isomorphisms. Accounting failures and financial scandals have placed social

pressures on organisations to manage their risks effectively (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009; Deloitte, 2020), along with government pressures to focus on compliance activities through regulation and the influence of implementing global guidelines (i.e. IIA) to ensure that the key elements are derived to improve organisational performance. Although IA is not implemented in many organisations, there is growing recognition that top management must respond to IA activities, resources and competencies in order to support internal controls and regulatory compliance requirements. As a result of the need for organisations to develop and implement IA, it is necessary to develop and implement an IBA framework that is both practical and useful in the context of the banking sector.

3.2.2.2 Ingenuity theory

Ingenuity theory, which focuses on organisational, societal and technological ingenuity in this study setting, emphasises the importance of innovation and cutting-edge practices (Lampel, Honig and Drori, 2014). This theory is a promising research avenue because it opens up many possibilities for developing an effective IA practice that can address key practical, social and economic issues that IA faces as well as how these issues interact with institutional constraints to affect IA's effectiveness in the banking sector. The essence of ingenuity theory, which arose from the Ingenuity Gap (2002), appears to define how societal ability deals with complex future challenges and issues with the goal of determining whether resource scarcity does not impede the growth of prosperity, while it would limit long-term economic development (Homer-Dixon, 2002). The nature of the problems that organisations face has become increasingly complicated and finding solutions to these problems necessitates a process that includes identifying and managing risks and opportunities, developing and implementing creative, innovative and useful ideas and activities, and analysing the consequences of change and improvement, both for individuals and for organisations as a whole.

Reflecting on organisational ingenuity includes not only invention but also ideas that can be used to solve problems, generate value and improve performance (Ungerer, Pretorius and Herholdt, 2011; Ali, Ahmi and Saidin, 2019). This can be used to help organisations develop, survive, and become more competitive as they seek to overcome the challenges (Lampel, Honig and Drori, 2014). Human thoughts, society's actions, and the development of institutions and organisations all require technical ingenuity to deal with physical problems. Social ingenuity is the institutionalisation of social constructions, which is important for adapting strategies that do not include new technologies but instead involve ideas for the development, reformation, and maintenance of institutions like professional bodies (Homer-

Dixon, 2002). It is also obvious that social and technological ingenuity are closely linked, with social ingenuity serving as a precursor to technical ingenuity, but their close dependence depends on an adequate supply of social ingenuity at many levels of society (Homer-Dixon, 2002). Lampel, Honig and Drori (2011) define innovation as ideas applied in a constrained institutional setting where change is unpredictable and creativity occurs within institutional limits. The embedded agency (organisations) dilemma's premise is that ingenuity is critical to stakeholders' bottom-up efforts (Walker, Schlosser and Deephouse, 2014). The importance of legitimising change in order to maintain legitimacy for stakeholders dealing with institutional constraints is also emphasised (Creed, Scully and Austin, 2002; Greenwood, Suddaby and Hinings, 2002).

IA should evolve and improve its quality and effectiveness through changes in operational strategy plans to meet stakeholder expectations and new regulatory requirements (Zain, Zaman and Mohamed, 2015). Changes to IA procedures and activities should include elements of creativity, such as unique ways of working, creative thinking, imaginative critical thinking and advanced problem-solving approaches. This helps stakeholders to get the information they need but requires fulfilling access to resources in line with the organisational objectives and strategies to create an organisational environment that accurately influences IA performance in organisations (Mihret and Woldeyohannis 2008). There is a lack of a unified concept of creativity and determining challenges in the context of IA, which is required to explain changes in IA practices and their impact on addressing issues and enhancing the status, quality and value proposition of IA. To make effective changes to IA practices that add value, improve the organisation's operations and the effectiveness of governance and control mechanisms, methodologies must be implemented. The concept of ingenuity provides methodological bridging by emphasising processes involved in managing boundaries, difficulties and the invention of ingenious solutions, creativity approaches and forms of ingenuity. There should be both local creative problem-solving and cases where genius has a global impact; these should both be included because they are very innovative ways to solve a problem (Lampel, Honig and Drori, 2014).

Finally, IA frequently encounters challenges in completing its work within organisations as well as meeting standards and framework components in key areas. To overcome these challenges, IA has the potential to use innovation at the corporate, business and operational levels. Organisational innovation shapes not only innovative ideas but also the credibility of researchers, societal responses and resources. Ingenuity theory is a valuable tool to look at

the research goal, explain changes, evolve and solve problems, and use ingenuity to deal with problems that have arisen while doing IA.

3.2.2.3 Combined institutional theory and ingenuity theory

While institutional theory describes how institutional constraints (also known as isomorphism) shape organisational behaviour, ingenuity theory is more likely to explain the changes that necessitate IA to meet stakeholders' needs and expectations (Al-Twaijry, Brierley and Gwilliam, 2003; Ridley, 2008; Lampel, Honig and Drori, 2014; Arena and Jeppesen, 2016). Ingenuity can help explain why and how IA practices like roles, processes, activities, frameworks, methodologies and changes improve IA effectiveness. This theory is based on the idea of a set of instructions or human ideas being generated and used to solve practical, social and technical ingenuity in ways that benefit the research goal. It helps to understand how ideas emerge and provides a framework for recognising them (Lampel, Honig and Drori, 2011).

The literature on theory integration considered opposing features that could occur between theories. Despite these reservations, several academics have empirically evaluated the validity of combining two complementary and co-dependent theories (Arena and Azzone, 2009; Lenz and Sarens, 2012). They may be applicable because both institutional and ingenuity theories are linked to organisational design or structure, which is embedded in organisational theory (Greenwood, Hining and Wheten, 2014). The key difference is that each takes a unique approach and proposes different solutions, which is supported by the scope of this research. Institutional theory, for example, focuses on achieving an external fit (e.g. conformity recognition, external support) by adapting its internal environment; this results in a meta-fit as well as performance and efficiency. Ingenuity theory, on the other hand, focuses on achieving an internal fit with an external environment. The key elements discovered as factors and variables supporting the development of an IBA framework have an impact on both theories. Institutional theory is influenced by institutional pressures on 'position', 'standard' and 'regulation', whereas ingenuity theory attempts to adapt to 'variations', 'change' and 'innovation'.

In Figure 3.1, the suitability of institutional and ingenuity theories in the context of IA is compared. Despite its emphasis on internal governance, the IPPF (2017) framework for IA acknowledges both internal and external variables, demonstrating the industrial applicability of mixing theories. Although it does not explicitly mention theories, the spectrum of variables referred in the ingenuity theory operates within and through existing rules and boundaries

(e.g. IPPF 2017, SOX Act of 2002) to solve current and future problems. Thus, the goal of this research is to determine whether institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983) combined with ingenuity theory (Homer-Dixon, 2002) can provide insight into IA effectiveness. The Researcher proposes a theory combination in order to investigate and explain how their correlation can ensure the performance, sustainability and effectiveness of IA in the banking sector.

Figure 3.1: Theoretical derivations of the research framework

Source: The Researcher

3.2.3 Current frameworks evaluation

The purpose of this section is to discuss the value of existing IA frameworks in terms of their contributions and limitations in the context of the proposed IBA framework as well as how the approach and process of the IA department could be applied to the banking sector. As previously stated, IA is a business operation that is dependent on both the internal control assessment and the annual IA plan (EY, 2017). In academic literature, the current practices of the IA programme are similar to those of the traditional audit programme, which involves

to some extent changes to internal governance and operations in banking organisations (Feghali and Hallak, 2019).

Lenz and Hahn (2015) note that IA implementation has been ineffective because many of the benefits of IA have not accrued to organisations that have implemented IA programmes. Such improvements are considered to be transparency, accountability, corporate governance, technological leverage and regulatory compliance as well as improved financial disclosure accuracy, and stricter financial reporting and control standards (PwC, 2012). Only a few researchers claim that banking organisations have developed a structured IA programme (Najah and Omar, 2018). They claim that the IA programme still requires improvement due to a lack of implementation guidance, policies and processes for providing banking services. Thus, the audit programme should include both standard operating procedures, and accounting and regulatory reforms. The failure, however, can be attributed to the implementation of the IA programme, which should have been effective in driving internal control systems in organisations.

While existing frameworks are acknowledged to provide valuable guidance on the process and content of their IA contributions, no specific IA framework exists to meet the needs of the banking sector. For example, banks could follow the ISO 9001: 2015 standard, the IPPF, the SOX Act of 2002 or the BCBS. Furthermore, it is necessary to demonstrate how internal controls are managed under various circumstances to effectively achieve organisational goals. The frameworks presented in the following sub-sections highlight the important factors that influence IBA framework implementation and aim to help the banking sector to improve the compliance standards with internal control systems. It has also revealed areas of implementation and influence that are weak when compared to strengths and opportunities. In response, this research proposes an IBA framework, which addresses the key issues and themes and is supported by practical guidance for establishing sustainable IA in the banking sector to drive long-term value. To summarise, the following sub-sections evaluate frameworks to understand if they indicate how IA practices should be followed, if they are aligned with emerging risks and if they provide guidance on how to develop internal control systems for the banking sector.

3.2.3.1 ISO 9001: 2015 framework on IA

The ISO 9000 standards have evolved into one of the most important management approaches in the world over the last two decades (Abuazza, Labib and Savage, 2019). However, the effectiveness of ISO 9001 quality auditing has been criticised for a focus on

compliance, a failure to detect product and process problems, a failure to predict quality management system (QMS) failures and a failure to add value to organisations. Changes in compliance would place a greater emphasis on performance-based auditing, resulting in better auditing and QMS (Elliott, Dawson and Edwards, 2007; Fonseca *et al.*, 2019). The development of various methods, guidelines, tools and techniques should lead to an improvement in auditing practices (Domingues *et al.*, 2019). Auditing and the use of QMS are well developed in domains other than IA and lessons from those domains could be applied to IA. Some researchers have advocated for the incorporation of performance measurement concepts and techniques into the ISO 9000 world in order to adapt to changing conditions of focus from compliance to improvement (Gupta, 2010; Alic and Rusjan, 2012). As a result of the identification of current issues, ISO 9001 certified organisations were confronted with significant barriers in the conduct of audits as well as on their impact on QMS performance due to the IA deficiency.

The ISO 9001: 2015 framework offers significant advantages for QMS with less emphasis on documentation and improved approaches such as consideration of the organisational context and relevant stakeholders, risk-based thinking and knowledge management (Fonseca, 2015). Lee (2004) notes that organisations should be agile (detective and resilient), adaptable (innovative and resilient) and aligned (constant purpose and value, transparency, authenticity, accountability, and forward-thinking, mutually beneficial stakeholder relationships). The most recent ISO 9004: 2018 standard includes some of the relevant performance measurement concepts. However, because these are not stated explicitly in the current certification standard (ISO 9001: 2015), it is unclear how organisations should implement and evaluate them. Freeman and Drown (2015) recommends that the risk to be identified, implemented and effectively assessed prior to registration and listing. While the ISO 9001: 2015 standard does not require a formal risk analysis record, auditors may look for one, and organisations may struggle to understand risk-based thinking (Abuazza, Labib and Savage, 2019).

In the absence of explicit PM audit criteria, auditors may make subjective decisions. This is an important consideration because top management expects IA to provide valuable information for the review and modification of QMS, and banking strategies and policies, which is currently not possible with current ISO 9001 IA compliance. Thus, an examination of the ISO 9001: 2015 standards-based framework reveals that there is no mention of how to measure performance through IA. In practice, this necessitates the creation of a performance-oriented IA approach with the goal of closing this gap.

3.2.3.2 IPPF

The IPPF is intended to provide guidance for professional IA practice in a timely and accessible manner while also strengthening the position of IA (Burnaby *et al.*, 2009). It was developed by the IIA (2005) to outline the mandatory requirements for IA practice (IIA, 2017). It defines IA, outlines the core principles, the Code of Ethics and Standards, practical implementation guidance and supplementary guidance, which profiles the minimum behavioural requirements of practitioners and organisations when conducting IA and providing services. Figure 3.2 depicts how this works.

Figure 3.2: The IPPF

Source: IIA (2017)

In order for IA to be effective, it necessitates thorough planning as well as a quick response to rapidly changing risks in order to add value and improve an organisation's effectiveness in the current unprecedented environment. In this regard, IA priorities should be aligned with the organisation's objectives and address the risks that have the greatest potential to impair the organisation's ability to achieve its objectives. Since IA is carried out in a variety of economic and cultural settings that differ in purpose, size and structure within organisations, its explosive growth may result in differences in IA practices worldwide, as well as in the application and adherence to standards, between large and small organisations, countries or sectors. Previous studies have never investigated and evaluated compliance with standards around the world or the level of variation in compliance among IIA affiliates (Burnaby *et al.*, 2009).

Feghali and Hallak (2019) indicate that standards are classified into three types: assignment, performance and implementation. The assignment attribution standards are related to the organisation's IA activities. Consequently, these standards, such as those relating to independence and objectivity, apply to all IA departments and internal auditors on a case-by-case basis. Researchers did not investigate compliance with all IIA standards; instead, they focused on compliance with IIA standards that are important for improving the effectiveness of IA (Feghali and Hallak, 2019). The IPPF (2017) suggests that it is concerned with updating the IA principles and identifying key stakeholders in the IA process management. It also recognises the significance of IA practice and the control culture. It does not, however, address how IA should be implemented in banking organisations or the IA qualities entrusted with its implementation that would result in effective IA implementation. Fadzil, Haron and Jantan (2005) found that the top managers of the IA department should have an impact on the monitoring part of internal control systems by adhering to professional competence standards and being objective. Although the IPPF standards have always been based on these principles, they have never been articulated. To be effective, IA practitioners and the IA activities with which they collaborate must be able to demonstrate that they have adhered to all of the aforementioned principles. If an IA activity does not meet any of the principles, it is not as effective as it could be in meeting the mission of IA.

These changes appear to be motivated not only by requests from the organisation's AC or BOD, or by institutional or theoretical changes, but also by opportunities (Deloitte, 2018). Thus, the discussion of the contradiction between financial and operational audits restricts the application of IIA insights. This could be due to the background of many IA functions, such as the background of the CAE, the activities and perspectives of the BOD and the AC on their IA functions. The main reasons for not implementing the IPPF standards in whole or in part are that the BOD or top management does not see them as adding value, managing compliance is time-consuming and IA activities lack adequate staffing. Many IA activities appear to face significant difficulties in proving their functionality. Finally, the assessment of the standards reveals that they have nothing to do with IA activities, though the size of their audit staff influences how frequently the standards are used.

3.2.3.3 The SOX Act of 2002

In response to the failure of large organisations, the US government enacted the SOX Act of 2002 to restore public trust in financial information. This Act establishes corporate responsibilities such as financial reporting (Section 302) and internal control management assessment (Section 404). It is well-intended legislation, but it has underlying problems with

the current regulations due to registrant confusion and disagreement with their external auditor as well as being a massive cost (Gupta and Leech, 2006). In today's world, where there is high accountability and many governance problems, these things are critical to an organisation's success in a better system of internal controls over financial reporting (ICoFR) (Hass, Abdolmohammadi and Burnaby, 2006).

This legislation was implemented in response to public demand for better corporate governance. Implementing and assessing ICoFR is an important aspect of good corporate governance that has spread globally because of the New York Stock Exchange's requirement that all organisations comply with the good corporate governance principles. Furthermore, the legislation has an indirect impact on IA activities by broadening their scope of work, specifically to ensure the effectiveness of the ICoFR. In response to this pressure, the IA department should revise the IA charter's requirements to ensure that GCG is used to comprehensively monitor the organisation's risks and controls. When the ICoFR is implemented, the charter should make it clear that internal auditors play a critical role in ensuring that internal controls on environmental issues and complex financial instruments function properly. The SOX Act of 2002 made top management, auditors and outside auditors more responsible for making sure that financial reporting was accurate and set up reporting channels (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006; Nagy and Cenker, 2007).

The internal auditor's objective assessments and opinions are a valuable input into the new requirements for internal review and disclosure of controls, increased attention to financial controls and financial reporting quality. Section 404 of the Act further supports this notion that management is responsible for establishing and evaluating an appropriate internal control structure, which needs future collaboration in conducting IA research. Findings indicated that disclosures of internal control deficiencies or weaknesses are more likely to be disclosed by more complex, smaller and financially weak organisations with frequent restructuring activities (Behrend and Eulerich, 2019). The Act It also gave internal auditors and accountants what they were looking for when it came to internal financial reporting (Cooper, Leung and Wong, 2006). To deal with the ongoing fraud that seems to be growing with new technology and traditional fraud schemes that keep being started and found, new laws and better enforcement of existing laws are needed.

There are some limitations to the SOX Act of 2002. This approach means that all financial reporting must be done, but specific required disclosures in statements in the financial reporting are not directly related (i.e. included) so receives less attention. In most cases, IA

plays an important role in many organisation’s compliance efforts to assist management with relevant risk and control documentation and testing as well as provide updates to top management and the ACs. This is a major limitation in the framework because the SOX Act of 2002 does not outline what it takes to make the framework work. Instead, it demonstrates that a process must be put in place to address practicality in internal control assessment (Gray and Ehoff, 2015).

3.2.3.4 The BCBS

The BCBS serves as a forum for banking supervision cooperation and is the primary global standard-setter for prudential banking regulation (Zinca, 2016). The BIS organises the BCBS, which serves central banks in their pursuit of monetary and financial stability. It recognises that strong internal control systems can help a banking organisation achieve its objectives (Al-Matari, Hassan and Alaaraj, 2016). The BCBS Core Principles and other relevant guidance issued by the BIS contain references to support the channels of communication for the IA function, as shown in Figure 3.3. Other bodies that provide relevant guidance include the International Standards for Auditing (ISA) issued by the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB) and the IIA standards. Figure 3.3 does not include all communication channels for parties other than the IA function (FRC, 2018).

Figure 3.3: IA function’s communication channels

Source: Adopted from BIS (2012)

The BCBS defines internal controls as a process carried out by the BOD, top management and all levels of staff. It is not just a procedure or policy that is put in place at a specific point in time, but it is put in place continuously at all levels of the bank (BIS, 2012). In this regard, Basel III aims to improve the banking sector’s ability to absorb disruptions caused by financial and economic crises, risk management and governance as well as improve banks’

transparency and disclosure (Ali and Bansal, 2019). Based on the assertions made above, they should have an impact on bank capital structures and business structures. Among the principles are management oversight and control culture, risk identification and assessment, control activities and separation of duties, information and communication, monitoring and correction of deficiencies and supervisory authority assessment of internal control systems (BIS, 2012). This means that internal auditors must be independent and trustworthy, and that each bank must have a permanent IA department. Furthermore, supervisors should keep in touch with the bank’s internal auditor on a regular basis and assess the IA’s strength.

There is no mention of how to ensure that the IA programme becomes a real instrument, effectively applied and integrated into the operation of the IA department, including the development of internal quality assessment indicators and the role and responsibilities of IA activities in the assessment of IA activities under the BIS (2012) standards-based framework. Sinha and Arena (2018) agree that the failure of IA frameworks is due to a lack of proper IA planning and implementation. The majority of IA implementation frameworks, including the BCBS standards-based framework, propose a prescriptive format, which could explain these failures.

3.3 Synthesis of framework derivatives

Based on the research evidence (Section 3.2), it is proclaimed first that there is a lack of research in the IA domain. Second, the investigation found a lack of understanding and controversies in the IA field, and third, the literature found significant limitations in previous studies that need to be addressed. These gaps help make the reason for this research much more robust and stronger; thus, the aim of this research is much more logical and reliable. Table 3.6 below summarises the confirmatory evidence of the research problem, which helps identify the key elements of the theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4) and the achievement of the research aim and answer the research questions.

Table 3.6: Research gap derivations

Derivatives	Identified literature gaps
Literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of a strategic alignment of IA; - Lack of IA practical guidelines; - Lack of strong institutional environment; - Lack of coherent theory; - Inadequate support from the AC and top management.

Systematic literature evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of resource allocation and poor governance mechanism; - Lack of reliability on organisational IT systems, outputs and performance; - Lack of adequate top management oversight and accountability; - Lack of a fully dynamic IA framework; - Inconsistent theoretical framework and quality of strategic planning; - Lack of capacity building and institutional development; - Lack of effectiveness on IA department performance; - Lack of quality of the internal control systems.
Framework evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is limited consideration of IA-related frameworks in the banking sector; - Inadequate approach towards IA with the relationship between corporate, cultural, operational, strategic and social functional areas.

Source: The Researcher

The literature investigation reveals a significant research gap in identifying IA challenges in the context of banks. However, there is a scarcity of research on IA in Bangladesh. There is a lack of studies that have identified and investigated the challenges confronting IA, including a geographical gap in Southeast Asia, and the specific context of Bangladesh. With this gap in mind, the first research question is developed to identify and visualise the main challenges faced by banks in general and Bangladesh in particular.

In the field of IA, there is a lack of understanding and debate regarding IA practices and effectiveness. Several studies have been conducted on this specific issue with varying results (factors recommended for further research), and it is still being debated in practice as to how researchers should understand the problem IA practices to be effective in the banking sector, particularly in the context of Bangladesh, how IA practices are to be maintained, what factors affect the practices of IA in banks, how IA should be sustained in banking organisations, and what significant steps should be undertaken to improve the effectiveness of IA and to achieve a sound IA, which authenticates the need for research questions two and three in this research.

Based on the framework evaluation, the current frameworks are conceptual and require empirical validations. There is no literature claiming that developing and implementing an IBA framework supported by practical guidance for the banking sector should transform the

banking sector in general, including Bangladesh. Based on this viewpoint, this research identified a significant research gap in the domain, namely that there is no consistent and high-level framework in the literature to guide banking organisations in effectively implementing IA while adhering to a strong institutional environment, which validates research question four in this research.

3.4 IBA framework

The IBA framework is derived from a systematic review of the literature, which identifies the key strengths and weaknesses of IA research discovered in the literature gap by utilising insights gathered from academic and industry-based contributions (Chapters 2 and 3). The first derivative is a contribution to the literature, the second derivative is an SLR, the third derivative is a framework evaluation, and the fourth derivative is the research gap. This framework is further supported by a fifth derivative, which strengthens the theoretical perspectives based on these four derivations. Reflecting on the framework's primary function, it is necessary to rely on key IA elements by investigating the current challenges and practices within internal and external environments. In this case, this research synthesises the research gaps (Section 3.3) found in the literature review, systematic literature evaluation, and current framework evaluation. This is meant to show that the IBA framework is both valid and necessary for the banking sector. Thus, the Researcher considers key attributes that are essential, such as consistency, dynamism, definitive, transparent, simplicity, and strategic focus on developing the IBA framework, which also provides practical guidance for effective implementation.

Key IA elements are implemented across the banking organisation by focusing on their strategic nature and addressing their requirements to close the research gap. Effective frameworks are essential for safeguarding assets and integrity, improving accountability, and preventing corruption across the banking sector. Thus, the framework should include IA measures, control assessments, and assurance of achieving a strategic vision, such as financial reporting reliability, operational effectiveness and efficiency, attaining skills and competencies, and integration of compliance with applicable rules, regulations, and legislation. As noted, corporate audit leaders often have a hard time promoting and developing consistent IA tools and approaches to deliver an impact assessment of how new standards should be incorporated into the context of organisations (KPMG, 2017). Therefore, the IBA framework encourages top management to use a consistent approach to the transition road map to help spread new standards across organisations and ensure

that behavioural changes are needed in the context of business processes and internal controls.

Figure 3.4: The theoretical IBA framework

Source: The Researcher

In Figure 3.4, the IBA framework has been developed that leads to an integrated, transparent, well-defined and risk-based approach to provide recommendations for the design and implementation of new internal control systems, alignment of IA with emerging risks, IA standards and governance, and IA quality assurance that improves the quality of audits and reporting while maintaining a level of consistency across banking organisations. In addition, the critical elements of IA development and implementation would enhance the ability to ensure its simplicity and explain IA practices to provide timely transparency to top management through more insightful and functional reporting, continuous monitoring, internal control assessment and more streamlined and flexible audits. A dynamic internal control assessment approach that changes as new risks emerge should help organisations find control trends and prioritise control gaps based on control-based principles (PwC, 2018). In this regard, banking organisations can then get the best assurance coverage.

Table 3.1 presents the key factors that help in developing the proposed IBA framework depicted in Figure 3.4. The framework is composed of the following pillars, which are discussed in the subsequent sub-sections. The four critical pillars, which are intertwined in the internal environment, are: IA input factors, IA foundation, IA integration and outputs (benefits). These elements are made up of effective oversight that is influenced and recognises the potential of IA by changes in the external environment due to regulatory, financial, political, economic and cultural aspects. This unifying framework should be able to show how quickly the banking industry is changing and dealing with many new risks and new opportunities (PwC, 2018). It is important for the IA department to inform top management about these new and more complicated risks, so that they can make well-defined decisions and take strong actions (Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

The dynamic, adaptive and progressive nature of the above framework (Figure 3.4) aims to employ best practices to streamline auditing processes with the need to keep pace with the changing legislative landscape, aiming to implement accountability, transparency and internal controls to provide independent assurance and sound corporate governance. Further supporting the notion is that this should be able to provide the ability to make consistent and timely decisions, reduce risks and meet the strategic vision in order to minimise negative consequences for the organisation. Regardless of their nature and culture, top management should monitor if there is any weakness or lack of internal controls and what remedial action should be undertaken to make them mandatory to be effective in identifying internal and external factors affecting organisations. Most banks need to have an IA department to manage new risks, add new skills, collaborate with other risk functions and use innovation and technology, but very few have a dedicated IA programme in place to meet their goals (PwC, 2015; Turetken, Jethefer and Ozkan, 2020). Thus, without a plan that clearly explains and captures the IA's functions, it is hard to stay on a clear path that fits with the IA's mission and vision. This means that IA needs to take the necessary tactical steps to develop its functions. But the challenge is to make sure that IA is part of an organisation's strategic plan in a way that leads to goals being met and shareholder value being added.

The challenge for IA is to ensure the long-term success of an organisation and it is the responsibility of IA to contribute added value in the form of appropriate assurance services. Based on the long-term economic and intergenerational risk perspective, the development of a suitable audit service to mitigate emerging risks is a top priority for IA departments in organisations. In this regard, a strong corporate culture encourages

collaboration between IA and audit teams because organisations and functions are eager to align capacity to thrive in response to changing opportunities and demands from the IA perspective. Even during routine audits, corporate leaders identify potential gaps that can be addressed proactively. The goal is to establish a relationship in which IA independence is respected and contributions are viewed as a means of improving organisations. This is because sound corporate governance enables organisations to properly manage and capitalise on different risks and opportunities for their long-term prosperity. As the highest governance bodies, the BOD and the AC should evaluate the effectiveness of the existing governance structure and processes in addressing risk categories to ensure adequate oversight over the organisation's significant risk issues.

The Researcher examined academic research and industry-based literature to identify the key elements that describe the relevant aspects of the dynamic interaction of key IA components and methods for establishing consistency in banking organisations when developing the IBA framework (Figure 3.4). The Researcher also incorporates critical findings from the literature gap into the theoretical baseline in order to develop the IBA framework. Moreover, the IBA framework should be strategically focused on incorporating key components of best practice in IA to ensure its sustainability in generating value and establishing a competitive advantage across the banking sector.

The proposed IBA framework provides a structured approach to addressing IA issues, themes, and derivations. This framework serves as a system or plan that can be incorporated into the concepts, elements, interdependencies, and interrelationships of research problems. By integrating this framework into research, the goals of arguing for the importance of researching the issue, determining the proposed solution to the problem, and contributing to the research rationale can be achieved (Maxwell 2012; Nilsen 2015). The theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4) offers a strategic vision for aligning the IA process, functions, structure, practices and effectiveness to promote unified accountability and transparency in the banking sector.

A robust and adaptable IBA framework is essential for successful implementation across organisations. This includes focusing on the key principles that banks must adopt to facilitate the effective management of strategies and objectives, governance process, and guiding principles of IA. This framework should enable the creation of a measurable and repeatable method (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013; Almodallah, Shahimi and Azmi, 2023; Grima *et al.*, 2023). To ensure and improve IA quality, an effective framework begins with the approval

of policies, practices, and procedures that support effective IA implementation (Badara, 2017). In addition, maintaining a high level of transparency and resilience in managing processes and activities is crucial because changes can occur because of internal or external influences. Given the current business environment, it is imperative that banks implement a dynamic framework that fosters a culture of financial resilience in the banking sector.

Identifying key elements and theoretical constructs is crucial for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of IA, which is essential for designing and developing an IBA framework (Figure 3.4). To provide reasonable assurance of quality to various stakeholders in banks, it is important that the IA operates in accordance with its strategy and continuously improves its operations, covering all aspects of the framework, including monitoring the IBA framework to ensure its effective and efficient operation and compliance with standards as well as adding value and improving organisational operations. For instance, internal auditors should familiarise themselves with the legislative universe of their organisations to ensure that structures and processes are adequate and effective in mitigating emerging risks.

A practical guidance on the implementation of the proposed IBA framework (Figure 3.4) is discussed, validated and presented in Chapter 6 (Section 6.5).

To improve efficiency and enhance the ability to identify and solve IA problems to achieve sustainable success, banking organisations should establish a comprehensive framework. This framework should encompass functional areas and include efforts to adapt to changes in internal and external factors as well as performance improvement. Additionally, a unified framework that emphasises the importance of strong organisational efficiency in the banking sector should be developed and implemented. The proposed IBA framework provides practical guidance for the implementation of IA with the goal of strategic advice, ensuring accurate financial statements, making risk-based decisions, and making organisations more resilient to new risks. The following sub-sections discuss the critical IA input elements for the IBA framework.

3.4.1 IA input factors to the IBA framework

The IA input factors for the IBA framework (Figure 3.4) are recognised as having a significant influence on achieving strategic vision, aligned assurance and organisational objectives in the formation and determination of the root causes of improving performance across banking organisations. These IA inputs, therefore, leverage existing IA activities to manage and

monitor continuously, and initiate the strategic direction of organisations aiming to align IA. Such input factors are different for each organisation and the compilation of a review of existing literature is, therefore, crucial for top management to understand the strategic and control objectives to define input factors that are appropriate for each organisation. Based on the literature findings, Chapters 2 and 3 found that the following are the most important input factors for IA:

- Key banking auditing challenges;
- IA alignment with emerging risks;
- Internal control systems;
- IA standards and governance;
- IA quality assurance.

The most important issues that affect the effectiveness of IA have been considered. This leads to a list of challenges that can be summarised as a lack of top-level support, IT issues, resource constraints and a lack of an overall risk-based IA approach (Newman and Comfort, 2018). As challenges have become an integral part of the organisational context, IA should assess and determine whether its value proposition is determined and aligned with the organisational strategy (Rensburg and Coetzee, 2015). In addition, the Researcher considers the link between IA and its strategic objectives of mapping the emerging risks associated with IA activities. This consideration should possess integrity, and gain credibility and respect to understand the building of relationships, demonstrate objectivity and good judgement, and communicate tough issues fairly and thoughtfully.

Most of the banking auditing challenges facing IA can be overcome with well-designed terms of reference that define roles and responsibilities that can be acknowledged (PwC, 2017). The lack of specific operational knowledge that senior and operational managers has, or that they should be aware of the lack of this in IA in general in their organisation. Consequently, managers should be encouraged to play an active role in empowering IA by sharing knowledge of the operations of organisations (Behrend and Eulerich, 2019). The effectiveness of IA practices is, therefore, linked to the overall effectiveness of the organisations in which they operate.

Considering the favourable impact that effective internal control systems have, they are a key component of the framework that helps an organisation to comply with its mandate and any relevant legislation, safeguard its assets and facilitate internal and external reporting. It

also helps ensure greater accountability, better management and increased cost-effectiveness, as controls help organisations run more smoothly, reduce costs, avoid waste, hold officials accountable for their actions and report to the public and supervisory authorities on the performance and value of money achieved. Various researchers support the notion that IA has a positive impact on the internal control systems (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005; Dellai and Omri, 2016). IA creates value for the performance of organisations through management by evaluating and improving the effectiveness of internal control systems (Moeller, 2009). It is recognised as a critical mechanism for internal control systems (Hanafi and Stewart, 2015).

Further supporting the notion that it is significantly and positively associated with value; IA adds value to organisations by adopting a systematic approach to improve and evaluate their internal control systems. Badara and Saidin (2014) argue that the internal control systems should influence the effectiveness of IA by monitoring its components. Research evidence indicates that having a dedicated accountability and transparency control system is important for raising awareness of new risks and figuring out how to deal with the biggest risks that could happen in different organisations (Najah and Omar, 2018; PwC, 2017). Whether the risks are internal or external, strategic or operational, financial or compliance-related, they have an impact on how resources are allocated, how decisions are made and how organisations can identify and respond to risks in a way that is appropriate for them.

One of the most important components to IA's success as a value-added and strategic business element is an effective and sound risk-based IA plan. In order to define the priorities of IA activities in accordance with the organisation's objectives, the CAE should develop a risk-based IA plan (ECIIA, 2018). Thus, modern IA should aim to understand the key risks of organisations and have the ability to assess and evaluate emerging risks proactively that add value to organisations. This enables IA to assist organisations in the efficient and effective allocation of organisational capacity and resources to mitigate risks, gain deeper and new insights and further develop their strategic role (KPMG, 2017). For instance, it is necessary to address emerging risks to develop effective IA and even for survival to overcome organisational challenges. For instance, key emerging risks that IA should consider and contribute valuable insight to the management in the development of the annual strategic audit plan include the following: (i) effective talent management, (ii) alignment of operations with the strategy and objectives of organisations, (iii) compliance management systems (CMS), auditing of organisations, culture and ethics, (iv) efficiency and effectiveness of the operational processes, (v) integrated enterprise risk management,

(vi) IT governance, and (vii) outsourcing and managing third-party relationships (KPMG, 2019).

Gramling *et al.* (2004) suggest that IA activities typically include risk assessment, compliance work and control assurance, all of which are directly linked to corporate governance. Other areas where IA can be concentrated include providing management consulting services, health, safety and environmental audits, and performing quality (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Politis, 2019). Bananuka, Mukyala and Nalukenge (2017) suggest that IA should include within its scope the design and operational effectiveness of internal governance structures and processes, the information provided to the BOD and executive management, and the processes and controls supporting strategic and operational decision-making. Understanding the perception of IA activities have been influenced by regulations, stock exchange requirements and corporate governance standards while the adequacy of the guidance adds strategic value to organisations, which lead to providing solutions to increasing the level of technological innovations and to increase compliance standards (Burnaby *et al.*, 2009).

The key benefits of integrating the environment of IA quality into strategic and operational planning should provide assurance over efficiency and effectiveness in the sharing of resources, knowledge and expertise and a critical platform for information exchange (Deloitte, 2016). It also enables organisations to focus on organisational needs and improvement opportunities, to solve problems outside of their traditional boundaries, to make changes in audit planning to enable process-oriented auditing and to implement changes by addressing policy misalignment (Lenning and Gremyr, 2021). However, effective implementation requires a functioning solution with a detailed implementation plan to increase the benefits and exceed stakeholders' expectations in pursuit of strategic and operational objectives. This includes methods and tools to continuously improve that clearly define roles and responsibilities, and adequate investment in ensuring a sufficient workforce and organisational resources.

The aforementioned IA input factors presented in this section were derived from the systematic literature evaluation and the literature gap (Chapters 2 and 3), which are regarded as critical to long-term IA practices and effective implementation of the IBA framework to add value, and improve an organisation's operations. To support this notion, the qualitative data analysis obtained from the empirical investigation discussed in Chapters 5, 6, and 7 is used to determine the significance of all the key elements discussed in this

sub-section. The following Sub-Section 3.4.2 discusses the IA foundation factors of the theoretical IBA framework.

3.4.2 IA foundation

This sub-section considers the key elements of the IA foundation as part of the theoretical IBA framework with a focus on risk-based IA in the current complex global context. The framework seeks to establish a new emphasis on long-term, compliance-based decisions. It emphasises the importance of ensuring a strategic approach by adding value to organisations' financial status, increasing accountability for identifying and evaluating key IA challenges and ensuring that banking organisations operate with integrity and in compliance with existing policies, laws and regulations. Conversely, a strong and independent IBA framework enables organisations to manage risks, control and mitigate risks related to misconduct, money laundering, and other forms of non-compliance to ensure efficiency and added value, thereby supporting organisational efforts to gain a competitive advantage over industry peers. This sub-section emphasises its strategic focus as it examines the framework's fundamental elements (Figure 3.4). This discussion focuses on some of the most important aspects of IA such as processes, functions, practices and effectiveness.

3.4.2.1 IA process

To improve an organisation's ability to achieve its strategic, business and operational tools, IA process that integrates its various phases including planning, execution, data gathering, data interpretation and follow-up, is required (KPMG, 2019; Abuazza, Labib and Savage, 2020). The IA outputs, on the other hand, are primarily concerned with providing information to senior management and the BOD that may be critical to effective decision-making. Thus, capitalising on the benefits of IA that are aligned with existing strategy planning and implementation, as well as operational processes at various levels, is critical (Mihret, 2014). While strategic planning necessitates the development, evaluation and implementation of decisions that can support the achievement of organisational goals, IA should enable the process to assess and measures risk and control (Sandle, 2016). One of the important aspects of the risk-based IA is a methodology that targets monitoring, assessment, identification and treatment of key risks that may obstruct their achievement in an organisation's risk management framework (ISO, 2015; Sandle, 2016). Thus, the process can be thought of as an IA cycle used in the IBA framework to ensure the creation and implementation of four major phases (Figure 3.5): (i) the alignment of the strategic vision, (ii) the understanding of rules, systems, risks and controls (RSRC), (iii) the evaluation and

implementation of RSRC, and (iv) the reporting and monitoring of changes and ideas. The following actions can be taken.

Figure 3.5: The four stages of IA cycle

Source: The Researcher

Figure 3.5 depicts how the IBA framework, as an essential component of the IA foundation pillar, aligns with the strategic vision and operational planning. Aligning the strategic vision with IA can improve performance and make it easier to implement core strategies while meeting key objectives. The principles in Figure 3.5 are derived from the current IA frameworks and standards specified in Sub-Section 3.2.3. This shows that the core of the framework is the alignment of IA with organisational goals and strategies, which is one of its most important parts.

- Stage 1: Planning to align the strategic vision. There are two key objectives at the planning stage. First, aligning the strategic vision by presenting robust bank cases, and second, preparing the control assessment to focus resources on higher control areas for banks.
- Stage 2: Understanding of the RSRC. The purpose of this stage is to determine the type of RSRC in an IA department and to classify them based on their value to banks.
- Stage 3: Evaluation and establishment of the RSRC. The objective at this stage is to evaluate and establish RSRC by defining their place in the knowledge base of the bank.
- Stage 4: Reporting and monitoring of changes and ideas. The final stage is to demonstrate the results of the IBA framework by producing a final piece of research that recommends actions to be taken on changes and ideas. The relevant details of these tools and techniques are provided in Chapter 6.

When a strategic context is developed, the strategic direction, vision and mission of organisations guide major organisational objectives that are set in parallel. The formulation

and implementation of core strategies within the organisational structure is determined by the identification of essential organisational objectives. Treatment controls are an important element of the IA process, and they should be closely aligned with the control assessment (i.e. identifying and analysing essential controls) (ICAEW, 2015). Improving the strategy's implementation is in perfect agreement when considering the degree of confidence in control measures with the actions performed in managing critical controls by using the relevant management tools (Coleman, 2015; Smooth, 2016). Following the formulation of core strategies, IA feedback may assist organisations in revising the underlying assumptions of their controls and organisational strategies as well as adapting to any internal or external changes that may arise.

3.4.2.2 IA functions

IA functions are an important component of the IBA framework because they should be able to check any area of operations in an organisation to see if policies and procedures are adequate, secure and working as intended or if new controls are needed to correct errors (Zaman and Sarens, 2013). Internal controls and IA have not always performed as intended in recent years, and they have failed to detect errors, mistakes and fraud in the banking sector. Based on the literature findings (Chapters 2 and 3), Figure 3.6 below is developed to support and enable the development of the IBA framework in the banking sector.

Figure 3.6: Key elements of IA functions

Source: The Researcher

Regardless of the depth and breadth of an organisation, the primary role of IA functions is to create and add value to its core activities (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009). In a true sense, this can be accomplished through the objectives and growth of organisations. Chambers and Odar (2015) emphasise that IA is one of the gatekeepers that failed during the economic crisis, and one solution is to strengthen the risk management function. Another research concluded that the IA functions identified numerous deficiencies in the early 2000s but these warnings were ignored (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). Therefore, this suggests that the supervisory committees did not prioritise risk reduction in general or the importance of IA functions.

For IA to be able to adapt at the same rate as changing strategic risks, the changing environment necessitates a dynamic planning function (Zain and Subramaniam, 2007). Strategic risks are becoming more important as IA functions are not regarded as a top priority. PwC (2018) notes that in meeting these requirements the key elements of IA functions have accounted for the central parts of a high-performance IA function. For instance, developing relevant and current IA programmes that align with the increased expectations of stakeholders, and developing an enhanced understanding of the risk landscape to effectively assess the management of emerging risks and the underlying internal control culture of organisations.

Given the increased business complexity caused by the audit approach's challenges in terms of scope, skills and experience, the depth and impact of reporting allows the audit team to better understand emerging risks and the control environment. The auditing profession must transform more effectively by implementing technology, freeing up time and resources to be more strategically focused (IIA, 2019). Thus, these tools and methods would improve insights into risk assessment, risk analysis and controls, which have always been needed and relevant for banking organisations.

3.4.2.3 IA practices

The development of IA practices in banks is another critical component of the IA foundation. This includes the impact of IA competence and independence on financial reporting quality (Abbott *et al.*, 2015), the impact of IA quality on management misconduct (Ege, 2015) and, the most sensitive yet, critical aspects of the IA process (Prawitt, Smith and Wood, 2009). As a part of its effective implementation across banking organisations, Section 2.6 (Chapter 2) discusses the importance of IA practices more in-depth. IA practices, in particular, are distinguished by norms and beliefs that pervade functional activities and increase the

likelihood of policy compliance and linkages to other functions (Deloitte, 2013). It is also critical to adopt the presence of emerging best practices in order to actively develop strategies to facilitate implementation and improve IA compliance. The best practices, such as responding to resource challenges, auditing culture, regulatory relations and quality assurance, tend to be more potent (Chersan, 2016). As a consequence, the assessment of IA practices should ensure that the implementation plan has a range of activities to fulfil its role in banks, and specific guidance is needed on how roles should be performed and how they should be more functional to work effectively.

Organisational structure and internal management relations within IA activities, as well as the relationship of audit executives to senior management, are the key measures for effective IA practices in organisations (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Badara and Saidin, 2013). Where the reporting relationship of the audit executive is undeveloped, such as administrative and functional, this creates a lack of confidence and instability in the auditing culture of organisations. However, if financial reporting is well defined, it can facilitate how IA activities fit within organisational governance and structure of the entity (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011). Thus, failure to address these key issues should not be overlooked in critical organisational areas.

Within the scope of this research, the inclusion of academic and industry-based literature analysed as part of the IA practice element is inspired and supported the development of the IBA framework. However, the literature suggests difficulties in measuring and implementing IA practices in maintaining governance processes and the lack of a generally agreed approach (Arena and Azzone, 2009; Erasmus and Coetzee, 2018). This shows that the implementation of IA recommendations by management as an outcome measure and the maintenance of a strong IA programme are the keys to meaningful and sustainable IA practices (Roussy and Brivot, 2016), and that the level of implementation of IA recommendations should be used as some of the objective measures of its effectiveness (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007; Arena and Azzone, 2009).

It is essential to determine how effective IA practices are and how they affect the implementation of an effective IBA framework for the banking sector. By increasing awareness to understand the motivations behind the establishment of an IA department and the identification of contextual forces, the research suggests that organisations that are able to make investments in IA should help to develop pragmatic approaches to further promote

the recognition of the IA profession in the contemporary environment. Further, this development of IA should enable a deeper understanding of the types of services that management is likely to seek from IA.

3.4.2.4 IA effectiveness

The requirements for the planning and design of the IBA framework in banks presented in this section are consistent with the methodology set out above. The methodology is structurally identical as it follows the strategy and objective requirements of the IA. BIS (2012) note that the quality assessment in banks depends on internal auditors, who are responsible for developing quality, and that the IA programme also serves as a basis for the provision of well-structured, sound recommendations, improving the activities of the IA. A more complete picture of the application of international standards on IA compliance should reveal the adequacy of the IA charter, which outlines IA aligned with its activities, objectives, policies and procedures (Nedyalkova, 2019).

The implementation of the framework is imperative in order to carry out an assessment of the IA. However, the contribution to the GRC of organisations should also focus on the effectiveness of activities, continuous improvement and adoption of best IA practices. The results of the assessment methods may be the same, but they may also be different. The Researcher agrees with Deloitte (2017) that a more in-depth analysis should be carried out to determine whether a new method, different from that adopted by the standards, is the most appropriate and effective for banks. It is important to have a framework for quality assurance and improvement of internal control systems in order to get an accurate picture of how well they work.

3.4.3 IA integration

The IBA framework's integration element (Figure 3.4) consists of three components: IA role and profession, IA policy and framework, and IA structure and reporting. Argento *et al.* (2018) argue that IA should incorporate perspectives into its IA programme while remaining independent and relying on integration into the key process. The alignment of IA with core organisational strategies focusses on high organisational risk areas and expands a significant opportunity for IA integration to get strong management support (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006). To balance the desire for consistency across organisations, IA should develop a regulatory agenda before taking any further steps towards integration (Deloitte, 2013). A clear and transparent financial reporting structure, accountability and good communication between key IA roles, supported by the critical role of professional

competencies and the effectiveness of IA in understanding the factors that influence audit effectiveness, are critical to the development of an effective IBA framework. For instance, internal auditors should have the knowledge, skills and expertise to gain key insights into the audit environment, including threats and opportunities that are present, evolving or on the horizon (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009). To address this competency issue, strategic planning efforts serve as the foundation for a bank's planning measures to align the IA programme with the ideals and direction outlined in the comprehensive IA plan (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: Key elements of IA strategic competency integration

Source: The Researcher

A strategic competency plan is developed based on Figure 3.7 by identifying required and available competencies. While gaps are identified, strategies are implemented to obtain this expertise through structure and reporting efforts, the development of current roles and professions and the operationalisation of audit effectiveness. The aforementioned issues have identified 'needs' areas of competence in order to drive changes in accountability and transparency, identify frameworks, tools and techniques, and factors that may influence the effectiveness of IA (Mihret and Grant, 2017). This plan is multifaceted and is viewed from three perspectives: the auditing profession as a whole, the audit entity and the individual

auditor. The strategic competency process identifies six key areas of competence and details the objectives, focus and implementation strategy for each area. This competency plan should provide an opportunity to improve each auditor's capacity so that, as needed, banks can provide insightful audits and services to their stakeholders. Thus, the framework, tools and techniques in the plan are all focused on improving existing skills through core critical thinking skills that are specific to IA. Core audit skills should always be a top priority in any action plan.

3.4.4 The outputs of the IBA framework

The previous factors have defined the context of IA outputs where the presence and implementation of an effective IBA framework is vital to banks, which engage in broader financial, economic and social roles. Along with aligned IA and internal control systems, its goal of being a valuable contributor to identifying and addressing emerging risks while containing costs can be achieved by focusing on three main areas: corporate, business and operational (Christopher, Sarens and Leung, 2009; Zaman and Sarens, 2013; Deloitte, 2017). These areas can be improved to develop a long-term vision and strategy, improve coordination across regulatory expectations and pressures, and change an operating model to give more assurance to outsiders about what they can trust. At a more granular level, it is critical to identify the specific corporate, business and operational benefits of implementing the IBA framework. However, the key challenges of IA demonstrate that IA personnel's knowledge, skills and competencies are aligned with the expertise required to deliver on vision and strategy (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). IPPF (2017) note that internal auditors must have sufficient knowledge, skills and competencies to carry out their duties. Another study done by Deloitte (2011) states that the compliance functions of banks needed adequate quantitative and qualitative resources.

The IBA framework outputs, shown in detail in Figure 3.8, are considered to be potential benefits that the IBA framework facilitates. Najah and Omar (2018) note that the internal auditor's role in regulatory compliance in banks remains too low to cope with any increase in compliance-related workloads or challenges. This suggests that the systemic nature of risks and interconnectivity in banks has created a need for a dynamic IBA framework that is flexible and can address emerging risks. Narayanaswamy, Raghunandan and Rama (2018) note that banks need to adopt policies and processes relevant to regulatory compliance. Many banks have set up a separate quality assurance department to conduct compliance testing across business lines and organisations in order to have an efficient IA activity, thus improving transparency with respect to compliance-related risks. It is also important for

auditors to specialise in risk categories and coordinate key management committee roles, stakeholder relationships and audit requirements, which is a way to get the right level of audit coverage while reducing costs.

Figure 3.8: Outputs of the IBA framework

Source: The Researcher

In addressing outputs of the IBA framework (Figure 3.8), it focuses on reporting capabilities to be able to provide feedback to the business before risks are realised that affect business performance most significantly such as failure to align IA with strategic vision and objectives. Understanding the internal control culture is a key input into the IA programme, which should provide greater assurance from the IA programme and judgemental selection of transactions based on predetermined criteria. The effectiveness of IA and its relationship to cost savings are two important and critical points of discussion on the possible benefits of the process.

The Researcher believes that the strategic nature of the IBA framework provides banking organisations with a competitive advantage. Various researchers have identified that the presence of a strong IA creates a significant advantage in terms of adapting to changing market developments, better alignment and accountability, digital presence, and expanding technology utilisation (Puci and Guxholli, 2018; Hazaea et al., 2020). Porter (1985) recommends three strategies to gain competitive advantage: cost advantage, differentiation,

and focus. To reduce the potential impact of strategic, operational, financial, and compliance risks, it is necessary to develop adaptable internal management systems that can adapt to new requirements and transformations by achieving a set of objectives and identifying challenging areas that pose risks to the organisation and opportunities for development. Rather than viewing IA as a compliance exercise, it is necessary to recognise its potential as a very important value-adding component that can help reduce risk and contribute to the establishment and operation of adequate internal governance. These changes and improvements give IA a chance to help the organisation's long-term value and performance through its independent role in the organisation and objective assurance services of internal processes.

The main issues that need to be addressed are adaptability and taking steps to become more agile, which include revamping not only internal processes but also core activities. The evaluation process and underlying methodology are made more transparent to make the IBA framework more realistic and relevant as the banking sector enters a new era. The ultimate goals remain the same: to strengthen trust in actions, support banking sector consolidation, share knowledge about IT and cyber risk development, and encourage banks to adapt more quickly to climate change and financial technology. All these goals aim to serve the common objectives of the sound banking sector.

3.5 Conclusion

Given the increased demand for IA and its implications in a variety of organisations in recent years, banking organisations have been persuaded to understand and implement its strategic importance in added value. The findings of the literature evaluation and the identified gaps further indicate that top management should concentrate on implementing IA to ensure long-term organisational performance and significant benefits. Based on Chapters 2 and 3, one of the most significant challenges that organisations face is a lack of clear and concise step-by-step practical guidance for implementing an effective IBA framework that needs to be aligned with the strategic vision. Recent research also indicates that strategic IA should allow top management to focus on developing a mature and sustainable banking auditing system while also focusing on the core objectives and internal control systems.

This chapter discusses the development of a theoretical IBA framework (Section 3.4), which is supported by key elements within internal and external contexts of the banking sector by evaluating current IA frameworks and by relevant contributions to academic and industry-

based literature. The proposed IBA framework is intended to fill the gap in the literature identified in Chapter 3 and Sub-Section 3.2.1. Among the most difficult challenges have been a lack of a fully integrated strategic approach to IA across the banking sector and a lack of top management support for IA implementation. To meet these needs, the IBA framework (Figure 3.4) aligns key factors important to IA adoption and implementation that are further substantiated through an empirical investigation to ensure their reliability and validity. Furthermore, this framework was developed to improve the continuity of organisational performance by carrying out monitoring activities and discussing ongoing initiatives by banking organisations, both of which are critical to achieving the strategic vision. Finally, an explanation of how this framework should be validated through means, methods and instruments is explored, explaining in depth the discussion of how the main research question is addressed.

Chapter 4: Research methodology and methods

4.1 Introduction

This research aims to investigate the challenges that IA faces in the banking sector. The preceding chapters have established the status of IA in the existing academic and industry-based literature, which addressed prior developments and literature gaps in the banking sector. They have also developed theoretical constructs, such as the IBA framework, to act as lenses that can be used to conceptualise and analyse the empirical findings. The purpose of this chapter is to present a discussion on the adopted research methodology and methods to focus on key aspects of broad philosophical viewpoints, approaches, strategies, data collection methods, procedures and analysis techniques (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: The research onion

Source: Adapted from Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019)

This research relied on systematic literature evaluation and interview data analysis to provide new insights into the research problem. This chapter presents the research design and justifies the research strategy by describing ‘how’ and ‘why’ it uses a qualitative approach for data collection and analysis in conjunction with the philosophical assumptions that underpin empirical research. In terms of the chosen research philosophy, this chapter is organised using an interpretivism followed by an explanation of a case study strategy that describes how data is collected, analysed and interpreted while ethical considerations are considered.

4.2 Research philosophy

A research philosophy is the 'preferred way of comprehending reality, developing knowledge, and obtaining information about the world' (Tracy, 2013, p. 38). It is essential to consider what should be investigated, how the investigation should be conducted and how the research findings should be interpreted. Understanding the current state of research in a given philosophy enables the establishment of a philosophy based on ideas or assumptions contained within a respectable body of scholarship (Lukka and Modell, 2010). Further to support this notion, researchers' explanations may be influenced by the ontological assumptions (the nature of reality), epistemological assumptions (the nature of knowledge), axiological assumptions (the values associated with areas of research and theorising) or methodological assumptions (strategies for gathering, collecting and analysing data) (Tracy, 2013). These assumptions are used to differentiate research philosophies, where researchers debate them based on beliefs, knowledge and reality (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). They have a high probability of affecting the research from the design stage to the conclusion stage.

Ontological assumptions are a subjective or objective reality that pertains to the difficulties that researchers may encounter in their research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Epistemological assumptions are philosophical beliefs about human knowledge (acceptable, legitimate or valid) and how individuals understand reality to discover knowledge (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Axiological assumptions refer to how the researcher's values or ethics influence the research process (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Methodology is another term for the process of conducting research to determine what the researcher believes (Tracy, 2013). In this regard, ontological and epistemological principles can be used to make research rules, methods and practices.

In terms of research philosophy, business studies are being conducted on a variety of philosophies including positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism and pragmatism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Choosing positivism as a philosophy would result in theory-tested research findings (Myers, 2013). Thus, this type of philosophy was not considered in this research because it is based on 'cause and effect' and the use of a scientific approach, which typically uses quantitative measures to test a theory in the form of hypotheses and statistical tests to generate knowledge. The key criticism of this philosophy is that it does not consider human interpretation and behaviour perspectives but rather considers it as an independent variable, and quantitative methods are frequently used (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014).

Critical realism is concerned with how the reality of 'deep structures' manifest themselves to shape observable events (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Thus, this philosophy was unsuitable for this research because it challenges positivism and interpretivism that seek to reveal beliefs and practices which lack freedom of human action (Scott and Usher, 2011). The ontological position in this philosophy provides a clear explanation of the layers of reality that comprise the phenomenon of socially constructed entities that are constantly influenced internally. In terms of epistemological assumptions, a clear explanation of the knowledge of causal or generative mechanisms behind the phenomenon is required. Similar to interpretivism, tools such as open-ended interviews, open-ended questionnaires and focus groups can be used in this philosophy, resulting in qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods data. However, data analysis involves the researcher's explicit values and tends to undertake historical analysis. That is, research values influence research findings (Guba, 1994; Scotland, 2012).

Pragmatism is regarded as a philosophical alternative to both positivism and interpretivism (Wilson, 2014). This philosophical point of view contends that the concepts emerge from actions, situations and consequences rather than prior conditions, and it recognises physical and social needs (Morgan, 2014; Wilson, 2014). Beyond objectivist conceptualisations, researchers can use pragmatism to investigate and comprehend the relationship between knowledge and action in context (Biesta, 2010). This argument asserts that a pragmatist approach allows researchers to be flexible in their methodological choices when answering research questions, while an objectivist and subjectivist perspective allows for adopting mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative) (Goldkuhl, 2012; Wahyuni, 2012). Therefore, this philosophy is inappropriate for this research context.

To summarise, the preceding discussion implies that the research philosophy chosen has a significant influence on the research design used to draw the conclusions. Using a single philosophy may not provide a comprehensive answer or an acceptable interpretation of the research findings (Tashakkori and Teddie, 1998). To address this issue, researchers should consider preventing philosophical pluralism (Knox, 2004). Scholars in accounting and auditing have identified a number of philosophies into which studies can be classified including positivism and interpretative (Hooper and Powel, 1985; Bryman and Bell, 2015). Thus, the Researcher acknowledges the possible biases by comparing and contrasting these two perspectives in this research context. The following sub-sections address key conceptual issues of these philosophies and justify the choice of an interpretative philosophy for this research.

4.2.1 Positivism philosophy

The positivism philosophy is rooted in the objectivist and regulatory dimensions, which tend to be realist, positivist, determinist and nomothetic. It serves as a justification for defending the status quo, social order, integration and cohesion, solidarity, equilibrium, satisfaction needs and actuality (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, quoted in Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This philosophy supports quantitative research because ontologically it is realist and epistemologically it is positivist. It has a determinist human nature and a nomothetic methodological assumption. Researchers employ a positivist epistemological approach to understand social reality within the philosophy. This involves using natural science tools or methods to collect and analyse data such as surveys and experiments (Chua, 1986). Also, the positivism approach to IA is viewed as a scientific approach that largely focuses on quantitative methods. In doing so, researchers aim to test hypotheses using observed data collected from experiments or surveys (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Research attempts to establish uniformity and consistency in the application of certain procedures and techniques such as correlational research, survey research, mixed explanatory, mixed convergent parallel design and mixed multiphase design. However, the purpose of this research is to investigate key factors, such as internal auditors, policymakers and regulators' judgements, which can account for and predict the phenomenon being studied. It is argued that the value of researching IA in this philosophy is to overcome and uncover the patterns of observational data by approaching stable quality assurance (Erasmus and Coetzee, 2017).

The positivism philosophy has been criticised because it does not consider the human agency's role in effectiveness and assumes that everyone who works on IA effectiveness has the same goal. It deals with human beings as any other natural object, and also fails to differentiate between people and social sciences from natural sciences (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Also, experimental methodologies oversimplify IA efficacy, therefore the complexity of the IA environment exceeds what can be represented in an experimental scenario (Humphrey, 2008). This has led researchers to investigate the interactions, power relations and meaning construction that attach to concepts and activities in IA effectiveness. This also involves a shift from a positivism to an interpretative philosophy (Chua, 1986; Humphrey, 2008).

4.2.2 Interpretative philosophy

The interpretative philosophy is subjectivist because of its epistemological position that aims to understand how people comprehend their reality by exploring the understanding of individuals and their subjective experiences rather than exploring from an objective

standpoint (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The focus of this research is the social construction of a phenomenon or reality that considers individuals' perceptions, shares their meanings and develops insights about observed cases (i.e. participants, banks) (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Understanding how individuals assign meaning to their activities is necessary for this process, as their actions, intentions and motives are influenced by the context in which they occur (Chua, 1986). Since reality is context-dependent, such an approach appears suitable and justified in the context of this research. Understanding the practical insights and meanings of how participants interpreted their IA practices, tools or techniques have been investigated, as well as the framework they used, which is beneficial and supportive of this research. Researchers must investigate the meanings that participants share and the various methods they use to construct and create meaning in the world (Ryan, Scapens and Theobald, 2002).

Given that this research examines the challenges that IA faces, the interpretative philosophy is appropriate because it provides both a practical and theoretical approach to the phenomenon. Furthermore, this philosophy improves understanding and provides an exploration and explanation of a phenomenon by incorporating individuals' personal perspectives and experiences (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Gray, 2014; Taylor, Bogdan and DeVault, 2016). Understanding interpretative research emphasises the social context's connotation of meaning (Myers, 2013). Using an inductive approach, qualitative methods and techniques can help to understand the human mind and actions because it is based on both ontological and epistemological principles (Bowling, 2014).

Due to the paucity of IA literature with predominant practical insights and meanings, this approach seems suitable and justified. This practical aspect also attempted to investigate and promote the interpretivist viewpoint; this research seeks to comprehend views, behaviours and phenomena (Thomas, 2017). Researchers who adopt interpretivism and acknowledge its inherent biases recognise that self-reflexivity and neutrality are crucial variables to examine and investigate research aim and answer research questions. Self-awareness allows researchers to recognise how their individual 'positionality' in terms of their own ideas, background, gender or race can cause information to be misinterpreted (Tracy, 2013; Thomas, 2017; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

This research considers criticisms of interpretivism for making broad generalisations as it is sensitive to individual meanings. Researchers are unable to generalise the findings of interpretative research to diverse organisational settings since the findings are subjective

and contextual. Because the procedures are open-ended, they may result in the unintentional revelation of lies, secrets and oppressive relationships. Another important thing to know about this philosophy is that the researcher’s personal subjectivity could have an impact on the research results, which could also put the privacy and autonomy of the participants at risk.

4.2.3 Justification of adopting interpretivism

The interpretative philosophy is preferred over the positivism in understanding current IA challenges because this research examines subjective experiences in the development and construction of an IBA framework. It recognises that subjective experiences and the use of IA are contextual and fluid, implying that the focus of this research is not to quantify the impact of IA on the development of an effective IBA framework (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The goal of this research is to investigate how people in the field provide and understand meanings as they adopt and implement IA, not how the field changes because of bank dominance or because people become disillusioned with IA. Table 4.1 is presented to provide justification for adopting the interpretative philosophy in support of this research context.

Table 4.1: Differences between positivism and interpretative philosophy

Features	Positivism philosophy	Interpretative philosophy
Rationality	Numeric and casual explanations	Subjective description and exploration
Ontology	Realism	Relativist
Epistemology	Dualist and objectivist	Subjective and transactional
Methodology and methods	Explaining relationships, quantitative methods, experimental (cause and effect), predictions and generalisations	Hermeneutical and dialectical, grounded theory, case study, ethnography, ethno-methodology, historical and documentary research
Sampling	Uses large samples (random or probability samples)	Uses small sampling (convenience, purposive or theoretical)
Scientific method	Testing of theory (deductive approach)	Generating theory (inductive approach)
Analysis of data	Identifying relationships among variables utilising statistical analysis	Using descriptive data analysis, searching for patterns, themes, holistic features and variations
Criticisms	Fails to differentiate people and social sciences from natural sciences	Generalising the results
	Dilute the complex to the simple by simplifying and controlling variables	Costly and time consuming
	Lack of generalisation is applicable in social sciences	Personal subjectivity may influence the research results
	Lack of differences in culture, belief and human experience	

Source: Adapted from Collis and Hussey (2014)

To address research question 1 (Section 1.5), it is necessary for banks to overcome the key challenges of implementing IA to enhance and protect the flexible and effective internal control systems of top management and implement the IBA framework. Regulators, researchers and standard-setters have identified new research opportunities that require greater transparency, innovation and transformation (Endaya and Hanefah, 2013; Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020; Hazaea *et al.*, 2021). Research questions 2 and 3 (Section 1.5) aim to identify the factors that affect IA practices to improve IA effectiveness by addressing issues of effective internal control systems, good governance, stakeholder accountability, and transparency in all financial activities and regulations. This is achieved by fostering shared meaning among internal auditors, practitioners, policymakers, regulators, and professionals, thereby facilitating banks' smooth operations and integration into the IBA framework. Finally, Research question 4 (Section 1.5) acknowledges that policymakers and regulators must consider the efficient use of the IBA framework to improve their organisation's operations and programmes. Meeting predefined performance standards should enable them to navigate their organisation's work efficiently.

These questions mentioned above acknowledge that IA represents a context-based physical phenomenon that must be understood in relation to the influences on the field from other stakeholders and material objects (IBA framework). Therefore, researchers in this philosophy must realise that IA is intersubjective as internal auditors are 'integrated and incorporated into interrelated experiences and meanings in situ, which change as conversations pass through time and people (durability and meaning)' (Cunliffe, 2010, p. 12). The interpretative philosophy has attracted numerous scholars in the accounting and auditing disciplines over the last two decades resulting in significant research output (Sarens and Beelde, 2006; Endaya and Hanefah, 2013; Chambers and Odar, 2015). Moreover, researchers in IA practice have demonstrated the progress that has been achieved in understanding the processes, experiences and meanings within IA disciplines (Cooper, Leung and Wong, 2006, 2006; Sarens *et al.*, 2011; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Power and Gendron, 2015; Chersan, 2016). Also, this philosophy supports systematic review in revealing the multiple perspectives of various stakeholders with sensitive knowledge of how the competition strengthens and augments their evolving understanding of phenomena (Suri, 2018). Thus, researching IA in this philosophy provides deeper insight into the phenomenon, while adopting a systematic review perspective that complements additional insights.

4.3 Research approach (deductive versus inductive)

The research approach is concerned with a wide range of strategies and techniques for collecting, analysing and evaluating empirical findings (Creswell, 2018). Exploratory research is an inductive rather than a deductive approach, and the research objectives are to discover patterns, facts, causes and meanings (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Gray, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This means that an inductive approach produces results based on meaning discovery as opposed to testing hypotheses (as in the deductive approach) (Bhattacharjee, 2012). Therefore, this research problem was investigated in support of the inductive approach, and the theory emerges after the results are generated, which is referred to as a 'bottom-up' approach (Figure 4.2) (Myers, 2013). This approach begins with observation to identify patterns followed by tentative hypotheses that are further investigated to formulate a theory.

Figure 4.2: Bottom-up (inductive) approach

Source: Burney (2008)

Conversely, a deductive (top-down) approach (Figure 4.3) entails identifying prior theories, developing and testing hypotheses, and providing an outcome on the causal understanding of a research problem (Collis and Hussey, 2014). This approach could have been useful if there had been enough empirical work on IA prior to the development of an IBA framework and enough research studies with the explicit goal of determining the relationship between IA and predetermined variables. Empirical research in this area of IA is still in its early stages, and the majority of studies are conceptual. An inductive approach is thought to be a good way to investigate IA in less structured ways and find out what actually happens in this field of work.

Figure 4.3: Top-down (deductive) approach

Source: Burney (2008)

For a variety of reasons, an inductive approach was deemed appropriate in this research context. First, before generalising theories and interpretations of research evidence that govern the relationships, the Researcher focused on gathering information about theoretical constructs and key elements of observed IA, identifying patterns to develop conclusions and formulating tentative hypotheses. Second, the goal of this research was to achieve its aim and objectives by examining real-world observations, indicating an inductive approach, whereas a deductive approach was insufficient because it does not always rely on real-world knowledge to provide conclusions. Third, this research lends support to an inductive approach that does not generate hypotheses to be tested empirically.

4.4 Research methods (qualitative versus quantitative)

Another critical point to consider is research methods, which define the overall framework for guiding systematic data collection and interpreting the data (Silverman, 2014; Bryman and Bell, 2015). It identifies the method by which researchers prefer to investigate and analyse the phenomenon (Silverman, 2014). It is the perception of research problems and the approaches associated with them that provide answers to research questions (Taylor, Bogdan and DeVault, 2016). The most common research methods are mono method (quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods) and multiple methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). To achieve the research objectives, the mono method (qualitative) was used as the primary research method for this research.

The use of qualitative methods enables the researcher to investigate a social issue in depth and detail in an open and comprehensive manner without the use of preconceived categories (Patton, 2002). It allows researchers to collect rich data and gain a deeper understanding of social issues using a small sample size. In-depth interviews, whether closed-ended or open-ended, yield direct quotations from participants about their experiences, opinions, feelings and knowledge. These methods also allow for direct observation as well as detailed descriptions of participants' activities, behaviours and actions in a variety of interpersonal and organisational interactions (Patton, 2002).

Conversely, quantitative research approaches are appropriate when the research identifies and measures statistical correlations between variables (Robson, 2002). By detecting relationships and creating predictions based on the results, this method develops empirical measurement and experimentation methods. The techniques used to gather and analyse data have been validated, while survey research has a high level of reliability (Babbie, 2004). Quantitative research may exclude relevant human experience (Cooper and

Schindler, 2011). This method was developed in response to the necessity to produce objective outcomes (Zikmund *et al.*, 2009). Thus, the Researcher summarised the benefits and drawbacks of qualitative and quantitative methodologies in Table 4.2 below.

Table 4.2: Advantages and disadvantages of qualitative and quantitative methods

	Qualitative	Quantitative
Advantages	Understanding and exploring behaviour, opinions and experiences from participant's perspective	Describing social phenomena and discovering facts
	Enhancing descriptions and generating theory	Allowing for the accurate measurement of variables
	Allowing for research insights and understanding phenomenon in depth	Providing a wide coverage of situations
	Supporting small samples	Supporting large samples from the population
	Describing experiences and theories	Supporting methods are standardised and structured
	Emerging and flexible design	Allowing fixed and standard design
	Empowering participants' opinions and views	Time-saving and economical
	Analysing inductive data (themes, text, images)	Analysing deductive data (numerical comparisons and statistical inferences)
	Multiple interpretations of reality exist (subjective)	Reality is fixed (objective)
Disadvantages	No clear measurement of data	Using inflexible methods
	Non-scientific and subjectivism	Quantitative data is still subject to researcher's biases, especially at the beginning of the research process
	Acknowledged and assumed to influence findings	Limited consistency in key factors
	Utilisation of small samples	Lack of subjectivity of human interpretation
	Limited generalising to similar conditions and contexts	Assumption of objective truth
	Data analysis and interpretations comparatively difficult	Generating lack of understanding
		Not applicable to immeasurable phenomenon Does not support generating a theory

Source: The Researcher

Using qualitative methods for this research allows for a wide range of perspectives, increasing legitimacy through semi-structured interviews and ensuring that all are assimilated. Conversely, a survey questionnaire is not an appropriate method of data collection in this research due to the obvious nature of the information required. Because this research requires detailed information, the Researcher was unable to examine additional data via the questionnaire. Furthermore, observation is not an appropriate method for this research because the goal is to investigate and comprehend participants'

perceptions of the effectiveness of IA. Interviews were thought to be the best way to obtain the qualitative data required in this situation.

This research employed qualitative methods because it involves the incorporation of multiple contextual and practical perspectives resulting in a diverse, strong and valid outcome (Gray, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This encourages qualitative inquiry into the subjective and qualitative aspects of concepts and meanings (Mason, 2004; Leavy, 2017). When qualitative data is analysed, it is more likely that new ideas and a deeper understanding of the research problem will emerge, which can lead to interesting findings (Rubin and Rubin, 2012; Taylor, Bogdan and DeVault, 2016; Creswell, 2018).

4.5 Research strategy

Research strategy is one of the significant components of research design, which presents clear guidance on conducting research (Mason, 2004). Several research strategies emphasise examining the relationship between research aims and questions to be answered through approaches such as experiment, survey, archival and documentary, case study, ethnography, action research and grounded theory, which are the most common in the business and management fields (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This section addresses key conceptual issues and explains why a case study strategy was chosen to conduct this research.

An experimental strategy uses predictive hypothesis to test the relationships and theories by applying different methods, usually in a laboratory environment (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). A survey is a structured research strategy that tends to be used for exploratory and descriptive research to collect data on a particular population using questionnaires or structured observations, and is mostly used in deductive research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Archival and documentary research depends on sufficient numbers of suitable secondary sources of documents to gather data from textual, visual and audio representations. This includes how researchers prepare for, structure, conduct and manage information flow from archival visits, interviews or structured examination of published materials (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Considering the attributes and difficulties of describing the range of archival and documentary sources, this strategy was inappropriate for the research context. Similarly, ethnographic strategy is ineffective due to being a kind of research that focuses on a specific group's cultural or social features (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Action research is ineffective since it involves participants in a learning process and the conclusions are based on practical

outcomes (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Due to the findings that emerge from coding and contrasting explanations, a grounded theory would be inappropriate for this research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

When using a qualitative case study, researchers can use some quantitative forms of data (Stake, 2000; Yin, 2014). This form of case study is not the presentation of a single case; it is a qualitative methodology. The Researcher chooses what or who the cases are and what the data is, setting time boundaries and methods of analysis. For example, researchers can thematically analyse participants' responses to interview questions and use the data from the Likert scale to support or refute what has been found. Researchers can decide what the data is, so it can be the results of the interview thematic analysis and numerical data that relates to the research questions. This research uses a case study as a qualitative methodology. The numerical data generated helps to support what was said in the interviews.

One of the major factors is that the phenomenon under investigation is influenced by the choice of case study, which indicates adaptability to qualitative data collection and analysis approaches, resulting in a rich mix of data and in-depth knowledge of IA (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 2014). The Researcher believes that this strategy is appropriate for such a diverse research field as IA, particularly in the banking sector, where strong generalisations are often difficult due to the highly individual nature of organisations, internal control systems and adherence to regulations and policies. Validity, reliability, generalisability and ethical considerations are types of assessments common in empirical research to make sure the research quality of a case study is good (Yin, 2014). This is covered in more detail in Section 4.9.

4.6 Research design

Understanding qualitative research design, selecting research objectives and questions, determining validity and assessing conceptual frameworks is essential for achieving goals (Maxwell, 2013). It is necessary to understand how the relationship between these components can be conceptualised. To justify and undertake a research project, such methodological variations in research design include a set of philosophical assumptions about the social world, research methods, data collection techniques, approaches to qualitative data analysis and a written record of the findings (Myers, 2013; Creswell, 2018).

Figure 4.4: Adopted sequential research design

Source: The Researcher

A sequential research design can be used for answering research questions, thereby achieving research objectives (Maxwell, 2013; Thomas, 2017). However, it is also critical to consider how the research is carried out and how it links to a variety of data collection and analysis procedures to develop a theoretical framework, and in turn, how the research is validated with new insights after data collection (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The use of a qualitative research strategy is intended to uncover responses and flexibilities allowing for the exposure of deep, multifaceted answers and meanings to comprehend and validate the phenomenon (Silverman, 2014; Leavy, 2017). In terms of data, tools and techniques, these approaches are referred to as primary (semi-structured interviews) and secondary (systematic literature evaluation).

In Figure 4.4, the research design begins by identifying the problems related to IA and is followed by a SLR in phase one. This phrase of the research identified the literature gaps, which provided the foundation to develop the theoretical IBA framework, incorporating the fundamental IA elements by analysing key academic and industry-based literature on current IA challenges. This was the primary contribution to this research. To support this process, key issues and themes were discovered in this research that were not addressed in previous research to support the framework development and implementation. In phase two, the Researcher collected qualitative primary data by conducting semi-structured

interviews and analysing interview data using thematic procedures. Finally, in phase three, the interview data is combined with the secondary literature findings, which enables the Researcher to recognise significance in the data and investigate the social environment and perceptions of research participants. In this context, the Researcher validates the theoretical IBA framework and also focuses on answering the main research question and achieving the research objectives.

4.7 Data collection techniques and procedures

For transparency and better clarity, data collection and analysis are divided into two categories. The first category is the development of the theoretical IBA framework. The second category is qualitative field research, which uses a sequential exploratory design based on both primary and secondary data to find out what participants think about the world. Secondary data will be discussed first.

4.7.1 Secondary data

Literature review

This investigation begins with a selection of academic papers and a search of online databases, which have been referred to the traditional literature review (Chapter 2). Initially, the research title was broadly searched and examined to identify preliminary literature, which was then assigned to a more specialised area and themes such as IA practices, IA effectiveness and IA functions. In this regard, the online search results yielded a diverse set of resources on a variety of topic areas where data retrieval covered a substantial part of the research problem and estimated data was impossible to count. Thus, the academic papers were chosen on their own merits and different techniques were used to assess their relevance, value and sufficiency (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

The review of previous literature begins with caution to ensure that relevant and up to date literature is found through a keyword and simple phrase search in electronic databases. Because of the complexities of data retrieved from research databases or internet search engines, the volume of research available have grown over time. Using an inductive approach, many key phrases were identified resulting in the observation of IA discipline's terminology shifting over time. However, the keywords and phrases produced significant results and using automatic alerts from electronic journals, such as Google Scholar resulted in a reduction in the volume of searches and timely access to new literature. Following the collection of research sources and contributors, an analysis of references relevant to the

newly identified parameters was performed. A literature synthesis in the form of field notes was created based on identified references (both electronic and physical format). The summaries of the data maintained by the Researcher were examined in the field notes and additional meanings were extracted, and evaluated (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013).

This literature review is mainly concentrated on academic sources such as peer-reviewed journals, while books and conference papers were excluded from the main analysis. The Researcher referred to definitions and other secondary findings as additional sources that were used. Various secondary data resources, such as industrial publications, reports, guidelines, rules, standards and regulations, were discovered and analysed in the case of practitioner legacies. A total of 243 papers were evaluated (147 academic papers and 59 practitioner papers). Finally, this phase is intended answer the research questions (Section 1.5) and to achieve the research objectives (Section 1.6), which were discussed and analysed in the literature review (Chapter 2).

Systematic literature review

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is a comprehensive process that involves qualitative analysis rather than simply quantifying the number of studies employing a particular research design, method, sample size range, or target population (Yin, 2014). This review provides a rationale and foundation for further in-depth investigation of the phenomenon, and its goal is to identify and evaluate existing literature, analyse and synthesise research evidence, and report evidence to provide solutions (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009; Boland, Cherry and Dickson, 2013). This research phase examines and interprets prior academic and practitioner studies on the problem addressed in the research paper (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

This review began with 243 initial sources identified, supported by additional supplemental references to ensure the validity of the literature findings and research gaps identified through systematic analysis. Unlike a literature review that focuses on research planning and exploration, this phase is task oriented and focuses on gathering and organising relevant information related to the phenomenon by identifying key elements, conducting an assessment, and synthesising the findings to provide a comprehensive view of the research problem (Greenhalgh, 2004).

Due to the nature of IA encompasses a broad field of study, the collected literature was evaluated thematically based on commonalities, differences, trends, and typologies to

produce primary themes and patterns related to the research problem (Dixon-Woods et al., 2005). As a follow-up to this examination, the derivation of the research problem is summarised in Table 3.2, which helps design the theoretical IBA framework (Chapter 3; Figure 3.4).

This research employed data in an interpretative manner to provide a deeper understanding of behaviours and attitudes regarding interchangeable terminology, meaning usage and their effects. To address the broad range of topics covered by the research problem, the Researcher divided theoretical perspective into key disciplines. These secondary sources of data selection and analysis were conducted manually based on the scope and questions that differentiated the inclusion and exclusion criteria, including questions related to the research paper (Boland, Cherry and Dickson, 2013).

To comprehend this phenomenon, this research uses qualitative reviews of academic journals, industry publications, policies, and government regulations. References from corresponding publications were considered for their relevance, type, focus, strengths, limitations, key determinations and inputs, and omissions during the selection process. To develop the IBA framework (Chapter 3), a method based on the four-quadrant framework (Althonayan, 2003) was used to evaluate the literature, which was customised to provide solutions to the research problem, as discussed in Sub-section 3.2.1. This method of identifying and categorising literature is useful for understanding the concentration and limitations of the existing literature in the field of IA (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007).

The SLR specifies the eligibility criteria for evidence as the inclusion and exclusion criteria for review and grouping of studies for synthesis. For instance, the Researcher selected inclusion criteria based on studies that focused on the challenges encountered by IA, current practices of IA and their effectiveness, and development of an IA framework supported by empirical validation. Peer-reviewed journals were used to ensure that the quality of the research and validity of the findings were high, information was available on highly detailed subject matter, complex analyses were reported, and the outcomes were sufficiently elaborated. Studies have compared certain issues and themes, such as challenges, practices, effectiveness, functions, roles, profession, policy, framework, structure, and reporting in an appropriate and consistent manner. In addition, the Researcher follows that the studies are published within a certain timeframe, such as two decades, while ensuring relevance, value, and efficiency.

In contrast, the Researcher introduced and implemented exclusion criteria for studies published before 2000; studies published in a language other than English; and excluded books, conference papers, and editorials. Owing to time or resource constraints and concerns about the validity and relevance of the studies, the Researcher decided to exclude studies based on study design features (randomisation or non-allocation of treatment), study conduct (quality or risk of bias of an individual study), language of publication, study size, or reporting of relevant data.

4.7.2 Primary data

Phrase three: Semi-structured interviews

The most used tool in qualitative research to establish rapport is the interview, which produces purposeful conversation between the researcher and one or more people (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Interviews help to collect valid and reliable empirical data about a phenomenon by providing insights into how research participants perceive the world and their real-life experiences (Bryman and Bell, 2015). When accomplishing this phase of the research, the interview design can be unstructured, structured or semi-structured. Unstructured interviews are not feasible given the purpose of this research because they may provide informal or unforeseen information while the research objectives are specific in nature. These types of interviews are mostly appropriate when the researcher does not know enough about a phenomenon to ask relevant questions. The structured interview is rejected because it produces significant quantifiable data and follows a standardised set of questions while inducing specific responses to the phenomenon. Although it reduces bias responses, it also organises a rapid method of collecting data and the nature of interviews makes it unsuitable for this research. Lastly, the semi-structured interview appears appropriate for this research, as it has been commonly used in qualitative social science studies and previous IA research (Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Eulerich and Lenz, 2019). Semi-structured interviews are an effective way to gather rich and detailed data because they use a pre-made format of questions and a list of themes that proceed in a specific and flexible direction (Yin, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Researchers who have adopted an interpretivist philosophy want to be able to gather information, then build and use the responses of interviewees to provide evidence for their research in an area that is still emerging such as establishing a framework (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In order to determine the motivations for developing and implementing an IBA framework, it is possible to investigate the less structured approach of a specific

phenomenon in ways such as participants' points of view, feelings and opinions in the particular context. Semi-structured interviews allow researchers to get first-hand, detailed accounts of experts' opinions about their actions, roles and practices, which provides credibility to the research (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This acknowledges that people think about the world in different ways, which allows the researcher to learn about new world views and new ideas about a phenomenon that can be used in real-world situations. Furthermore, this research provides an opportunity to compare and contrast IA with prior developments in relevant fields, which is significant in establishing the implications of IA for creating an IBA framework with practical guidance. The use of hypothetical questioning during the interviews helps to reveal how internal auditors or other stakeholders face current challenges in IA and also the social reality of IA to improve its effectiveness. Interviews that are semi-structured can help with the preparation of some questions that were asked of the participants in the sample. Some questions may come up during a conversation that are free-flowing and could be either closed-ended or open-ended questions.

During the interview, the interviewer should be able to provide feedback to interviewees and request clarification on their responses (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013). An interview guide (Appendix) assists in increasing consistency and ensuring coverage of all different aspects of the research (Bazeley, 2007). Myers (2013) notes that an interview guide reduces the researcher's bias. This ensures that the interview questions are complete and accurate to answer the main research question and achieve its objectives. Semi-structured interviews allow participants' perspectives on current challenges to be elicited and elaborated upon to modify or validate the theoretical IBA framework. Each section of the interview guide consists of one general question about the IA challenges and more specific questions about the key elements of the IBA framework with the goal of clarifying interviewee responses. Thus, this research was conducted consistently and systematically to ensure that an interview guide consisted of two sections that were useful and effective.

Selection of participants

The participants were chosen based on their expertise, extensive experience and response rate to the interview invitation. Participant's preferences are limited to those who are IA practitioners, internal auditors or administrators, IA policymakers or regulators and professional members of the Institute of Cost and Management Accountants of Bangladesh (ICMAB), ICAB, Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), and Chartered Institute of Management Accountants (CIMA), or hold either a Certified Public Accountant

(CPA) or Chartered Internal Auditor (CIA) in banking organisations. The following methods were used to select participants for both telephonic and video conferencing interviews:

- **Direct approach:** Individuals working in IA or internal control systems departments (or other types of terminology) in the banking sector were identified. The selection criteria included participants who had direct involvement within one of the above-mentioned institutions, with a focus on IA practitioners, internal auditors, administrators (e.g. CAE, audit manager), top managerial positions (e.g. CEO, Chief Operating Officer, CFO), and IA policymakers or regulators (e.g. AC members, or BOD).
- **Indirect approach:** Identification was accomplished through peer recommendations (snowballing and recommendations from professional members of ICMAB, ICAB, ACCA, CIMA, IIA, other CPAs based in the banking sector, Internal Control and Compliance Division (ICCD) members, members of the CAGB, and members of the Ministry of Finance). In this way, the use of professional associations ensured that the participants who took part in the interviews and those who recommended them were affiliated, which meant that the interviews were aimed at a specific, targeted audience.

Key factors, such as banks, departments, and role superiority have influenced the participant selection criteria. Social media (e.g. LinkedIn) was used to target specialised professionals, and invitations were sent to members via open-access communication platforms, such as email and WhatsApp. This primary data collection has numerous advantages, including unbiased data, originality and accessibility, all of which increase the value of research. This is also a good way to find new, valid and trustworthy data (Zikmund et al., 2013).

The first round of interviews was conducted between March and May 2021, whereas follow-up interviews were conducted between July and August 2021. In the first round of interviews, the Researcher focused on a pilot test to ensure that the interview questions were appropriate for gathering primary data. Five interviewees ensured that the data collection methods and procedures were reliable to maximise the values of the interview data and make any necessary changes. The second round of interviews involved 16 interviews, despite the fact that there were a high number of interview questions, which provided a broader perspective for understanding the phenomenon, indicating the greater reliability of the research results. The interviews were conducted for an average of 30-45 minutes, depending on the participants' characteristics. In the final round, the questions were

prepared as pre-coded themes (20 out of 39 questions), which helped overcome difficulties in refining the potential themes and questions. Participants were informed that alternative answers were also welcome instead of the pre-coded themes that had been prepared to start the discussion. The outcome helped to finalise the interviews in terms of their meanings and structure, which addressed real-world perspectives on investigating IA challenges and validated the IBA framework.

Sampling population

The sample population is a subset of a larger total that may include people, products, locations, services, organisations and a variety of other things (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In practice, sampling is defined as the selection of elements that are typically extracted rather than the entire population (Cooper and Schindler, 2006). This entire procedure is known as the 'sampling frame'. A sampling frame is a collection of the units from which a sample is drawn. It represents the target population that has been operationalised. For the specific group of units in this research people were asked to participate in the research (Kolln, Ongena and Aarts, 2019). Purposive expert sampling and snowball sampling techniques were utilised to obtain the sample. Because it is impossible to determine the total population within the banking sector in Bangladesh, both purposive and snowball sampling approaches appear to be relevant for collecting data for this research.

Purposive expert sampling, which is an appropriate qualitative technique when considering the objectives of this research, was used as the primary method of data collection. Expert sampling is suitable because it is used to select participants with specific expertise to obtain their perspectives, views, ideas and opinions on IA issues (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This is used to select professionals with IA experience by obtaining perspectives on practicing IA from internal auditors and other stakeholders such as policymakers, regulators and professionals. Using direct selection yielded 12 participants, then 9 participants were included after the snowballing technique, giving a total of 21 participants. Furthermore, snowball sampling was used to increase the number of research participants with sufficient experience in banking organisations. This technique is useful when a sample population is unique. Thus, the initial interviewees were asked to recommend other professionals with extensive experience, who might be interested in participating in this research. This sampling technique yielded Nine interviewees were included in the study.

In qualitative phenomenology studies, the determination of sample size is not guided by statistical formulas but rather by the principles of data saturation, which refers to the point at which collecting additional data no longer provides new insights or information. Therefore, the most appropriate approach for calculating the sample size in qualitative phenomenological research is to continue data collection until data saturation is achieved (Creswell, 2018). To justify the sample size in this research, the researcher provided a clear description of the data collection process, including the number of participants, the criteria used for participant selection (Appendix A- Stakeholder analysis), and a comprehensive explanation of how data saturation was reached. This demonstrates rigor and transparency in the research design, ensuring that the sample size is appropriate and aligned with the aim and objectives of this research.

The number of participants recruited may vary depending on the context of the research, type of phenomenon being studied, and degree of data saturation attained (Lobe, Morgan and Hoffman, 2022). Instead of aiming for a particular number determined by statistical calculations, the emphasis is on choosing a sample size that permits thorough investigation and saturation of the data. Thus, there is no established formula for determining sample size in qualitative phenomenological research. The total sample size for this research was 21. In qualitative research, sample sizes are usually very small (Creswell, 2018), and are identified based on saturation conditions. A sample size of 5-25 participants is ideal for phenomenological research (Creswell, 2018). As stated, 'there are no sample size rules in qualitative research' (Patton, 2002, p. 244). Inductive and exploratory research attempts to illuminate phenomena for which the primary themes cannot be identified in advance, making it difficult to determine the sample size. It is unethical to identify how many people are needed for something that has not yet been determined (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

4.8 Data analysis and approach to writing up

Qualitative analysis is based on systematic impressions of researchers who report their findings in a structured and transparent manner to answer research questions. The qualitative data was chosen based on how well it fitted into the research problem.

4.8.1 Qualitative analysis: interview data

The interview format was semi-structured in nature to generate meaningful views of social reality about participant's perceptions within a specific context (Mason, 2004). It is one of the most used methods in qualitative research, while its outcomes depend on participant's

ability to interact and express opinions and the Researcher's knowledge to interpret and narrate by presenting statements rather than what interviewees said (Mason, 2004; Bryman and Bell, 2015). This interview technique is compatible with interpretative philosophy, which reflects the research problem and is aimed at investigating the qualitative dimension of a phenomenon. Thus, the interview data collection focused on the following complementary techniques:

- Telephone interviews (a total of 12 telephone interviews);
- Video conferencing interviews (a total of 9 video conferencing interviews).

Due to geographical and situational barriers, cost and time constraints, the global pandemic COVID-19 and Bangladesh being on the UK government's red list for travel, the above approaches have been adopted to collect the interview data (GOV.UK, 2021). Similarly, researchers have considered combining video conferencing with telephone interviews to obtain additional perspectives (Lobe, Morgan and Hoffman, 2020). This dual approach is distinguished by the fact that it provides the Researcher with several sample identification options. Furthermore, each interview followed an identical semi-structured format for accuracy, with the goal of preserving an interviewee's speech using a digital voice recorder. The Researcher conducted the analysis using NVivo 12 Pro software (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Using this software tool is effective and time-saving, and is largely based on the Braun and Clarke (2006) approach.

Interview pilot testing

Initially, the Researcher developed 39 questions, and then following pilot testing, two more questions were added and nine questions were refined to provide practical insights about the research problem. To remain and align with the research aim and objectives, a total of 41 questions were finalised, which are correlated to investigate the challenges, validate the IBA framework and answer the research questions. The interview questions were divided into two sections. The first part consisted of nine questions that referred to general information and respondents' profiles (Q1–Q9) (e.g. organisation size, job role, job focus, experience, professional certifications), which validates competency and the quality of participants to undertake this research. The second part (Q10–Q41) was developed from the three key elements of the theoretical IBA framework: IA input factors (Q10–Q19), IA foundation factors (Q20–Q30) and IA integration factors (Q31–Q41).

On constructing Question 9, it seemed inappropriate to use the word 'adopted' by asking if setting up IA in the organisation resulted in change for the better. Instead, 'in your opinion,

what areas of IA are established in your organisation that benefit you in your role?' is preferred. This would gather information on IA already established and working in their expert opinion. Likewise, Question 12 was formulated to clarify a list of things that could help the organisation overcome IA challenges. Questions 24 and 25 were also reworded as they initially included 'what is the extent of IA practice' and 'explain some principles', asking the interviewee what IA practices they think are most valuable. These questions could be misinterpreted and seem negative. Hence, it became common practice to state that IA practices are in place in the organisation where all members were responsible.

In Question 35, clarification was needed to illustrate if an organisation uses the IA framework to gather more information (e.g. has the IA framework been implemented across all IA practices in the organisation or if the framework has not been implemented then why not) and to avoid biased answers. In order to ensure that the question did not influence the answer to Question 36, a 'neutral' word was omitted. In Question 38, participants were offered as pre-coded themes supported by the potential answers, when referring to the contributions of the IA and its strategic priorities. The Researcher provided additional guidance in Questions 39 and 40 in order to clarify the questions and the level of response that was expected.

4.8.2 Interview instrument and protocol

The purpose of interview guidance is to keep semi-structured, in-depth interviews situational and conversational (Patton, 2002; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The interview guide is used as a tool that includes a series of broad themes to be discussed, which directs the conversation towards a research problem with a view to answering the research questions. This also helps in reducing researcher bias by employing non-directional, pre-specified questions and probes (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In this regard, the interview guidance (Appendix) is organised around key questions about participants' perceptions to investigate current challenges and evaluate practices that may have an influence on IA effectiveness. It also includes some probing questions to elicit deeper responses related to IA, which would help to refine and develop the IBA framework.

Using a semi-structured interview approach has generated information for the main research question and the core objectives of this research, but there were more opportunities for respondents to give further explanations and answers based on their deep knowledge and experience of the phenomenon. Hence, questions were developed in both closed-ended and open-ended formats, and there was a chance for wider thoughts and responses due to

the importance of the objectives to be achieved. However, the Researcher drew on sources that relied on question typology in developing the interview questions, as used by Kvale (2012) and Yin (2014), and designed them as open-ended as possible to allow participants to articulate their responses without imposing preconceived categorisations that might inhibit responses (Fontana and Frey, 2005).

Respondents were not asked to provide a definition of IA to avoid stereotypical responses. They were instead asked to share their perspectives and opinions on how IA effectiveness is evaluated or assessed to identify current IA challenges or how effective the current framework is in their prospective organisations. A supervisory team from the accounting and auditing fields reviewed the interview guidance for relevance, clarity and completeness. Given the difficulties in obtaining an appointment with the participants and avoiding the loss of any valuable information, the Researcher used an 'interviewing the investigator' strategy as a subject and proposed becoming a 'vulnerable observer', which entails creating a personal story about 'what went on in the backstage of doing research' (Ellis and Bochner, 2000, p. 741; Chenail, 2011). Following on, the Researcher's Director of Studies (DoS) provided additional feedback on the interview guidance as well as changes to improve the interview instrument and approach to validating this research.

Researchers conduct semi-structured interviews by establishing rapport, outlining the research objectives and assuring the participants of confidentiality (Yin, 2014). As suggested by previous research (Bazeley, 2007), the 'ice-breaking' introduction is required to overcome any potential reluctance on the part of the interviewees to freely provide information. The Researcher obtained the participants' signed consent for their participation in the research and for the interviews to be audio taped prior to the start of each interview, and assured the participants that the organisation they represented would be completely anonymous. Other than the Researcher and supervisory team, no one else would have access to the taped interviews and transcribed scripts. The Researcher also informed the participants that they could opt out of the research at any time during or after the interview. Participants were also informed that they could request a copy of the transcript to ensure the reliability and validity of the interviews. However, if the responses of the participants revealed an emerging theme, then this new theme would be pursued before returning to the interview guide. This approach is consistent with previous research (Rijamampianina, 2016; Lenning and Gremyr, 2021). Probing questions were used to get more information or to clear up ambiguous statements (Patton, 2002; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

In order to encourage truthful responses from participants to some potentially sensitive subjects, the interview questions were framed to prevent any relationship with the organisation. These include areas such as potential conflicts between senior management and the AC over IA policy and resources, the commitment of the internal control systems to corporate governance, accountability and transparency issues. Instead of sharing their personal experiences participants are asked to share their point of view or opinion. Each interview was concluded with the participant being asked if there was anything else they would like to add or if the topic had been adequately covered. This is also known as a closing or clearing question (Patton, 2002). In many cases, this resulted in a summary of key points raised earlier in the interviews. All interviews were conducted in Bengali and then translated into English with great accuracy. Only those parts of the foreign language interviews that the Researcher chose to use as quotes to show reliability and authority over reporting the findings were retained. This makes translation of the data easier as it is not necessary to translate all interviews (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

4.8.3 Thematic analysis

In order to interpret the interview data, TA was chosen as a generic approach to accommodate a broad range of questions for analysing qualitative data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This type of analysis provides flexibility on questions related to benefits and challenges, which means they do not need to adhere as closely to questions or analysis based on the meaning of experience. TA is a foundational method for analysing semi-structured interview data that leads to rich descriptions, explanations and theorising from a subjectivist position (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The theoretical positions of this type of analysis illustrate how to identify, analyse and report the patterns (themes) within data. A rigorous thematic approach can produce an insightful analysis that achieves the research objectives by answering the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This TA combined with the research questions outlined in Section 1.5 allows for an investigation of the interview data collected from two perspectives: (i) from a data-driven and inductive coding perspective; and (ii) the collected data is consistent with the research questions to provide sufficient information (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Despite similarities, the primary distinction between grounded theory and TA is in their methods for coding 'themes' or coding from data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The major characteristic of grounded theory is that the data analysis process begins concurrently with the data collection process, which is inconvenient for researchers who want to measure what differences exist between participants. Thus, this type of analysis is inappropriate in

this research context. Another reason is that the data must be collected in two stages (at the start and end of the research project) using theoretical sampling (determined during data collection), which is not compatible with TA (Miles and Huberman, 1994). In contrast, hermeneutic and TA are similar in that they both focus on interpreting data and are useful for developing theory (Bryman, 2008). However, hermeneutic analysis is unlikely to be appropriate for analysing data that focuses solely on participants' visions due to issues with its analytical principle, which was deemed unsuitable for use in this research. This is because its analytical principle is the comprehension of the entire text, and data interpretation segments are guided by anticipated explanations (Myers, 2013). This was the last step in interpreting the research. Braun and Clarke (2006) summarised the TA process in six phases, which is presented in Figure 4.5 below.

Figure 4.5. Thematic data analysis process

Source: Adapted from Braun and Clarke (2006)

The thematic process (Figure 4.5) began with familiarity with the data and was internalised through the translation and transcription of the interviews in written form. Researchers argue that the first phrase is key to data analysis, further recognised as an interpretative act with interpretative qualitative methodology (Lukka, 2010). The audio recordings were listened to several times to ensure accurate translation and transcription of the 21 respondents. The Researcher translated all interviews from Bengali into English with the aim of understanding the meaning, views and opinions rather than the language or linguistic features. The pre-translated transcripts provided a means of communicating with the supervisory panel during the coding and theme development processes. The majority of the translated transcripts

were completed immediately following the interviews to allow for any clarification or justification. This procedure was performed using Microsoft Word Office 365, and the data were stored in a private UWS One Drive (Microsoft) to meet the Data Protection Act 2018. The completed interview transcripts were imported into NVivo 12 Pro, where they were used to examine a set of themes to produce the codebook.

This analysis was conducted in three distinct stages. Initially, the Researcher engaged in open coding by re-examining the textual data to identify the relevance and connections between the challenges associated with IA and the observations made by the participants to validate the IBA framework. This procedure also explored the practices that underline IA and affect its effectiveness and efficiency, which helps to identify emerging and core elements of the banking sector. Subsequently, the Researcher probed the data to validate the IBA framework's five key phrases, documented and developed provisional categories and codes based on them. This research compares the challenges and emerging themes of IA implementation in the banking sector with the existing literature on IA.

The primary objective of this research was to systematically analyse the interview data using the thematic procedures outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) to provide detailed descriptions, explanations, and theories from a subjectivist perspective. This analysis contributes to achieving the research aim, objectives, and questions, which enhances the trustworthiness and reliability of the data. In addition, it allows for a comparison with the existing literature and frameworks, highlighting the similarities and differences between the research findings and previous research. The analysis also acknowledges flexibility in data exploration, visualisation, and comparison, which is straightforward and easy to understand. The following section examines the quality of this research.

4.9 Research quality

Qualitative research designs are generally assessed in terms of their reliability, validity and ethical considerations (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The following sub-sections discuss these issues further, which have been used to ensure research quality remains reliable and valid by maintaining ethical considerations.

4.9.1 Reliability

In order to ensure reliability in qualitative research, examining trustworthiness and using a consistent approach throughout the study is crucial (Gibbs, 2018). Yin (2014) recommends documenting the research procedure using a detailed protocol as an important step to

assess the reliability of qualitative research. Gibbs (2018) further suggests the following procedures for reliability:

- Examining the accuracy and credibility of interview transcripts;
- Writing memos and comparing data with the codes to ensure the consistency of code meanings;
- Sharing the analysis with other coders on a regular basis;
- Collaborating with other researchers to cross-check the developed codes.

It is argued that reliability requires a clear decision process to ensure consistent interpretations in qualitative research (Noble and Smith, 2015). Due to the subjectivity of the coding process, researchers stress the necessity of coding reliability (Vaismoradi, Turunen and Bondas, 2013). To improve the reliability of the codes, Creswell (2018) recommends that they need to be cross-checked by another coder (not the Researcher). By following this strategy, the Researcher confirms that this process used. The following reliability strategies have been adopted (Figure 4.6) to increase the credibility of the research findings.

Figure 4.6: Reliability strategies

Source: Adapted from Creswell (2018)

The participants were chosen using the same criteria, and the interviews were conducted in a systematic and dependable manner with consistent lines of questioning. To ensure that the research approach was followed throughout the interviews, each participant was asked the same questions using an interview protocol and guidance (Appendix). Due to the fact that the reliability of qualitative data cannot be measured numerically, it is better to interpret it as trustworthy. Only participants who met the predetermined criteria were considered ensuring that future researchers could replicate similar criteria to obtain similar results (Appendix). By comparing the audio file to the written text, the professional proof-reader and the Researcher double-checked the accuracy of the interview transcripts. The consistency of the interview transcripts was coded by referring to the research objectives and questions in mind. In addition, the coding descriptions were used frequently to interpret the data with a high degree of accuracy. In addition, a memo for the coded interviews was also written. The DoS randomly reviewed the codebook's consistency and accuracy. The Researcher reported the codes and interpretations, discussed them with a supervisory panel and revised them to ensure their accuracy and truthfulness. Finally, the research's dependability was demonstrated by comparing the findings to previous research (Chapters 5 and 6).

4.9.2 Validity

The validity of qualitative research is another critical issue in terms of the appropriateness of tools, processes, data credibility and contributions to the body of knowledge, which depends on the philosophical paradigm. Generally, the accuracy of findings is referred to as validity in qualitative research (Thyer, 2012). In order to validate the qualitative data, the perspectives of the Researcher, lens of the research participants and the lens of audience members (reviewers and readers) are of the utmost importance in determining the criteria and process involved in the qualitative research (Figure 4.7) (Creswell and Miller, 2000).

The nature of this exploratory research and the interpretative philosophy has led to the selection of three techniques to address the validity issue: disconfirming evidence, thick, rich description and peer debriefing (as opposed to a single theory) (Creswell and Miller, 2000). It is noteworthy that the validity procedure for researchers to stay at the research site is prolonged engagement, which was not considered despite the fact that it has been considered from the perspectives of research participants. As mentioned in the previous Sub-Section 4.7.1, the Researcher could not travel to the research location for an extended period due to the COVID-19 restrictions imposed by the UK government. Additionally, the data collection method involves semi-structured interviews and the information in the IA

department or ICCD is confidential within banking organisations. Thus, this validity method is inapplicable to this research.

Paradigm assumptions/lens	Systematic paradigm/ Postpositivist	Constructivist/ Interpretivist	Critical paradigm
Lens of the Researcher	Triangulation	Disconfirming evidence	Researcher reflexivity
Lens of the research participants	Member checking	Prolonged engagement in the field	Collaboration
Lens of external audience members (Reviewers, Readers)	The audit trail	Thick, rich description	Peer debriefing

Figure 4.7: Validity procedures within paradigm assumptions and qualitative lens
Source: Adapted from Creswell and Miller (2000)

To increase the credibility of qualitative data analysis, researchers should pursue and present disconfirming evidence (presenting negative viewpoints), which could influence the findings by considering biases (Creswell, 2018). The disconfirming views were reported analytically in the empirical findings and analysis (Chapters 5 and 6). The descriptions ‘thick and rich’ refer to the notion that the Researcher must provide extensive descriptions and proof of the themes that have been uncovered for the research outcome to be more valuable (Creswell, 2018). The Researcher presented a sample of quotations from participants to support the discovered themes in the analysis. The Researcher attempted to discuss various themes in depth to enrich the data analysis and maintain the accuracy of the findings, which also enables readers to make decisions about the applicability of the findings to other settings or similar contexts (Creswell and Miller, 2000). An in-depth discussion of the themes revealed was carried out, which added to the richness of the findings backed by a sample of interviewee responses (Appendix). The peer debriefing method is employed to increase the accuracy of data analysis. The data analysis and interpretation were discussed by an expert panel comprised of academic supervisors as well as the Researcher. This panel went over the code and interpretation in detail. A peer reviewer (DoS) who was familiar with the

research topic looked at a random sample of the coding (nodes) to make sure it was correct, gave written feedback and made this research more credible.

4.9.3 Ethical considerations

Researchers need to explain why maintaining ethical standards is critical when conducting moral research to make the best or most appropriate decision (McMurray *et al.*, 2004; Neuman, 2014). The present research followed the ethical guidelines established by the UWS to achieve the research objectives. Essentially, the Researcher obtained approval from the ethics committee before beginning the data collection process (Appendix). Prior to conducting interviews, participants were given detailed information about the research themes and objectives via interview guidance. The Researcher also informed participants that the collected data and findings would be used solely for the purpose of this research. Interviews were conducted and gathered in accordance with ethical considerations such as not mentioning the participants' names or identifying information. The data gathered was used for analysis, and all participants were made aware that they needed to provide signed consent to participate in the research (Appendix). This research was carried out with integrity to contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of IA with regional significance. Furthermore, this research has no negative impact on the respondents' personal gains.

Researchers are strongly advised to consider disclosure statements, which are regarded as an important ethical standard when conducting social science studies (Bhattacharjee, 2012). Normally, disclosure entails providing sufficient information to respondents during the data collection process by explaining the nature and purpose of the research. In line with the aforementioned observation, such information is critical prior to data collection because it should be provided to potential respondents in order for them to decide whether or not to participate in the research. The Researcher explained to the participants that the interview was part of a Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) programme. Such information includes the Researcher, DoS, Assessor and Second Supervisor's email addresses, phone numbers and the name of the institution, which were provided on the cover page of the interview guidance.

4.10 Summary

This chapter covers the research methodology from a theoretical and analytical standpoint. The qualitative nature of this research was to gather a comprehensive understanding of the research problem, which is particularly valuable when the major theory or framework lacks literature support. The adopted research philosophy was interpretative, as described in

previous sections of this chapter, and its worldview allowed the Researcher to understand in-depth about the research objects and examine them in the context of the banking sector. Phenomenology is used to support the core research topic, which focuses on describing the key challenges of the IA phenomenon from the perspective of practitioners for it to be an effective practice in banking organisations. The research design and methodology employed in this research are summarised in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of research design and data collection techniques

Research Methods	Techniques
Research approach	Inductive approach
Research philosophy	Interpretivism
Research design	Sequential research design
Type of investigation	Thematic and analytical approach
Time scope	Cross-sectional qualitative research
Data collection method	Telephonic and video conference
Structure of the interview	Semi-structured interviews
Data type	Secondary and primary
Measurement	Thematic coding

Source: The Researcher

This research adapted the research onion model developed by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), which involves conducting semi-structured qualitative interviews to evaluate the research contribution. Utilising the research onion, this investigation assessed the ‘research strategy’ under which the interviews fell. Nevertheless, the research onion’s qualitative ‘strategies’ component is less coherent than its quantitative section, which includes ‘survey’ as a method of data collection, compared to case study research or thematic procedures, which encompass both data collection and analysis. While the research onion model is useful in identifying different methods of data collection and analysis, it is lacking in terms of coherence and clarity, particularly in its treatment of qualitative ‘strategies’. For instance, semi-structured qualitative interviews are not equivalent to surveys, and the research onion does not include a strategy for phenomenological research, although it can be expanded to cover narratives or discourse. However, it is feasible to classify surveys or experiments as methods for data collection, and

it is unclear how they can be considered equivalent to case studies, grounded theory, and phenomenological research.

Furthermore, the adapted research onion functioned as a heuristic framework for developing the methodology and research design in this research. While the research onion for qualitative studies does not aspire to be the sole approach for creating a research design, it aims to offer a general guide and provide a flexible model for developing methodology, allowing researchers to select the most appropriate theories or practices from the existing layers to address research questions (Lobe, Morgan and Hoffman, 2022). However, the presented model (Figure 4.1) is viewed as a step-by-step process for constructing a theoretical IBA framework and qualitative strategies that validate the framework's elements, ensuring consistency among the chosen tools, techniques, and underlying philosophies. This approach led to the development of a coherent and logical research design.

To summarise, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather qualitative data. The interview guidance was produced based on the key elements of the theoretical IBA framework, which is presented in Chapter 3 after a systematic review of the literature and framework gaps. Purposive expert sampling and snowball sampling were used to select participants. TA was used to analyse the data. The findings of the literature review (Chapter 2) and systematic literature evaluation (Chapter 3) were also supported to obtain the empirical data. All of these methods were chosen to help achieve the research objectives and answer the main research question by facilitating and supplementing them. To emphasise the Researcher's identification of academic excellence, this chapter concludes with a review of data quality, covering reliability, validity, and ethical considerations. This chapter serves as a basis for the subsequent collection and analysis of primary data (Chapters 5 and 6), which provides a real-world perspective as well as a comprehensive guide to previous chapters.

Chapter 5: Research findings and analysis

5.1 Introduction

The previous chapter discussed research methodologies and methods, and justified the collection of interview data and TA for this research. This chapter presents the empirical findings derived from qualitative data research, which was obtained through semi-structured interviews. For this investigation, the Researcher uses TA to classify specific themes and patterns to uncover new emergent themes and new insights to gather a deeper understanding of the phenomenon (Trochim, 2009; Creswell, 2013). This chapter also aims to lay the groundwork for refining the theoretical IBA framework supported by practical guidance depicted in Figure 3.4, which is further validated in Figure 6.1.

The remainder of this chapter examines the two sections of the interview questions: Part I: Respondent and general information (Q1-Q9), and Part II: Development of the IBA framework (Q10-Q41).

5.2 Interview data analysis

The interview questions reflect the focus of the research to enable the systematic retrieval of a collection of qualitative findings divided into two sections: Section I: General information and Section II: Development of the IBA framework (Appendix – interview guidance). It was necessary to follow the ethical principles and guidelines discussed in Section 4.9 before proceeding with the data analysis. The participants' information was revised and remained unidentifiable by other parties. However, the participants' responses and perspectives on current IA challenges in the banking sector are pursued in the analysis section and replaced by unique IDs to adhere to the ethical guidelines (R1 to R21). During the analysis, the Researcher used NVivo 12 Pro to process and organise the collected qualitative data.

The Researcher first created critical factor codes to represent emergent themes and sub-themes identified in the interview transcripts to analyse the qualitative data. The Researcher also refers to these codes in the analysis, putting them in brackets in each section. In this regard, initial codes were labelled to reduce the likelihood of repetition and were applied to all 21 semi-structured interviews to provide descriptive findings that investigate current IA challenges to validate the IBA framework with practical guidance rather than theoretical assumptions (Ignatow and Mihalcea, 2017).

The interviewees were chosen based on their knowledge, practical experience and understanding of the phenomenon. Most respondents were top IA professionals from

various banking institutions who had been involved in the development and implementation of IA in their corporate, strategic or operational roles. To answer the research questions (Sub-Section 1.6), a balanced representation of top professionals from IA, internal controls and compliance was considered in many cases where they were chosen based on their professional standing, knowledge of the IA process, and in charge of its development and implementation. The amount of balance may be questioned, but coding allows for the initial analysis of research findings to be done in a way that ensures the integrity and transparency of the results.

The same coding approach was used to create themes and sub-themes before uploading the transcripts into NVivo 12 Pro. This method was chosen to ensure that the initial automatic coding (nodes) remained consistent throughout the data analysis, as discussed in the following sections and sub-sections. There were 41 questions in total, with 21 of them being semi-structured and the remaining 20 being open-ended questions designed to elicit new research insights. To ensure the objectivity of the semi-structured questions, the format of the questions allowed for different or optional answers that aligned with the respondents' own views. These response options, such as open-ended and semi-structured questions, were addressed to provide a starting point for discussion and to demonstrate a thorough understanding of the phenomenon's various interpretations. This procedure enables the collection of preliminary data that determines the nature of the research phenomenon (Bazeley, 2007).

Furthermore, the main selection criteria focused on the banking sector, experience in terms of the participant's role within the organisation and the tasks they performed related to IA. Based on the initial criteria, some respondents were identified and invited and the Researcher's professional network, while the remaining respondents joined and contributed because of the initial participant's recommendations (snowball sampling). The unprecedented disruption of COVID-19 and the resulting social distancing requirements outlined by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the UK government guidelines (GOV.UK, 2021) in recent years, all 21 interviews were conducted via online audio and video calls via international calling cards and WhatsApp rather than face-to-face interviews. This resulted in a total of 21 interviews, over 16 hours of analysis time and 43,629 words of qualitative data. The table below summarises the respondents' codes, interview length and settings:

Table 5.1: Interview participants

No	Participant code	Duration	Words	Interview setting
1	R [1]	47.22	3680	Online video calls
2	R [2]	63.55	3632	Online audio calls
3	R [3]	41.29	2392	Online audio calls
4	R [4]	68.56	2732	Online audio calls
5	R [5]	44.13	1975	Online video calls
6	R [6]	41.32	1837	Online audio calls
7	R [7]	46.37	1661	Online video calls
8	R [8]	64.10	1741	Online video calls
9	R [9]	47.18	1871	Online audio calls
10	R [10]	34.25	1913	Online audio calls
11	R [11]	29.14	1765	Online video calls
12	R [12]	37.47	1673	Online audio calls
13	R [13]	61.41	1775	Online audio calls
14	R [14]	46.45	1869	Online video calls
15	R [15]	47.16	1695	Online video calls
16	R [16]	55.42	1897	Online audio calls
17	R [17]	29.45	1927	Online video calls
18	R [18]	26.52	2004	Online audio calls
19	R [19]	41.35	2189	Online audio calls
20	R [20]	31.40	1387	Online audio calls
21	R [21]	56.20	2014	Online video calls
<i>Total 21 interviews</i>		<i>Duration: 959.94 min, [16 hrs 39 min 40 sec] 16:39:40</i>	<i>43629 words</i>	<i>9 online video calls, 12 online audio calls</i>

Source: The Researcher

As shown in Table 5.1, the interviews (nine video conferencing and 12 telephone interviews) were conducted using online video conferencing, telephonic calls using international calling cards and WhatsApp providing the Researcher with a diverse perspective. Despite the fact that other options were available, the 43,629 words allowed for a thorough examination of the research problem in practice. The sub-section that follows provides information about the participants' profile.

5.2.1 Part I: Respondents and general information (Q1–Q9)

The respondents and general information are the focus of the questions in this section. Q1 asked respondents to identify their area of work in the banking sector (IA_INST). Q2 inquired about the size of their organisation (IA_SIZE). Q3 determined their job title (IA_TITLE). Q4 investigated years of experience in their current position in the organisation (IA_ROLE). Q5 inquired about the length of time respondents had worked in IA (IA_EXP). Q6 inquired about the respondents' responsibilities who have been focusing on IA (IA_ASP). Q7 determined professional qualifications specific to the interviewees' work (IA_PQ and IA_PC). Q8 investigated the interviewees' tasks on IA in their organisation (IA_TASK). Q9 investigated IA that had already been developed and was working in the interviewees' favour (IA_AREA). The following sub-sections elaborate on the analysis of the interviewees' responses.

5.2.1.1 Respondents' area of organisation (Q1)

The purpose of this question was to understand more about the organisations in which the respondents work in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Figure 5.1 below depicts the results for five different types of institutions.

Figure 5.1: Percentage distribution of respondents' area of organisation

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.1 shows that respondents' organisational areas vary by category, with private commercial banks covering nearly half the percentage at 47.62%. Knowledge on organisational dispersion helps in comprehending the diversity of respondents' affiliations and, consequently, their implications.

5.2.1.2 Size of organisation (Q2)

Another important factor to consider was the size of the organisation in which the respondents work. A variety of factors need to be considered when evaluating an organisation such as assets, revenue turnover, annual growth, profitability and a variety of internal factors (Dang *et al.*, 2018). Some respondents' organisations, which are the AC members of the central bank of Bangladesh, may be insignificant. An organisation's size can be determined in other ways such as revenue turnover. However, respondents have reported employee numbers the most for informational purposes implying that they work for a large enough organisation to identify IA challenges and evaluate effective IA practices.

Figure 5.2: Percentage distribution of respondents' size of organisation

Source: The Researcher

Shown in Figure 5.2, the highest percentage groups (38.10% and 33.33%) were in medium to large sized organisations, with a significant percentage reduction in the smallest sized group (100 to 500 employees, 4.76%). As previously stated, the number of employees in various banking institutions, such as public, private and specialised banks, may not necessarily reflect the size of the organisation because determining the actual number of their employees is difficult. It is argued that size has no significant impact on the processes, responsibilities or tasks of the IA in banks (Ljubisavljevic, 2013). Extending this argument, financial organisations have advanced to a much higher level of IA development than economic entities, but they continue to underperform in many areas in developing countries when compared to developed countries.

5.2.1.3 Respondents' job title (Q3)

The purpose of this question was to assess the respondents' job title to investigate the implications of accountability. Due to the nature of the intersection of IA disciplines, a clear separation of respondents' roles was impossible because their roles were intertwined in some aspects of strategic or operational capabilities. This relates to literature that mentions duplication or fields that are intertwined.

Figure 5.3: Percentage distribution of respondents' job title

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.3 depicts an overview of respondents' job titles with seven respondents (33.33%) holding qualified or experienced internal auditor roles, six respondents (28.57%) holding head of IA or equivalent roles, two respondents (9.52%) holding the AC members, two respondents (9.52%) holding trainee internal auditor roles, one respondent (4.76%) holding a CAE role, and finally, one respondent (4.76%) holding a trainee internal auditor role. It is interesting to note that the majority of interviewees are highly qualified professionals with 61.9%. Question 6 expands on the respondents' roles and responsibilities.

5.2.1.4 Respondents' current role (Q4)

This question extracted the timeline with current organisations to further ascertain the rigour and legitimate validity of respondents' opinions, which is illustrated in Figure 5.4 below.

Figure 5.4: Percentage distribution of respondents' current role

Source: The Researcher

The duration of respondents' current jobs identifies that 90.48% have been in their current role for at least three years, some even more than five years 42.86%. Only 9.52% of respondents had at least one year but fewer than three years of experience. To summarise, this indicates that the respondents have extensive IA experience in their current roles within organisations, which helps in examining the challenges and practices they are facing for developing and implementing in their prospective IA department.

5.2.1.5 Respondents' experience (Q5)

In the previous question respondents were asked about their experience in their current organisation. In this question, they were asked about their overall experience (IA_EXP). Also, making a decision about seniority demonstrating that respondents' who have a longer length of experience, not just in their current organisation, have seniority, thus credibility for this research. Thus, a preliminary analysis may only provide a partial understanding, but Figure 5.5 shows these variances in more detail.

Figure 5.5: Percentage distribution of respondents' experience

Source: The Researcher

A substantial 80.95% of the respondents had at least five years of experience, with 4.76% of them having over 10 years servitude. Only 20% of the respondents had less than five years' experience. It suggests that the respondents have the necessary skills and knowledge to carry out IA activities, which are discussed in greater detail in the following question.

5.2.1.6 Respondents' responsibilities (Q6)

While the previous questions focused on terminologies and/or position designations, this question focused on responsibilities to gain a better understanding of the respondents' growing emphasis on the potential of IA (IA_ASP). This type of investigation seeks to highlight practical experience as well as limited expertise and the grounds for shared practices. Given that respondents were chosen based on strict criteria, these findings provided more credibility to the respondents' opinions. Most respondents who answered this question believed they had dual or triple roles, focusing on multiple segments of IA development and implementation, based on a total of 51-word selection frequencies elicited in defining roles.

Table 5.2: Respondents' responsibilities

Responsibilities		Coding frequency	Relative frequency
Initial attributes allocated by the Researcher	Control assessment or measurement	4	6.98%
	Fund management	1	2.91%
	Fraud detection and investigation	2	4.65%
	Monitoring operational activities	2	2.91%

Quality control system	1	1.74%
Quality assurance and improvement programme	3	7.56%
Risk assessment or measurement	13	26.16%
Implementation- technical	2	2.33%
Implementation- operational	3	3.49%
Implementation- strategic	5	5.81%
Internal control and compliance	15	35.46%
Total	51	100.00%

Source: The Researcher

Table 5.2 illustrates that the respondents prioritised internal control and compliance (35.46%) and risk assessment or measurement (26.16%) the most. Technical implementation and quality control systems were the least prioritised (2.33 per cent and 1.74 per cent, respectively).

To acknowledge these differences in roles and responsibilities, R [8] makes the following statement: *'We can't just sit back and watch as things change around us.'* From a technical point of view, to keep up with emerging innovations and trends, risks and opportunities, IA practitioners should take the initiative to stay current by preparing themselves in the IA department to face any technological advances. Respondents indicate the need to develop new skills and adopt novel approaches to auditing.

R [1] acknowledges that IA responsibilities are complex: *'We must not only explain the risks and opportunities that lie ahead, but also demonstrate the value of the IA function in this process to be future-ready to assist organisations in adapting and growing in the face of change.'*

Similarly, R [11] emphasises a similar point of view: *'A detailed risk assessment guided by a deep understanding of the organisation as well as its environment is required if you want to conduct an effective quality audit. It should also act as a strong deterrent to any activities that are not in the best interests of the public as well as a source of confidence for stakeholders.'*

Conversely, R [5] takes a different stance and believes that *'a continuous process of risk assessment should be used with revisions made as needed.'*

To summarise, when assessing the risks that an organisation faces, it may take several iterations before it has a complete picture of its controls and processes. Thus, top

management and employees should have a thorough understanding of the organisation's risk profile and the importance of risk mitigation.

5.2.1.7 Respondents' professional qualification (Q7)

The respondents were asked if their current position is conditioned on specific professional qualifications as a continuation of credentials that are thought to be recognised and comprehended for essential ideas in IA. Although the level of subordination, professional qualifications, and practical experience of IA employees, IA strategy and IA activities must be appropriate for IA to be independent and objective, they add value to the organisation by improving its ability to manage itself (Savcuk, 2007). The pressure on organisations to obtain certifications is depicted in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6: Percentage distribution of respondents' professional qualification

Source: The Researcher

The obvious question for respondents is whether their current employment position is conditioned on a fully or partially professional certification. Based on the research findings, most respondents (86%) agreed with the statement that it is required, while 14% claimed it was not necessary in their current jobs. Although there has been a shift in the IA job market towards preferring IT-related professional certifications over traditional accounting certifications, maintaining compliance was found to be positively related to IIA membership length, human orientation, professional certification and the number of hours of continuing professional education (Abdolmohammadi, 2009; Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Thus, it is believed that adhering to a professional certification benefits a candidate and certifies their suitability for a specific IA role in their future endeavours and, more specifically, benefits the organisations they serve.

Figure 5.7: Percentage distribution of respondents' professional certifications

Source: The Researcher

Some of the conclusions drawn in Figure 5.6 have been challenged by the findings depicted in Figure 5.7, which argue that the requirement for certification is indirectly mandated during the recruitment and selection of the IA candidate. While certifications are both voluntary and optional, as indicated by respondents (86%), the consensus was that they are 'recommended'. R [7] states that *'it is necessary to understand the dimensions of the IA department workload and is recommended to get certified by professional organisations.'* In support of this point of view, R [18] states that *'organisations looking for professionally qualified candidates while not officially mentioned sometimes select and recommend those who are qualified.'* Within these lines, R [11] explained that *'as a member of professional organisations, I've learned how to provide assurance while ensuring that both internal and external risks are properly identified and handled,'* and R [7] agreed and supported this statement saying, *'as a contributor, I'm able to give back to the community and assist others in their professional development by networking and sharing information.'*

5.2.1.8 Respondents' area of tasks (Q8)

This question essentially defines the respondent's area of tasks within the given organisations after assessing expertise and experience in the IA area. The evidence provides an opportunity to understand comprehensive views about the respondents' accountability constraints and investigates any possible outcome framed by designated roles and expressed views.

Figure 5.8: Respondents' area of tasks

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.8 shows that respondents prioritised internal control and risk governance (20.19%), monitoring and policy making (16.95%), communication between departments (12.59%), execution of an annual audit plan (10.83%), application of audit methodology (10.83%), data governance and systems infrastructure (10.83%), fraud detection and compliance (8.06%), accountability and financial reporting (7.59%), and measuring and assessing risks (2.13%). To acknowledge these differences in task areas, R [11] makes the following statement: *'I am primarily in charge of internal control and governance procedures, policy formulation and implementation, and the development of internal control structures and activities. One of my primary responsibilities is to oversee the activities of the other branches, which are all overseen by the head office.'*

R [5] agrees that tasks in a technological context are complicated: *'My primary responsibilities include developing and maintaining relationships with senior technology and other business leaders as well as working with the CAE to provide assurance over key risks in technology applications and processes, data governance and system infrastructure.'*

Furthermore, R [19] emphasises a similar point of view: *'I have a proven track record of establishing and maintaining a balance between the needs of internal control and the needs of compliance. Setting internal control standards is the first step in the process, which is followed by an assessment of how well the requirements were met.'*

5.2.1.9 Respondents' area of work (Q9)

This question, which follows an assessment of experience and expertise, essentially defines the respondents' interaction with IA development and implementation within their given

organisation to illustrate a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' area of work (IA_AREA) that is established and provides benefits. In terms of accountability constraints, and to investigate any possible outcome framed by the designated area in their expressed views, the Three Lines of Defence Model's (3LoD) principles were accepted to allow for a synthesised view. Table 5.3 depicts how respondents' interactions with IA governance were classified into three categories: first line (management), second line (emerging risks and compliance) and third line (reporting to the BOD and the AC). Due to the multiple responsibilities reported, the 3LoD model was used as a guide to determine respondents' designated areas of work.

Table 5.3: Categorising area of work in aligning with the 3LoD model

Categorisation of roles in aligning with the 3LoD model					
1st line of defence		2nd line of defence		3rd line of defence	
Management		Emerging risks and compliance		Reporting to the BOD and the AC	
Internal control process	R [1]	Risk assessment	R [7]	Financial reporting	R [2]
	R [9]		R [11]		R [6]
	R [13]				R [21]
	R [20]				
Fraud, money laundering mitigation	R [5]	Compliance	R [4]		
			R [12]		
			R [16]		
Operational audits	R [10]		R [17]		
	R [19]		R [18]		
		Digitisation and leveraging technology	R [3]		
		Quality assurance	R [8]		
		Internal auditing programme	R [14]		
			R [15]		
Related frequency of 33.33%		Related frequency of 52.38%		Related frequency of 14.29%	
Total 100%					
<i>R = Respondent</i>					

Source: The Researcher

The evidence shows that the risk landscape becomes more complex and dynamic, therefore, organisations must identify and respond to emerging risk events faster and more effectively (Deloitte, 2020). For operational risk governance in banks, the IIA developed the 3LoD. Traditionally, IA activities were expected to provide assurance while remaining objective and impartial. A business-focused, technology-driven approach is becoming

increasingly important for organisations. The BCBS defines the principles of the 3LoD model and a systematic structure is strongly advised (Luburi, 2017). In summary, the 3LoD was chosen because it was mentioned by many respondents and is a consistent practice in banks.

5.2.2 Part II: Development of the IBA framework (Q10–Q41)

In this section, the questions are intended to demonstrate the credibility of the development of the IBA framework development. This section began by looking into the questions related to the key IA input factors, followed by the IA foundation factors, and finally the IA integration factors that may affect IA in the banking sector. Referring to Figure 3.4, each question focuses on a key element of the theoretical IBA framework (Chapter 3). The following sub-sections provide a list of interview questions along with factor codes, which represent themes and sub-themes, for better understanding and clarification, while also providing an analysis of the interviewees' responses.

5.2.2.1 IA input factors which may affect IA (Q10–Q19)

One of the key internal environments that influenced the development of the IBA framework was identifying the IA input elements in banks to gain significant additional insights into the practical implementation. The theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4) specifies five primary IA input elements: (i) key banking auditing challenges (Q10, Q11, and Q12), (ii) IA alignment with emerging risks (Q13), (iii) internal control systems (Q14, Q15), (iv) IA standards and governance (Q16, Q17), and (v) IA quality assurance (Q18, Q19).

The questions in this section are aimed at supporting the development of the IBA framework. The main challenges (IA_MCHAL) in implementing IA in banks was discussed first (Q10). Then each question focused on a key element of the theoretical framework as indicated above. Q11 and Q12 investigated the current challenges (IA_CCHAL) and overcoming the current challenges (IA_OCHAL) of the internal environment of IA, respectively, while Q13 examined the key emerging risks that face IA (IA_EMRISK). Similarly, Q14 and Q15 investigated the strategic alignment of IA and internal control systems and their benefits in the organisation (IA_SA) and (IA_BIAICS), respectively. Q16 determined the risk and control issues (IA_RICO) and Q17 investigated the organisation's improvement provided by the BOD and the AC (IA_IMPRO). Finally, Q18 and Q19 investigated whether there is a sufficient level of IA planning for effective quality assurance (IA_IAP) and what impedes successful implementation of an IA plan (IA_IAP). The sub-sections that follow discuss the

interviewees' responses in depth by analysing and comparing them analytically with the literature findings.

5.2.2.1.1 Main challenges facing IA implementation (Q10)

This question sought to investigate the main challenges facing IA implementation in the banking sector (IA_MCHAL). This query seeks to identify challenges associated with how IA practices can improve governance and risk management to improve IA effectiveness while adhering to governmental policy reforms. Key findings indicate that the challenges, such as the accountability of the head of the IA department to management, the establishment of the AC by management, a lack of access to regular refresher courses and management's hostile attitude towards audit reports, may serve as impediments to the effective functioning of the IA department (Abaidoo, 2015).

Figure 5.9: Main challenges facing IA implementation

Source: The Researcher

Consistent with the literature findings, Figure 5.9 illustrates that a lack of a dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance (23.42%), and a lack of a strategic vision for IA (20.54%) have been significant challenges in recent years for banks. Respondents also reported a lack of resources and talent management (18.98%), a lack of agile auditing methodologies (16.52%) and poor application of regulations and standards (13.87%). R [5] asserts the argument towards regulations and standards by stating that *'further regulation of IA activity could lead to a lack of standardised and comprehensive professional standards and ethical conduct'*, whereas R [4] asserts that *'a local or pan-national approach to regulation is possible, but unlikely. There are numerous benefits to having a single set of global standards.'*

While R [8] states that agile methods are necessary in this current environment as ‘when internal auditors use agile methods, it is easier for them to respond quickly and effectively to both internal and external changes. Being adaptable is also useful in times of crisis (such as the current COVID-19 issue).’ In contrast, R [14] expresses an opposing viewpoint:

Working in an agile manner may make it difficult for IA departments to prioritise and carry out audits in a constantly changing or disrupted environment. It is the strategic mindset that an IA department adopts to focus on accelerate audit cycles, stakeholder needs, reduce wasted work, generate less documentation and drive timely insights.

R [7] provides additional information:

In the planning, fieldwork and reporting stages of its audits, my bank has used an agile strategy. The aim is to get to the field as soon as possible. Typically, the first two weeks of an audit are devoted to planning. The entire team is involved in the audit.

R [10] goes on to say ‘*numerous benefits can be gained by implementing agile methodologies in my teams, such as clearer outcomes, increased engagement with the product or service, fewer documents, empowered teams, faster delivery cycles and improved planning.*’

The empirical evidence resulting from the analysis highlights an emphasis on resources and talent management, which agrees with Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi (2020), who state that an agile IA team with monitoring abilities, knowledge and competence is required to fill the performance gap that arises from achieving the strategic vision. Given the complexity of the organisational environment, it is difficult to reliably prevent misconduct and address the majority of potential risks. Another notable finding is that developing efficient IA practices in banks is impeded by a lack of dynamic IA framework implementation with practical guidance, a lack of agile auditing methodologies and a lack of compliance with regulations and standards. These findings highlight the significance of establishing an IBA framework, which is the purpose of this research. Another significant finding is that many respondents mentioned difficulties in integrating independence and objectivity, transparency and accountability into audit plans and coordinating assurance across organisations.

5.2.2.1.2 Organisations' current IA challenges (Q11)

The purpose of this question was to identify current challenges that IA faces in banking organisations (IA_CCHAL). In recent years, the industry-based literature has emphasised the importance of considering how IA research can go beyond current challenges (Deloitte, 2018). Thus, it is necessary to investigate current challenges that allow academics to examine existing knowledge gaps in IA, which could be related to IA quality, the changing roles of IA and IA practice. In contrast, academic literature by Van Helden and Uddin (2016) and Roussy and Perron (2018) suggests that understanding pragmatic insights about current and emerging issues in terms of methods and theoretical premises to close knowledge gaps may have an impact on established and emerging IA practices in specific organisational settings (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020).

Figure 5.10: Organisations' current IA challenges

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.10 shows that respondents have reported that the current challenge for banks is a lack of strong internal control systems (37.79%). Respondents also reported a lack of a risk-based IA approach (23.37%) and a lack of clear methodology for leveraging technology (17.16%) as significant emerging challenges in recent years. Other key challenges, such as a lack of top management support (6.84%), difficulty in gathering evidence (5.05%), a lack of integrated monitoring activities (3.68%), a lack of IA reporting (3.37%) and inadequate communication of information (2.74%), have a significant impact on IA in banks. R [1] summarises the findings of this question in terms of internal control systems stating that *the*

internal control system's design must be based on a cost-benefit analysis based on the available resources.' This indicates that a robust internal control system should always be supported in order to mitigate risk in the banking payment process.

R [21] illustrates the following:

Senior management's ability to override accepted control, employee collusion, inadequate control culture, the use of memory, reliance on a single performance indicator, uncontrolled delegation of responsibilities and retrospective transaction recording are some risk signals to check for.

R [6] provides additional information:

We see a variety of scams being perpetrated because of poorly enforced or inadequate controls, resulting in financial losses and brand damage. As a result of this lack of principles, we are observing quality issues, increasing error rates and operational inefficiencies.

R [11] elaborates on the significance of a risk-based approach:

Risk-based planning is necessary, but I believe it is time to rethink how IA plans are created and focus on the fundamental goal of value-based auditing, which is to improve and add value to an organisation's operations. IA may have a stronger influence if the organisation reaches a higher level of maturity.

This empirical evidence is consistent with Mihret and Grant (2017) who state that when evaluating the effectiveness of internal control systems, organisations should consider how to implement an IA plan that is agile in IA reporting, forward-thinking in communication and information, integrated in monitoring activities and a risk-based IA approach, all of which must be aligned with organisational strategy. Another interesting finding is that the banking sector is currently facing critical challenges in developing IT audits, adopting emerging technological innovations and levels of collaboration between the IA and IT functions due to a lack of a clear methodology for leveraging technology and top management support. Another noteworthy finding is the significance of evaluating the risk-based approach, which includes defining the corporate governance role that internal auditors should play in organisational developments. This was consistent with the findings of Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi (2020) who state that IA is one of the internal control methods that can be used to improve and strengthen governance through appropriate risk reporting and classification.

5.2.2.1.3 Overcoming current IA challenges (Q12)

The aim of this question was to identify and address critical elements that could assist banking organisations in overcoming current IA challenges (IA_OCHAL). IA work engagements have evolved beyond the traditional role of detecting fraud by including key tasks such as analysing agile methods, analysing dynamic and visual elements of audit reports, and introducing financial data protection methods (Deloitte, 2018). These include investigating the organisational culture, working on electronic risk assessments, ensuring that general standards and procedures are followed and analysing banking performance. A lack of systematic development of the IA profession’s key challenges exacerbates the problem by providing a more aggregated and contextualised picture to support much-needed practice-oriented literature research (Lenz and Sarens, 2012; Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

Figure 5.11: Overcoming current IA challenges

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.11 depicts some of the potential solutions for overcoming the current IA challenges. The two strongest possible solutions for banks to overcome the challenges of implementing IA are strategy and governance, and building relationships (13.99% each). Improving risk and control analysis was the next highest result (13.65%), followed by improving the quality of internal control systems (10.24%), framework implementation (8.70%) and a strong IA process with (7.17%). Other options for overcoming challenges include maintaining better management oversight (5.80%), developing financial reporting quality (5.46%), improving

soft skills and knowledge (4.44%), maintaining communication and accountability (4.27%), and measuring and assessing IA effectiveness (4.10%). Finally, professional development receives the lowest solution idea (2.90%).

The findings emphasise that respondents identified key factors for overcoming current challenges. R [1] argues, more specifically, that the responsible bank must create an internal control environment because *'the control environment of an organisation sets the tone and shapes its employees' awareness about controls supported by discipline and structure.'* R [9] adds that the use of current resources as well as ensuring that audits are cost-effective and stay within the allocated budget assist because of the following:

IA is subject to the same rules as the rest of the organisation. Due to time and content constraints, special or supplementary audit engagements may be required. IA management must ensure that budget constraints are met or that necessary changes are explained despite the increased workload.

While R [3] is also seen to be embracing technology:

Internal auditors have to make yet another pivot to accommodate the shifting needs caused by technological disruptions that fundamentally alter how work is done to sustain and improve on our successes. To adapt, internal auditors need to embrace technology in ways they have never done before.

R [10] also emphasises the importance of implementing a workforce strategy:

IA is becoming more important in most banks, but there are still numerous challenges to overcome. Surpassing expectations is one of the most difficult challenges. We must ensure that our value proposition meets those requirements. Audit departments must ensure that the increased value expected from a workforce strategy is met and delivered by the board and management teams.

Consistent with the empirical findings, this research illustrates that developing relationships and implementing an IA strategy are important determinants of overcoming challenges. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that risk and control analysis can predict the quality of internal control systems. While there is a lack of empirical evidence on IA processes and their impact on organisational and environmental factors (Alzeban 2015), maintaining communication and accountability, as well as measuring and assessing IA effectiveness,

are all important factors for effective IA practices (Arena and Azzone 2009; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011). Critical stakeholder perceptions should define professional development (Sarens and De Beelde 2006), which necessitates that institutions manage stakeholder expectations, particularly in the provision of financial information. Institutions must be able to provide financial information that is accurate, relevant and understandable (Kaawaase *et al.*, 2021). Organisations must have an IA quality in terms of workforce competency to achieve quality financial reporting, and such personnel must be able to comply with professional standards and norms.

5.2.2.1.4 Key emerging risks (Q13)

The purpose of this question was to identify the key emerging risks confronting IA in the banking sector (IA_EMRISK). Prior research in Section 2.4 shows that IA necessitates adaptability due to the emerging risks, which are ingrained in organisational operations and continue to be important determinants in maintaining strong governance and accountability (Dubihlela and Gwaka, 2020).

Figure 5.12: Key emerging risks

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.12 depicts the most recent emerging risks to IA in the banking sector. Respondents identified six types of emerging risks for organisations. Human capital and talent management pose the most significant risks (44.27%). Digital disruption and cybersecurity are the second-highest risks (35.32%). Other risks were organisational culture, behaviour, and soft controls (9.17%), changes in laws and regulations (6.88%), sustainable auditing resilience (3.21%), finally followed by corruption, fraud and bribery disruption (1.15%).

R [1] asserts that most banks in Bangladesh are facing significant risks in the digital workforce, as they quoted the following:

The IA is no exception where technology and globalisation are reshaping and are being severely impacted by the volatility and rapidity of change. Stakeholders, for the most part, want to focus more on the risks and concerns of the future rather than the past.

While R [12] adds support by stating: *'As a final takeaway, IA must focus on the recruitment and retention of game-changing talent. It is becoming increasingly important for organisations to ensure that their IA teams are properly trained and developed in the current candidate market.'*

R [4] also argues that changes in laws and regulations resulted in governance and administrative solution requirements. R [6] states that additional development would benefit both current and future audit leaders in the banking sector:

We need to focus on seven areas: emerging risks, sustainability and climate change; data ethics; artificial intelligence governance; talent management; recruiting and retaining game-changing talent; being a champion for strong governance; and innovating the way it is so we preserve and create value.

In summary, human capital and talent management (Deloitte, 2021), digital disruption and cybersecurity (KPMG, 2021), and organisational culture, behaviour and soft controls (IIA, 2021) are among the identified emerging risks, which are consistent with industrial literature findings. The key findings also support the literature in Sub-Section 3.2.1 where the systematic gap evaluation emphasises the need for assistance in identifying and mitigating emerging risks through the development of risk management protocols that are commensurate with the changing risk landscape. In such risk assessment areas, IA professionals are increasingly being reviewed and evaluated for capacity building to adapt and be forward-thinking (Dubihlela and Gwaka, 2020). Thus, when it comes to changing rules and regulations, maintaining auditing resilience and adapting to emerging risks, the BOD and AC are forced to think outside the internal environment.

5.2.2.1.5 Strategic alignment between IA and internal control systems (Q14)

The purpose of this question was to identify factors that influence the strategic alignment of IA with internal control systems in terms of generating long-term value in banking

organisations (IA_SA). Based on the literature, the findings suggest that the qualities of a value-added IA department in organisations are shaped by the aims and strategies pursued, as well as the level of risk encountered and the quality of strategic planning, which determines the extent to which an adequate value-added profile is obtained (Mihret and Woldeyohannis, 2008).

Figure 5.13: Strategic alignment between IA and internal control systems

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.13 demonstrates that safeguarding assets (45.28%) is one of the most important elements in aligning IA with internal control systems, followed by communication and documentation (23.50%), productivity (18.05%) and continuous monitoring (12.98%). Regarding the primary factor for generating value, R [6] asserted the following:

Because of a greater emphasis on the need for adaptability in the workplace, internal auditors' mindsets have shifted significantly over the last year and a half. Agile's scope of practice includes culture, risk assessment, audit execution and reporting. With the help of modern technology and with the overarching aim of increasing the value stakeholders derived from the organisation's people, a people-centric culture can be adopted.

Meanwhile, R [9] explains that the source of operational efficiency is the internal control systems: *'Internal control is essential for effectively running a corporation. An organisation cannot ensure that the interests of its stakeholders are protected unless it has a strong internal control system.'* However, an additional 45.28% of respondents state that asset

safeguarding is an essential component of internal controls in the banking sector. R [7], for example, revealed that *‘with strong internal controls in place, organisations can avoid financial losses, operational waste, environmental irresponsibility or corporate fraud as well as reputational harm that may be impossible to recover from.’* In support of this viewpoint, R [12] states that financial reporting is not dominant because: *‘in the governance of an organisation, internal control over financial reporting continues to be a primary topic of focus.’*

Analysing the responses reveals that strategic alignment towards IA and internal control systems is critical for developing a long-term feasible approach as this should help to mitigate issues such as poor automated oversight, insufficient organisational alignment and IA team resources, lack of accountability, insufficient training and guidance, and lack of organisational commitment. Similar findings were reported in the literature reviewed in Sub-Section 2.5.2, where strategic alignment could lead to the resolution of existing practice challenges and the improvement of organisational performance (Deloitte, 2021). This finding highlights the IA’s resources’ ability to provide significant added value when faced with strategic changes that affect their structure. Apart from top management and/or the BOD, the level of credibility of the IA function as well as the auditees, is critical to being aligned with the organisation’s strategy.

5.2.2.1.6 Benefits of implementing IA and internal control systems (Q15)

The aim of this question (IA_BIAICS) was to determine the benefits of implementing IA and internal control systems in the banking sector. Based on the research findings, effective corporate governance simplifies monitoring and control, which improves financial reporting quality by providing insights into how the benefits of IA and internal control offer a critique of the research to focus on supporting IA (Nalukenge *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 5.14: Benefits of implementing IA and internal control systems

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.14 depicts the advantages of implementing IA and internal control systems as claimed by respondents. Regulatory compliance (33.10%) and integrated financial reporting (27.93%) are perceived as the most beneficial. Other desirable benefits include organisational performance (17.93%), fraud risk management (14.48%) and accounting system development (6.55%). Internal control systems are beneficial to institutions because they enable them to achieve more aims. R [1] asserts that *'although an effective internal control system can keep the right individuals informed about the organisation's progress towards its aims, it cannot make a bad manager a good manager.'* R [16] agrees with this assertion and reports that *'there is a positive rapport between IA and internal control systems, and thus, internal control programmes can achieve their aims more flexibly.'*

This indicates that the internal control programme must include a committed management team that is held accountable for a good internal control structure, and although this is critical it is not a guarantee of success. The findings revealed a general agreement that assurance is critical not only in banks but also in regulatory compliance and substantive testing. R [9], for example, explains that the *'internal control, in general, is not a guarantee that the organisation could achieve its aims. Because all internal control systems have inherent limitations, they can only provide acceptable assurance.'*

Respondents who agreed with regulatory compliance argued that banks must notify the IA department of the significant time consumption associated with the vouching technique, which necessitates the development of accounting systems. This finding is consistent with the literature, which suggests that a monitoring and control layer for continuous auditing of organisational process controls could be developed and implemented (Alles and Gray, 2006). Citing academic literature, Section 2.4 emphasises the importance of a transparent approach to fraud risk assessment to facilitate effective governance and improvements in the technical function of IA as well as skill requirements (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Thus, discovered cybersecurity threats and non-compliance occurrences are among the positive effects of IA access controls on reported internal control gaps, which necessitate accountability (Steinbart *et al.*, 2018).

5.2.2.1.7 Determining risk and control issues (Q16)

This question aimed to establish risk and control issues that should be addressed to the BOD and AC in organisations for successful IA operations in the banking sector (IA_RICO). The IA's strong relationship with top management is argued to be based on the idea that

internal auditors must constantly advise management on how to improve operations in order for the IA's independence not to be undermined (Roussy and Brivot, 2016).

Figure 5.15: Determining risk and control issues

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.15 investigated the risk and control issues raised by respondents. Operational and IT resilience were the most important issues (31.52%). The second important issue was organisational integrity (25.04%) with financial resource allocation being next (23.27%). Three other issues raised by respondents were corporate governance, transparency and reporting (13.11%), innovative audit techniques (4.42%) and organisational sustainability (2.65%). However, R [1], R [3] and R [7] anticipate that risk and control issues should continue to grow, especially since some organisations have failed in risk management and financial control capacity (Marriage, 2018). R [21] emphasises, '*internal auditors must recognise and communicate operational errors with the management because they can have significant financial consequences*', meaning that the financial accounts reveal the first signs of trouble in the organisation's operations.

Despite the fact that risk and control measures are in place in financial reporting, R [10], R [13] and R [16] believe that banking organisations are imperceptible in terms of fraud control. Worryingly, R [23] believes that some sort of fraud has occurred:

The financial statements and ratios should reveal whether the organisation is operationally and strategically successful. The financial figures may reveal whether or not the organisation is experiencing operational difficulties. This is true unless fraud or financial manipulation is used to conceal the true situation.

When asked if they reported on organisational sustainability, only 2.65% of respondents stated that the strength of IA with top management and the AC is based on the ability to create relationships and deliver work in an understandable manner. The cost-benefit analysis is positive and R [2], R [11] and R [12] substantiate this. R [12] elaborates:

The recommendations should include a cost-benefit analysis as well as an explanation of the risks associated with the control gaps we identify. This is the gap, this is the threat, and I've approached it by co-creating solutions and action plans.

To summarise, the findings suggest that the importance of operational and IT resilience should be immediately reported to the BOD and the AC in determining the IA effectiveness. It is argued that allocating financial resources is a critical factor in the effectiveness of IA activities (Alzeban and Gwilliam, 2014). Management should have monitored organisational integrity at all intervals in developing countries, where systems and infrastructure are not as good as in developed countries, and analysed it for corporate governance, transparency and reporting issues. Thus, this should be one of the core competencies because communication skills are required to improve IA quality, which is strongly related to financial reporting quality (Sarens, 2009; Bailey, 2011; Narkchai and Fadzil, 2017; Kaawaase *et al.*, 2021).

5.2.2.1.8 BOD and the AC support (Q17)

The aim of this question was to look into how the BOD and the AC can assist organisations in the banking sector (IA_IMPRO). While AC's informal interactions are strongly linked to knowledge and experience, IA quality and independence, IA must enter the corporate governance space to conduct audits more effectively by providing more reliable assurance to the BOD (Zaman and Sarens, 2013; Chambers and Odar, 2015).

Figure 5.16 depicts the supportive elements that could improve IA in banks by the BOD and the AC. Most respondents agreed that reviewing and assessing the IA work plan should help IA (14.68%). Other factors to consider include technology adoption (12.61%), training and guidance (11.23%), financial reporting and related internal control (11.05%), monitoring and assessing IA quality (10.36%), focusing on emerging risks (9.84%), providing financial resources (9.50%), assurance on control resilience (8.81%), incorporating adaptability into the strategic vision (8.29%) and effective and high-quality communication (3.63%).

Figure 5.16: BOD and the AC support

Source: The Researcher

R [14] reports that *‘as a result of the complexity of gathering and maintaining data, there are a wide range of cybersecurity concerns and a rising reliance on platforms offered by third parties, typically leveraging technological advancements such as cloud computing.’* Meanwhile, R [21] adds: *‘Organisations are finding it increasingly difficult to track and identify all potential sources of risk. Malicious actors have more avenues for attack and more partners to check for compliance as their online presence grows.’*

When asked to describe the incorporation of adaptability into the strategic vision, R [5] states:

As a way to keep track of all the reporting requirements listed in the standards, the AC may consider creating a checklist consisting of the following topics: charter; organisational independence of the IA activity; audit plans and resources; the results of audit engagements; quality assurance and improvement programme; and conformance with the Code of Ethical Conduct.

R [13] provides assurance on control resilience: *'A third-party IA is required. Using the IA department, the BOD or the AC can identify operational issues such as ineffective control design, control weaknesses and poor KPI performance.'*

R [12] and R [19] report a further derivation of fraud prevention, believing that effective fraud prevention tools and techniques are essential, resulting in banks being subjected to implementing regulations. Another point of view on providing financial resources is expressed by R [17], who sees fraud threats as a major issue that must be addressed. Furthermore, R [5] emphasises a culture of integrity:

Members of the BOD and the AC are responsible for ensuring that corporate fraud is effectively and responsibly controlled. The task of fraud prevention is to keep an eye on actions. They should also assess their ability to detect and respond to fraud threats as well as the organisation's integrity culture.

To summarise, the presence of independence, training and guidance, and auditing and accounting experience have all positively influenced compliance with IA standards (Alzeban, 2015). Research by Ramamoorti (2003) notes that regular interaction with AC members can help organisations focus on organisational performance and improve governance, decision-making and resource allocation, allowing them to be more aligned with their strategic aims. Improving the audit work plan, improving financial and related internal control competency, proactively focusing on emerging risks and demonstrating institutional factors such as management support and the audit team involvement were predicted to influence IA effectiveness, resulting in a more rigorous and efficient audit approach.

5.2.2.1.9 Effective quality assurance (Q18)

This question sought to ascertain the scope of the IA plan as well as any additional engagements required to provide a sufficient level of quality assurance in banking organisations (IA_IAP). Various IA actions, such as the use of quality assurance methodologies, grading IA reports and following up on issues to ensure remediation, have an impact on the effects of various institutions, and legal and regulatory systems on IA quality and effectiveness (Lin *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 5.17: Effective quality assurance

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.17 demonstrates that producing quality assurance is very successful (very/somewhat effective total of 76%). When it came to the findings, there was a significant difference between those who lacked sufficient local regulatory expertise and those who required expert assistance to ensure their audits covered the right risks and were of high quality. The number of respondents neutral in their responses was 5%. Under these conditions, R [10] rates the comments as positive:

The IA plan contains a wealth of information and insight into the organisation. Internal auditors can use their professional skills and knowledge of the organisation's operations to make judgements on the effectiveness and efficiency of the operations as well as management's achievement of set objectives and aims.

R [6] says 'IA examines whether the system, principles, rules and regulations, as well as the books of accounts, are up-to-date and in compliance with the principles and practices.' In fact, several respondents expressed ineffective opinions (19%). For instance, R [20] says the following:

The chief auditor is in charge of creating and maintaining a 'risk and control' culture throughout the organisation. They must establish a strong governance framework within the department and organisation by developing an IA activity charter, IA policies and procedures, and sophisticated IA methodologies, codes of conduct and whistle-blower policies.

To summarise the findings, IA can assist management in preventing them from concealing or altering earnings or accounts by increasing transparency and increasing the likelihood of discovery (Prawitt, Smith and Wood, 2009). Examining the audit scope, risk and control matrices, and test plans to ensure compliance with all regulatory requirements is important. Before producing a fieldwork working paper to assess the depth and quality of audit work, the audit team must provide regular feedback on the quality of work at various stages of the audit.

5.2.2.1.10 Implementation of IA plan (Q19)

This question sought to investigate the key factors that might impede the successful implementation of an IA plan in a banking organisation (IA_IIAP). In practice, the most used indicators of IA effectiveness are its efficiency in delivering the annual IA work plan and accepting and adopting IA recommendations (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011).

Table 5.4: Implementation of IA plan

Theme	Sub-themes	Sub-theme description	Coding frequency	Relative frequency
Control (25.19%)	Cost-effectiveness	Awareness of solid internal controls	6	19.66%
	Accounting records	Financial accounting	5	5.53%
Measurement (16.40%)	Independence	Difficulty in measuring the level	5	2.10%
	Objectivity	Organisational demands	5	0.95%
	Competency	Critical thinking abilities	5	0.95%
	Practices	Organisational setting and auditee attributes	6	12.40%
Positioning (28.49%)	Culture	Audit techniques and risks	2	4.96%
	Cooperation	IA with other managerial departments	1	3.44%
	Effectiveness	Lack of understanding	3	5.15%
	Performance	Regulations and organisational demands	5	7.06%
Resources (12.80%)	Framework	Establishing legal framework	4	8.21%
	Manpower	IT knowledge and shortages	4	1.34%
	Knowledge	Research and development	2	3.44%
	Financial	Resources	1	4.01%
Vision (16.79%)	Technical	Technology	4	4.01%
	Institutional	Capacity building and development	4	4.96%
	Professional	Co-operation and networking activities	1	7.82%
	Resolution	Internal dispute	1	0.57%
	Support	Top management	1	0.76%
	Techniques	Tools and techniques	1	2.68%
Total	20 Sub-themes		Sub-themes frequency= 66	Total= 100%

Source: The Researcher

As shown in Table 5.4, some of the research mainstreams have been identified and are consistent with the literature (Gramling *et al.*, 2004; Causholli, 2009), which are positioning (28.49%), control (25.19%), vision (16.79%), measurement (16.40%) and resources (12.80%). All variable effects, for example, allude to cultural deficiencies (4.96%). In response to a potentially hazardous organisational culture, R [1] asserts that *'when things go wrong at work, toxic organisational cultures are usually to blame.'* While some internal auditors prefer to focus on audit issues that are more easily quantifiable, organisational culture risks should never be overlooked. Another response by R [21] emphasises the importance of fostering a positive organisational culture:

An unhealthy organisational culture may allow a minor problem to escalate into a major one. Expect the BOD to question you about where you were when IA ignored organisational culture because the BOD faces serious accountability for their organisation's flaws.

R [21]'s statement corresponds to planned and documented IA that adheres to a risk-based procedure to ensure that they are focused on relevant concerns and completed on time. Furthermore, R [20] asserts that skills, competencies and workforce shortages all impede the effective implementation of an IA plan:

Your audit strategy is the result of a great deal of effort and time. You broaden the scope of your audit to include all of your organisation's processes and divisions. Then, you collect risk data and obsess about scores in order to appropriately prioritise dangers. After you've assessed the risks, you'll be able to create an audit plan. Because it is built around a list of entities, this audit plan is known as an 'entity-based audit plan.'

Furthermore, the audit universe used in the assessment should contain objectives and risks rather than entities as the starting point for a proper risk-based strategy. R [15] says that *'the adoption of new technologies like blockchain and cloud computing, as well as how to manage these difficulties, are the most serious issues facing the IA today.'* R [15] also provides convergent evidence for the overall relationship: *'Managing risk and improving controls necessitates a risk culture audit.'* A lack of command over the environment and culture is frequently the source of control issues. For the time being, it appears that the BOD and the AC are content with a risk management system that is ineffective.

In summary, IA must be structured in such a way that the plan can be implemented. This strategy determines the structure of the IA department. Positioning and resources are two of the most important aspects of the organisational element. Some participants believe that resistance to capacity building and the cost of doing so are among the issues preventing them from positioning and resourcing efficiently and implementing the IA plan (R [9], R [11] and R [14]), which is consistent with the literature findings (Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012). If senior management and the supervisory board have established formal requirements that risk management be an integral part of the organisation's decision-making processes but refuse to put these requirements into action, it is difficult for the internal auditor, as claimed by a number of respondents.

5.2.2.2 Foundation factors which may affect IA (Q20–Q30)

Q20–Q30 assess the IA foundation factors, which are focused on key internal elements: (i) IA process (Q20, Q21), (ii) IA functions (Q22, Q23), (iii) IA practices (Q24, Q25, Q26, Q27), and (iv) IA effectiveness (Q28, Q29, Q30). The sub-sections that follow explore various categories associated with sub-themes.

Discussions started by investigating the process (IA_PRO) in the organisation (Q20). Then, each question focused on a key element of the theoretical framework as indicated above. Q21 investigated the importance of aligning the process of IA with the organisational vision (IA_ALIGN). Q22 investigated the IA functions that are implemented (IA_FUNCT) in the internal environment of IA, while Q23 examined the IA programmes (IA_PROGR). Similarly, Q24 and Q25 investigated the IA activities and nature of IA that are currently practiced in the organisation (IA_ACTIV) and (IA_NATURE1 and IA_NATURE2), respectively. Q26 determined the most effective IA practices (IA_EPRACT) and Q27 investigated the internal and external factors that might impede the good practices of IA (IA_IPRACT). Q28 addressed the issue of the greater effectiveness of IA in the organisation (IA_EFFECT) and Q29 investigated the nature of measuring the effectiveness of IA (IA_MEASURE). Finally, Q30 described the overall standards to achieve IA effectiveness within an organisation for protecting the governance control mechanisms (IA_STAND). The analysis of the interviewees' responses is explored in the following sub-sections.

5.2.2.2.1 Process of IA (Q20)

The aim of this question was to assess the effectiveness of the IA process in banking organisations (IA_PRO). However, the administration of IA is more concerned with achieving programme objectives than with the value gained from improvement actions. This results in

differences in the perceived value of IA, particularly at key stages of the process (Elliott, Dawson, and Edwards, 2007), where factors influencing auditees' change readiness after undergoing IA processes include audit information quality, organisational change and audit information accessibility (Kidron, Ofek and Cohen, 2016).

Figure 5.18: Process of IA

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.18 shows that 80.95% of respondents agreed that the IA process was effective (very effective/somewhat effective). R [12], R [13], R [14], R [17], R [20] and R [21] are among those who support the IA process's consensus idea. R [21] exemplifies culture as an aspect that is related to an organisation's strategic vision as well as its skills and knowledge. R [14] makes the following claim that *'the essential framework of the organisation, including documentation of the structure, the audit organisation and the necessary communication procedures, must be identified in the IA charter.'* Indeed, R [10] expresses a practical viewpoint from within their organisation: *'IA can play an important role in all stages of the corporate management process in terms of risk and control. Thus, the audit process model frequently includes all of the required steps of the corporate decision-making process.'*

Furthermore, R [12] emphasises the importance of having quality audit methodologies in conjunction with technology support and people, arguing that *'one of the primary aims of IA is to advance the risk strategy as well as to improve the overall performance and processes of the organisation.'* To summarise, the quotes above attribute adding value to the IA process by improving agility and more adaptable procedures, which necessitate a change in auditing methodologies as well as the implementation of new digital and technical tools in banking organisations.

5.2.2.2.2 Aligning IA process with the organisational vision (Q21)

The aim of this question was to assess the significance of aligning the IA process with the organisational vision in banking organisations (IA_ALIGN). While the audit approach to analysing organisational risks provides a pathway for change, it also introduces a risk-based approach to IA practices. If these risks materialise, they may have an impact on the operation of the IA process, the quality of control and the organisational vision. Demanding the identification and assessment of these risks during the audit process has resulted in the refinement of existing audit weaknesses or the development of new controls, both of which should improve audit quality (Ozaydin, 2010; Benli and Celayir, 2014).

Figure 5.19: Aligning IA process with the organisational vision

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.19 found that 48% of respondents claimed that it was 'very important' to align the IA process with the organisational vision. Following on, 'somewhat important' (38%) came next, then 'neutral' (9%) and 'slightly important' (5%) determinants came last.

In terms of the main determinant factors for aligning with the IA process, R [5] identifies an audit culture and a technique strategy as key pillars, recommending an optimised resource and stating that *'most organisations are unable to see how an analytic programme can change their audit culture and technique.'*

To accomplish this strategic aim, organisations need a variety of resources at their disposal such as integrating data and analytics. Moving on from audit culture and technique strategy, R [10] adds another point of view by stating that *'a control mechanism is in place to ensure*

its aims are met. These elements are made up of separate mechanisms used by individuals and processes within the organisation.

5.2.2.2.3 Improvement in IA functions (Q22)

The purpose of this question (IA_FUNCT) was to look at the IA functions currently in use in banking organisations and how they could be improved. While most organisations have embraced IA reforms ensuring independence and impartiality as well as incorporating IA into risk management, control and governance operations have become increasingly important. Based on the literature evidence, a high-quality IA function can improve the quality of financial reporting and audit efficiency (Al-Akra, Abdel-Qadera and Billahb, 2016; Gros, Koch and Wallek, 2017).

Figure 5.20: Improvement in IA functions

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.20 depicts a collection of findings that connect and interrelate different areas. Based on a set of four critical criteria, the IA functions that could be improved are as follows:

Competence and performance: 7.39% of respondents believed that a lack of competence and performance was impeding the advancement of the IA function. R [5] states the following:

The current system is insufficient to prevent fraud, adding that the procedures must be substantially rebuilt. This, however, does not, in my opinion, justify the addition of additional bureaucratic procedures. Instead, we should simplify things and promote education as well as use common sense. IA and risk management are frequently viewed as cost centres due to a lack of experience in these areas,

but this is a disaster. It doesn't matter how many stars you give an audit report if it isn't worth anything.

Implementation of processes and controls: 22.36% of respondents believed that processes and controls could be improved. R [11] refers to using appropriate strategies. While R [15] agrees and states the following:

Developing good processes and controls is the most difficult problem, some members of the group see even the most fundamental constraints as impediments to their incalculable consequences. They issued a warning about the regulatory-caused slowdown in operations. When politics assumes the role of government, this group invariably triumphs.

Monitoring: 45.91% of respondents agreed that a lack of monitoring has an impact on IA functions. While R [18] states that *'while IA functions should be linked to the overall strategy of the organisation, they should set KPIs based on their own special strategic objectives.'*

Digital transformation: 24.35% of respondents stated that their organisation has not undergone digital transformation. R [1] states that *'as the corporate environment evolves and technological advances, innovations and disruptions come in, IA needs to transition from a retrospective to a forward-looking function.'*

Furthermore, the above findings indicate that several of the issues raised in previous literature studies remain relevant (Section 2.4). Little thought has been given to how organisations' IA functions should be organised to ensure the independence of their auditors as part of the overall monitoring system. Surprisingly, most respondents were unconcerned about technological limitations. Also, R [8] and R [9] argues that IA should report administratively to the AC of the BOD and the organisation's CEO.

5.2.2.2.4 Efficiency of IA programmes (Q23)

The aim of this question was to determine the efficacy of IA programmes in banking organisations (IA_PROGR). The literature findings indicate that a variety of factors influence the quality of strategic project reports and their effectiveness in IA functions. The AC is interested in risk management reports, while executive management is interested in internal control reports (Eulerich, Kremin and Wood, 2019).

Figure 5.21: Efficiency of IA programmes

Source: The Researcher

Respondents' views on IA programmes, specifically how effective they are when implemented in organisations, are as follows: somewhat effective (61.90%), very effective (28.57%) and neutral (9.52%). R [2] emphasises that it is a tool for accountability. R [18] explains *'auditors can manage the testing requirements for engagements and avoid scope creep by using the audit programme as a guide and a fence.'* These observations demonstrate the importance of engagements in practice, and that due diligence and performing high-quality audits should help stakeholders gain confidence. When discussing audit preparation, R [21] emphasises that *'additional steps, such as creating a work schedule, were taken as part of the audit preparation. To carry out a specific audit task, an auditor must have access to a large amount of specialised and up-to-date information.'* R [16], who understands that developing digital platforms and programmes is a critical control, has a similar point of view.

There are some practical implications for improving IA procedures in the local corporate environment through the development of digital platforms and programmes, highlighting how IT environments necessitate attention to strategic risks while activating digitalisation mechanisms. The findings indicate that both the government and management must improve their efficiency and effectiveness. This is accomplished by identifying financial and operational weaknesses, system inadequacies and system deficiencies as well as investigating the causes of deviations from acceptable performance criteria. Thus, an incident response plan could be developed that specifies how people should react. R [5] emphasises the importance of standardising procedures and functions. Furthermore, a

strong internal control environment is an essential component of a structure that is well-designed and implemented and can help an organisation achieve its aims while also improving its overall operational effectiveness and efficiency.

5.2.2.2.5 IA activities (Q24)

The aim of this question (IA_ACTIV) was to investigate IA activities in banking organisations. Effective IA planning includes developing aims, activity schedules, personnel and budget planning, and activity reporting to maintain effective governance and operational efficiency. A comprehensive plan for the implementation and execution of IA activities is required to mitigate the effects of institutional, cultural and demographic factors (Nerantzidis *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 5.22: IA activities

Source: The Researcher

As illustrated in Figure 5.22, there is noticeable difference between the top IA activities. The three most frequently mentioned activities are assurance and compliance (30.69%), sharing best practices (24.26%) and risk-based assurance (17.08%). Three other IA activities were identified: financial statement fraud (11.88%), audit training and leadership (9.16%), and engagement outcome (6.93%).

The role of IA in corporate governance is concerned with the execution of economic operations and attempts to improve the rationality of these actions and associated controls (Mihret and Grant, 2017). Given that IA evolved as an internal business function for management focused on anti-fraud activities and financial transaction verification (Ramamoorti, 2003), R [13] suggests the following: *Failures in IA are frequently caused by*

a misalignment with the organisation's strategic vision. The alignment of IA with the organisation's overall strategy and business aims is a common issue.'

R [24] elaborates on this point: 'One of the most important aspects of an internal auditor's job is control. Internal control is the primary foundation for auditing, with all other audit activities serving as a backup to this risk.' Another activity for an organisation is to disseminate best practices. A closer examination of the data reveals that they are interconnected, as mentioned by R [13], R [15], R [19] and R [21]. Furthermore, R [21] supports this by stating the following:

Many recent corporate misstatements that have caused public outrage and brand damage, in my opinion, are the result of this imbalance. When IA or other assurance functions and business departments implement the strategy in disparate or misaligned ways, disaster is almost inevitable.

The above findings are intriguing because they corroborate various IA activities and demonstrate that there was a conceptual push to associate IA with risk management and internal control assurance, as well as to encourage ACs to rely on IA work when evaluating the effectiveness of internal controls (Boyle *et al.*, 2012).

5.2.2.2.6 The nature of IA (Q25)

The aim of this question (IA_NATURE) was to determine the type of IA used in banks. The findings are in line with the literature that the mandatory use of IA has resulted from consistency in application and compliance with standards, as well as the types of skills and competency requirements important for the practice of IA such as competition, increased communication and stakeholder expectations (Burnaby and Hass, 2011).

Figure 5.23: The nature of IA-1

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.23 illustrates that respondents believe the following about the nature of IA practices: requires improvement (47.62%), improved (28.57%), mandatory (14.29%) and inconsistent (9.52%). This means that 47.62% of organisations are facing some uncertainty, precisely due to the fact that effective implementation of quality frameworks and regulations contributes to more successful and measurable IA practice. Findings that demonstrate a positive relationship when using excellent practices, such as those obtained by R [11] and R [21], may differ from what is required by the rules that govern the IA profession. Similarly, R [18] employs an unidentified point of reference that could be supported in activating and measuring the IA functions.

Figure 5.24: The nature of IA-2

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.24 depicts four major IA practices that emerged as key drivers, including error and fraud prevention (37 percent%), technology development (27%), internal control processes (22%) and aligned assurance (14%). The prevention of errors and fraud appears to be the primary justification for implementing effective IA practices, with only minor differences between technology development and internal control processes. Data shows that internal control processes, as exemplified by R [15], must be considered effective in reducing errors and fraud. R [15] states that *'an established internal control process outlines financial transactions as well as administrative and management responsibilities. When procedures and protocols are well-defined, employees know what they are supposed to do and how to do it.'*

R [15] states that *'there is still ambiguity regarding the purpose, processes and activities of IA.'* This aligns with the perspectives of Lenz and Hahn (2015) and allows for a more in-

depth understanding and appreciation in practice. R [11] believes that each aspect influences the next and vice versa:

Governance processes are included in internal control and risk management systems. The traditional view of internal control and how it aids in the management of significant risks is more easily discussed than the more traditional approach, which holds that internal control exists to manage risk.

R [18] considers the consequences of a changing technological landscape: *'To remain relevant, organisations and auditors must be prepared to adapt to a constantly changing technological landscape. We must get rid of those who are unable to learn new skills or embrace technology.'*

The findings show that the aim of IA has remained consistent over time, with the exceptions of being broadened to increase organisational value, meeting a rise in stakeholder expectations and aligning with technological developments. Thus, stakeholder attitudes towards IA shifted from negative to respectful and appreciative. In this regard, organisations must ensure that IA strategies are aligned with risk assessments by evaluating the effectiveness of the IA programme while focusing on areas with the highest residual fraud risk and new or untested controls. The technology that underpins the audits should be scrutinised as well.

5.2.2.2.7 Effective IA practices (Q26)

The aim of this question (IA_EPRACT) was to investigate the areas that demonstrate the most effective IA practices in banking organisations. The use of a risk-based approach in audit engagement planning is significantly related to entity size in the financial sector and is more proactive in enterprise risk management (ERM) implementation (Castanheira, Rodrigues and Craig, 2010). Based on the literature findings, different common practices regarding potential ways of organising and integrating the IA function into organisational governance are identified, which extend the benefits and challenges for internal auditors in different organisational settings through a unique inside-view (Roussy, 2015; Roussy and Perron, 2018; Eulerich and Lenz, 2019).

Figure 5.25: Effective IA practices

Source: The Researcher

As shown in Figure 5.25, the risk-based IA plan (56.64%) appears to be attempting to create value by providing more efficient, effective and relevant audits. Respondents place emphasis on systematic process implementation (21.94%) and stating the organisation’s ability to combine many aspects, tactics and procedures while focusing on the areas that pose the most risk to customers, stakeholders, employees, the community and the environment. This relates to the IA governance and control review (8.04%) indicating that the expected internal controls are in place. Other areas, such as skills and resources (6.21%), independence (4.90%) and dealing with challenges (3.45%), had low response values.

In this case, identifying a risk universe is critical before developing an audit plan. However, the IA department’s aim is to use a risk-based auditing methodology to focus on the most critical risks to management. Despite the fact that the audit plan is typically based on an audit universe of departments or procedures, auditors frequently believe that it is risk-based. While R [18] further asserts that the risk-based IA plan is as follows:

The first step in risk-based auditing is a thorough evaluation and analysis of management’s most critical threats and vulnerabilities.... a thorough review of all audits on the plan aims to identify potential risks and provide management with information on how to mitigate them.

These findings highlight the multifaceted duties to anticipate and plan for risks because of the impartiality and experience that auditors bring to the table in terms of understanding an organisation’s operations, compliance and governance. One of the key expectations is that risks are effectively managed. When R [17] says, *they are better able to handle any area*

because of their years of expertise’, he makes an important point, and also states: ‘Auditor, HR/collection manager and operations manager are just a few of the positions I’ve worked in.’

R [21] believes that the BOD and the AC must provide adequate support: *‘When developing a risk-based IA plan, the auditor should consider two risk elements: specific events or risks and how they may affect the achievement of the organisation’s objectives, and generic risk variables that may signal a higher or lower degree of risk.’* This confirms R [4]’s viewpoint of *‘audit findings’*, and echoes a far more moderate expectation: *‘IA should currently be staffed with a diverse group of qualified, technically capable, knowledgeable and skilled auditors with sufficient organisational knowledge to analyse and integrate audit findings.’*

To conclude, R [19] supports the implementation of a systematic process by stating that *‘the BOD and the AC would want to ensure that the procedure is followed in a systematic manner.’* In contrast to the literature, which discusses the difficult task of ensuring effective IA practices (Section 2.6 and Sub-Section 3.3.2.2), the empirical findings reveal a difference that delegates and sets expectations through the establishment of a roadmap for effective practices.

5.2.2.2.8 Factors that hinder good IA practices (Q27)

The purpose of this question was to identify internal and external factors that may impede good IA practices in banking organisations (IA_IPRACT). Consistent with the literature findings, increased IA involvement in evaluating financial reporting leads to improved financial reporting quality. However, internal auditors participate in ERM assurance tasks, but some also engage in activities that may undermine objectivity (Zain, Subramaniam and Stewart, 2006; Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema, 2012).

Table 5.5: Factors that hinder good IA practices

Theme	Sub-themes	Sub-theme description	Frequency	Relative frequency
Internal factors (74.05%)	Control	Lack of quality in systems	9	11.25%
	Decision	Biased decisions	10	3.75%
	Governance	Poor compliance and standards	8	13.74%
	Operation	Operational responsibilities	9	12.34%
	Process	Lack of effective implementation	1	1.25%
	Quality	Effects and continuous improvement	6	7.34%
	Resource	Skills, experience and technical	2	6.41%
	Risks	Strategic objectives and risks	7	12.34%
	Strategy	Lack of sufficient alignment	3	5.63%
	External factors	Government	Regulations	1
Outsourcing		Assurance providers	1	9.38%

External factors (25.95%)	Regulatory	Regulatory consequences	6	1.88%
	Standards	Regulatory bodies	6	6.72%
Total	13 Sub-themes		Sub-themes frequency= 69	Total= 100%

Source: The Researcher

Table 5.5 reveals that poor compliance and standards (13.74%) are among the most significant factors impeding good IA practices, followed by the next five that are operational responsibilities (12.34%), strategic objectives and risks (12.34%), a lack of quality in control systems (11.25%), assurance providers (9.38%) and regulations (7.97%). R [15] states the following are important factors that impede good IA practices: *'In my opinion, IA is primarily concerned with enforcing compliance and fails to recognise the significance of conducting an independent risk assessment to guide its audit strategies.'* R [13] provides a systematic viewpoint by stating that *'internal processes and procedures must be in place to deal with the identified risk. These errors must be identified for corrective action to be taken'*, whereas quality and continuous improvement are classified by R [13] and R [19] where *'IA can be used to combat fraud in ways that are beyond the scope of IA.'*

The evidence seeks to demonstrate the difficult challenge for the IA department to become valuable in the organisation by making effective contributions that exceed compliance requirements. This can be achieved by establishing a knowledge centre to collect information and provide invaluable insights about the IA. In addition to thoroughly understanding the key processes and systems, IA should be aware of any new changes within the organisation on a regular basis through effective informal communication with the BOD and the AC. Another critical step is to document quality standards and share them with organisations that can benefit from them. IA can use this knowledge to help audit leaders become more knowledgeable about emerging risks, gain insights into solutions to deal with them and reduce biased decisions.

The notion that audit findings and recommendations are detrimental to a banking organisation's success is the root cause of biased decisions. Therefore, it is crucial for the IA department to recognise that success is not measured by the issues that IA explores but by the useful information provided regarding controls and risks to help banking organisations achieve their objectives. Although internal auditors may have a biased self-assessment that is less valuable in gaining acceptance and relevance, it is essential for stakeholders to appreciate the service rendered by internal auditors. To achieve this, internal auditors must

be proactive and repetitive in communicating that the entire organisation benefits when the IA is allowed to operate with independence and objectivity.

Internal auditor’s efficiency is enhanced when they possess the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to perform their responsibilities. In addition, it is necessary to understand the factors leading to top management bias in accounting entitlements, as well as how they can be moderated and eliminated (Abdulhussein, Al-Refiay and Wahhab, 2023). Furthermore, independence is a vital aspect of internal auditors' work, as it enables them to carry out their duties objectively and without bias, protects the validity and reliability of their work, and ensures that they can perform their responsibilities without interference from personal, financial, or departmental biases (Parves and Bhuyan, 2023). The evidence of this research confirms that biased decisions are a significant obstacle to good IA practices, and respondents perceive them as biased as they are within the organisation that provides IA services. Therefore, it is essential to decide whether to perform IA of risk culture separately. However, respondents recommended that integrating risk culture audits into every audit could help mitigate some of these biases.

5.2.2.2.9 Effectiveness of IA (Q28)

The purpose of this question was to address the issue of increased IA effectiveness in banking organisations (IA_EFFECT). Internal auditors’ ability to speak up, particularly in contentious situations, deserves more consideration in the behavioural dimension, which includes conflict and discomfort as highly significant factors in IA effectiveness (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010; Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Lenz, 2013). Furthermore, the data in Figure 5.26 is thematically consistent with systematic research findings that reveal trends in IA effectiveness (Sub-Section 2.4.1), whereas Quadrant III (implementation, Table 3.2) alludes to effectiveness and practical implementation.

Figure 5.26: Effectiveness of IA

Source: The Researcher

Understanding risk and risk maturity (23.28%), developing assurance activities (19.74%), improving the purpose and value of IA (16.72%), improving IT skills and experience (15.60%), and addressing strategic focus (11.64%) are among the most important key issues identified for greater effectiveness. These sub-themes also emerged when lower values emerged such as improving access and engagement (7.59%) and changing organisational culture and attitude (5.43%).

R [18] believes that effectiveness adds value to investments, whereas others, such as R [21], believe that effectiveness, in addition to meeting organisational objectives, ensures the upkeep of regulations and standards. This is consistent with the findings of the literature, specifically Sub-Section 2.4.1. R [2] suggests the following in this regard: *'I believe you need practice counsel from an experienced audit executive, the moments of truth in an auditor's life and the audit cycle in order to make better decisions and appreciate how important IA is.'*

R [11] makes the case for organisational culture and attitude, stating the following:

There is a lot of rapid change and evolution going on, and only the most forward-thinking audit professionals should be able to adapt to the shifting landscape. You may fail if you do not have a long-term vision. Internal auditors must be able to predict the weather rather than simply reporting on it when it occurs.

The findings contribute to a better understanding of risk and risk maturity through more structured risk-based auditing. Reduced proclivity to falsify financial information and potential risks, improved access, and engagement with financial reporting quality are all consistent with those found in the literature, implying that IA should be more able to ensure that identified risks associated with strategic activities are adequately managed (Lenz and Hahn, 2015; Abidin, 2017).

5.2.2.2.10 Measuring IA effectiveness (Q29)

The purpose of this question was to investigate the nature of measuring the effectiveness of IA in banking organisations (IA_MEASURE). In order to measure the IA's effectiveness, the Researcher conducted three steps, which is in line with the literature, the first step being the identification of common themes in the literature, the development of a theoretical framework consisting of internal and external factors and the consideration of promising to improve IA's value proposition (Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

Figure 5.27: Measuring IA effectiveness

Source: The Researcher

Respondents were asked to share their thoughts on the nature of measuring effectiveness. This included a summary of perspectives on the causes of IA effectiveness and their potential relationship to organisational performance (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). While the cost of IA is easy to calculate, evaluating its benefits is more difficult due to the fact that IA findings can have both direct and indirect consequences. However, when it comes to effectiveness, more than half of the respondents (57.14%) rate their practices as somewhat positive and 28.57% rate them as very positive. After considering the options, R [11] concludes that *'the number of audits undertaken or the number of concerns discovered should not be used to determine the success of an IA.'*

While 4.76% respondents were neutral, R [14] and R [15] emphasises the importance of ensuring that individuals understand processes, particularly IA recommendations. After determining that IA effectiveness varies, R [18] evaluates IA recommendations by stating that *'employee discipline and management's willingness to implement audit recommendations are critical to an organisation's long-term success. Writing fair and useful suggestions, persuading an organisation's management to adopt these recommendations and monitoring their implementation are all tasks of an audit.'* Only 9.52% of those polled oppose measuring IA effectiveness. R [21] claim that *'it is not the auditors' responsibility if employees and management of an organisation refuse to accept the auditors' advice.'*

Consistent with the literature findings, IA quality and management support have a significant impact on audit effectiveness, whereas organisational setting and auditee characteristics have little impact, which is consistent with previous research (Mihret and Yismaw, 2007). The presence of these effects demonstrates a link between IA and bank performance in

terms of operational efficiency, organisational growth, higher profitability, solvency and organisational continuity (Omolaye and Jacob, 2017).

5.2.2.2.11 Standards for IA effectiveness (Q30)

This question sought to identify the standards for achieving IA effectiveness in protecting governance control mechanisms in banking organisations (IA_STAND). This would imply that the IA's ability to foster effective monitoring has improved, and that top management support is the primary determinant of IA effectiveness for organisational independence (Cohen and Sayag, 2010).

Figure 5.28: Standards for IA effectiveness

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.28 illustrates that 38.10% of respondents thought the standards were evolved in control governance but only partially implemented across departments, while 33.33% claimed the standards were mature in control governance embedded at the organisational level. Only 14.29% reported robust control governance, 9.52% developed but not yet implemented across the organisation and 4.76% reported control governance that was in its early stages of development. R [6] state that *'internal controls are an essential component of any strategy for improving corporate governance in general, reducing risks and ensuring consistent financial transparency. There appears to be widespread agreement on the importance of safeguarding governance control mechanisms.'*

Furthermore, R [18] supports and justifies this finding: *'Even if there is.....no legal or professional requirement to do so, which would imply all information is treated with the utmost care whatever the circumstances.'* R [1] introduces another point of view on implementation: *'In order to address both the higher-risk and lower-risk issues, audit steps should be grouped in descending order as needed and as time permits.'*

R [3] comments on the robustness in control governance: *'The audit scope of responsibility can include programmes, procedures, information systems, geographical locations, products, services and general ledger accounts.'* Professional proficiency, organisational independence and career advancement were discovered to have a significant relationship with IA effectiveness, contrary to the popular belief that audit quality is typically compromised due to compliance with international auditing standards and local audit legislation (Tackie, Marfo-Yiadom and Achina, 2016; Yeboah, 2020). Findings also discovered that independence, objectivity and management support, as well as the use of the IA function as a management training ground, all have an impact on the effectiveness of IA (Dellai and Omri, 2016; Huong, 2018; Musah, Gapketor and Anokye, 2018).

5.2.2.3 Integration factors which may affect IA (Q31–Q41)

The integration factors involved identifying how key internal environments influence attaining the IBA framework in banks. To this end, three main internal IA integration elements were specified by the theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4): (i) IA role and profession (Q31, Q32, Q33), (ii) IA policy and framework (Q34, Q35, Q36, Q37), and (iii) IA structure and reporting (Q38, Q39, Q40, Q41). For clarity purposes, the various categories of these elements are considered, and sub-themes are outlined in the following sub-sections.

Discussions started by investigating how important it is to monitor the measurement of IA roles and performances in the respondents' organisation (IA_MROLE) (Q31). Then, each question focused on a key element of the theoretical framework as indicated above. Q32 investigated the existence of the IA profession to facilitate organisational expansion (IA_POE) of the internal IA environment, while Q33 examined the status of tracking IA competencies and reporting performance (IA_TRACK). Similarly, Q34 and Q35 investigated use of the IA policy manual, including clear implementation guidelines (IA_POLICY) and any professional IA framework the organisation follows (IA_FRAME). Q36 and Q37 examined whether the current framework meets the IA requirements (IA_FRAMEREQ) and whether the organisation has not implemented an IA framework (IA_FRAMENOT). Q38 investigated IA's contribution towards success and delivery of its strategic priorities (IA_CONTR). Q39 explored how IA can be sustained in the long term (IA_SUSTAIN) and Q40 investigated the most significant future challenges in the implementation of IA (IA_FCHAL) (Q40). Finally, Q41 focused on the greatest change for organisations in coming years (IA_FORECAST). The analysis of the interviewees' responses is elaborated in the following sub-sections.

5.2.2.3.1 Measuring IA roles and performance (Q31)

The aim of this question was to determine the importance of tracking the measurement of IA roles and performance in banking organisations (IA_MROLE). R [21] makes a similar point to R [9], who emphasises consensus when it comes to performance measurement. Giving internal auditors, for example, the opportunity to develop the variety of skills required to carry out audit activities as part of the IA transformation process is critical, with a focus on the ability to detect potential risks and strategies to manage and mitigate them.

Figure 5.29: Measuring IA roles and performance

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.29 illustrates that 67% of respondents claimed it was very important for monitoring and measuring roles and performance, while another 33% reported it was somewhat important. A potential explanation for respondents' resistance to monitoring the measurement of roles and performance could be found in gaps in poor structural and functional arrangements (Christopher, 2019), and exploring this resistance could compromise or manipulate the role. Misalignment between the role and evaluation, on the other hand, leads to difficulty in assessing tasks clearly enough to act in a specialised capacity (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011), and refraining from taking on operational responsibilities and practice variation (Arena and Jeppesen, 2016).

Several studies have investigated the factors that are thought to influence the decision to monitor the roles and performance. While R [9] states that in order to be successful in measuring the roles, *'prior to becoming an internal auditor, I was responsible for financial and operational controls that were linked to internal policies and specific external threats.'* This indicates that it is uncommon, well-thought-out, hidden, time-evolving and typically unorganised, and it could be implemented in a variety of ways. To summarise the findings,

auditors should be able to analyse massive amounts of data using new technology instead of relying on the traditional sampling method. Internal auditors should be able to go beyond financial reporting to include advancements in data analytics, artificial intelligence and cyber security.

5.2.2.3.2 Existence of the IA profession (Q32)

The aim of this question was to determine the existence of the IA profession, which supports the growth of organisations in the banking sector (IA_POE). Regulatory interventions that encourage the expansion of internal controls and risk management, in addition to governance measures, have a significant impact on the evolution of the IA profession (Power, 2004; 235. Park, Lee and Kim, 2019). To contribute to long-term strategic value, the IA profession must focus on progressive assurance services, governance, risk management and control processes (Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

Figure 5.30: Existence of the IA profession

Source: The Researcher

Concerning the question of how the existence of the IA profession facilitates organisational growth, a key understanding was that 33.72% of respondents reported concerns about compliance monitoring of operational controls. Coordination and reliance were mentioned by 23.46% of respondents, making it the second most influential thematic category in terms of organisational expansion. Despite differing research perspectives, it is argued that a consolidation of IA and its core function of assurance, with the aim of establishing IA as a profession, has been identified and is consistent with the literature (Lenz and Sarens, 2012). For instance, key themes extracted also included strategy implementation (17.63%), quality assurance and improvement (15.64%) and fraud auditing fieldwork (9.55%). R [1] asserts

that ‘from the start, the best internal auditors understand that they are dealing with people as well as processes and systems.’

R [7] takes knowledge and experience into account, as ‘internal auditors must use a friendly tone when reporting their findings to upper management. By sharing our knowledge and experience in this area, we can help make things go more smoothly.’ Everyone involved in the audit should understand that the primary aim of the audit is to improve rather than to ‘name and shame’ individuals under investigation. It is critical to communicate to auditees that they are free to express their opinions throughout the audit to the top management. Overall, R [15] provides converging evidence for the auditee relationship by stating the following:

The auditees should be made aware of the issues you’ve identified and given specific instructions on how to correct any non-conformances or close out the observations you’ve identified. Because the audit is not confidential, you should make it clear to the auditees that they are free to peruse your notes and results.

5.2.2.3.3 Tracking status of IA (Q33)

The purpose of this question was to clarify the concept of tracking IA competencies and reporting IA performance in banking organisations (IA_TRACK). The literature findings are based on IA trends and practices as well as in-depth perspectives on the skills and competencies required and the potential for additional IA skill development (Chersan, 2016). The IA’s reporting channels are extremely unclear, and multiple reporting channels such as the BOD and AC, have the potential to divide the IA’s loyalties (Beasley *et al.*, 2009).

Figure 5.31: Tracking status of IA

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.31 depicts the current state of organisational competencies for reporting performance. More than half of respondents reported the status as somewhat mature (52.38%) indicating that it is optimised for organisational needs. Surprisingly, only 4.76% of respondents believe they are fully mature (i.e. fully optimised). In comparison, 42.86% of respondents believed their organisations were slightly mature, having been implemented but not fully integrated. Consistent with the literature, the findings indicate that both input-based and output-based measures are founded on observations where the embedding process has to be managed effectively. As R [12] responds, *'IA is increasingly concerned with the organisation's total risk management, ensuring that each department has the policies, procedures, organisational structure and governance in place to manage risk effectively and to support organisational value.'*

R [20] regards their organisation as mature. While IA is undeniably beneficial, determining how much value is added is never easy. Input-based measures, for example, clearly have limitations in that they assume but do not demonstrate value addition. Output-based metrics, on the other hand, face their own set of challenges due to trailing indicators. As a quality assurance activity, IA provides a sense of security while also highlighting any issues with an organisation's processes. R [8] and R [11] define their organisations' IA competencies as semi-mature, optimised for organisational needs but not completely optimised for the organisations' needs. R [20] asserts the following: *'Although IA is influenced by regulatory and legal considerations, organisational expectations and competition, they must be adaptable in order to meet the organisation's aims as well as professional competency criteria.'*

R [17] contributes to the discussion by stating the following:

Because of this relationship, auditing can maintain some independence from the organisation and its management. It could be used to ensure that management responds to critical discoveries as soon as possible. It is the primary means by which we communicate critical information to the entire BOD as well as the audit committee.

Each of these respondents' points of view adds significantly to understand the current state of competency monitoring for reporting performance in the banking sector. The literature, on the other hand, emphasises the importance of filling management gaps through a wide

range of personal and organisational talents that are constantly strengthened and developed into essential skills and knowledge.

5.2.2.3.4 IA policy manual and implementation guidelines (Q34)

The purpose of this question was to determine whether or not an organisation has IA policy and implementation guidance in the banking sector (IA_POLICY).

Figure 5.32: IA policy manual and implementation guidelines

Source: The Researcher

The respondents (100%) have claimed that the IA policy manual and implementation guidelines were followed, as shown in Figure 5.32. Based on the literature, findings illustrate that the relationship between IA and the AC is critical in ensuring that no levels of the organisation below the BOD obstruct essential activities or appropriate decisions that expand organisational possibilities and reduce risks. In contrast, an active and educated AC provides the ultimate independent and objective examination of the corporate control environment. R [7] and R [21] recommend that the IA policy manual be evaluated and assessed on a regular basis to reduce challenges. R [3] supports this point of view by stating the following: *'IA policy is the AC's primary source of information for carrying out its mandates and obligations. These departments must work together in ensuring financial reporting integrity in light of increased responsibilities scrutiny.'*

This necessitates the involvement of the executive branch. R [4] states that the only way to achieve IA policy and manual implementation was with executive-level support, but R [18] believed that *'internal auditors should not be required to report to multiple levels of management, as this may undermine or dilute recommendations and their implementation.'*

5.2.2.3.5 Professional IA framework (Q35)

The aim of this question was to understand if the professional IA framework (IA_FRAME) was used in banking organisations. Based on the literature findings, IA practices in developing countries converge to best practices faster than in developed countries (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011). The approval of a specific framework for the banking sector was an unexpected finding. R [2], R [19] and R [21] endorsed the new Basel III regulations to strengthen bank resilience. Similarly, the Basel III regulations reduce the risk of bank defaults and improve financial soundness in times of potential financial distress, as indicated in Sub-Section 3.2.3.4.

Figure 5.33: Professional IA framework

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.33 illustrates that 67% of respondents reported they do not apply a professional framework, while 33% claimed they do, implying a lack of enforcement and emphasising the research gap on implementing the dynamic framework. R [9] emphasises the importance of an effective framework: *'An effective IA framework's ability to build and maintain solid connections throughout an organisation is critical to its success in becoming more transactional, putting long-term efficacy in jeopardy, and I'm concerned about this trend in banks.'*

In contrast to empirical findings, the literature primarily represents the IPPF in developed countries (IIA, 2018). The factors that contribute to IA success differ depending on the region and/or organisation, and there is no one-size-fits-all approach (Chambers, 2015; Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen, 2018). Literature findings elaborates on a comprehensive framework based on stakeholders' perceptions of the factors of IA effectiveness as well as an examination of how these determinants interact with one another in response to internal and external environmental changes (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020), R [11] further added:

As the risk landscape shifts and shuffles, the IA department is under increasing pressure to be everything to everyone. We must be adaptable, data-savvy, tech-savvy, financially and non-financially aware, highly emotional and capable of assisting our stakeholders in monitoring and reforming organisational culture in order to succeed in today's environment.

To summarise, banking organisations are vulnerable to fraud, regardless of size or location, in the context of Bangladesh, because they do not implement a dynamic IA framework. It also makes no distinction between public and private organisations based on their activities, environmental impact, sustainability or number of years in operation. The banking sector may be more vulnerable because it cannot afford the most effective safeguards or devote sufficient resources to fraud prevention and detection.

5.2.2.3.6 IA framework requirements (Q36)

This question aimed to identify how current frameworks meet the IA requirements in banking sector organisations (IA_FRAMEREQ). Considering the significance of establishing an effective framework for banks in Bangladesh, it is imperative to investigate the efficacy of requirements employed to devise and execute key elements for strategic implementation.

Figure 5.34: IA framework requirements

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.34 shows that only 4.76% of respondents believe their current framework is very effective, despite the fact that a dynamic framework is still needed. Despite a sizable proportion of respondents claiming that this question was irrelevant to them (66.67%) due to the previous question, 28.57% claimed it was somewhat effective. Increasing the

dynamism of the effective framework may be viewed as an opportunity for the IA to be held accountable. R [17] had the following response:

There is always a cost-benefit trade-off when it comes to internal controls and framework implementation; they must be practical, helpful, viable and compatible with both operational and control aims. As long as resources are involved, there may be a trade-off between the benefits and costs of any legislation.

Returning to dynamism, R [3], R [15] and R [16] argue that framework revision is critical. R [16] holds the following beliefs:

Management has been looking for ways to improve the management of the organisations they oversee since the dawn of time. Internal controls have been implemented to ensure that the organisation is on track to meet its financial objectives and fulfil its mission as well as to avoid any unexpected events. As the economic climate shifts, consumer expectations and ambitions shift, necessitating reorganisation for future growth.

In conclusion, in today's rapidly changing environment, the dynamic framework demanded by IA is critical for ensuring congruence between strategic vision and mentality. The IA department's engagement with stakeholders can be improved by maintaining or boosting the IA framework's vitality.

5.2.2.3.7 Barriers to implement IA framework (Q37)

The purpose of this question was to determine why organisations in the banking sector did not implement the IA framework (IA_FRAMENOT). Literature findings indicate that internal auditors face greater challenges in maintaining independence and adhering to established rules and regulations in the public sector than those in the private sector (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). This indicates that effective compliance monitoring is critical to implementing an effective framework.

Figure 5.35: Barriers to implement IA framework

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.35 illustrates that 66.67% of respondents reported they use Bangladesh Auditing Standards (BAS) and current ICCD guidelines provided by BB to assess the effectiveness of internal controls and compliance. These findings suggest that the IA framework should involve important strategic issues, with most interviewees believing that the IA framework implementation should be included in the IA strategy due to its independence, and may cause management to change policy requirements in some critical areas. To that end, R [1] asserts the following:

Risk management and governance are the only areas of contribution that are discouraging. Because advisory services can be applied to all other areas of contribution, I would prioritise governance, performance (efficiency and effectiveness), internal controls and risk management. Productivity and quality control include advice on governance structures, administration and monitoring of internal control systems, and evaluation and improvement of risk management processes.

To summarise the findings, there is a gap in the literature (discussed in Sub-Section 3.2.1), that should be filled by emphasising the easily understandable and measurable IA framework, which can be implemented with practical guidance in the banking sector.

5.2.2.3.8 IA contributions to the strategic priorities (Q38)

The aim of this question was to identify factors that contribute to the success and delivery of IA's strategic priorities in banking organisations (IA_CONTR). The findings of the literature

indicate that compliance auditing is more common than value-added auditing, which focuses on the aims and strategies pursued by organisations as well as the level of risk they face in order to shape the characteristics of a value-adding IA department. The quality of strategic planning influences the extent to which an adequate value-added profile is achieved (Mihret and Woldeyohannis, 2008).

Figure 5.36: IA contributions to the strategic priorities

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.36 shows that 29.17% respondents identified information and communication as the critical priorities to ensure successful IA integration. R [18] elaborates on the significance of information and communication by stating the following:

While I agree that the BOD, management and IA all play important roles, I also believe that the efforts of all of these groups should be directed towards achieving the organisation's aims. Effective coordination, teamwork and communication are required for workplace effectiveness.

R [17] states a similar observation: *'IA performance should not be defined by the number of audits completed or the number of issues discovered. Furthermore, the eyes of a satisfied customer are the best indicators of the quality and effectiveness of IA work.'*

Figure 5.36 shows that 17.68% of respondents viewed innovative audit delivery and change as important success factors, followed by compliance focus (17.18%), integrated risk evaluation and monitoring (16.19%), and governance and control weakness (11.87%). Aligning IA activities with the organisation's strategy and objectives (7.42%) and business resilience (0.49%) ranked last on the list of strategic priorities. R [6] discusses the

importance of rules and regulations by stating that *'I agree that IA must operate within a set of rules and regulations in order to generate value.'*

Furthermore, the term 'success' should be defined in terms of the contribution of IA to the organisation's long-term profitability and expansion. Responsible business management and protecting shareholders' interests may be strong success indicators and IA can help make this happen. The findings regarding rule and regulation compliance are consistent with Chambers (2015), who state that there may be a problem if an organisation's success is used to measure IA success. However, as long as basic audit principles are not jeopardised, the sandbox strategy is the most effective because it allows management to use different business models to achieve success; thus, IA is one area that benefits from this.

5.2.2.3.9 Sustainability of IA (Q39)

This question attempted to identify key IA areas that needed to be investigated in order for the banking sector to sustain IA over time (IA_SUSTAIN). The findings indicate that IA develops and consolidates organisational relevance by activating IA effectiveness at the same time (Lenz, Sarens and D'Silva, 2014), resulting in organisational learning and transformation. In contrast, new IA effectiveness drivers have emerged from the IA field (Roussy, Barbe and Raimbault, 2019).

Figure 5.37: Sustainability of IA

Source: The Researcher

Figure 5.37 illustrates that there was an agreement among interviewees that the innovative IA department (23.87%), fraud prevention and detection (22.07%), technical skills, knowledge and capabilities (20.87%) and integrated financial reporting (17.27%) are all supporting areas that need review for sustainable IA. R [18] discusses further the importance

of technical skills, knowledge, and capabilities, and reports that *‘technology, an understanding of disruptions in business and new inventions must be necessary for internal auditors to identify risks and support management in building appropriate mitigation measures.’* R [13], with the same view, states that *‘some significant developments have taken place in the way that the profession has changed the way it produces value, and this has caused IA to reconsider the way it has worked and provided its services.’*

This argument is further delineated in the quotation from R [21]: *‘The lack of hands-on technological expertise is a major challenge. Auditors, particularly in large organisations that have gone digital, must improve their skills and knowledge in order to be effective.’*

Figure 5.37 also illustrates that aligning and measuring IA effectiveness (9.46%) and ethical and professional development (6.46%) are also factors in IA integration. A closer look at the data indicates that they are intertwined with one another, as stated by R [4], [5], [13] and [16]. Additionally, R [19] substantiates this by stating the following:

Data analytics skills are a must-have for auditors. This is not an issue for the younger generation, as they have grown up in a digital world. However, there are still many traditional auditors who have lacked with the digital skills in today’s organisational environment.

An innovative IA department is necessary according to the majority of the respondents. R [20] shares a similar view, asserting that *‘IA is increasingly moving into the digital platform and becoming a major strategic partner in the organisation. Digitising audits has been widely acknowledged as a necessary step in order to deal with challenges such as cost savings and logistics.’*

5.2.2.3.10 Future challenges of IA (Q40)

This question attempted to highlight the most significant future challenges in the banking sector’s IA (IA_FCHAL) implementation. Based on the literature, IA is hampered by a lack of manpower and top management support, while auditors rarely cooperate, resulting in difficult situations. Although the size of the AC and the presence of a separate risk management committee promote IA sustainability in the financial sector, auditor knowledge and training on effective auditing procedures are limited (Ahmad *et al.*, 2009; Alhajri, 2017).

Figure 5.38: Future challenges of IA

Source: The Researcher

IT systems and technological risks (43.22%) may be the most significant future challenges confronting the banking sector. Other important themes identified in these responses include adapting to new strategies (15.97%), financial and regulatory resilience (14.23%) and commercial awareness (12.35%). Respondents also indicated quality control culture and process (7.38%) and relocating audit resources (6.85%) as future challenges. R [18] is convinced that *'delegating risk assessment responsibility to the AC is analogous to delegating responsibility for quality control and assurance to the AC. Risk management is usually done too late and at an inconvenient pace.'*

Consistent with the literature, R [1] and [21] state that the process of identifying, evaluating and managing IT systems and technology risks should begin as soon as a decision is made. Organisations, in the face of uncertainty, always require risk-adjusted decisions. R [5], R [11] and R [14] all agree on this precise adaptation to new strategies. With the increased need to leverage technology, IA is able to perform more valuable and higher-level tasks, which increases its visibility within the organisation. R [21] holds the belief that this requires executive-level support, and this view is found in the literature, where it is believed that executive-level support is the only way to overcome future challenges (Deloitte, 2021).

Furthermore, R [20] suggests that technical skills, knowledge and capabilities as well as a labour shortage have the following effect:

IA departments are confronted with a number of challenges, and the profession as whole faces even more. Some of them contain both opportunities and barriers.

IA positions, for example, have become increasingly difficult to fill, resulting in salary increases for many practitioners.

Policies on digital technologies are another factor that could cause issues for the banking sector. R [15] explains that *'IA methods in an IT environment can be improved through the use of new digital technologies and the acquisition of knowledge and skills that are compatible with the use of these technologies.'* When the benefits of internal controls are deemed to be less than the actual resources, IT systems and technology risks may also be regarded as impediments (Protiviti, 2021). Similarly, R [3] and R [21] believe that IA procedures must evolve to keep up with the increasing reliance on technology, which benefits from both efficiency gains and greater insights into the organisation, enhancing its value perception and trustworthiness.

5.2.2.3.11 IA predictions/forecasts (Q41)

This question aimed to focus on the greatest change of IA for organisations in the banking sector (IA_FORECAST). Some banking organisations are planning much more digitisation, but the challenges are expected to be artificial intelligence, automation, cloud-based platforms, cyber security and audit plans, which must support organisations' control and risk maturity. R [11], R [15], R [19] and R [21] agree that the integration of skills, knowledge and competency must become more integrated and efficient. As advocated by R [20] and R [21], this entails the prediction of increased community and environmental sustainability among both users and organisations.

Figure 5.39: IA predictions/forecasts

Source: The Researcher

The importance in changing and improving technological advancement is impact positively, which is emphasised by R [7]: *'Data analytics may be a valuable tool for internal auditors as the technology landscape continues to evolve and we move much further into a digital world.'*

Another question R [11] and R [8] asks is whether increased government policies and bank priorities result in advancements in IA practices. R [11] further concluded *'perhaps it is necessary to have a strong organisational culture that supports risk management, compliance and IA. If these elements are missing, internal auditors are unlikely to receive support for audit findings.'*

Another promising trend was the framework's implementation and implementation-driven initiatives. R [4] believes that increasing automation, cyber security and audit plans must fill gaps in IA, allowing organisations to become more agile. In support of this, R [5] states that *'internal auditors may rely on someone's word that something is being done correctly rather than conduct a poll and verify it because they know the people, they are auditing. Internal personnel who were present every day but failed to notice that policy violations were common.'*

On the other hand, R [2] believes that it is not always be possible to automate everything. R [21] contends this view and states that *'investing in an organisation that has a high-quality audit offers investors and other stakeholders' peace of mind that the organisation's financial statements are accurate and reliable, allowing them to make well-informed decisions.'*

Risk maturity helps to identify, assess and manage risk actively and systematically (Betti and Sarens, 2020; Lenz and Hoos, 2023). This ability can be measured by how well banking organisations understand and address potential risks that may impact on operations, reputation and financial stability. For instance, a low level of risk maturity may result in an internal auditor performing a risk assessment to determine the scope of audit engagement, which can be a time-consuming and costly approach. By contrast, a high level of risk maturity enables an IA to provide assurance on the risk management process and use the outcome of the process to plan audit engagement (Coetzee and Lubbe, 2013). Achieving risk maturity is crucial for banking organisations because it enables them to navigate uncertainties effectively, develop robust risk management frameworks, and foster a culture of proactive risk awareness. Banks can better prepare for and manage potential risks by enhancing resilience in dynamic business environments. R [19] emphasised that *'instances of risk maturity may involve senior management being aware of major issues or significant risks;*

however, these risks are not formally captured to determine whether they are on the organisation's risk radar'. Therefore, it is essential for banking organisations to strive for risk maturity to ensure long-term success.

In summary, regardless of the size of the IA team, their skills or competencies, the use of digitisation is critical and unavoidable in the banking sector. Recent developments provide an even greater opportunity for robust auditing as well as industry insights on how digitisation solutions can enhance IA by building good relationships with senior management and peers before and after the audit process, which may be instrumental and indispensable when rendering effective IA services that truly matter. Finally, by using a communication protocol as stakeholder mapping, it systematically maps out stakeholders and ensures frequent and timely interaction.

5.3 Conclusion

This chapter was composed to demonstrate the need for an IBA framework in the banking sector through thematic data analysis, which is unique to the nature and purpose of this research. In this regard, this chapter collected and analysed qualitative interview data by investigating current IA challenges based on the research questions posed in Section 1.6. There is a lack of strategic alignment of IA with key banking auditing challenges, a strong institutional environment within the framework of IA in the context of developing countries, and a lack of clear practical guidance that considers the needs and implications of banking organisations, as presented in the concluding part of Chapter 2. However, this chapter builds on the theoretical IBA framework established in Section 3.4 by developing semi-structured questions to validate the framework's key elements.

This empirical part of the research focused on respondents and organisations with the aim of gaining a deeper insight into the nature of IA challenges in the banking sector where the respondents work. Both the interview findings and the SLR (Chapters 2 and 3) agreed on the importance of the IBA framework and its critical elements in influencing IA in banks. Based on the qualitative findings in this chapter, key IA challenges must be addressed by focusing on emerging risks, establishing internal control processes, addressing key risks and control issues, aligning strategic vision and mindsets, and integrating the IA process with the organisational vision. The research evidence also suggests that each element of the proposed theoretical IBA framework investigates and confronts significant challenges, implications and phrases of implementation in the context of banks, which are discussed in detail in the following Chapter 6.

Furthermore, this chapter takes a systematic approach to investigating the three key pillars such as IA input factors, IA foundation and IA integration of the IBA framework by evaluating and validating them appropriately with practical implementation guidance as discussed in Chapter 6. Initially, 41 interview questions were developed, with 12 questions devoted to IA input factors, 11 questions devoted to IA foundation and 11 questions devoted to IA integration factors. Respondents stated that they support the strategic alignment of IA and internal control systems, and intend to seek BOD and AC support for quality assurance and improvement. Despite this view, respondents were concerned about significant emerging risks and the lack of a mechanism of policy and framework (control, governance, risks and operation) in their prospective organisations to assess, address and mitigate key trends. In contrast, the nature of IA practices requires improvement and further investigation, with the overall status of standards for the effectiveness of IA in protecting governance control mechanisms still immature. Thus, the empirical findings also suggest that the current practices should rely on the implementation of a risk-based IA approach, digital transformation and compliance monitoring on operational controls.

Overall, the findings supported the research objectives as outlined in Section 1.5, based on the empirical evidence presented in this chapter. The research findings also supported the research aim of establishing an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance, whereas the literature arguments concluded that the need for a comprehensive understanding of existing IA practices has minimised IA's problematic status. Respondents expressed interest in implementing the IBA framework due to a lack of consideration for aligning IA practice with activities, programmes and monitoring, emphasising the importance of adequate management oversight and accountability as well as the development of a strong internal control process to safeguard assets, maintain compliance monitoring of operational controls and integrate financial reporting.

Finally, this chapter establishes a systematic baseline for the following chapters. Chapter 6 validates the IBA framework based on the research findings, and evaluates and synthesises the implications of research conclusions, as well as the literature findings from Chapters 2 and 3, to provide academics and industry with practical guidance in adopting the IBA framework.

Chapter 6: Discussion of the findings

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapter provided evidence that shows the perceptions of research participants from the banking sector in a descriptive manner. This chapter evaluates and justifies the research findings thematically to reinforce the validity of the IBA framework utilising thematic analysis to aggregate responses to the main research question. Furthermore, the research findings are critically compared to academic and industry-based literature (Chapters 2 and 3) as well as empirical data detailed in Chapter 5. Through the findings, this investigation explores patterns and themes, and connects the threads of academic and industry-based literature to generate the necessary research insights (Smith and Sparkes, 2016). In this regard, the Researcher investigates significant issues in the field of IA in relation to the research findings and the body of existing literature. This chapter also establishes links between this research, academic research and the practical context of the banking sector, and is divided into four sections:

- The first section discusses the thematic empirical findings in relation to the research objectives described in Section 1.5, by analysing and presenting the implications for the IBA framework that is validated in Figure 6.1 (Sections 6.2 and 6.3);
- The second section validates the IBA framework using research data derived from semi-structured interviews that incorporate emergent themes and sub-themes in Section 6.4;
- The third section provides practical guidance for the IBA framework, emphasising its strengths to ensure its effective implementation throughout the banking sector (Section 6.5);
- The final section contains an evaluation of the IBA framework (Figure 6.1) outputs (strengths), a concise assessment of the research findings, their significance and associated limitations (Section: 6.6).

The aim of this research is to develop an IBA framework to fill the literature gap as described in Chapter 3 as well as to provide practical guidance to the banking sector and academia. While the mandate of IA has been researched in a variety of industries, no research has been found in the context of banks in Bangladesh, and insufficient consideration has been given to how general practices apply to banks, implying that no research has addressed

their unique needs. Therefore, this research investigates the challenges of IA in banks by developing an IBA framework based on research objectives and questions.

6.2 TA in the context of research objectives

This section is designed to examine thematic findings and how they relate to the research objectives and literature findings discussed in Chapters 2 and 3. Furthermore, the findings of this research are consistent with the research aim, objectives and research questions, which are presented in Table 6.1 below.

Table: 6.1: Correlation between research aim, objectives and questions

Research aim	Research objectives	Research questions
To investigate the challenges facing IA in the banking sector and to develop an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance.	RO1: Identify and evaluate the current challenges of IA in banks	RQ1: What are the challenges facing IA in banks in general and in Bangladesh specifically?
	RO2: Analyse the current practices of IA in banks	RQ2: What are the key factors that affect IA practices in banks in Bangladesh?
		RQ3: How can the effectiveness of IA in banks and in Bangladesh be enhanced?
	RO3: Evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh in order to develop an effective IBA framework	RQ4: How effective is the current framework of IBA in general and in Bangladesh?

Source: The Researcher

Table 6.1 demonstrates consistency with the rationale of the research framework. This research employed an SLR for more reliable and credible results from academic and industry-based contributions to fill the literature gaps, develop an IBA framework for implementation in the banking sector, and propose new directions for future research that can enhance IA. Previous literature has been carefully reviewed to identify the factors that could contribute to the development and validation of the IBA framework and IA subject area. The foundation for understanding the context of the existing literature and describing how the research problem can extend current knowledge was established through theoretical constructs and research gaps. It also helps to understand the factors that influence effective IA practices, the challenges facing IA implementation, and how these relate to the development of the IBA framework for the banking sector. Furthermore, the following sub-sections investigate the implications of the empirical findings in relation to the

research context by achieving the aim and objectives, answering the questions, theoretical contributions, and arguments with previous research.

6.2.1 Research objective 1: Analysing current challenges facing IA in banks

As indicated in Chapter 5, there is a significant shift in the IA department, including a faster rate of change than previously experienced and a need for stronger, even more effective professional standards and framework implementation. The banking sector is undergoing rapid and profound change because of a variety of factors, including technological and regulatory developments as well as further macroeconomic and societal developments. Internal and external stakeholders are expected to have a strong defence system in place, but they also need to be flexible enough to look for opportunities that may arise from IA challenges. This could be done by setting up an effective IBA framework in banks. The qualitative data analysis has identified key challenges in implementing IA in the banking sector, which were discussed in Chapter 5. These will now be discussed in greater detail in the following sub-sections.

6.2.1.1 IT systems and technology risks

The findings of the interview data show that nearly half of the respondents (43.22%) agreed that a lack of understanding of IT systems and technology risks was critical to the integrity of the IA programme implementation, financial reporting processes and internal control environment in the banking sector. A greater emphasis on IT systems and their integrated applications addresses a lack of alignment with organisational objectives, which has a significant impact on data processing and reporting for IT risk analysis. Furthermore, the use of IT systems helps to provide information confidentiality, effectively, efficiently, and with compliance, availability and dependability, has been debated in the literature, with implications for IT quality, performance, competence and meeting the essential assumptions (Deribe and Regasa, 2014).

The literature findings also revealed a positive relationship between audit quality elements, information technology, accounting and finance, as well as related risks and international auditing standards, where risks provide a context for analysing IT and manual controls (Feghali and Hallak, 2019). In this regard, data can be altered due to insufficient computer security resulting in significant errors in the operational activities of banks. Thus, appropriate safeguards should be in place to ensure that data is only modified in accordance with management's standards (Protiviti, 2020). Routine maintenance is required for adopting and developing technologies by modifying the existing IT platform, which may necessitate

regression testing (Deloitte, 2021). The literature on emerging technologies focuses on their significant benefits and implementation strategies, but they may also pose significant risks (Mihret, James and Mula, 2012).

Internal auditors must understand changes in the IT environment to evaluate management's process for initiating, processing, and recording transactions. Part of this understanding includes identifying potential sources of misstatement by identifying risks and controls within the IT platform. This is a critical method of the top-down strategy for identifying major accounts and disclosures as well as their relevant assertions during the risk assessment process (Deloitte, 2020). Furthermore, technology is evolving for all organisations with significant implications for identifying key risks to address in risk assessments, detecting risk events and preventing outbreaks from emerging risks.

When assessing the risks associated with the implementation of new technologies, as well as how those risks differ from those associated with more traditional legacy systems (e.g. resources, rapid tool development, use of third parties), risks may arise due to programme or application-specific factors that differ from standard IT risks (Lenning and Gremyr, 2021). Understanding the risks posed by new technologies during the system development life cycle should assist auditors in developing a suitable audit response tailored to the circumstances of an organisation. Expertise in new technologies, risk assessment, control design, implementation, and efficacy should be investigated. If specialised skills are required, they should thoroughly understand the expert's field of expertise before accepting the work.

6.2.1.2 Lack of strong internal control systems

Respondents (37.79%) reported a lack of strong internal control systems for achieving operational goals, mitigating risks, improving process performance and accountability, stabilising internal operations and corporate functions, increasing financial confidence and reducing external audit fees. However, the size of the organisation, the level of internal risks and the presence of an effective AC are regarded as critical factors in driving internal control systems (Mihret and Grant, 2017). Although the IA is underdeveloped as an internal corporate governance instrument, it is required for evaluating the effectiveness of internal control systems through the implementation of corporate governance standards (Ismael and Roberts, 2018).

In addition to the general research findings, the literature emphasises that internal controls are intended to provide reasonable assurance in organisations, such as operational efficacy and efficiency as well as accurate and trustworthy financial reports, all of which must be in accordance with applicable rules and regulations (Mihret and Grant, 2017). Previous research has focused on creating an effective internal control environment that ensures that an organisation's resources, such as financial or technical resources, are allocated for their intended purposes reducing the risk of misappropriation (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). R [7] states that there should be clear protocols and rules for monitoring and performing internal controls throughout the year, rather than just during an external audit, to allow for greater efficiencies within the organisation.

Senior executives, the BOD and the AC have more control over how the organisation operates and what internal controls are in place. In this regard, organisations should help issues with tailored oversight to the organisation's needs. If they have well-established internal controls, they may be able to reduce the scope, time and fees of external auditors as well as the need for programme adjustments and rebuilding following an external auditor review. IA is a method of monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of internal control systems that was developed in response to the deficiencies of various lower control levels (Motubatse *et al.*, 2015; Najah and Omar, 2018).

The execution of economic activities within management's predetermined frameworks and services to improve economic activities and controls is suggested to be conceptualised as disciplinary mechanisms in current corporate governance settings (Mihret and Grant, 2017). Internal control quality, on the other hand, is related to IA function competence, IA quality assurance level, follow-up procedure and the AC involvement in analysing the IA programme and results (Oussii and Taktak, 2018). Ali Khadim (2018) notes that internal control systems had a significantly positive impact on the prevention of accounting fraud in banks. Audit activity and audit performance, along with professional skill and objectivity, have a significant impact on the information and communication aspects of internal control systems (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005).

6.2.1.3 Lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance

The lack of a dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance is a common theme in the literature that can be observed in the banking sector. As a critical aspect of strong corporate governance, the IA should assess and contribute to the overall improvement of the organisation's GRC mechanisms using a methodological and disciplined approach

(Deloitte, 2020). Some of the literature suggests creating a conceptual framework that could be applied to all IA functions, but empirical evidence has yet to validate this suggestion (Elbardan, Ali and Ghoneim, 2015). While the research findings did not prove the existence of a sector-specific framework for the banking sector and in Bangladesh context, they did partially substantiate the need for a foundation upon which organisations can build an IA strategy for success in the long term. While new risks have emerged in maintaining quality assurance and improvement, organisations should make significant changes in resolving issues to improve IA performance (IIA, 2020). The findings in Chapter 5 indicate that respondents believe a dynamic framework and implementation guidance may improve quality assurance and make better use of IA resources. This emphasis should be maintained because aligning strategic vision and mindset influences IA practices, and organisations should maintain excellent operational and IT resilience, deal with digital disruption and cyber security, and use human capital and talent management.

6.2.1.4 Lack of risk-based IA approach

Despite a thorough review of the IA literature, the findings revealed that 23.37% of respondents believe the banking sector lacked the experience to adopt and implement a risk-based IA approach to respond to regulatory changes. The literature supports the idea that this approach can improve corporate governance by providing insight into the monitoring process that drives IA performance, improving the quality of supervision through IA practitioner education and developing new IA standards (Benli and Celayir, 2014). As risks emerge and become more complex in the age of technology, the role of IA is expected to expand to include risk governance, culture and behaviour, sustainability and non-financial reporting measures to protect assets (Goodwin-Stewart and Kent, 2006; Erlina *et al.*, 2018).

Banks may want to reconsider redefining responsibilities in their IA methods to prevent financial reporting scandals, manage high levels of risk management engagement and schedule annual audits, paving the way for identifying high-risk priority areas to improve IA quality (Ayagre, Appiah-Gyamereh and Nartey, 2014; Amoush, 2017). A risk-based IA plan, for example, is intended to focus on and assess the effectiveness of internal controls used to reduce losses and unfavourable consequences such as financial statement errors, fraud or reputation damage. This strategy necessitates redefining the IA team's role by learning how they might determine the type and sufficiency of the risk based on their understanding of how to promote transparency and collaboration with external auditors during the risk assessment process (Erlina *et al.*, 2018). By implementing more methodical documentation of their scope and risk maturity, the measures are thought to improve strategic value during

risk assessment. The evidence also suggests that a systematic control mechanism for identifying new and emerging risks need to be implemented, which could be aided by obtaining feedback from external audit assurance providers.

The banking sector's risk assessment and audit preparation methods have yet to be fully standardised (Koutoupis and Tsamis, 2009). Respondents have raised questions about why banks are not using the risk-based IA technique, despite the BB's insistence on its use during audits. Due to changes in economic conditions, corporate disruption, sustainability and climate change, BOD oversight effectiveness, and artificial intelligence implementation, it is necessary to adapt to the risk-based IA approach and incorporate its methodology with technology to embed strategic resiliency in the IA department (Deloitte, 2021). It is argued that a critical component of a risk-based IA methodology is the ability to change audit plans and deal with the most severe implementation risks that jeopardise the organisation's ability to meet its objectives (Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012).

Banks have faced new systematic risks in recent years, thus top management must evaluate risk management strategies for systematic risks, and enhance and reinforce the risk-based IA approach to reduce the direct impact on revenues and avoid indirect influences such as fraud risk by unethical employees taking advantage of current conditions (Tamimi, 2021). As a result of the risks that organisations face, audit efforts are concentrated on financial statements that may contain errors or omissions. In terms of prospective research, the goal should be to consider developing technology to help audit work by improving audit efficiency and organising how large amounts of data should be handled as well as using a more targeted risk-based IA method to better examine large amounts of data.

6.2.1.5 Lack of strategic vision of IA

According to 20.54% of the respondents, a lack of strategic vision in IA can lead to decreased efficiency, poor performance and a lack of accountability in banks. A strategic approach to the role entails working with the audit team to determine where to focus its investment, and adapting assurance and consulting work to meet organisational objectives that attempt to innovate and generate positive change in organisations (Dubihlela and Gwaka, 2020). In recent years, there has been a surge of interest in the concept of integrating the strategic vision by managing new risks, developing new skills, collaborating with other risk functions and leveraging technology to evolve the IA department (KPMG, 2020).

In comparison to previous research findings, the strategic IA plan should be linked to the mission, vision and tactical initiatives to aid in the evolution of the set of functions. Stakeholders should be able to understand the vision for IA and how it connects with the organisation in achieving strategic objectives because of their participation in the AC. It is critical to align the IA function's strategic vision and mindsets by providing relevant resources such as technology and establishing a wider range of capabilities (IIA, 2020). Academics believe there is a significant misalignment of goals because organisations require a team of auditors with specific risk management skills to assist the BOD or the AC in making the best decisions possible in terms of sustaining effective organisational governance (Moeller, 2012). This implies that the significant misalignment of goals is due to a team of auditors assisting the BOD or AC a larger group of people so more room for error and not enough auditors to help.

6.2.1.6 Lack of resources and talent management

One of the most common issues for banking organisations is a lack of resources and talent management according to 18.98% of the respondents. Although it is difficult to find skilled employees, managing a decentralised workforce is much more difficult because organisations participate in hiring, training and terminating employees in banks. The findings of this research supported the previous research indicating that the risks associated with talent management have a direct impact on IA departments (Gantz, 2014). Because the banking sector is complex, IA teams of high-quality auditors should strive to improve efficiency and creativity by embracing and implementing new IA techniques and technologies such as advanced analytics, process automation and artificial intelligence (Protiviti, 2019).

Banks should prioritise upskilling their employees so that they are more familiar with technology, such as automation and analytics, and can complete their tasks more efficiently. Time is saved by automating routine and repetitive tasks, for example, more time should be available for analysis, risk assessment and gap closure while utilising fewer audit resources. Analytical and critical thinking, business acumen, risk management, information technology and cybersecurity are all skills that IA departments must teach their employees (PWC, 2019). Upskilling current talent is the preferred strategy in this context for non-technology-related qualities such as analytical and critical thinking, communication, business acumen and risk management. These developments strengthen the findings by implying that the IA work plan could be used even more effectively, especially in high-risk areas like

cybersecurity, talent management and organisational governance. Overall, respondents believe that current assurance services are adequate, but they recommend some improvements in assurance reporting such as teams of professionals who focus on meeting the needs of new technology and are comfortable working with large amounts of data, while also monitoring and addressing risks that may arise because of data and technology advances.

6.2.1.7 Lack of clear methodology to leverage technology

A lack of clear methodology to leverage technology was identified by 17.16% of the respondents. Despite the fact that most banks use various technologies to collaborate across branches, research indicates that accounting departments and audit teams should be better equipped in terms of technology (KPMG, 2021). Systematic limits and long response times have made it difficult to audit efficiently. Although using protected shared drives is a step in the right direction, it comes with limitations and functional difficulties. Therefore, audit platforms must be considered to facilitate collaboration while also speeding up and automating workflows, risk management and comprehensive reporting (Dubihlela and Gwaka, 2020). However, leveraging technology may present some challenges, and cybersecurity and other risks such as strategic or operational risks have been recurring themes on the AC agendas in recent years. Several organisations are investing in IT infrastructure, analytics and security-based solutions to address this and other technological threats, therefore allowing them to conduct successful audits.

Furthermore, the digital revolution in IA exemplifies how assessing technical advancement and associated risks can supplement rather than replace human judgement on an organisation's actions. It promises profound change and enormous opportunity, but it also introduces new risks and uncertainties. To ensure that IA can establish the full value and benefits of its functions, senior executives, the BOD and the AC should increase their support for IA innovation and automation investment. Internal auditors, for example, can be relieved of constraints, while duties can increase the capacity and opportunities for functional areas to grow more effectively and efficiently bringing value to the organisation.

6.2.1.8 Lack of agile auditing methodologies

A lack of agile auditing methodologies was identified by 16.52% of the respondents. IA is currently operating in a global business environment marked by increased competition, technological advancements and significant uncertainty in retaining skilled labour. This suggests that demand for IA is growing much faster than capacity causing value delivery

issues and the inability to exceed stakeholders' expectations. However, capacity multipliers have been used by IA departments in three major areas: strategic staffing solutions, altered procedures and technological applications (Dubihlela and Gwaka, 2020). Strategically using audit technologies, data analytics and automation to increase the percentage of relationships built and the effectiveness of audit work aids in the resolution of many common audit challenges, such as developing a valuable and relevant audit plan; unless the audit plan is entirely comprised of routine compliance or checklist-based activities.

Agile methodology is quickly becoming a must-have for audit teams (Deloitte, 2021). It supports IA in resolving common issues by shortening turnaround times and increasing stakeholder interaction, collaboration and participation. Focusing on competencies, developing strong relationships, cultivating a consulting service culture and aligning audit goals with organisation's objectives make an audit department very relevant and desirable for performing rapid audits. Internal auditors must become more proactive in anticipating risks, streamline workpapers, deliver impactful, relevant, timely, readable, and visually pleasing reports, access applicable skillsets and deepen specialised skillsets (Deloitte, 2018). Current efforts to address these issues are ineffective, and IA departments require a better change management process. In this regard, agile IA is one such change technique as well as the most easily applicable to overcoming current issues.

6.2.1.9 Poor application of regulations and standards

Integrating IA best practices is a subjective term implying that IA departments follow standard operating procedures. It appears that the banking sector's poor application of regulations and standards accounts for approximately 13.87% of the respondents' views. IA procedures differ from one another because departments differ and upper management's requirements differ. By implementing appropriate auditing processes, each audit department should achieve regulatory compliance and management objectives (Steinbart *et al.*, 2018). Making risk assessments, completing high-quality audit work, issuing audit reports, following up on issues and reporting to the AC are all examples of good auditing methods (Christopher, 2018). Finally, IA departments strive to continuously improve their performance in standard practices.

6.2.2 Research objective 2: Reviewing current practices of IA in banks

The empirical findings of this research aim to add value to the field of IA research by focusing on the banking sector, which is underserved, particularly in Bangladesh. The second research objective was to examine how banking organisations practice IA. As discussed in

Chapter 5, the data revealed that the nature of IA effectiveness varies across organisations with almost half the respondents claiming that their prospective organisations require further improvement. As described in Sub-Section 5.2.2 (development of the IBA framework), the analysis was focused on three main questions (Q25, Q26 and Q27), each of which was directed at interviewees concerning current IA practices. The major findings revealed that interviewees had differing perspectives on the areas that represented the most effective IA practices (Q26). Furthermore, half of the respondents confirmed their belief that internal issues (i.e. control, governance, operation and risks) are the most likely to inhibit effective IA practices in the banking sector.

6.2.3 Research objective 3: Reviewing the current framework on IBA and addressing gaps

This section discusses the primary themes and sub-themes identified for the development of the IBA framework. The key aim of this section is to understand the emergence of current IA frameworks and gaps in the banking sector as well as how they can affect organisational objectives by aligning strategic vision and mindsets via dynamic risk assessment, risk and risk maturity, and integrated risk evaluation and monitoring. The research findings articulate how key factors, such as IA input factors, IA foundation factors and IA integration factors, are handled and where these key controls are located across banks. The research findings, aligning IA with key input factors (six sub-themes), key IA foundation factors (five sub-themes), the importance of IA integration (nine sub-themes) and the importance of the internal and external environment, are all important for refining and validating the IBA framework to provide a practical guidance.

6.2.3.1 Aligning IA with key input factors

Despite increased exposure and buy-in from the BOD and the AC, IA departments in the banking sector face significant challenges including emerging risks and control issues, insufficient compliance standards, and quality assurance and improvement failures. These difficulties are consistent with the literature findings, which include the IA strategy's immature implementation, complex financial disclosures and business models, expanding regulatory guidelines and compliance, risk quantification, governance failures, monitoring and oversight, information sharing and communication (Roussy and Perron, 2018). This subsection examines Q10–Q29 (Sub-Section 5.2.2), which investigated the important internal environment IA input factors that influence the development and implementation of the IBA framework. The following are the essential parameters based on research data and relevance to validate the IBA framework.

Safeguarding assets

Safeguarding assets is considered to be a very important priority amongst respondents (45.28%). Internal controls provide reasonable assurance for asset protection, financial record validation, fraud prevention, efficient and continuous record keeping in the accounting system, and monitoring organisational performance (PwC, 2019). This refers to the implementation of internal controls to ensure that financial information is accurate and reliable, that assets are protected from loss and theft, that policies, laws and regulations are followed, that resources are used economically and efficiently, and that operational goals and objectives are established (Fadzil, Haron and Jantan, 2005). Technology can assist in addressing risks, which would undoubtedly improve the quality, rigour and efficiency of internal controls. In this context, organisations should consider how they can use technology in a safe and ethical manner to act more autonomously, whether to protect or develop assets. Thus, having a strong and effective internal control system ensures asset quality and allows for effective financial reporting.

Human capital and talent management

In recent years, human capital and talent management have become important considerations in IA, and the effectiveness of an IA team is determined by establishing what resources are required to provide value to the organisation. This is supported by 44.27% of the respondents. For example, evaluating technological resources and implementing audit management technology to centralise documentation, improve collaboration among team members and stakeholders, and gain real-time visibility into IA performance are regarded as critical elements in adding value to organisations. Evidence also suggests that auditing locations with the right skill set and knowledge helps organisations run more efficiently. An IT subject matter specialist, for example, assists IA in covering all bases in terms of effective leadership and the development of a departmental plan. Because the banking sector is involved in the adoption and development of technology, this study's findings suggested that internal auditors should be cross-trained by understanding general organisational procedures and controls in other departments of the organisation. By specifying the types of data that must be collected, saved and analysed for the organisation to be more effective, the cybersecurity and data security protocols can be improved.

Digital disruption and cybersecurity

Digital disruption and cybersecurity are at the forefront of a threat that has grown exponentially in recent years due to a number of high-profile cyberattacks on infrastructure and other high-profile banking targets such as BB (Mazumder and Sobhan, 2020). This was

supported by 35.32% of the respondents. Since cyber criminals exposed data vulnerabilities, data privacy concerns and third-party threats have emerged as critical factors. Furthermore, rapid employee turnover and digitisation in the banking sector jeopardise an organisation's talent. Simultaneously, organisations must continue to manage supply chain risks resulting from digital disruption as well as compliance risks that have emerged in a more strictly enforced legislative and regulatory environment, particularly in banks in Bangladesh.

Regulatory compliance

In response to ever-increasing regulatory requirements, IA has shifted its focus to assisting banks in responding to changes in internal behaviours, such as audit work and cultural differences, as well as information and communication technology and other disruptors. Nearly a third of respondents agreed with this (33.10%). IA departments are still developing and refining strategies to address the many aspects of the current environment (Deloitte, 2021). In an era when global economic challenges, increased pressure on major financial organisations and changing business landscapes have resulted in stricter regulations in most major industries and countries around the world, the phrase 'regulatory compliance' has become a buzzword (Deloitte, 2021). Thus, organisations are gradually improving the procedures and structures required for regulatory compliance. The growing impact of new legislation, as well as the consequences of non-compliance within organisations, has prompted the BOD or the AC to place a greater emphasis on regulatory compliance to improve the IA effectiveness in the banking sector.

Operational and IT resilience

The establishment or expansion of ecosystems adds complexity and disruption to operational and IT resilience, an area identified by 31.52% of the respondents. Organisations that struggle to align talent, resources and procedures with the IA strategy are under increased pressure to improve coordination and communication to promote agility in the banking sector. Auditors can help businesses rethink their approaches to strategic workforce planning and ensure that strategic decisions are made in the context of a strong risk culture (Al-Akra, Abdel-Qadera and Billahb, 2016). The rapid pace of technological innovation combined with external forces has put significant pressure on organisations to digitally transform their operations to remain competitive and potentially relevant. Many digital transformation projects have failed because of a lack of strategic focus or alignment, flaws in internal control or governance concerns (Gros, Koch and Wallek, 2016). Security issues are more likely to emerge and spread as procedures and technologies evolve. Cybersecurity issues, human error, software integrations and a variety of other factors

should all create or increase risk points implying that businesses are embracing artificial intelligence, which has enormous potential for improving productivity and streamlining procedures.

IA positioning

In terms of organisational culture, cooperation, effectiveness, performance and framework, IA positioning is an intriguing component in IA that is emerging, identified by 28.49% of the respondents. The findings back up organisations' IA strategy, which states that increased investment in technology must put it far ahead of the competition (Eulerich, Kremin and Wood, 2019). To thrive in an era of constant change, IA information assurance teams must embrace a mindset change, coordinate and rely on auditing culture, monitor and assess IA effectiveness, and maintain standards in tracking competencies. Researchers believe that being flexible and adaptive in IA should help organisations stay on top of the current risk environment while also allowing future concerns to be addressed and mitigated quickly (Nerantzidis *et al.*, 2020).

6.2.3.2 Importance of IA foundation factors

This sub-section provides an understanding and explanation of Q20–Q30 (Sub-Section 5.2.2), which investigated the internal environment foundation factors that influenced the development and implementation of the IBA framework. Based on research evidence, the key factors identified are outlined below in order of their relevance to validating the IBA framework.

Continuous monitoring

Continuous monitoring and its overall benefits should be included in organisations' IA programmes, which is supported by 45.91% of the respondents. However, only a small percentage of people in their organisations would have recognised the full potential of such programmes. This could be because executives do not see a compelling business case for implementing continuous monitoring solutions. Given the current environment of increased risks, changing regulations and compliance costs, investigating the possibility of implementing such a solution within the organisation is an excellent first step. Management should be able to operationalise the total risk management effort because of the continuous monitoring, allowing the organisation to shift away from rule-based exception reporting to Continuous Controls Monitoring (CCM) solutions and towards solutions that deliver actionable insights in the form of dynamic dashboards, encouraging behavioural change throughout the organisation (Deloitte, 2021).

Digital transformation

As the number of digital transformation initiatives increases, identified by 24.35% of the respondents, the banking sector must prioritise governance, security and IT asset management. The number of access points increases as an organisation's IT infrastructure becomes more complex and new applications are introduced into the corporate technology ecosystem. When the sophistication of cyberattacks are combined with the diversification of threat, modern tools are used such as artificial intelligence, and the risks begin to outweigh the promise and benefits of transformative technology. Thus, IA should maintain cybersecurity readiness while also monitoring future IT vulnerabilities. This was consistent with Lenning and Gremyr's (2021) assertion that an integrated and transparent approach to dealing with digitisation should consider both opportunities and challenges by developing a solid digital IA strategy and identifying any non-compliances.

Risk and risk maturity

Despite significant risk management efforts in many areas, organisations lack a comprehensive understanding of the primary risks, identified by 23.28% of the respondents. Whether their resources are spent on assurance, gaps in coverage, severe control failures or unanticipated risk occurrences, all are negative consequences of low-risk visibility. Organisations achieve their strategic goals by providing fascinating insights into how to get there while addressing all potential risks along the way. This reflects the importance of IA to organisations as part of their risk management and control systems as well as the prominence of the IA profession and its vitality (Lenz and Hahn, 2015).

To achieve strategic goals and manage risk, the banking sector should assess the appropriate level of risk maturity, which should be reflected in the risk management plan to influence risk improvement actions. Continuous improvement is required in this regard to achieve the targets in risk maturity strategies for effective risk management. The risk management strategy should be developed with adequate time and resources. Risk maturity entails more than just the structural consideration of ensuring a framework is in place; it also necessitates an assessment to determine whether or not it is beneficial. This means that organisations must evaluate whether risk management improves overall performance, whether the risk management function is properly functioning and whether objectives are met.

Process and control implementation

Meetings, training and pilot testing are all common components of the implementation of a control process, an important element identified by 22.36% of the respondents. Testing for a new control can take weeks or months depending on the number of teams involved in the implementation. System access control, for example, may take several weeks, especially if automation is used. The cost of the automation that must be coded and verified before it can be put into production should be recorded or, at a minimum, estimated. The auditing process is intended to determine where and what to audit and may include evaluations of control strategy, control adequacy and effectiveness, performance quality, unit performance reporting and follow-up.

Value creation of IA

Creating value with the most recent innovations is especially important because the potential exponential pace of computing capacity and machine learning poses significant risk and may even necessitate an IA paradigm shift as requirements and opportunities grow. This is supported by 16.72% of the respondents. The banking sector should be encouraged to develop and improve its capabilities in the following areas: technological, regulatory and commercial awareness; the development of a more adaptable and progressive methodology; strategic mindsets and a deeper understanding of risk management; the development of new and broader specialisms as well as specialism mainstreaming using new tools and technology; integration of IT abilities; and in-depth knowledge and understanding of the banking sector (IIA, 2020). Understanding the organisation, developing relationships, demonstrating objectivity and sound judgement, and communicating difficult problems fairly and intelligently are all critical to adding value to an organisation.

A study by Zinca (2016) discovered that most organisations use approaches that are primarily quantitative and have fewer qualitative features when it comes to measuring IA value. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the audit function's procedures and processes can be improved in order for it to gain value and credibility (Zinca, 2016). Another study discovered that the goals and strategies pursued, as well as the level of risk faced by the organisations that IA assists with, appear to shape the characteristics of a value-added IA department. The extent to which a suitable value-added profile is obtained in a given setting is influenced by the quality of strategic planning for and marketing of IA (Mihret and Woldeyohannis, 2008). Based on this research and literature evidence, IA adds significant value by improving governance processes, lowering audit fees and detecting fraud (Ronkko, Paananen and Vakkuri, 2017).

6.2.3.3 Importance of IA integration in the IBA framework

Q31–Q41 (Section 5.2.2) examined the importance of IA integration in the IBA framework. Based on research evidence, the key factors identified are outlined below based on their relevance to validating the IBA framework.

Compliance monitoring of operational controls

In recent years, regulatory compliance obligations have continued to establish operational efficiency and quality control in the context of good governance with top management becoming more aware, as supported by 33.72% of the respondents, which are in line with the literature findings (Feng *et al.*, 2015; Cheng, Felix and Indjejikian, 2019; Henk, 2020). Thus, compliance monitoring is critical for maintaining quality assurance and organisational operations to meet regulatory and internal process requirements (McKinsey, 2012). Monitoring is a critical component for resolving regulatory compliance challenges, which need to be augmented in banking organisations by developing a rigorous and comprehensive compliance monitoring programme to maintain regulated status and operational controls. Internal control, on the other hand, is a critical factor in establishing responsibility as well as monitoring and managing operations in organisations (Jones, 2008). For example, the technical knowledge and efficiency of internal auditors have a positive impact on internal control systems and contribute to more reliable financial reporting (Oussii and Taktak, 2018). A rigorous approach should be used to facilitate the systematic pursuit of high-quality governance, procedures, methodologies and infrastructure in compliance and critical areas.

Information and communication

Changing demands have altered the role of IA, which now necessitates strong information and communication to drive effective governance, risk management, compliance and quality assurance in today's banking environment, as stated by 29.17% of the respondents. Other researchers agree, affirming that IA reduces information irregularities between the BOD and the AC (Sarens and Abdolmohammadi, 2011). Thus, the IA team must make constructive recommendations to improve performance by addressing risks and improving processes as a possible means of providing information to the department about creating value in organisations (Soh and Martinov-Bennie, 2011; Roussy and Brivot, 2016). The IA and corporate control environments are receiving increased attention and resources to comply with regulations and implement dynamic frameworks. Effective internal auditors, in this case, serve as a frontline where additional value can be created by improving processes and information to support management decisions and reviewing the organisation's compliance

with published, documented procedures (Eulerich and Eulerich, 2020). Internal auditors should perform operations, provide management-level reports and understand the processes in place, as well as develop organisational facilities where actual work is performed and records are kept, and design and perform appropriate tests to evaluate supporting internal controls.

Innovative IA department

An innovative IA department is critical because IA faces significant challenges such as minimising the impact of audits while maximising insights, streamlining processes for planning, fieldwork and reporting, determining the appropriate resourcing model, improving the utilisation of technology and demonstrating added value in organisations (PwC, 2019). By focusing on the three key pillars previously identified (technology and innovation with advanced technology solutions, future auditors and smarter auditing), growth is seen as a means of addressing the challenges of evolving performance and driving positive change (Protiviti, 2021). IA has been slow to adopt innovative approaches that provide real-time analysis on specific risks due to a lack of strategic foresight, a lack of budgeting and a lack of resources (Deloitte, 2021). Thus, the auditing function must evolve to meet the changing needs of the organisation, which is critical for IA to fulfil its mission of developing internal skills and capabilities.

Based on the research evidence and findings from the literature, internal auditors should embrace new technologies to avoid using obsolete systems, utilising the data and tools at their disposal to make a difference (Peterson, 2018). To achieve an effective and efficient IA function, new strategies and techniques for conducting IA activities must be implemented (Sumritsakun and Ussahawanitchakit, 2009). In a disruptive and constantly evolving organisational environment where evolution takes the form of innovation and organisations are constantly developing new methods, technologies and structures to increase performance, deliver timely strategic insights and enhanced value, the need for IA to do more has intensified (Deloitte, 2017).

Fraud prevention and detection

Accounting fraud and poor governance have demonstrated in recent years that dishonesty not only reduces revenues, dependability and operational efficiencies, but also severely harms an organisation's reputation (KPMG, 2020). This is recorded by 22.07% of the respondents. Initially, fraud detection and prevention were viewed as legal and security concerns rather than accounting and auditing concerns, but attitudes have shifted

dramatically in recent years and internal auditors are now in charge of serious fraud-related issues. This implies that organisations should put in place a comprehensive fraud detection and investigation policy with the goal of reducing fraud and identifying opportunities related to a specific set of operational controls. The development of monitoring controls by the BOD and the AC, policies and training, employee screening and internal fraud controls are all critical components of effective fraud protection in the banking sector. Internal controls' ability to provide reasonable assurance that both incidences of fraud and general resource misuse are reduced is supported by research data and literature that acknowledge the importance of fraud prevention and detection policies and procedures.

The research evidence also emphasises the importance of IA in detecting accounting fraud as well as investing in IA methods and training guidance to improve organisational performance (Drogalas *et al.*, 2017). Key findings show that IA departments are more effective at preventing fraud than outsourced operations (Salameh *et al.*, 2011). Thus, IA is regarded as a critical control mechanism for directing, monitoring and measuring an organisation's resources, which is essential for detecting and preventing fraud as well as safeguarding the organisation's physical and intangible resources.

Technical skills, knowledge and capabilities

Internal auditors face increased responsibility in terms of competencies and skill requirements to meet diverse and divergent obligations as business and corporate governance partners with senior management (Fourie *et al.*, 2013). This is supported by 20.87% of the respondents. Technical competence in areas such as framework understanding, required IA capabilities, business acumen, and governance, risk and compliance is required. As previously stated, technological audit abilities have grown in importance in recent years, but competence should make the difference when attempting to respond to changing needs and work on IA projects that the IA team has never attempted. Thus, concentrating on more broadly valuable talents and soft skills such as listening, communication, persuasion, teamwork and critical thinking, is important for demonstrating a clear strategy for improving IA operations within organisations.

IA is viewed as a place to learn and develop the ability to deal with uncertainty as well as to experience innovative problem-solving abilities (Gras-Gil, Marin-Hernandez and Garcia-Perez de Lema, 2012). Auditors, for example, can strengthen their relationship and project management skills by interacting with key internal and external stakeholders. Furthermore, the operational dimensions of IA include planning resource management and strategic

knowledge, improvement and innovation, all of which are critical for preparing organisations for productive change (Mihret, James and Mula, 2010). This reflects the importance of auditors developing leadership skills such as the ability to analyse a situation and make practical recommendations based on what is most important. A department that prioritises fundamental abilities over skill sets should become desirable and valuable to the organisation.

Integrated financial reporting

Integrated reporting is a method of presenting information about an organisation's strategy, governance, performance and prospects in a clear and simple manner that takes the commercial, social and environmental context into account and leads to the creation of value and better decision-making (PwC, 2019; Deloitte, 2021). This is identified by 17.27% of the respondents. Scholars have argued that IA is a critical component of financial reporting quality, which is an important component of accountability (Bananuka, Mukyala and Nalukenge, 2017). Banking organisations must maintain IA quality in terms of competence and adherence to norms (e.g. a code of conduct for professional accountants) and professional standards to achieve quality financial reporting processes. The BOD or the AC should have the necessary proficiency, such as financial expertise and knowledge, to carry out their duties (Nalukenge *et al.*, 2018; Bananuka *et al.*, 2019).

Due to the enormous risks that organisations are facing, one of the factors that has been highlighted is the requirement for IA to provide real-time reporting to senior management and the AC. As a tool for this purpose, an IA dashboard that provides performance indicators and serves as a channel for regular communication with top management is recommended (PwC, 2019). Thus, the banking sector should introduce and embed integrated reporting in organisations through activities such as engaging stakeholders, developing a value proposition and strategy, aligning internal control processes with strategy and developing an integrated dashboard that should produce effective financial reporting.

Innovative audit delivery and change

The organisational structure of the IA department should be ambitious in terms of reporting lines and opportunities for growth, while also ensuring successful continuity. Innovative audit delivery and change was supported by 17.68% of the respondents. Ernest and Young (2021) note that IA is a technical and diverse profession with a high level of accountability. It entails systematic supervision, which entails matching skills, providing opportunities for advancement and instilling in employees a desire to enable real-time risk monitoring and

timely reporting of high-risk findings. Creating a formal methodology to formalise a data analytics programme that describes how data can be found, gathered and analysed, as well as integrating data analytics into the strategic vision, is a significant challenge for IA departments in the banking sector. Setting up a successful IA team necessitates a thorough understanding of the organisation's strategy and associated risks as well as an analysis of resources to determine whether they are required to create value for the organisation.

Furthermore, a renewed focus on areas such as investment, training, continuing professional development and technology tools is required to ensure that IA practices are aligned with the needs of organisations by improving communication between auditor and auditee with a defined culture and process for quality control (PwC, 2019). The rapidly changing macro-environment and technological innovation forced them to realign their practices to new audit objectives and evolving risks. To shape the future of IA, internal auditors and standard setters must understand current trends and innovations (Christ *et al.*, 2021). Thus, innovative audit delivery and changes should be reframed as emerging risks and investigated as evolving operations, defining their strategy and recommending processes to drive the inevitability of change.

Integrated risk evaluation and monitoring

Banking organisations have recognised the need for a more comprehensive approach to risk evaluation and monitoring based on a coordinated dynamic risk assessment, a view shared by 16.19% of the correspondents. To enable a coordinated effort, shared risk terminology, risk ratings and a collaborative risk assessment methodology must be developed. The findings of the literature and research evidence suggest that other risk and control functions should be able to participate in the audit process, which is linked to and consistent with the risk reporting protocol (KPMG, 2019). The findings also reveal a diverse range of risk management systems in terms of the actual adoption of an integrated risk management system and risk identification strategies employed by organisations (Arena and Azzone, 2006). However, additional research should be conducted to justify examining and redesigning audit procedures to better address technology-based risks (Christ *et al.*, 2021). A continuous risk assessment process can increase the value of IA and other risk and control oversight responsibilities while reducing data quality and availability issues (Omolaye and Jacob, 2017). The BOD or AC may eventually adopt this technique into IA practices to increase overall risk and environmental awareness. An integrated, organisation-wide risk assessment can take IA to a higher level of monitoring and risk assessment. Identifying emerging risks and determining whether key risks are effectively managed by the

organisation through the implementation and execution of mitigating controls are required to evaluate an organisation's risk assessment processes for major strategic initiatives.

Quality assurance and improvement

Problem identification is linked to system development and must be improved through standard management procedures of quality assurance and improvement (IIA, 2020), which is recognised by 11.74% of the respondents. Risks must be identified, assessed and controlled by prioritising an organisation's reputation and overall status, resourcing the drive for quality, efficient and effective procedures, establishing a quality role for the workforce and ensuring audit managers monitor and supervise work in the banking sector. The findings of the literature suggest that IA plays an active role in corporate governance, which is strongly associated with the presence of a quality assurance and improvement programme, a risk-based audit strategy and the AC support (Sarens, Abdolmohammadi and Lenz, 2012). Quality assurance and improvement programmes are also more common and effective in organisations that have a larger IA agenda and regularly perform advanced IA activities (Sarens *et al.*, 2011). In contrast, there is significant variation in high levels of non-compliance based on the use of quality assurance and improvement programmes (Burnaby *et al.*, 2009). Evaluation models that can be used to determine whether quality requirements are met are being developed because of embracing a culture of doing things correctly and always improving.

6.2.3.4 Importance of internal environment in the IBA framework

IA must understand the organisation's plans by focusing on emerging risks to evolve and prosper with the strategy and provide effective and high-quality communication, assurance and consulting services (Dellai and Omri, 2016). With the rapid changes that have impacted organisations in recent years, the BOD and the AC should provide more monitoring and assessing of IA quality, assurance on control resilience and integration of adaptability into the strategic vision in the banking sector. The findings of this research suggest that most organisations have not benefited from embracing technological improvements and advances in financial reporting and related internal controls, which can all provide insights into their business requirements and operations. Having a unique blend of knowledge about the issues that organisations face can assist in resolving, embracing and evolving change requirements by providing financial resources, reviewing and assessing IA work plans, and providing training and guidance. Based on the findings, the BOD and the AC should continue to focus on the risk management department and the importance of collaboration with the IA department in banks to achieve the best results (Tamimi, 2021).

The risk assessment methods chosen should have a significant impact on an organisation's IA strategy (Arena and Jeppesen, 2016). Certain procedures necessitate the participation of specific personnel as well as a distinct risk assessment approach. It is critical that the approach taken is consistent with the culture of the organisation. It should be noted that risk assessment is regarded as the most difficult and critical component of the IA process. Failure to conduct a risk assessment in the most effective and efficient manner, including proper identification and assessment of high-risk areas, has a significant impact on the subsequent phases of the audit cycle, which include planning, fieldwork, execution and reporting (Park, Lee and Kim, 2019). In this regard, audit planning should not be based solely on annual risk assessments. Planning should be agile, adaptable, data-driven and analytics-driven with as much input from the BOD or the AC as possible. Risk assessment in IA is a continuous process that necessitates a variety of approaches. The most valuable element is data analytics.

6.2.3.5 Importance of external environment in the IBA framework

External factors of the IBA framework refer to the role played by the government, particularly the BB, in facilitating the adoption of emerging technologies, developing strategies and managing banking organisations, upgrading appropriate policies and quality assurance frameworks for best IA practices, providing regulatory changes to adopt cultural growth, and maintaining a strong internal control culture.

The rapid pace of disruption and innovation requires new skills for risk-induced disruption and whether or not to embrace innovation in order for organisations to be successful in the long run. The findings of this research show that organisations need to change their IA strategy for dealing with disruption and innovation. To support this notion, the respondents have claimed three possible scenarios that could happen if an organisation adapts to implementing the IA strategy. When it comes to preparing for disruption and learning new skills, for example, inflationary pressures are becoming more important for many industries, including the banking sector, and economic conditions could have an impact on organisations and the way they work. To address inflation-related risks, it is necessary to consider which skills need to be developed as part of the IA profession.

6.2.3.6 Importance of technology in the IBA framework

The findings of this research suggest that technological advancements should be implemented to address the challenges faced by banks in Bangladesh. However, these advancements present significant challenges due to the complexity of technology adoption,

which necessitates the implementation of proactive measures of effectiveness and efficiency through IA. If banking organisations do not adopt emerging IT developments, they may encounter increased risk, financial fraud, inefficiency and inability to detect the manipulation of financial reporting. Moreover, the reliability of financial statements may decrease and weaknesses in the application of IA tools and techniques may emerge. Thus, various technological tools, such as data visualisation and analytics, should be implemented to enhance the effectiveness of innovative audit delivery in the IA department. In addition, the skills and expertise required to manage emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning should be developed. The respondents also emphasised the importance of internal auditors being knowledgeable about emerging technologies to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of IA.

Understanding the evolving roles of IA, including their legitimacy, relevance and impact, should offer a promising metaphor for enhancing value propositions (Lenz and Jeppesen, 2022). In this regard, technology can improve IA performance in a risk-based manner while considering that environmental changes are crucial, and internal auditors' characteristics must be clarified to effectively implement IT, big data analytics, and artificial intelligence to develop and implement efficient IA practices that can help prevent fraud and promote good governance (Hazaea *et al.*, 2022; Nerantzidis *et al.*, 2022). The literature argues that changing governance effectively develops IA practices and advanced models that predict IA effectiveness (Lenz and Hoos, 2023). For instance, ESG risks pose significant challenges and threats to the role of IA in the banking sector and must be addressed to ensure the effectiveness of the IBA framework. This research considers that external element changes affect the transformation of IA and its role in implementing the IBA framework, which provides value propositions, value creation and a competitive advantage to the banking sector. This research also confirms that operational and IT resilience and digital transformation play a significant role in developing and implementing IA, particularly in banks in Bangladesh.

The findings also indicate that the banking sector should modify its IA procedures by addressing challenges, tools, and skills, thus supporting the notion that technology can transform banks by altering their operations. For instance, artificial intelligence is advancing from simple task automation to full-process automation in conjunction with other intelligent automation technologies in the banking sector (Islam and Stafford, 2021). This development should enhance data analysis accuracy and speed, financial reporting and compliance, user experience and services, risk management, and fraud detection. Consequently,

technological innovation boosts the effectiveness and efficiency of IA by improving data analysis capabilities, meeting stakeholder expectations, and adapting to changing business dynamics. This should enable internal auditors to respond quickly and adaptably to changes, and deliver more value by providing advanced analyses, strategic recommendations, and predictive insights. Therefore, a strategic task should be incrementally innovating in a manner that integrates stakeholder expectations, technological developments, and the need to respond quickly and reliably to changes in risk, work trends, and macroeconomic advances. By adopting innovative IA practices, the IA department can continuously enhance its methodologies, tools, and processes to improve its performance in a rapidly changing business environment.

The increasing prevalence of unpredictable risks has necessitated innovative technologies that offer both challenges and opportunities. For instance, cutting-edge analytics can help uncover hidden risks that were previously obscured by historical data. Research suggests that artificial intelligence has the potential to revolutionise the workplace by automating tasks such as data collection, manipulation, form-filling, calculations, and predictable actions based on predefined logic or decision trees (Jokipii and Rautiainen, 2023). When combined with machine learning, artificial intelligence can perform more intricate tasks, such as budgeting and forecasting. Although critical thinking and problem-solving cannot be fully automated and require a human brain, artificial intelligence can be used to handle structured data. However, it is limited when it comes to providing a deeper understanding of human behaviour and experiences, as it lacks the ability to contextualise information.

Banking organisations should strategically integrate artificial intelligence into their IA processes and educate internal auditors on their applications, advantages, and limitations. Internal auditors must also develop the skills necessary to audit machines and automated processes, which are becoming increasingly relevant in banks. Understanding how artificial intelligence processes information is crucial for improving human-machine communication, and achieving consistent results is just one of the many specialised skills required to navigate new technologies in the banking sector. As data-driven decision making becomes the norm, banking organisations must develop a comprehensive digital strategy to ensure that data are treated as valuable assets that can assist in making informed decisions and improving operations. This involves data collection, storage, governance, analysis, and utilisation.

Although technology offers several benefits, it also poses significant challenges and limitations such as cybersecurity. With the increasing reliance on digital systems and interconnected technologies, cyber threats continue to evolve in the banking sector, posing significant risks to data privacy, financial systems, and business continuity. Another challenge faced by IA is the impact of climate change and sustainability. IA is expected to make realistic risk assessments and informed decisions regarding the effectiveness of the implemented sustainability measures, estimate these risks accurately, and ensure that appropriate measures are implemented to mitigate them. Overall, it is crucial for banking organisations to address these challenges and develop strategies to navigate the ever-changing technological landscape.

6.3 Synthesis of research findings

By addressing the challenges through research objectives, the identified empirical findings represent a knowledge extension in the context of the banking sector. This research examined empirical evidence to investigate the key IA challenges, current IA practices, IA alignment with key input factors, IA foundation factors, and IA integration factors that comprise an effective IBA framework for the banking sector. Chapters 2 and 3 formed the foundation for the theoretical underpinnings, which are addressed in research objective 1. This section synthesises the research findings to provide a more complete understanding of the discoveries.

Table 6.2 Summary of research findings

Research objectives	Key factors (Themes)	Research findings (Sub-themes)
RO1: Identify and evaluate the current challenges of internal auditing in banks	Key challenges of IA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of strategic vision of IA (29.78%) Lack of risk-based IA approach (27.68%) Lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance (26.87%) IT systems and technology risks (26.14%) Lack of resources and talent management (25.73%) Lack of agile auditing methodologies (24.23%) Lack of strong internal control systems (22.26%) Lack of clear methodology to leverage technology (20.32%) Poor application of regulations and standards (14.26%)
RO2: Analyse the current practices of internal auditing in banks	Nature of IA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology development (26.93%) Internal control process (22.16%) Prevention of errors and fraud (36.70%) Aligned assurance (14.20%)
	Effective IA practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk-based IA plan (56.64%)

		Systematic process and implementation (21.94%)
	Factors that hinder good IA practices	Internal factors (i.e. control, governance, operation and risks) (49.67%) External factors (i.e. outsourcing, government) (17.35%)
RO3: Evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh to develop an effective IBA framework	Aligning IA with key input factors	Safeguarding assets (45.28%) Human capital and talent management (44.27%) Digital disruption and cybersecurity (35.32%) Regulatory compliance (33.10%) Operational and IT resilience (31.52%) IA Positioning (28.49%) Key emerging risk and control analysis (13.65%) Internal control systems quality (10.24%)
	Key foundation factors of IA	Monitoring (45.91%) Digital transformation (24.35%) Risk and risk maturity (23.28%) Process and control implementation (22.36%) Value creation of IA (16.72%)
	Importance of IA integration	Compliance monitoring of operational controls (33.72%) Information and communication (29.17%) Innovative auditing IA department (23.87%) Fraud detection and investigation (22.07%) Technical skills, knowledge and capabilities (20.87%) Integrated financial reporting (17.27%) Innovative audit delivery and change (17.68%) Integrated risk evaluation and monitoring (16.19%)
	Importance of internal and external environment	BOD and the AC support Align to strategic vision and mindsets (13.39%) Dynamic risk assessment (26.16%) Quality assurance and improvement (11.74%) Resources (49.67%) Outsourcing (9.38%)

Source: The Researcher

As summarised in Table 6.2, the empirical findings are critical factors in the development of a validated IBA framework and its successful implementation with practical guidance in the banking sector. The findings are solely based on the responses of interviewees to banking organisations. These findings provide suggestive evidence for understanding the challenges that affect IA implementation as well as contribute to identifying key factors in the development of an IBA framework applicable to the banking sector, which is discussed in the following section.

6.4 Validation of the IBA framework

The purpose of this section is to incorporate the empirical findings into the theoretical IBA framework depicted in Figure 3.4. The Researcher conducted an in-depth systematic gap analysis using the four-quadrant framework, which resulted in the validation of key framework elements. This section validates the IBA framework and provides practical guidance for implementation based on the findings of academic and industry-based research contributions as well as the findings of the empirical investigation. In this regard, the Researcher intends to analyse theoretical assumptions gathered from the literature as discussed in Chapters 2 and 3 through empirical analysis and validate the theoretical IBA framework.

The theoretical IBA framework is based on five derivatives: literature review (derivate one), systematic literature evaluation (derivate two), research gaps (derivate three), supporting theories (derivate four) and supporting frameworks (derivate five). Despite the fact that it incorporates derivatives and a two-dimensional view of academic and industry perspectives, this initial version of the framework serves as a baseline for the validation phase. Its primary goal was to fill the literature gap (Sub-Section 3.2.1) by aligning IA with key elements of the internal and external environment in the context of the banking sector. The Researcher first investigated the current IA challenges as described in Chapters 2 and 3, then empirically elaborated on their significant consequences for effective IA practices to improve the effectiveness of IA in Chapters 5 and 6. The final step is to provide a validated IBA framework to the academia and industry with a proposed five-step guidance for implementing the framework.

Referring to Section 3.4, the theoretical IBA framework was developed around four key elements: IA input factors, IA foundation, IA integration and output factors, each representing a fundamental element of the internal and external organisational contexts for IA implementation with significant benefits for banking organisations. External circumstances, such as regulatory, financial, political, economic or cultural changes, are assumed to have an impact on banking organisations. Key banking auditing challenges, IA alignment with emerging risks, internal control systems, IA standards and governance, and IA quality assurance are the key input elements highlighted by the SLR, as shown in Figure 3.4. Furthermore, the four major elements of the IA foundation pillar are the IA process, IA functions, IA practices and IA effectiveness (Sub-Section 3.5.2), whereas the IA role and profession, IA policy and framework, and IA structure and reporting are considered key IA integration elements in the theoretical IBA framework.

Based on the empirical investigation, the Researcher sought to validate the importance of key factors influencing the implementation of the IBA framework (Figure 6.1), which were outlined as theoretical pillars in Figure 3.4. That means the IBA framework depicted in Figure 6.1 reflects some key empirical findings that influenced the evaluation of the theoretical version of the framework given in Figure 3.4. It also shows which organisational aspects have changed because of the empirical findings; all major changes to the theoretical framework are highlighted in red. The steps outlined in Section 6.5 of the practical guidance are represented by the numbers 1 to 5 in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Validated IBA framework

Source: The Researcher

A comparison of Figures 3.4 and 6.1 reveals that the IA integration pillar is undergoing the most significant transformation due to the findings discussed in Chapters 5 and 6, where a new element, IA governance, has been added. This would be performed before IBA framework and IA integration tasks are carried out, resulting in IA alignment implementation now being considered as three stages, which are discussed in detail in subsequent sections. This new element demonstrates how important it is for the banking sector to have a

coordinated effort of an innovative department, technical skills, knowledge and competency, fraud prevention and detection, information and communication, innovative audit delivery and change in the IA implementation cycle. Building internal support for IA, as well as incorporating human capital and talent management, and operational and IT resilience into the IBA framework, is among the first steps towards addressing digital disruption and cybersecurity. This also shows how important it is to have good IA governance in the internal environment.

The transformation of the IBA framework (Figure 6.1) into a cyclical element is another change to the IA foundation element. The empirical investigation has identified key elements of IA that should work together to achieve an efficient and effective balanced framework such as BOD and AC support, quality assurance and improvement, and policy and framework supported by control, governance, risks, operations and outsourcing. Because there is no universal approach to IA, the expectation gap between 'what the audit does and does not do' remains a source of concern for the IA department. As regulators shift towards integrated financial reports, internal auditors and ACs provide more insight and perspective, which results in expectations rising. The unpredictability of output creates risk and complicates IA in addressing how the interconnection of the five elements contributes to the output of technological applications. In today's unique environment, having a well-defined IA foundation adds value and increases an organisation's effectiveness, but planning and being able to react quickly to new risks are needed for successful IA. Thus, IA priorities should be aligned with the goals of the organisation with a focus on the risks that have the greatest chance of preventing the organisation from achieving its goals.

The IA integration originally comprised of IA role and performance, IA policy and framework and IA structure and reporting (Sub-Section 3.4.3), whereas Figure 6.1 shows the IA governance element as part of the IA integration that now consists of the following: an innovative IA department; technical skills, knowledge and competency; fraud prevention and detection; information and communication; and innovative audit delivery and change. The empirical findings showed two integration-related elements to be critical to IA implementation, which are an innovative IA department, and fraud prevention and detection. To support this notion, the BOD and the AC need to develop IA strategies to ensure that the audit work remains relevant and useful in ensuring that resilience is built within the operating model of organisations. In this regard, the focus should be on ensuring visible impact in the delivery of audit activities. For instance, agile auditing processes promise a more dynamic approach to audit work that focuses on delving into matters and bringing resolutions through

shorter and more collaborative methods. As a result of this, the agile approach brings the same dynamic into assurance audits. This means that the agile approach helps to build strategies that clearly show the impact of the audit work and bring value to organisations.

After analysing and synthesising the empirical findings (Chapters 5 and 6), the Researcher concluded that the following key elements should be considered at an organisational level as continuing efforts throughout implementation, rather than as discrete phrases:

- Align to strategic vision and mindsets
- Dynamic risk assessment
- Risk and risk maturity
- Integrated risk evaluation and monitoring
- Accountability
- Internal control process
- Safeguarding assets
- Compliance monitoring of operational controls
- Integrated financial reporting

Banking organisations have experienced failures of elaborate strategies drafted by experts because their organisational culture is not aligned with the business strategies. The purpose and vision of the organisation must be clearly communicated by the top management, and the organisation's beliefs and values must also be aligned. In this case, IA plans, organisational culture and the IA strategy formulation process are all relevant. They need to be involved in agility, digital transformation and evolving new business models, while IA's role in assessing the culture and strategies is more important in aligning the strategic purpose and vision. Creating a dynamic risk assessment necessitates identifying the risk categories in banks. For example, money laundering, terrorist financing and other illegal financial activities can take place through a variety of different methods or channels. Even within the same risk category, a spectrum of risks may be noticeable. As appropriate, a bank's risk assessment process should address the various degrees of risk associated with its products, services, customers and geographic locations. Improper risk identification and assessment can have a big impact, causing problems in many areas of internal controls and a weak compliance plan.

Various external and internal risks must be assessed by the IA department. Setting up objectives that are interconnected and internally consistent is a pre-requisite for risk

assessment. Risk assessment is the identification and analysis of relevant risks to achieving the objectives. Because economic, industry, regulatory and operating conditions have changed, mechanisms for identifying and mitigating unique risks are required. Furthermore, the difficulties in staffing the IA department are associated with a scarcity of qualified candidates who possess the unique set of skills required in the modern IA department. In order to be effective, analytical abilities, business knowledge, communication skills, integrity, courage and conflict resolution abilities are just a few of the critical skills and attributes required in the IA department.

Many IA practitioners raise the question of independence when concerned about providing insights and opinions to management. While stakeholders want internal auditors to be actively involved with their insights and advice, independence is important and must not be ignored. For instance, internal auditors can choose which consulting services can be performed without compromising independence, both individually and functionally. IA is strategically placed in an organisation to give their point of view, challenge management or provide insights. These inputs can be valuable in bridging the gap between perception and reality. IA is also a catalyst for change in an organisation and promotes collaboration for the benefit of the organisation. When IA provides insights supported by data, research or best practices, it is an independent point of view and not a biased opinion.

Respondents also reported that the role of IA is dynamic and unconventional and many people find it difficult to understand. To achieve the strategic objectives and solve problems, a CAE or head of the IA department influences behaviours, becomes a change agent and produces accountability. Hence, a CAE or head of the IA department is called a catalyst and strategist when supporting the achievement of an organisation's strategies by partnering with the business and providing advice and insights on anticipated risks. To meet the service requirements and become a catalyst and strategist, a CAE must balance their talents, capabilities and costs. In addition, a CAE is also stewards when providing independent and objective assurance to the AC and top management.

The development of the IBA framework was based on the identified IA challenges, which were initially examined and raised regarding their practice and effectiveness in the banking sector. Further validation of the framework confirmed by the respondents helps in assessing its adoption, acceptability and utilisation for implementing risk-based IA, which makes it effective at identifying and managing risks, and addressing broader organisational issues, such as strategic alignment or external environmental sustainability. However, the

application of technology enables banking organisations to change and evolve, thereby creating and developing internal control capabilities and allowing internal auditors to adapt to the changes carried by technological changes in the current business environment (Shuwaili *et al.*, 2022; Parves and Bhuyan, 2023). The ultimate goal of the framework is to contribute to the efficient implementation of integration with key internal governance systems, resulting in efficient process and control implementation and demonstrating a comprehension of how to measure performance through IA in banks and Bangladesh. The framework is persuaded to support the implementation of consistency across the banking sector, which reduces the disparity between financial and operational audits, because managing compliance takes time, which is critical for achieving IA activities that lack IA staffing and resources.

The framework should contribute towards adaptation to a changing landscape that includes rapid changes in technology, business models and stakeholder expectations, which are the key reasons for the contradiction between financial and operational audits. Furthermore, this research makes a valuable contribution to building trust in financial reporting and internal control management to improve financial transparency and corporate governance, which lacked in the existing frameworks in the context of banking sector (Almodallah, Shahimi and Azmi, 2023; Grima *et al.*, 2023). However, the exclusion of financial statement disclosures from financial reporting weakens compliance efforts (Hazaea *et al.*, 2023) and proper IA planning and implementation within a highly complex and difficult environment for determining capital requirements and risk assessments, resulting in inconsistencies and a lack of transparency in the IA programme and internal quality assessment (Gurrea-Martínez and Remolina, 2019). Thus, the validated framework intends to guide the use of various resources, tools and techniques that BOD, AC and internal auditors can adopt to improve performance and their ability to effectively manage and explore human capital, talent management, operational resilience, and IT resilience to tackle digital disruption and cybersecurity. It would be pertinent for the banking sector to improve performance, highlighting the need for more efficiency and effectiveness in financial reporting by creating digital transformations that acquire, assimilate, transform, and leverage technology.

The empirical evidence indicates that the banking sector is facing significant pressure from internal and external factors to implement IA across banking organisations. This also suggests that IA has evolved from a compliance exercise to an accounting tool, and that the alignment of IA with strategic vision and mindsets has been a critical factor in the long-term sustainability and accountability of the IBA framework. However, technological

advancements and incremental improvements through the application of the IBA framework are necessary to ensure the continued success of IA.

The proposed IBA framework (Figure 6.1) was validated using the responses of 21 experts through a thematic analysis. This research is novel in that it develops a validated IBA framework for evaluating the implementation efforts and benefits of IA for the banking sector in Bangladesh. This framework also provides a practical guidance for incorporating IA into a banking organisation's strategy. However, the final framework will be tested and applied in a real-world work environment to further refine and eliminate any weaknesses in the framework. The following sub-sections focus on providing a practical guidance for each key implementation phase, as depicted in Figure 6.1.

6.5 Practical guidance for implementing the IBA framework

As stated in Section 1.5, the purpose of this research is to investigate the challenges that IA faces as well as to establish an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance for the banking sector. In this section, a practical road map is provided, outlining five phases (numbers 1-5 shown in Figure 6.1) for implementing the IBA framework. This practical guidance helps provide a way to strengthen an organisation's IA approach and communicate its IA practices to internal and external stakeholders. As previously indicated, this guidance is created for organisations at various stages of IA development and implementation. Organisations can use this practical guidance to accomplish the following:

- Describe their current and future IA challenges;
- Identify methods to improve their current IA programmes;
- Recognise existing banking tools, standards and guidelines that may be useful in implementing the framework;
- Assess and inform about IA strategy to internal and external stakeholders.

Regardless of an organisation's current IA practice, this practical guidance can be incorporated into an organisation's strategic vision. Also, this guidance can assist organisations that do not have a formal IA programme in understanding, evaluating and establishing the organisation's main IA activities and its strategic priorities. This guidance provides additional ways to analyse existing IA programmes and identify areas for improvement, while aligning current efforts to the framework for those organisations that have a formal IA programme in place.

6.5.1 Phrase 1: Establishing the external environment

The Researcher believes that banking organisations are operating in an increasingly complex and competitive organisational environment that is subject to the external dynamics. This section emphasises the importance of establishing to external context in which banking organisations operate as the first crucial phrase in constructing the IBA framework (Figure 6.1, Phrase 1). A variety of factors influence how banking organisations operate including regulatory, political, economic, cultural and financial aspects. These external factors should have an impact on existing IA practices in banks, addressing the BOD and the AC to adapt to the sustainable environment. However, external factors influence the internal organisational setting in which banking organisations evolve. The Researcher suggests that as a first step in implementing the IBA framework, the BOD and the AC should investigate external contexts by applying and establishing different analytical tools and techniques.

The findings of this research indicate that the external environment has become more difficult, particularly when it comes to dealing with diverse external risks and changes in regulations found in more digital and integrated activities. As a result of this transformative external environment, the IA role has evolved in recent years. In addition to assessing more specific business, strategic and functional risks, the BOD and the AC should consult with the IA department for insights into dynamic risk assessment across the organisation. This means that the IA team must stay involved in business integrations and IT system installations and meet with stakeholders on a regular basis to discuss the potential changes that these initiatives may bring to the organisation, the risk landscape, the compliance culture and other critical areas. PESTEL (political, economic, social-cultural, technical, environmental and legal) and SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) analysis can be used to investigate external factors and their impacts on banking organisations. The PESTEL framework can be used to identify macro-environmental issues, which helps organisations understand how they affect implementing the IBA framework to generate effective management operations. Similarly, SWOT analysis can help to identify potential or inefficient areas across the organisation. The Researcher emphasises the importance of determining which tools should assess the external environment and which are best suited to the current organisational structure.

Following on, current and future challenges should be identified and their assessment process should be aligned with the organisation's IA strategy. Such an approach is carried out by applying agile auditing methods. These help to adopt a more dynamic approach to

IA, focusing on delving deeper into issues and resolving them in more time-efficient, collaborative ways. The flexibility of IA enables the BOD and the AC to tailor the IBA framework to specific organisational needs and objectives while leveraging IA practices that have previously been shown to be effective across the organisation. Finally, human capital and talent management, operational and IT resilience, digital disruption and cybersecurity should all be included within the IA strategy for recognising and assessing external influences.

6.5.2 Phrase 2: Understanding key IA input factors

Following the determination of the external environment's dynamics, the Researcher proposes that the BOD and the AC should focus on understanding and identifying the essential IA input factors of the internal environment that appropriately align its critical elements (Phrase 2). IA input elements are as follows: (i) key IA challenges, (ii) key emerging risks, (iii) internal control systems, (iv) regulatory compliance, and (v) IA positioning, which are critical to the IBA framework's development and implementation (Figure 6.1). These IA activities not only identify and comprehend high-level organisational goals and strategies, but also help the techniques used to achieve the specific organisational goals by identifying key challenges and emerging risks. In this regard, business objectives are classified as strategic, functional, or process-level in some organisations.

To gain a better understanding of the challenges and expectations as well as opportunities to engage and assist organisations in innovative ways, the BOD and the AC should align their strategic vision and mindsets. These trends highlight the importance of IA becoming more technologically enabled, having essential skill sets aligned with IA practices and achieving real-time risk management and control engagement. In order for IA to be aligned with the strategic vision and mindset, key challenges and risks must be identified, analysed, and mitigated. In order to better serve the organisation, management must take the lead in reforming IA. This entails developing a roadmap as well as cultivating an innovative internal control system and mindset that needs to be integrated into audit service delivery.

Based on the findings of this research, internal motivations for changing the role of IA capabilities required to meet emerging business risks, as well as heightened stakeholder expectations and adaptability, are significant success factors. Management must start thinking differently by re-evaluating the design and capabilities of IA in a way that embraces the benefits of methods and technologies that are transformational. This should be accomplished by increasing IA effectiveness and efficiency while fulfilling the core mission

of the function, which is to protect organisational value and maintain regulatory compliance. As the banking sector evolves and changes, it is critical that the BOD and the AC consider the organisation's specific risk environment and organisational objectives, which have proven beneficial in the growing number of IA transformations. The Researcher agrees with Lenz and Hahn (2015), who discuss the cross-sectoral model of GRC functions and roles (Chapter 2), that the BOD and the AC should concisely and effectively keep good practice models. The findings in Chapters 5 and 6 support the Researcher's claims that the foundation of a good practice model is the creation of dynamic and robust governance responsibilities as well as clear frameworks and guidance.

This section considers the need to be involved with an organisation's compliance efforts with applicable laws and regulations as an integral part of internal control systems, in addition to the key IA input factors that are critical to the implementation process. However, it is important to note that compliance efforts are the responsibility of management. The IA's role is to ensure that management meets that responsibility through risk evaluation and monitoring. The Researcher believes that the BOD and the AC should focus on identifying and compiling culture, cooperation, effectiveness, performance and a framework that IA should consider when developing the IA plan, while keeping in mind the significant challenges and risks. The Researcher emphasises the importance of aligning IA with key challenges, risks, controls, compliance and positioning. Internal factors discussed in this section should be well-understood, well-defined, measured, aligned with one another and integrated into the IA programme and strategy.

6.5.3 Phrase 3: Defining IA foundation factors

The importance of defining the IA foundation elements is emphasised in this section. The determination of the IA process, functions, practices and effectiveness has been a recurring theme in the literature (Beasley *et al.*, 2009; Lenz and Hahn, 2015). BODs and ACs are still struggling to determine the best IA methodology for ensuring successful IA functions, practices and effectiveness. Organisations can delegate responsibility for IA practices to various groups or committees, but depending on the type of organisation, implementing appropriate processes and controls is a good place to start. The BOD and the AC must think holistically to improve the performance of IA processes and organisational business models. In this context, it is critical to build new learning spaces where techniques and teams can differentiate efficient processes to make rapid progress and regularly implement new advancements into the IA process.

IA can support strategic digital objectives in a variety of ways, which include ensuring that the organisation understands how digital and other innovation initiatives align with and enable the overall corporate strategy (i.e. what their purpose is and why they are important). In the case of projects that have been derailed due to disruption caused by the pandemic, for example, an IA can assist the BOD and the AC in understanding these issues and bringing projects back on track through closer oversight and input from senior management. As a result of unprecedented growth opportunities for the IA profession and advances in technology, the globalisation process has accelerated significantly. The complexity and sophistication of banking operations has necessitated significant changes in governance, risk management, controls, and compliance processes. It is clear that all of these changes present enormous opportunities for internal, co-sourced and external IA functions to add even more value to their respective organisations.

To ensure that the risk assessment process is simple to complete and produces high-quality results, the IA foundation must be supported by a risk-based plan. As part of the risk assessment process, the scope, context and criteria should all be clearly defined. In this regard, defining risk criteria and risk models in the future must necessitate a more focused and collaborative approach in which organisations should work more effectively together. This means that the BOD and the AC should assess how reliable and practical their organisation's risk criteria and models are for identifying and assessing risks. They should investigate how organisations can use collaborative risk scenario development to assess risks holistically. Previous judgemental approaches should not limit the scope and context of the risk-based IA plan. Finally, the Researcher emphasises the IA's support for the concept of simplicity in defining the IA foundation elements appropriate for each banking institution. The BOD and AC should focus on determining which IA process is best for their organisation, then focus on how to implement it across the organisation, measure its effectiveness and ensure accountability.

6.5.4 Phrase 4: Designing IBA framework

This section provides recommendations for implementing the IBA framework elements of the IA integration pillar, which connects critical internal elements like BOD and AC support, quality assurance and improvement, policy and framework (control, governance, risks and operation), and outsourcing. Each element must be thoroughly understood, defined and aligned with the IA integration pillar. In Sub-Section 3.4.3, IA integration is presented as a major element of a dynamic IBA framework that can support effective implementation across

the organisation. Because the IBA framework pillar design is a new addition to the validated IBA framework shown in Figure 6.1, this section provides practical implementation guidance.

Firstly, the Researcher recommends that top management begin designing the IBA framework by understanding strategic inputs and ensuring that the organisation remains resilient in achieving organisational objectives. Despite the fact that organisations may not plan audits based on traditional risk assessment, the analysis may indicate that the area is high risk. Thus, it is recommended that the BOD and the AC continue to look for key risk indicators and create dashboards for ongoing risk monitoring. The Researcher also notes that an annual risk-based assessment founded on business objectives and strategy provides an understanding of the risks that are expected to appear on the organisation's objectives, but there should be a quarterly agenda item for top management to discuss any risks that have surfaced which have not been discussed or have been missed. In aligning the audit approach with the organisation's strategic objectives, the annual risk assessment should include quality assurance and improvement, adding value to the organisation.

The roles of the BOD and the AC are demanding more elaborate reporting structures and the large number of stakeholders that IA serves sets the BOD and the AC apart from other executive positions. Even if the BOD and AC roles are unique, they must use their business acumen to view the IA department as a part of the organisation to be successful. Practical business experience and the ability to deal with situations that arise in the organisation on a regular basis are the two factors required for good business acumen. A good understanding of the organisation's strategy and the industry in which it operates is also part of business acumen. A successful IA leader must align IA activities with the organisation's strategy and priorities.

The literature review found that the majority of researchers, including industry practitioners, believe that internal controls are the responsibility of IA. Internal controls include explaining the difference between IA and internal controls to business process and risk owners. Internal controls are actually the responsibility of an organisation's highest level of governance, which has been delegated to various functions in recent years. All functions within an organisation must maintain and improve internal controls. Internal auditors and non-auditors, for example, manage stakeholders' expectations of IA as the function responsible for internal controls in various organisations. Even within the IA profession, however, the vast majority of people are unaware of the distinction between IA and internal controls. This is primarily due to the fact that the two functions have always been combined over the years,

whereas today, with the exception of some large organisations, IA is always combined with internal control, risk management or compliance functions, which can impact the auditor's objectivity and independence.

Formulating a dynamic IBA framework is central to the employment of IA implementation. Identifying the organisation's IA strategies, the risks associated with developing a plan and operational activities as a business leader, is helped by spending time with other business leaders in the organisation who can assist. The Researcher recommends speaking to stakeholders as a business leader, not an auditor, by addressing issues from their perspective and using language they understand. Although each stakeholder has different expectations, it is a worthwhile exercise for the BOD and AC to engage with their own stakeholders to explore where they excel and where they can improve to add value to the IA role and the organisation. Stakeholder feedback and advice are extremely important tools that the BOD and AC can use in their pursuit of continuous improvement.

The respondents in this research strongly believed that while many qualities are required of IA leaders, communication and relationship-building skills are critical for IA in gaining, obtaining and maintaining buy-in from other executives and leaders in the organisation. This is also significant because internal auditors must be influential and able to communicate effectively to play a key role in the organisation. Knowing the key stakeholders and employing strategies and communication styles to positively influence the BOD and AC in developing relationships is key. Furthermore, the BOD and the AC must gain the trust of the stakeholders, which can be accomplished by understanding their needs and providing valuable insights and advice. Partially outsourcing IA can also help a bank's management keep competitors from learning about its competitive advantage, confidential information or bank-specific technology. Those functions that do not involve sensitive information can be outsourced to competent service providers, saving the bank the costs of full-time internal staff members to manage an outsourceable function. Increasing cost-effectiveness, profitability, liquidity and solvency would improve bank' financial performance.

The IBA framework, which incorporates key findings from qualitative research, emphasises the importance of banking organisation's understanding, defining, aligning and communicating the critical elements of IA at all stages of implementation. Providing the appropriate level of human capital and talent management, supported by operational and IT resilience, can ensure that implementation is effective and well-accepted throughout the organisation. Policies and frameworks for control, governance, risks and operations must

be simple, practical, easy to understand and supported by top management to be effective and sustainable.

6.5.5 Phrase 5: Aligning IA governance as part of the IA integration

Establishing an innovative IA department, developing technical skills, knowledge and competency, fraud detection and prevention, information and communication, innovative audit delivery and change are all part of the IA governance phrase. The Researcher suggests that the BOD include a sufficient number of independent non-executive directors (NEDs) to ensure that stakeholder interests are fairly represented, and management override and collusion are avoided, and that early detection measures are in place. The NEDs' primary responsibility should be to oversee fraud risk assessment and appropriate countermeasures, while their accountability and appointment should be made directly by the shareholders.

Assuring that anti-bribery and anti-corruption legislation has resulted in clearly defined organisational anti-bribery and anti-corruption programmes should be the responsibility of top management. Structure, risk assessment (including third-party due diligence, policies and procedures), communication and training, monitoring, reports and investigations, enforcement and sanctions are part of developing and maintaining a formal anti-bribery and anti-corruption programme. The Researcher recommends that the organisation use audit observations in these and other areas. Given the current risk environment, banking sector disruption and mounting pressures on organisations, IA is poised to take the lead on a larger stage and under a brighter spotlight than ever before.

The Researcher emphasises how professional standards, internal control systems and IA operations are currently assisting in the accountability and integrity of the banking sector. Therefore, enhancements to the prevention, detection and reporting of fraud and corruption are proposed. It may be the most effective method of increasing IA's contribution to integrity, transparency and accountability. Despite the fact that IA objectives have been developed with an emphasis on GRC, this research reveals a disconnect between internal auditor tasks and the major IA objectives, with the exception of internal control and risks. Internal auditors have also provided internal consulting and advice on IT system issues, strategic risks and financial issues. Internal auditors must specify how and in what ways they can actively contribute to effective organisational governance if they are to do so. The findings of this research indicate that internal control, risk assessment and management processes are regarded as critical elements for IA to contribute to strong organisational governance.

The main observation of the Researcher regarding this stage of implementation is that it can be subjected to an organisation's cyber-related fraud risk, which is the most significant challenge faced by banking organisations for innovative audit delivery and change. Thus, banking organisations must adopt a new paradigm to reduce fraud risks. As a result of the rapid digital transformation, they must understand the evolving fraud risks and design a fraud risk management framework capable of mitigating these fraud risks sustainably, effectively, and efficiently. In addition, the next generation of fraud risk management should be able to leverage technology and reduce compliance costs. Digital fraud controls that combine advanced data analytics and human expertise to predict, prevent and detect fraud are becoming increasingly important for banks. Finally, determining the outputs of the IBA framework varies across the organisation depending on their strategic priorities. Sub-Section 3.5.4 elaborates on key benefits of the IBA framework, which is further discussed in the following section, while Chapter 7 broadens the focus on its key strengths.

6.6 Outputs of the IBA framework

Given the complexity of the IA challenges, the validated IBA framework (Figure 6.1) discovered three core outputs: sustainable competitive advantage, business performance improvement, and operational efficiency. By implementing the framework across banking organisations, which would also be customised and subject to change in various ways to enhance IA effectiveness and good governance, and ensure long-term sustainability of the IA approach.

- ***Sustainable competitive advantage:*** Currently, banking organisations face increased pressure from various stakeholders, such as regulators, customers, and society, to become more sustainable. This indicates that organisations that align their vision, strategy, and governance in their strategy and daily ways of working have a strong competitive advantage. However, when embarking on their sustainability journey, organisations should reconsider the role of their risk management and internal control culture to effectively address the opportunities and challenges that come with it. Organisations' risk management, internal control, and IA functions can add value by taking a deeper dive into identifying and mapping emerging risks specific to the organisation's context (e.g. the level of assurance, transaction and compliance audits, risks related to environmental changes), and the effectiveness of the existing internal controls.
- ***Business performance improvement:*** This IBA framework leverages existing IA activities to continuously monitor, manage, and improve business performance based

on four key benefits: interaction between the BOD and AC, alignment between organisational strategy and vision, integration with financial and technical resources, strategic mindsets, and priorities.

- **Operational efficiency:** The Researcher confirmed that the benefits of the IBA framework have significant outputs in terms of operational efficiency. This framework identifies and visualises the alignment of knowledge, skills, and competencies; integrated financial reporting; and efficient IA processes to improve IA quality and, ultimately, operational effectiveness. Additionally, respondents confirmed that the implementation of a sound framework can only significantly improve operational efficiency in the presence of effective corporate governance and internal control quality.

Given the complexity of IA and the key elements included in the IBA framework (Figure 6.1), the researcher understands and confirms that it may be difficult to adopt and implement the framework in the early stages. Academia and industry can mitigate this limitation by customising the IBA framework and conducting future research collaborations after its practical implementation.

6.7 Conclusion

This chapter investigated the implications of empirical findings and the level of agreement with the academic and industry-based literature contributions. The analysis was carried out in accordance with the research aim and objectives outlined in Section 1.5. The findings revealed that interviewees' perspectives on the key challenges in banking organisations differed, while the banking sector has been identified as lacking in an effective framework and implementation guidance.

The findings highlighted that the key challenges of IA included (i) IT systems and technology risks (43.22%), (ii) a lack of strong internal control systems (37.79%), (iii) a lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance (23.42%), (iv) a lack of risk-based IA approach (23.37%), (v) a lack of IA strategic vision (20.54%), (vi) a lack of resources and talent management (18.98%), (vii) a lack of agile auditing methodologies (16.52%), (viii) a lack of clear methodology to leverage technology (17.16%), and (ix) poor application of regulations and standards (13.87%). This chapter also considered the key challenges and various factors that impede IA practices in this context, with the aim of exploring the steps that can be taken to improve the effectiveness of IA by validating an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance.

Overall, it is possible to conclude that the contribution of empirical findings leverages the derivations that contributed to the validation of the framework. On these grounds, the IBA framework has been linked to a number of elements that define the framework's position in current IA research. Furthermore, the Researcher presented a five-phrase practical guidance for the proposed IBA framework to be implemented in banks. Finally, the following Chapter 7 concludes the research by reiterating the key findings and how they relate to the research aim, objectives and questions, respectively. It also emphasises the contributions of the research, its limitations, future research directions and recommendations.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

The Researcher examined how IA's literature has evolved, developed and validated the theoretical IBA framework (Figures 3.4 and 6.1), discussed the research methodology and methods for collecting and analysing interview data, used participants for the research samples, and conducted research in the sector specific to banking organisations. This research has produced a number of conclusions, which are summarised in this section. Based on the review of the traditional literature and SLR evaluation, the Researcher concludes that IA is under-researched and that little research has been undertaken in recent years, particularly in the context of the banking sector. Generic research on a wide range of accounting and auditing issues is becoming more common, and this opens up many opportunities in the field.

The Researcher has found that top management should plan IA in such a way that it is carried out in a cost-effective, efficient, effective and timely manner. The planning process must include the creation of a comprehensive, well-thought-out strategic plan that clearly defines the desired future of IA. Furthermore, detailed tactical plans that support the predominant strategy and clearly describe the specific initiatives required to achieve the necessary transformation are also required. Too often it is difficult for IA to enter immediately into tactical planning, particularly when it comes to the adoption of technology, without understanding how the overall strategic and tactical plans fit together. The nature, size and operation of the organisation and observations, the availability and competencies of staff, the audit methodology best suited to the operations to be audited and the general content of the report to be prepared must be considered when preparing the IA plan.

This research has revealed that IA must carry out actions that support the IA strategy in the banking sector. Annual IA planning and assurance engagements are two major activities that produce the IA strategy. The annual IA plan's focus must be on enabling value delivery that is consistent with the value proposition and the expectations of key stakeholders as well as being consistent with the organisation's risks, objectives and strategies. In contrast, IA engagements must focus on improving the effectiveness of the organisation's GRC processes. The annual IA plan and IA engagements must be risk-based with effective and efficient execution. This necessitates the creation of IA manuals and the standardisation of IA processes and reporting. IA assurance activities must be coordinated with other

assurance providers to avoid gaps. Audit work must be done well and with due professional care.

It is critical to identify, analyse, evaluate and prioritise the risks that an organisation faces when approaching risk assessment, allowing them to take a holistic view of the problem and attack its root causes. The findings of this research revealed that risk assessment allows an organisation to identify deficiencies in its operations. In addition, the evaluation, design and implementation of IA activities must start with a thorough self-diagnosis that includes the contributions of functional leaders in charge of various areas who have a better understanding of the emerging risks that the organisation is currently faces. This process prioritises risks based on their possibility of occurrence, the impact they may have on the organisation and the factors that contribute to them. Based on this evaluation, organisations allocate the necessary and sufficient financial and technical resources to prioritise and address the most significant compliance and strategic risks. This process assesses existing controls, detects hidden threats and develops risk-mitigation strategies.

To the best of the Researcher's knowledge, little academic research has been conducted to date into the investigation of current challenges in the banking sector. This research has found that the technological revolution has transformed the way consumers conduct and interact with their banking operations. Therefore, banking organisations must provide innovative services for customers or face competition from other financial institutions and service providers. For instance, technology adoption is driving internal efficiency and effectiveness, and client-facing innovation, necessitating more adaptable IA resources and talents with technical skills, knowledge and competency in the current organisational setting. To address this challenge, an orderly succession plan for 'critical roles' within IA is required, with the aim of analysing leadership requirements and mitigating the impact of potential key personnel outflows. In this way, organisations can use professional development programmes, managerial feedback, training, continuing education and mentoring as common ways to grow and keep talent in the same place.

The findings of this research indicate that the current risk and control environment has made finding and retaining talent difficult. This has two implications for IA: as a process needs to be in place to attract and retain talent, and a continuous IA programme needs to be in place. It must ensure that the organisation has a process in place to attract and retain talent through role and performance measurement, and also that it develops a continuous IA programme to ensure that IA professionals have critical thinking skills, auditing knowledge and

technological competency. Internal auditors, for example, are expected to meet existing needs and legal requirements in terms of flexibility, function and quality, as raising awareness and appreciation for IA throughout the organisation is an important responsibility.

There have been few empirical academic studies that attempt to explain why IA must consider a wide range of emerging risk factors throughout the digital transformation life cycle to ensure that GRC mechanisms are well integrated into banking operations. Banking organisations should develop a solid digital strategy to ensure that IT-related developments are well-managed, generate a return on investment, and meet organisational needs and stakeholders' expectations. There is a poor understanding of how the IA department should ensure that the regulatory compliance function has adequate controls. This could be guided by a dynamic risk assessment and establishing an internal control process that identifies regulatory priorities and evolves based on changing organisational requirements. The Researcher believes that future collaboration should examine challenges facing IA such as a lack of organisational knowledge, a lack of audit action in monitoring processes, a lack of top management support and external auditors' preference not to rely on the work of the IA.

The findings of this research revealed that the development and implementation of IA have faced significant challenges due to a lack of institutional capacity, the different strengths of accounting standards used and the existence of social consensus to carry out audit work in the banking sector. This can be overcome by strengthening long-term auditing resilience, which requires modern financial management to strengthen the overall IA function. Banking organisations continue to face significant challenges because of the macro-economic environment, keeping up with technological change, shifting customer behaviours and expectations, new competitors and a complex regulatory landscape. There is a clear need for a framework that can be used to look at how an organisation's strategic approach to IA can improve accountability and help it be more sustainable.

The Researcher recognises that when confronted with a challenge, there are always unique opportunities to assess creativity and ingenuity, which can be grouped into common categories with similar themes. This indicates that the organisational environment is changing and that new opportunities are being explored through the development of an innovative IA department and the alignment of the IA strategy with the organisational strategy. Addressing the challenges could have substantial consequences, implying that effective leadership at top management is required to recognise and elevate the IA department's stature and reputation. The most important things are to keep improving

through new tools, techniques and practices, to keep being professional, to keep learning and to show dedication to the IA field through better management oversight.

Similarly, this research found that IA must develop a dynamic risk-based IA plan to adapt to changing environments and become indispensable by utilising data analytics and technology-based auditing tools. Furthermore, a new type of IA known as 'agile auditing' is emerging, which is required for continuous management collaboration and an iterative auditing approach to ensure organisations meet expectations. Internal auditors must adopt this approach to remain effective and provide real value in banking organisations. The audit approach is expected to be based on a clear and concise systematic methodology. Thus, more IA professionals should be included in the audit team to make the professional judgements required to reach an opinion and work independently and objectively, which is required for organisational independence.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from this research is that IA provides a holistic view of management's priorities in risk management and quality assurance, which can be achieved through a shared strategic vision that enables such a transformation in organisations. Furthermore, the status of the IA function should correspond to senior management's expectations for it to be viewed as critical within organisations, whereas internal auditors should demonstrate business acumen and add value to the organisation. The research also shows that the activities of internal auditors are changing, as is the complexity of business transactions in a more dynamic regulatory environment, implying that more work is involved in developing the expanded set of skills and knowledge required to perform audits. Laws and regulations for IA are seen as the main problems that make it ineffective.

The Researcher concludes that internal auditors are increasingly expected to provide a more forward-looking view of the world and insights that can add value to IA. Future researchers should use larger samples and more sophisticated data collection and analysis technologies as well as conduct deeper analyses in the areas of IA. The future development of IA is critically dependent on human capital and talent management, operational and IT resilience, and the BOD and AC support for IA development and implementation.

To summarise, in developing and implementing IA priorities must be shifted away from compliance and financial controls and towards risk coverage and organisational relevance, which necessitates identifying and prioritising tasks that contribute positively to the

organisation's success. The most important ways to overcome this are to define and refine the strategic IA vision, develop the ability to monitor emerging risks, improve risk identification and assessment processes, and focus on high-risk areas through the development of an appropriate risk-based IA plan. It is also critical to create comprehensive data analytics programmes that are integrated into the audit life cycle and to align IA activities to measure effectiveness and contribute to the achievement of the organisation's goals. Identifying cost-saving opportunities and lowering overall IA costs while improving risk coverage could be achieved by structuring IA to meet the needs of the organisation by balancing assurance and advisory work without compromising independence.

The remainder of this chapter discusses the research aim, objectives and questions that consider the empirical findings. Sections 7.3 and 7.4 investigate contributions of research in terms of knowledge and practice, and research limitations, respectively. In Section 7.5, the Researcher makes recommendations for future research.

7.2 Research aim, questions and objectives

This section demonstrates that the research aim, objectives and questions stated in Sections 1.5 and 1.6 have been met and answered. The research aim is as follows:

- To investigate the challenges facing IA in the banking sector and to develop an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance.

The evaluation of the systematic literature and the collection of interview data show that the above research aim has been met. Chapters 2 and 3 revealed various aspects of academic and industry-based contributions that identified key challenges and significant IA elements (both internal and external) to fill research gaps in the banking sector. This enabled a discussion of previously published IA research with a solid theoretical and empirical foundation for the development of the theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4) in Chapter 3. The IBA framework (Figure 6.1) closes a gap in the literature by demonstrating an understanding of various IA themes and elements that have a direct impact on its design, adoption and implementation for the banking sector. Figure 6.1 reflects the empirical findings and provides the validated IBA framework with five-phrase practical guidance for the banking sector and academia.

7.2.1 Research questions related to IA research

Addressing the research questions entails investigating the research gap to ensure that the study is carried out precisely in accordance with the research aim and objectives by

revealing what is lacking in guidance. Thus, research questions are frequently viewed as extensions of aims and objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). However, the first two sub-questions in this research are based on the current challenges of IA and its practice in the banking sector in Bangladesh. The first question is as follows:

- What are the challenges facing IA in banks in general and in Bangladesh specifically?

To address this question, which concerns current challenges, the Researcher first reviewed the current IA literature, as reported in Chapters 2 and 3. Key IA challenges were identified as IT system and technology risks, a lack of agile auditing methodologies, a lack of clear methodology to leverage technology, a lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance, a lack of resources and talent management, a lack of risk-based IA approach, a lack of strong internal control systems and a poor application of regulations and standards. This research was undertaken with a specific focus on identifying the perspectives of IA professionals regarding their perceptions of the challenges faced by the IA in the banking sector. Within the theoretical exploration of the key challenges faced during implementing IA, this research identified that there is a lack of literature that focuses on the challenges of IA in banks in general and in Bangladesh specifically. Thus, the key factors acknowledged are extracted from the general literature, while some constraints reduce the potential of IA, as presented in Table 7.1 below. Likewise, the interviewees agreed on most of the key challenges as discussed in Chapters 5 and 6. Despite the industry-specific effective IA practices, this research also emphasises that the implication of limited practical guidance hinders IA implementation in banks.

Table 7.1 General and specific key challenges of IA

Literature gaps	Key factors (themes)	Key banking challenges	Key factors (themes)
The need for comprehensive understanding of IA alignment with emerging risks	IA alignment with emerging risks	IT systems and technology risks	IA alignment with emerging risks
The need for quality of the internal control systems	IA process and internal control systems	Lack of strong internal control systems	Internal control systems
The need for a changing role of IA and a leadership agenda	Changing role of IA and leadership agenda	Lack of risk-based IA approach	Risk-based IA
The need for expertise, resources and meeting a new role	Value proposition, evolving skills and competencies	Lack of resources and talent management	Resource and talent management

The need for active involvement in strategic vision development	Strategic vision and mindsets	Lack of strategic vision of IA	Strategic vision
The need for the effects of IT and the link between internal auditors and auditees	IT effects	Lack of agile auditing methodologies	Agile auditing methodology
The requirement for dependability in organisational IT systems, outputs and performance	Integrated internal controls	Lack of clear methodology to leverage technology	Leveraging technology
Poor consideration for aligning IA practice with activities, programmes and monitoring	Integrity and regulatory challenges	Poor application of regulations and standards	Regulations and standards
The need for relevant guidance for implementing the IBA framework	Effective IA implementation	Lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance	Practical guidance

Source: The Researcher

- What are the key factors that affect the IA practices in banks in Bangladesh?

To address this question, the findings of the primary and secondary research were examined, analysed and interpreted. Based on the theoretical evidence in Sections 2.4, 2.6, and 2.7, IA practice is affected by the context in which it occurs (Alhajri, 2017; Betti and Sarens, 2020; Lenz and Hoos, 2023). Due to the nature of operating conditions are different in each country, government regulations and the implementation of IA standards may vary in maintaining sustainable auditing resilience (Stewart and Subramaniam, 2010; Jarva and Zeitler, 2023). However, it is necessary to make IA more effective and efficient; thus, banking organisations should develop technology as an effective function that enhances internal control systems and risk management practices, resulting in improved financial performance and stakeholder confidence. To align strategic goals with technology adoption, which improves synergies and efficiency, it is necessary to determine the factors that make IA effective.

The interview results identifies and confirms the key factors that affect IA practices, such as biased decisions, skills, experience and technical, strategic objectives and risks, government regulations, assurance providers, regulatory bodies, and consequences, which contribute to close the literature gaps identified and presented in Table 3.6. The results of this research also confirm that integrated financial reporting and strategy implementation for

IA improves internal control effectiveness. Nonetheless, the primary challenge for effective IA practices is adapting to understanding discomfort and technological disruptions in order to be efficient. Combining IA and IT can improve the work processes of technology-related internal auditors, resulting in a profitable IT transformation in banks. Having an appropriate technology-related internal auditor work process is critical for ensuring the effective and efficient use of technology. This process can help IA improve its performance and gain a competitive advantage. For instance, internal auditors should possess the skills and knowledge necessary to perform their duties, and successfully integrate complex and sophisticated technology into their processes. The empirical findings identified significant factors affecting IA practices in the banking sector and the evidence confirmed to close the literature gaps.

The third research question addresses major steps that can be undertaken to enhance the effectiveness of IA in banks in Bangladesh.

- How can the effectiveness of IA in banks and in Bangladesh be enhanced?

The interview data analysis showed that almost 85.21% of respondents believed measuring effectiveness to be essential to developing an IBA framework, while most respondents reported that technology development, internal control process, prevention of errors and fraud, aligned assurance, risk-based IA plan and systematic process implementation were also important to enhance the effectiveness of IA. More than half of the participants agreed that a consistent change in organisational culture and attitude, improving access and engagement, understanding risk and risk maturity, improving IT skills and experience, and improving the purpose and value can build on IA effectiveness and help to transition it towards a more rigorous approach. The empirical findings noted below in Table 7.2 have been identified as the significant factors influencing the effectiveness of IA in the banking sector and the information found to close the literature gaps.

Table 7.2: IA effectiveness

Literature gaps	Key factors (themes)
The need for capacity building and institutional development	Technology development
The need for consideration in the relationship between IA and the internal control systems	Internal control process
The need for strategic alignment of IA	Prevention of errors and fraud
The need for support from the AC and top management	Aligned assurance

The need for effectiveness in IA department performance	Risk-based IA plan
The need for resource allocation and governance mechanism	Systematic process implementation
The need for adequate management oversight and accountability and the development of a strong internal control culture	Internal factors (i.e. control, governance, operation and risks)
The need for adequate approach towards IA with the relationship between corporate, operational, strategic, cultural and social functions	External factors (i.e. outsourcing, government)

Source: The Researcher

7.2.2 Research question related to the IBA framework

The review of the literature in Chapters 2 and 3 concentrated on various aspects of IA issues, themes and trends that helped in the development of the IBA framework.

- How effective is the current framework of IBA in general and in Bangladesh?

To address this research question, the most effective way to respond is through policy responses. After evaluating various IA frameworks that have been adopted around the world by different industries, their effective implementation remains a major challenge, particularly in developing country contexts like Bangladesh. The applicability of these existing frameworks to Bangladesh in general requires further investigation, as the country faces unique challenges such as limited institutional capacity, a need for more political support, a lack of technical resources and a lack of adequate national and local research. Due to the lack of a comprehensive framework in Bangladesh for managing internal control systems in the banking sector, this research recommends adopting and implementing the IBA framework, which is supported by practical guidance. Thus, the list of criteria for an effective IA framework is compared, reviewed and filtered to select only those that are relevant for research purposes and incorporate the target sample of banks into the Bangladesh setting.

The current frameworks discussed in Sub-Section 3.2.3 highlight the importance of factors that influence IBA framework implementation and aim to help the banking sector to improve compliance with internal control systems. It has also identified implementation gaps and capitalised on associated strengths and opportunities. Interventions can also be developed to fill identified gaps. In response, this research proposes the IBA framework, which addresses the key issues and provides practical guidance for establishing sustainable IA in the banking sector to drive long-term value. Research objective 4 addressed this matter and was identified as an effective approach by providing a solution to the research problem.

7.2.3 Answer to the research objectives

The Researcher set three detailed research objectives as follows:

- To identify and evaluate the current challenges of IA in banks;
- To analyse the current practices of IA in banks;
- To evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh in order to develop an effective IBA framework.

A SLR (Chapters 2 and 3) was used to review the current IA literature, which provided key research contributions to the effectiveness of IA and IA functions, processes, structure, challenges and practices related to the research topic. This research applied the four-quadrant framework and categorised the academic and industry-based literature in order to identify the literature gaps utilised by combined theories (institutional and ingenuity theories). A variety of IA standards, guidelines and frameworks were examined, and the relevant key factors were incorporated into the theoretical IBA framework after synthesising the initial literature, systematic literature and framework gaps. The theoretical IBA framework (Figure 3.4) was established during the first phase of this research (Chapters 2 and 3). Due to the empirical findings as described in Chapters 5 and 6, the IBA framework (Figure 6.1) has evolved with a focus on identifying and validating key factors related to the internal and external environment of banking organisations that are important for the IA practices and their effectiveness, the alignment of IA with the existing organisational setting and the effective implementation of IA. Thus, the IBA framework has evolved into a validated accounting and auditing tool in the field of IA for practical application to increase accountability, achieve strategic vision and achieve integrity in the IA profession within the banking sector.

The first objective is as follows:

- To identify and evaluate the current challenges of internal auditing in banks.

This objective was addressed based on insights from participants gathered through interviews in the context of empirical data, and it represented the first stage of identifying primary data. The empirical findings outlined key IA challenges, which were discussed in detail in Chapters 5 and 6, and revealed that the following are the most significant:

- i. IT systems and technology risks;

- ii. Lack of agile auditing methodologies;
- iii. Lack of clear methodology to leverage technology;
- iv. Lack of dynamic IA framework and implementation guidance;
- v. Lack of resources and talent management;
- vi. Lack of risk-based IA approach;
- vii. Lack of strategic vision of IA;
- viii. Lack of strong internal control systems;
- ix. Poor application of regulations and standards.

In comparison to relevant literature and empirical findings, this research highlights specific requirements and demonstrates that generic principles can be applied to dynamic IBA framework implementation supported by practical guidance in an efficient and effective manner in the banking sector, which can be customised on an organisational basis to meet organisational requirements and stakeholders' expectations.

The second objective is as follows:

- To analyse the current practices of internal auditing in banks.

This objective evaluated the current practices of IA since the existing research is insufficient to demonstrate its potential effectiveness in the context of the banking sector. To achieve this goal, this research involved revising prior literature supported by an evaluation of the institutional framework, regulatory environment and relevant literature evidence and addressing interview questions to respondents to understand new and innovative practices across banking organisations. This objective shows that banking organisations are aware of the potential IA practices and greater attention to current developments and innovations can be achieved by adopting a more innovative and risk-based approach. Despite the fact that effective practices are very different from internal and external factors in many aspects, and even though their strategic priorities have made limited progress, little research has been done on the effectiveness of IA. The applicability of the regulatory environment to the institutional framework compares and demonstrates the effectiveness of IA through synthesis of the literature reviewed.

The empirical findings revealed that organisations struggled to align assurance, internal control processes, error and fraud prevention, and technology development. The evidence demonstrated that the current practices require improvement (47.62%) and necessitates to remain effective in independence; addressing challenges; skills and resources; IA

governance and control review; systematic process implementation; and a risk-based IA plan. The aforementioned results further supported the focus on integrated assurance and the adoption of technological innovations while highlighting the idea that the key factors for effective practices are still yet to be achieved. The basic premise of this argument demonstrates a narrow view of IA while previous literature partially addressed the internal and external factors that impede the current practices of IA in banking organisations. Further to support this objective, good IA practices that are identified emphasises different IA activities and their beneficial implications to assist scholarly attention in identifying future avenues for perceived effectiveness that could become more problem-focused by integrating and expanding existing knowledge.

The third objective is as follows:

- To evaluate the current framework on IBA and identify, and address the gaps in relation to the banking sector in Bangladesh to develop an effective IBA framework

This objective examines and evaluates the current IA frameworks and identifies gaps in the banking sector in Bangladesh. The results of the assessment of current frameworks are presented in Sub-Section 3.2.3. An analysis of related IA frameworks revealed that the banking sector gave limited consideration to IA frameworks in terms of their needs and complexities in the current risk and control environment. The current frameworks do not give consideration to the relationship between IA and internal control systems in banks. In addition, it is also revealed that insufficient attention is given to the relationship between strategic, corporate, operational, cultural and social aspects of IA. It was concluded that poor consideration of aligning IA practice with audit activities, audit programmes and monitoring processes has tended to prevent the adoption of an effective IBA framework so this addresses the research problem.

To remedy this shortcoming, the intention of this research is not to develop a new IA model but rather to propose an effective IBA framework by applying existing and presumably familiar theories, models and frameworks, and justifying empirical findings that can be used by academics and industry. The proposed IBA framework must be able to provide guidance on the assessment of effective practices for IA in the banking sector. Despite previous IA framework shortcomings, the current framework evaluation's implications support the research framework. Overall, this objective was met, assisting the research aim.

The aim and objectives of this research have been pursued to address the three research sub-questions presented in Section 1.6. However, the following sub-sections are discussed in detail by addressing the shortcomings of the findings from Chapters 5 and 6, which are compared with the literature and empirical findings to close the literature gaps.

7.3 Contributions to knowledge and literature

This section addresses the research’s major contributions to the body of knowledge and literature. The Researcher acknowledges that both internal and external influences have an impact and significance on adopting and implementing the IBA framework. To the best of the Researcher’s knowledge, this is one of the first studies that has developed a framework supported by empirical evidence specific to the banking sector that has examined key challenges that can hinder sustainability in IA practices while simultaneously examining the development of IA over the last decades. As indicated in Chapter 3, this research found an experimentally unexplored and unaddressed gap in the literature on IA. Table 7.3 summarises the key contributions of this research.

Table 7.3 Summary of research contributions

Research contributions	Description	Figure/Chapter
Literature review	Initial literature gap	Chapter 2, Section 2.8
Development of the theoretical IBA framework	Systematic literature evaluation	Chapter 3, Section 3.2
	Systematic literature gap	Chapter 3, Sub-Section 3.2.1
	Systematic framework analysis	Chapter 3, Sub-Section 3.2.3
	Systematic framework gap	Chapter 3, Sub-Section 3.3
	Theoretical IBA framework	Chapter 3, Figure 3.4
	Outputs (benefits) of IBA framework	Chapter 3, Figure 3.8
Research methodology and methods	Qualitative research design	Chapter 4
Empirical analysis	Qualitative research findings	Chapters 5 and 6
Validation of the IBA framework	Validated IBA framework	Chapter 6, Figure 6.1
Practical guidance	Practical implementation guidance	Chapter 6, Section 6.5

Source: The Researcher

Theoretical knowledge contributions:

- **Literature gap:** Initial literature gap, systematic literature gap and systematic framework gap contributes to the literature and provided direction for future research;

- **Key challenges:** This research has identified key challenges that can hinder sustainable internal auditing practices. This provides a significant contribution to the knowledge base;
- **Combining institutional and ingenuity theories:** This research is applied a combination of two theories to develop the theoretical IBA framework as fifth derivative. This provides a significant contribution to the literature;
- **Theoretical IBA framework:** A substantial contribution is made to the literature by proposing the theoretical IBA framework for the banking sector;
- **Key internal and external elements:** The Researcher acknowledges that theoretical and validated internal and external elements have an impact and significance on adopting and implementing the IBA framework. It provides a significant contribution to the literature;
- **Qualitative research design:** Most empirical academic research on IA has been conducted using a quantitative survey, tending to overlook the external context offered by the qualitative research. Thus, the qualitative research design method used in this research adds value to the literature;
- **Research findings:** The findings of this research indicate that IA practices differ among banks and typically rely on a highly customised framework and IA policies that are aligned with each organisation's strategic vision and structure, which contributes to the practice;
- **Validated IBA framework:** To the best of the Researcher's knowledge, this research brings a new dimension that has developed an effective IBA framework supported by practical guidance specific to the banking sector, which significantly contributes to the literature.

Practical contributions:

- **Validated IBA framework:** This research developed an IBA framework for the banking sector, which makes a considerable contribution to the practice; By implementing the IBA framework across banking organisations, which would also be customised and subject to change in various ways to enhance IA effectiveness and good governance, and ensure long-term sustainability of the IA approach.
- **Benefits of the IBA framework:** Given the complexity of IA challenges identified from the data collection, the validated IBA framework explored three core outputs:

sustainable competitive advantage, business performance improvement and operational efficiency.

- **Validated key internal and external elements:** This framework developed and provided an understanding of the complexity of the interactions of key IA elements in the internal and external environments that influence the ability to manage emerging risks and current control issues across banking organisations effectively;
- **Research findings:** The significance of comprehensive understanding of prevailing IA practices cannot be overstated in light of the fact that it has diminished the problematic status of IA in implementing the IBA framework. This is because of the failure to consider the alignment of IA practices with relevant activities, programmes and monitoring. This highlights the necessity of effective management oversight and accountability, establishment of robust internal control processes to protect assets, ensure compliance with operational controls, and integrate financial reporting, which contributes to practice.
- **Practical guidance:** A practical road map is provided, outlining five phrases for implementing the IBA framework. This practical guidance helps provide a way to strengthen banking organisation's IA approach and communicate its IA practices to internal and external stakeholders.

This research developed an IBA framework (Figure 6.1) for the banking sector, which makes a considerable contribution to the literature. This framework developed and provided an understanding of the complexity of the interactions of key IA elements in the internal and external environments that influence the ability to manage emerging risks and current control issues across organisations effectively, specifically focusing on the banking sector. Twenty-one professionals with substantial expertise in the field of IA were chosen for the interviews because they were familiar and well-informed with practical and theoretical insights gained from work experience. The findings of this research indicate that IA practices differ among banks and typically rely on a highly customised framework and IA policies that are aligned with each organisation's strategic vision and structure. As shown in Chapters 2 and 3, this has also been found in the literature.

Finally, most empirical academic research on IA has been conducted using a quantitative survey, tending to overlook the external context offered by qualitative research. To the best of the Researcher's knowledge, the IA field in the banking sector is highly heterogeneous and complex while regulatory responses need improvement in risk management and

banking management, so obtaining a good understanding of its concepts and nature requires familiarisation with sustainable operational activities, banking sector development and external contexts. Thus, the qualitative research design method used in this study adds value to the literature.

7.4 Limitations of the research

This section identifies the research limitations based on the Researcher's intricate knowledge of the subject matter, access to information, knowledge and skills, and the availability of value in time and efficiency to complete the research project. These are presented below:

- ***Focusing on the banking sector:*** The IBA framework addresses the specific and significant issues related to IA in banking organisations and applies the research findings to the banking sector.
- ***Participants limited to banking organisations:*** This research's empirical conclusion was limited to participants who worked for banking organisations. In order to lessen the impact this limitation had on the interview sample, IA professionals were chosen who had considerable experience in IA, internal control systems and corporate governance as policymakers.
- ***Qualitative methods as a research strategy:*** A limitation of applying qualitative approaches has emerged in empirical findings; it cannot be extended to larger populations with the same degree of certainty like quantitative methods can. This is due to the fact that the findings of this research were not tested to see whether they were statistically significant or may have carried a potential for bias.
- ***Limited sample size:*** This research is based on the results of 21 interviews. The size of the banking sector, however, highlights and justifies this relatively small sample size. Another common issue with interviews is that not all interviewees make excellent participants, and some participants find it difficult to share sensitive information about the complexity of banking auditing challenges.

7.5 Recommendations for future research

The literature review revealed that most published research on examining IA challenges and developing the framework is theoretical and unsupported by empirical evidence in banking organisations, indicating that further research is needed (Hanefah and Endaya, 2013; Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Previous research did not show how socioeconomic and cultural changes could affect IA (Mihret and Grant, 2017), what factors make IA practice

effective and measurable (Lenz, Sarens and Jeppesen, 2018) or how IA's traditional role was more important than its value-added activities (Kotb, Elbardan and Halabi, 2020). Given the nature of exploratory research, the findings of this research suggest and provide a foundation point for further research into a variety of emerging themes and topics relating to IA within and outside the banking sector.

- The first suggestion is that a strategic IA alignment framework be further developed, which should be examined in non-public organisations, private organisations, the public sector and not-for-profit organisations. This would provide information on how the framework's implementation varies among organisations and sectors. IA alignment also has many strategic and structural challenges. This would help to figure out how much specialised knowledge about these issues is needed and how IA could improve corporate governance and risk management in emerging economies, and countries that are still developing;
- Another suggestion for future research is how IA and ERM can be combined in current practice and whether there is a difference between large and small organisations. In this regard, future research may be able to determine whether there is still a chance to build an IA and ERM comprehensive framework that can operate as a judgement support system within a variety of factors in internal and external environments. In order to increase the generalisability of the findings, future research on this topic might use a more quantitative methodology by applying a range of statistical analysis and a larger sample group. Furthermore, such research may result in a visual and structural simplification of the model;
- The Researcher recommends that future research should focus on understanding new and innovative approaches and practices that have the ability to add value and elevate the status of the IA profession and risk management. These should provide an insight into IA's current position and benefit academic researchers by opening up new research opportunities in this field. Further to support this notion, a thorough examination of the benefits and drawbacks of innovative IA techniques can give internal auditors and standard setters a better understanding of current advances and innovations to predict the future of IA;
- The final suggestion is to understand how the use of artificial intelligence, big data analytics and emerging technologies enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of IA, and the challenges and limitations of adopting, and implementing technological advancement in the public sector in the context of emerging or developing countries.

To conclude, future researchers may choose to investigate specific issues that affect the strategic IA alignment framework to better understand how individual framework parts work together and what changes could be made in the future.

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Appendix

Interview guidance

Investigating the challenges facing internal auditing in the
banking sector: The case of banks in Bangladesh
(Semi-Structured Interview- Banking Sector in Bangladesh)

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University of the West of Scotland

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Consent form

Title of Research: Investigating the challenges facing internal auditing in the banking sector: The case of banks in Bangladesh

Please read and confirm your consent to being interviewed for this research by initiating the appropriate box (es) and signing and dating the form.

1. I confirm that the purpose of the research has been explained to me that I have given information about it in writing, and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any implications for my legal rights.
3. I give permission for the interview to be tape recorded by the research investigator, on the understanding that the tape will be destroyed at the end of the research.
4. I wish to participate in the research under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the Information Sheet.
5. I agree to take part in this research project.

Participant's name: _____ Date: _____ Signature: _____

Researcher's name: _____ Date: _____ Signature: _____

Researcher's contact

Shailendra Bhowmik

Director of Studies (DoS) contact

Dr Abraham Althonayan
Senior Lecturer/ Director of Studies
Brunel University London

Personal details withheld.

Participant information sheets

You are being invited to take part in this research project, which seeks to investigate the challenges facing internal auditing in the banking sector in Bangladesh. In order to decide whether or not to take part in this interview, it is important to understand why this research is being conducted and what your participation will entail. I would appreciate if you could please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with your colleagues or other people. Please ask, if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Thank you for reading this.

Purpose of the research

This research project is being carried out as part of a DBA degree at the University of the West of Scotland in the United Kingdom. The aim of this research is to investigate the challenges that internal auditing facing in the banking sector in Bangladesh and to develop an effective Internal Banking Auditing (IBA) framework supported by practical guidance.

Recent instances of corruption and collapse in a number of major organisations have revealed inadequate internal control mechanisms. It has also emphasised the need for greater transparency to protect shareholders and stakeholders around the world, especially in Bangladesh. The banking collapse, in particular, prompted regulators and governments to refocus on internal auditing as a key governance mechanism. Thus, the challenges have resulted in the development of an Internal Banking Auditing (IBA) framework supported by practical guidance, which gives the audit committees and boards of directors in the banking sector a prominent role to play. Although there are numerous researches conducted on internal auditing on a global scale, there is no research focusing on Bangladesh context, particularly in the banking sector. Therefore, I would like to invite you to take part in this research project, which should not last more than 30-45 minute. Your responses are very important in enabling the researcher to fulfil the following research objectives and questions:

- To evaluate the existing literature and identify literature gaps on the challenges of internal auditing in the banking sector in Bangladesh;
- To identify and evaluate the current challenges of internal auditing in banks;
- To analyse the current practices of internal auditing in banks;
- To evaluate the current framework on internal banking auditing and gaps in the banking sector in Bangladesh.

The main research question posed as follows:

- What are the main challenges of internal auditing in banks in Bangladesh and what major steps can be taken to improve the effectiveness of internal auditing?

To answer the main research question, the following sub questions need to be answered:

- What are the challenges facing internal auditing in banks in general and in Bangladesh specifically?
- What major steps can be undertaken to enhance the effectiveness of internal auditing in banks in Bangladesh?
- How effective current framework on internal banking auditing in general and in Bangladesh?

Contributions of the research

I am sure that you will agree that this is an important piece of research and the advantages of taking part in this research are as follows:

- This research should contribute to the internal auditing research area that carries regional significance;
- it will get deeper into the challenges that internal auditing facing in the banking sector;
- and the research findings may help banks to give proper attention towards internal auditing implementation.

Description of the research procedures

If you agree to be in this research, you will be expected to a 30 to 45-minute on the above subject area. You have the right to withdraw from the research at any time.

Confidentiality

This research is anonymous. The information you will provide will be treated as strictly confidential. The Researcher will not be collecting or retaining any information about your identity. The records of this research will be kept strictly confidential. Research records will be kept in a locked file and all electronic information will be coded and secured using a password protected file. Researcher will not include any information in any published report that would make it possible to identify you. Data collected may be shared in an anonymised form to allow reuse by the Researcher and other third parties. These anonymised data will not allow any individuals or their institutions to be identified or identifiable.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the consent form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason. Please return Withdrawal of Consent form, as indicated in the following page.

Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved by the university's ethics review procedure and subsequently endorsed by the ethics procedures of University of the West of Scotland. The University of the West of Scotland's Research Ethics Committee monitors the application and delivery of the University's Ethics Review Procedure across the University.

Yours sincerely,

Shailendra Bhowmik
Student ID: B00322944
DBA Programme
School of Business and Creative Industries
University of the West of Scotland

Personal details withheld.

17/02/2022

Dear Shalendra Bhowmik,

Your application 10885: Investigating the challenges facing internal auditing in the banking sector: The case of banks in Bangladesh, submission 14948, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Interview Questions

Title of Research: Investigating the challenges facing internal auditing in the banking sector: The case of banks in Bangladesh

Researcher: Shailendra Bhowmik, DBA student at School of Business and Creative Industries, UWS.

Part I: General information

1. Which institution within the banking sector does your organisation primarily operate? *(Please select one option)*
 - a. State-owned commercial banks (SOCBs)
 - b. Specialised banks (SDBs)
 - c. Private commercial banks (PCBs)
 - d. Foreign commercial banks (FCBs)
 - e. Non-scheduled banks (NCBs)
 - f. Other (please specify)
.....

2. Please specify the size of your organisation based on the number of employees *(Please select one option)*
 - a. Between 100-500
 - b. Between 501-1000
 - c. Between 1001-2000
 - d. Above 2000
 - e. Other (please specify)
.....

3. What is your current job title in your organisation? *(Please select one option)*
 - a. Audit Committee member
 - b. Executive/Senior management
 - c. Head of internal audit, or equivalent
 - d. Qualified/experienced internal auditor
 - e. Trainee internal auditor
 - f. Other (please specify)
.....

4. How long have you been in your current role? *(Please select one option)*
 - a. At least 1 year but fewer than 3 years
 - b. At least 3 years but fewer than 5 years
 - c. At least 5 years but fewer than 10 years
 - d. Other (please specify)
.....

5. How many years have you worked in internal auditing? *(Please select one option)*
 - a. At least 1 year but fewer than 3 years
 - b. At least 3 years but fewer than 5 years
 - c. At least 5 years but fewer than 10 years
 - d. Other (please specify)
.....

6. Which aspect of internal auditing are you mostly focused on in your organisation? *(Please select as many as you deem appropriate)*

- a. Control assessment/measurement
- b. Risk assessment/measurement
- c. Internal control and compliance
- d. Implementation - operational
- e. Implementation - strategic
- f. Implementation - technical
- g. Other (please specify)

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7. As a professional, is your current role conditioned by a fully/partly professional qualification (i.e. CA, CMA, ACCA, CIMA, CPA etc)?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. I do not know

If yes, the certification(s) name is/are.....

8. In your current role, what are your tasks in terms of internal auditing in your organisation? *(Please select as many as you deem appropriate)*

- a. Communication between departments
- b. Internal controls and governance process
- c. Management oversight and accountability
- d. Perform and control the audit cycle
- e. Measuring and assessing the risks
- f. Financial reporting
- g. Policy making and monitoring
- h. Internal control structures and activities
- i. Other (please specify)

.....

9. In your opinion, what areas of internal auditing are established in your organisation that benefit you in your role? Please explain.

- Please specify
-
-
-

Part II: Development of the Internal Banking Auditing framework

10. In general, what do you consider to be the main challenges in implementing internal auditing?

- Please specify
-
-
-

11. In your opinion, what are the current challenges of internal auditing in your organisation?

- Please specify
-
-

12. Following on from the previous question, how can the current internal auditing challenges be overcome within your organisation?

Please specify

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13. What do you believe is the most significant emerging risk facing internal auditing within your organisation?

Please specify

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14. In general, what do you think that a strategic alignment of internal auditing with the internal control system is a feasible approach in terms of generating value in the long term?

Please specify

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15. What do you think the benefits are if internal auditing and internal control systems were implemented/improved in your organisation? Please explain.

Please specify

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16. Following on from previous questions, how does internal auditing determine what risk and control issues should be reported to the board of directors and the audit committee within your organisation?

Please specify

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17. In your opinion, how can the board of directors or the audit committee improve internal auditing in your organisation?

Please specify

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18. How effective is the coverage of the internal auditing plan and additional engagements for producing a sufficient level of quality assurance in your organisation?

a. Very effective

- b. Somewhat effective
 - c. Neutral
 - d. Somewhat ineffective
 - e. Very ineffective
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

19. Can you tell me what are the main factors that might impede the successful implementation of an internal auditing plan within your organisation?

- Please specify
-
-
-

20. How would you describe the process of internal auditing within your organisation?

- a. Very effective
 - b. Somewhat effective
 - c. Neutral
 - d. Somewhat ineffective
 - e. Very ineffective
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

21. In dealing with governance mechanisms, how important is aligning the process of internal auditing with organisational vision in your organisation?

- a. Very important
 - b. Somewhat important
 - c. Neutral
 - d. Slightly important
 - e. Not important
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

22. In terms of the internal auditing functions that are implemented in your organisation, do you think there is room for improvement? Please explain.

- Please specify
-
-
-

23. Thinking of internal auditing programmes specifically, how effective are they in your organisation if they have been implemented?

- a. Very effective
 - b. Somewhat effective
 - c. Neutral
 - d. Somewhat ineffective
 - e. Very ineffective
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

24. In your view, what internal auditing activities are in place in your organisation? Please explain.

Please specify

.....

25. How would you describe the nature of internal auditing that is currently practiced in your organisation?
 (Please select one option)

- a. Improved
- b. Requires improvement
- c. Inconsistent
- d. Mandatory
- e. Other (please specify)

.....

26. In your opinion, what areas represent the most effective internal auditing practices in your organisation?

Please specify

.....

27. What are the main inhibitors (internal and external) that might impede the good practices of internal auditing within your organisation?

Please specify

.....

28. Can you explain how you would address the issues for greater effectiveness of internal auditing in your organisation?

Please specify

.....

29. How does your organisation view the nature of measuring the effectiveness of internal auditing?

- a. Very positive
- b. Somewhat positive
- c. Neutral
- d. Somewhat negative
- e. Very negative
- f. Other (please specify)

.....

30. How would you describe the overall standards to achieve internal auditing effectiveness within your organisation for protecting the governance control mechanisms?

- a. Robust control governance

- b. Mature control governance embedded at organisational level
 - c. Evolved control governance but partially implemented across departments
 - d. Developed but not yet applied organisation wide
 - e. Very immature, at its early stages of preparation
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

31. How important is monitoring the measurement of internal auditing roles and performances in your organisation?

- a. Very important
 - b. Somewhat important
 - c. Neutral
 - d. Slightly important
 - e. Not important
 - f. Other (please specify)
-

32. Based on your personal observations and experiences, how does the existence of the internal auditing profession facilitate organisational expansion within your organisation?

- Please specify
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33. In your opinion, what is the overall status of tracking internal auditing competencies and for reporting the performance of internal auditing in your organisation?

- a. Mature (fully optimised)
 - b. Somewhat mature, optimised to organisational needs
 - c. Slightly mature, implemented but not fully integrated
 - d. Immature, initial implementation phase
 - e. Considered but not yet applied
 - f. Not considered
 - g. Other (please specify)
-

34. Does your organisation have an internal auditing policy manual, including clear implementation guidelines? *(Please select one option)*

- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. I do not know
 - d. Other (please specify)
-

If the next question does not apply, please go to the question 38.

35. If applicable, does your organisation use any professional internal auditing framework as a frame of reference? *(Please select one option)*

- a. Yes (please specify.....) (please go to question 36)
 - b. No (please go to question 37)
 - c. I do not know
 - d. Other (please specify)
-

36. How does the current framework followed meet the internal auditing requirements within your organisation?

- a. Very effective
- b. Somewhat effective
- c. Somewhat ineffective
- d. Very ineffective
- e. Other (please specify)

.....

37. In your opinion, why has your organisation not implemented an internal auditing framework?

- a. Do not wish to follow
- b. Follow something else
- c. Other (please specify)

.....

38. How does internal auditing currently contribute to your organisation's success and delivery of its strategic priorities?

- Please specify

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39. From your experience, what are the main areas to review so that internal auditing can be sustained in the long term within your organisation?

- Please specify

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40. In general, which are the most worthwhile future challenges that you would recommend in the implementation of internal auditing in banks?

- Please specify

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41. Lastly, how do you think internal auditing should be focusing on in the coming three years to have the greatest change for the organisation, if at all? Any predictions/forecasts of future trends?

- Please specify

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There are no further questions, is there anything that you would like to bring up or ask before closing the interview?

- Please specify

Would you like to receive a copy of the summary and findings from this research?

If yes, please provide your email address: (The email address collected in this interview will be stored securely and only used for the purposes of supplying you with a copy of the summary and findings from this research as per your request. This is in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act 2018).

Thank you very much for your participation.

Sample interview transcript

Q1. Which institution within the banking sector does your organisation primarily operate?

Interviewee: State-owned commercial banks (SOCBs).

Q2. Please specify the size of your organisation based on the number of employees.

Interviewee: Above 2000.

Q3. What is your current job title in your organisation?

Interviewee: Internal auditor.

Q4. How long have you been in your current role?

Interviewee: It's been 4 years since I joined this organisation.

Q5. How many years have you worked in internal auditing?

Interviewee: Almost 6 years. Before this job I was in internal auditing department of an NGO.

Q6. Which aspect of internal auditing are you mostly focused on in your organisation?

Interviewee: Internal control and compliance. Internal control and compliance are integral parts as controls are part of the process designed and compliance fulfils those processes.

Q7. As a professional, is your current role conditioned by a fully/partly professional qualification?

Interviewee: Yes, I am FCA and FCCA member.

Q8. In your current role, what are your tasks in terms of internal auditing in your organisation?

Interviewee: In our department, we set out safeguards to minimise internal control and risks. We design policies, rules, regulations, and laws that help to minimise risks and protect assets, ensure accuracy of records, promote operational efficiency, etc. We make sure the designed policies are adapted properly.

Q9. What areas of internal auditing are established in your organisation that benefit you in your role?

Interviewee: Recently, our organisation became fully digitalised and tech-heavy, which means leveraging technology inside the internal audit department to automate some functions and operate more efficiently.

Q10. In general, what do you consider to be the main challenges in implementing internal auditing?

Interviewee: The main challenges in implementing internal auditing are lack of independence and objectivity; difficulty in measuring and assessing internal auditing effectiveness; and the cost associated with implementing an internal audit department.

Q11. In your opinion, what are the current challenges of internal auditing in your organisation?

Interviewee: The current challenges are considered to be a lack of top management support, a lack of strong internal control systems, and poor compliance standards with internal auditing practice.

Q12. Following on from the previous question, how can the current internal auditing challenges be overcome within your organisation?

Interviewee: To overcome the current challenges, I think it should: maintain better management oversight; measure and assess internal auditing effectiveness; and maintain better internal communication and accountability.

Q13. What do you believe is the most significant emerging risk facing internal auditing within your organisation?

Interviewee: I think it could be the adoption of digital technologies becoming obsolete, business resilience, staff well-being and talent management, or regulatory-driven risk.

Q14. In general, do you think that a strategic alignment of internal auditing with internal control systems is a feasible approach in terms of generating value in the long term?

Interviewee: I strongly agree with that. As the environment is changing, internal auditing needs to have dynamic planning to adapt at the same speed as the strategic risks change.

Q15. What do you think the benefits are if internal auditing and internal control systems were implemented/improved in your organisation? Please explain.

Interviewee: There are lots of positives to implementing internal auditing and internal control systems in my organisation, such as detecting and preventing fraud, investigating loss of assets, regulatory compliance, and so on.

Q16. Following on from previous questions, how does internal auditing determine what risk and control issues should be reported to the board of directors and the audit committee within your organisation?

Interviewee: The financial statements and ratios should reveal whether the organisation is operationally and strategically successful. The financial figures may reveal whether or not the organisation is experiencing operational difficulties. This is true unless fraud or financial manipulation is used to conceal the true situation.

Q17. In your opinion, how can the board of directors or the audit committee improve internal auditing in your organisation?

Interviewee: For internal auditing to improve, the audit committee needs to be updated with the financial reporting processes, audit processes, and information about internal control systems. The audit committee should oversee whether the audit processes are run by proper laws and compliance. The BOD should oversee the audit report submitted by the audit committee carefully to find any discrepancies.

Q18. In your opinion, how effective is the coverage of the internal auditing plan and additional engagements for producing a sufficient level of quality assurance in your organisation?

Interviewee: I think it's somewhat effective. Internal auditing helps to accomplish an organisation's goals, and employees show their skills and understanding of the organisation's objectives in their practices.

Q19. Can you tell me what are the main factors that might impede the successful implementation of an internal auditing plan within your organisation?

Interviewee: The main challenges, I think, are lack of capacity building and institutional development; difficulty in measuring the level of independence, objectivity, and competency; lack of management support; and lack of an audit monitoring process.

Q20. In your organisation, how would you describe the process of internal auditing?

Interviewee: Somewhat effective.

Q21. In dealing with governance mechanisms, how important is aligning the process of internal auditing with organisational vision?

Interviewee: Very important.

Q22. In terms of the internal auditing functions that are implemented in your organisation, do you think there is a room for improvement?

Interviewee: Yes, the audit process needs to improve and be more effective as the audit goes through audit planning, fieldwork, reporting, and follow up.

Q23. Thinking of internal auditing programmes specifically, how effective are they in your organisation if they have been implemented?

Interviewee: Very effective.

Q24. In your view, what internal auditing activities are in place in your organisation? Please explain.

Interviewee: Many recent corporate misstatements that have caused public outrage and brand damage, in my opinion, are the result of this imbalance. When IA or other assurance functions and business departments implement the strategy in disparate or misaligned ways, disaster is almost inevitable.

Q25. How would you describe the nature of internal auditing that is currently practiced in your organisation?

Interviewee: I think it has improved a lot. Yes, there is lots of room for improvement. Internal auditing increases the effectiveness of internal controls. It is also helping the management to correct situations that have been diverted from the actual outcomes.

Q26. In your opinion, what areas represent the most effective internal auditing practices in your organisation? Please explain.

Interviewee: Internal control and compliance represent the most effective internal auditing practices in my organisation.

Q27. What are the main inhibitors (internal and external) that might impede the good practices of internal auditing within your organisation?

Interviewee: I think these are a lack of excellence in operational responsibilities and poor alignment with the strategic objectives and risks. Compliance standards have a limited impact on internal auditing practices.

Q28. Can you explain how you would address the issues greater effectiveness of internal auditing in your organisation?

Interviewee: There is a lot of rapid change and evolution going on, and only the most forward-thinking audit professionals should be able to adapt to the shifting landscape. You may fail if you do not have a long-term vision. Internal auditors must be able to predict the weather rather than simply reporting on it when it occurs.

Q29. How does your organisation view the nature of measuring the effectiveness of internal auditing?

Interviewee: I think the effectiveness is improving. It's somewhat positive. Organisation have been able to identify significant risks and have been able to rectify these.

Q30. Standards to the internal auditing effectiveness

Interviewer: How would you describe the overall standards to achieve internal auditing effectiveness within your organisation for protecting the governance control mechanisms?

Interviewee: The standard has evolved control governance but partially implemented across departments.

Q31. How important is monitoring the measurement of internal auditing role and performance in your organisation?

Interviewee: It is somewhat important. I think it does help management to continually review business processes and find any deviations.

Q32. Based on your personal observations and experiences, does the existence of the internal auditing profession facilitate organisational expansion within your organisation?

Interviewee: Yes, it helps the organisation grow. As the effectiveness of operations grows, business tries to grab the new opportunities when they're available.

Q33. In your opinion, what is the overall status of tracking internal auditing competencies and for reporting the performance of internal auditing in your organisation?

Interviewee: Somewhat mature, optimised to organisational needs as internal auditors works independently and they give their advice to management and to boards.

Q34. Does your organisation have an internal auditing policy manual, including clear implementation guidelines?

Interviewee: Yes.

Q35. If applicable, does your organisation use any professional internal auditing framework as a frame of reference?

Interviewee: No.

Q36. How does the current framework followed meet the internal auditing requirements within your organisation?

Interviewee: Not applicable.

Q37. In your opinion, why has your organisation not implemented an internal auditing framework?

Interviewee: Follow something else. Current ICCD guidelines help to evaluate the efficiencies of the controls and make sure the compliance runs properly.

Q38. How does internal auditing currently contributes to your organisation's success and delivery of its strategic priorities?

Interviewee: I think business resilience. However, the challenges that business has faced recently have put a huge stress on day-to-day operations. To survive, all organisations have had to rapidly re-engineer some of the fundamentals. These sessions will focus on the valuable strategic perspective that internal audit can provide in ensuring that there are robust plans and structures in place to adequately protect the business.

Q39. From your experience, what are the main areas to review so that internal auditing can be sustained in the long term in your organisation?

Interviewee: Improving technology capabilities, aligning and measuring the effectiveness of internal auditing, and empowering the internal auditing department to innovate are three ways to improve.

Q40. In general, which are the most worthwhile future challenges that you would recommend in the implementation of internal auditing in banks?

Interviewee: The challenge could be the lack of integration of qualified talents and skillsets.

Q41. Lastly, how do you think internal auditing should be focusing on in the coming three years to have the greatest change for the organisation, if at all? Any predictions/ forecasts of future trends?

Interviewee: Investing in an organisation that has a high-quality audit offers investors and other stakeholders' peace of mind that the organisation's financial statements are accurate and reliable, allowing them to make well-informed decisions.'

Thank you very much.

Stakeholder analysis

Individuals	Characteristics/Criteria	Data collection method
Stakeholder category- 1 (IA practitioner in the banking sector)		
IA practitioner who support new internal auditors and establishes a common foundation of skills and knowledge related to IA best practices.	acting as an IA practitioner; at least two to three years experience in the IA related field; responsible for the development of junior staff members or mentoring capacity; Recognise the components of IA attributes, nature of work, engagement planning, engagement work and engagement communication	Semi-structured interviews
Stakeholder category- 2 (Internal auditor in the banking sector)		
Internal auditor who provide an independent guarantee that organisation's risk management, governance and control processes are operating effectively by monitoring and evaluating the risks and processes.	acting as an internal auditor; at least three to five years experience in the IA related field; performing risk assessments on key organisation's activities introduce the concepts of internal control, risk, governance and technology	Semi-structured interviews
Stakeholder category- 3 (IA policymaker or regulator in the banking sector)		
IA policymaker or regulator who aimed at enhancing the overall effectiveness of IA, and its impact, as a benchmark of good practice against which organisations can assess its functions by clarifying expectations and requirements.	acting as chief audit executives, executive and non-executive directors, and in particular members of audit and risk committees; at least three to five years experience in the IA related field; ensures training, recruitment, secondment from other parts of the organisation or co-sourcing with external third parties and overall governance responsibility; constructive and co-operative relationship with stakeholders which supports sharing of information relevant to respective responsibilities.	Semi-structured interviews
Stakeholder category-4 (IA professional members of IIA, ICAB, ICMAB, ACCA, CIMA, CPA, MoF, COAGB)		
IA professional members of key auditing standard setters, institutes, professional organisations and public bodies within the banking sector.	has a good understanding of IA methods, including cumulative and strategic IA; has at least 2 years of experience in undertaking and reporting on IA; ensures that assets are safeguarded, information (financial and others) is timely and reliable, errors and irregularities are discovered and corrected promptly; establishes compliance with applicable laws and regulations as well as policies and procedures.	Semi-structured interviews